

Flexible Powers Narcissistic-Type Numbers¹

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Abstract

This paper works with extensions of narcissistic numbers as flexible powers narcissistic numbers with positive, and positive-negative coefficients. This is reorganized version of author's previous work [12] done in 2017.

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1 Introduction

An n -digit number that is the sum of the n^{th} powers of its digits is called an n -narcissistic number. It is also sometimes known as an Armstrong number, perfect digital invariant (Madachy 1966 [6]), or plus perfect number. Hardy in 1940 [2] (pg. 25) wrote, there are just four numbers of three digits, which are the sums of the cubes of their digits:

$$153 = 1^3 + 5^3 + 3^3$$

$$370 = 3^3 + 7^3 + 0^3$$

$$371 = 3^3 + 7^3 + 1^3$$

$$407 = 4^3 + 0^3 + 7^3$$

The above four numbers have the same digits on both sides except the power 3 and are with 3 digits. There are four more numbers with 4 digits:

$$1634 := 1^4 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 4^4$$

$$4151 := 4^5 + 1^5 + 5^5 + 1^5$$

$$8208 := 8^4 + 2^4 + 0^4 + 8^4$$

$$9472 := 9^4 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 2^4$$

¹This work is reorganized version of author's previous work <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a147.pdf> [12] done 2017

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Above numbers are with fixed power. Relaxing this condition, we many have much numbers with flexible power, for example,

$$\begin{aligned} 132 &:= 1^1 + 3^1 + 2^7 \\ 2353 &:= 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 3^7 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Moreover, instead of having positive coefficients, we can have positive-negative coefficients, for example,

$$\begin{aligned} 128 &:= -1^1 + 2^7 + 8^0 \\ 9942 &:= -9^1 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 2^7 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The following four numbers are known in the literature [3, 4, 5]:

$$\begin{aligned} 3435 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 \\ 438579088 &:= 4^4 + 3^3 + 8^8 + 5^5 + 7^7 + 9^9 + 0^0 + 8^8 + 8^8 \\ 48625 &:= 4^5 + 8^2 + 6^6 + 2^8 + 5^4 \\ 397612 &:= 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The first two are having the same power as of bases. The last two numbers are such that the power is in reverse order of digits numbers. Our aim here is little different. We want to bring numbers similar to one given in (1) and (2), where only the bases follows the digit's order, and the powers are flexible both for positive, and positive-negative coefficients. The work is limited up to 5 digits. The numbers **3435** and **48625** appearing in (3) are also appears in our study. The number **397612** appears in author's another work [17]. The only number left **438579088** is for further study.

Let's consider the following expression:

$$abc\dots = a^{m_1} \pm b^{m_2} \pm c^{m_3} \pm \dots, a, b, c, \dots \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}, a \neq 0. \quad (4)$$

For simplicity, let us the write the (4) as

$$abc\dots = (a, b, d, \dots)^{(m_1, m_2, m_3, \dots)} \quad (5)$$

Detailed study of numbers arising due to equation (4) or (5) are given in [16, 17]. If the powers and bases are of same digits with different permutations, then the equation (5) can be re-written as

$$abc\dots = (a, b, d, \dots)^{(a, b, c, \dots)} \quad (6)$$

Numbers arising due to (6) are defined as **permutable powers selfie numbers**, and studied by author [17]. See below some examples,

$$\begin{aligned} 23 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 \\ 1364 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3 \\ 3435 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 \\ 3045 &:= -3^4 + 0^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 \\ 78205 &:= 7^2 - 8^0 + 2^5 + 0^8 + 5^7 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

From (7), we observe that the powers and bases are of same digits with different permutations. For detailed study of this work refer author's work [17]. Study on numbers in different situations see summary of author's work [13, 15].

In this work, aim is to write **narcissistic-type numbers** according to (4) **flexible** powers in two situation, one with **positive coefficients** and another with **positive and negative coefficients**.

2 Flexible Powers: Positive Coefficients

In this section, we shall give narcissistic-type numbers with flexible powers and positive coefficients. It is understood that $0^a = 1, a \neq 0$ and $0^0 = 1$.

$1 := 1^1$	$267 := 2^1 + 6^3 + 7^2$	$779 := 7^2 + 7^0 + 9^3$
$2 := 2^1$	$283 := 2^5 + 8^1 + 3^5$	$794 := 7^2 + 9^3 + 4^2$
$3 := 3^1$	$308 := 3^5 + 0^0 + 8^2$	$849 := 8^3 + 4^4 + 9^2$
$4 := 4^1$	$332 := 3^4 + 3^5 + 2^3$	$935 := 9^2 + 3^6 + 5^3$
$5 := 5^1$	$333 := 3^2 + 3^4 + 3^5$	$946 := 9^3 + 4^0 + 6^3$
$6 := 6^1$	$334 := 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^3$	$973 := 9^3 + 7^0 + 3^5$
$7 := 7^1$	$347 := 3^1 + 4^0 + 7^3$	$994 := 9^1 + 9^3 + 4^4$
$8 := 8^1$	$357 := 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^3$	
$9 := 9^1$	$370 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 0^1$	$1034 := 1^1 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 4^5$
	$371 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 1^0$	$1042 := 1^1 + 0^0 + 4^5 + 2^4$
$24 := 2^3 + 4^2$	$372 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 2^1$	$1073 := 1^1 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 3^6$
$43 := 4^2 + 3^3$	$373 := 3^1 + 7^3 + 3^3$	$1074 := 1^1 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 4^5$
$63 := 6^2 + 3^3$	$374 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 4^1$	$1234 := 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^5$
$89 := 8^1 + 9^2$	$375 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 5^1$	$1243 := 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^0 + 3^6$
	$376 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 6^1$	$1255 := 1^1 + 2^2 + 5^4 + 5^4$
$132 := 1^1 + 3^1 + 2^7$	$377 := 3^3 + 7^1 + 7^3$	$1306 := 1^1 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 6^4$
$135 := 1^1 + 3^2 + 5^3$	$378 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 8^1$	$1323 := 1^1 + 3^4 + 2^9 + 3^6$
$153 := 1^1 + 5^3 + 3^3$	$379 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 9^1$	$1326 := 1^1 + 3^3 + 2^1 + 6^4$
$175 := 1^1 + 7^2 + 5^3$	$407 := 4^3 + 0^1 + 7^3$	$1349 := 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^5 + 9^2$
$209 := 2^7 + 0^1 + 9^2$	$445 := 4^3 + 4^4 + 5^3$	$1356 := 1^1 + 3^6 + 5^4 + 6^0$
$224 := 2^5 + 2^7 + 4^3$	$463 := 4^1 + 6^3 + 3^5$	$1362 := 1^1 + 3^0 + 6^4 + 2^6$
$226 := 2^1 + 2^3 + 6^3$	$518 := 5^1 + 1^0 + 8^3$	$1364 := 1^1 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3$
$254 := 2^7 + 5^3 + 4^0$	$538 := 5^2 + 3^0 + 8^3$	$1386 := 1^1 + 3^4 + 8^1 + 6^4$
$258 := 2^8 + 5^0 + 8^0$	$598 := 5^1 + 9^2 + 8^3$	$1426 := 1^1 + 4^0 + 2^7 + 6^4$
$262 := 2^7 + 6^1 + 2^7$	$629 := 6^2 + 2^9 + 9^2$	$1498 := 1^1 + 4^4 + 9^3 + 8^3$
$263 := 2^8 + 6^1 + 3^0$	$737 := 7^1 + 3^6 + 7^0$	$1542 := 1^1 + 5^1 + 4^5 + 2^9$
$264 := 2^1 + 6^1 + 4^4$	$739 := 7^1 + 3^1 + 9^3$	$1634 := 1^1 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 4^4$

1672 := $1^1 + 6^4 + 7^3 + 2^5$
1676 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 7^3 + 6^4$
1765 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 6^4 + 5^3$
1836 := $1^1 + 8^3 + 3^3 + 6^4$
2048 := $2^9 + 0^1 + 4^5 + 8^3$
2064 := $2^9 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 4^4$
2193 := $2^2 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 3^7$
2203 := $2^3 + 2^3 + 0^1 + 3^7$
2223 := $2^1 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 3^7$
2236 := $2^4 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 6^0$
2243 := $2^3 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 3^7$
2253 := $2^6 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 3^7$
2263 := $2^3 + 2^5 + 6^2 + 3^7$
2264 := $2^9 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 4^5$
2283 := $2^4 + 2^4 + 8^2 + 3^7$
2315 := $2^1 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 5^3$
2317 := $2^7 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 7^0$
2320 := $2^2 + 3^7 + 2^7 + 0^0$
2324 := $2^3 + 3^7 + 2^7 + 4^0$
2332 := $2^3 + 3^2 + 3^7 + 2^7$
2333 := $2^6 + 3^0 + 3^4 + 3^7$
2334 := $2^1 + 3^4 + 3^7 + 4^3$
2336 := $2^5 + 3^4 + 3^7 + 6^2$
2343 := $2^7 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 3^7$
2345 := $2^5 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^3$
2352 := $2^3 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 2^5$
2353 := $2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 3^7$
2356 := $2^3 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^2$
2372 := $2^3 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 2^7$
2373 := $2^7 + 3^2 + 7^2 + 3^7$
2376 := $2^3 + 3^6 + 7^3 + 6^4$
2380 := $2^7 + 3^7 + 8^2 + 0^0$
2395 := $2^1 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 5^3$
2396 := $2^7 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^4$
2397 := $2^7 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 7^0$
2407 := $2^1 + 4^1 + 0^1 + 7^4$

2427 := $2^1 + 4^2 + 2^3 + 7^4$
2433 := $2^1 + 4^0 + 3^5 + 3^7$
2436 := $2^5 + 4^0 + 3^7 + 6^3$
2437 := $2^3 + 4^0 + 3^3 + 7^4$
2443 := $2^7 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 3^7$
2464 := $2^7 + 4^2 + 6^4 + 4^5$
2467 := $2^6 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 7^4$
2470 := $2^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 0^0$
2474 := $2^3 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 4^3$
2483 := $2^5 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 3^7$
2532 := $2^6 + 5^2 + 3^7 + 2^8$
2536 := $2^3 + 5^3 + 3^7 + 6^3$
2537 := $2^1 + 5^1 + 3^7 + 7^3$
2574 := $2^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 + 4^2$
2577 := $2^1 + 5^3 + 7^2 + 7^4$
2626 := $2^1 + 6^4 + 2^5 + 6^4$
2627 := $2^1 + 6^3 + 2^3 + 7^4$
2664 := $2^3 + 6^4 + 6^4 + 4^3$
2674 := $2^4 + 6^0 + 7^4 + 4^4$
2707 := $2^8 + 7^2 + 0^0 + 7^4$
2722 := $2^6 + 7^4 + 2^0 + 2^8$
2732 := $2^5 + 7^0 + 3^7 + 2^9$
2733 := $2^3 + 7^4 + 3^4 + 3^5$
2735 := $2^7 + 7^4 + 3^4 + 5^3$
2736 := $2^9 + 7^0 + 3^7 + 6^2$
2738 := $2^5 + 7^1 + 3^7 + 8^3$
2739 := $2^7 + 7^3 + 3^7 + 9^2$
2746 := $2^7 + 7^4 + 4^0 + 6^3$
2747 := $2^1 + 7^3 + 4^0 + 7^4$
2753 := $2^9 + 7^2 + 5^1 + 3^7$
2757 := $2^3 + 7^3 + 5^1 + 7^4$
2773 := $2^1 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 3^3$
2777 := $2^5 + 7^0 + 7^3 + 7^4$
2794 := $2^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^4$
2843 := $2^7 + 8^3 + 4^2 + 3^7$
2863 := $2^7 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 3^7$

2864 := $2^5 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^5$
2932 := $2^3 + 9^3 + 3^7 + 2^3$
2933 := $2^3 + 9^1 + 3^6 + 3^7$
2934 := $2^1 + 9^3 + 3^7 + 4^2$
2953 := $2^5 + 9^3 + 5^1 + 3^7$
2973 := $2^3 + 9^3 + 7^2 + 3^7$
2978 := $2^6 + 9^0 + 7^4 + 8^3$
2994 := $2^9 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 4^5$
3145 := $3^1 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 5^5$
3147 := $3^6 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 7^4$
3154 := $3^3 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 4^0$
3165 := $3^1 + 1^0 + 6^2 + 5^5$
3167 := $3^6 + 1^0 + 6^2 + 7^4$
3212 := $3^7 + 2^9 + 1^0 + 2^9$
3214 := $3^7 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 4^5$
3215 := $3^4 + 2^3 + 1^0 + 5^5$
3235 := $3^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 5^5$
3237 := $3^4 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 7^4$
3238 := $3^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 8^3$
3244 := $3^7 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 4^5$
3254 := $3^4 + 2^5 + 5^5 + 4^2$
3255 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 5^3 + 5^5$
3257 := $3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 7^0$
3274 := $3^6 + 2^7 + 7^4 + 4^2$
3292 := $3^7 + 2^9 + 9^2 + 2^9$
3294 := $3^7 + 2^1 + 9^2 + 4^5$
3295 := $3^4 + 2^3 + 9^2 + 5^5$
3324 := $3^4 + 3^7 + 2^5 + 4^5$
3325 := $3^7 + 3^0 + 2^9 + 5^4$
3342 := $3^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 2^7$
3345 := $3^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3$
3374 := $3^5 + 3^6 + 7^4 + 4^0$
3385 := $3^2 + 3^5 + 8^1 + 5^5$
3429 := $3^7 + 4^0 + 2^9 + 9^3$
3432 := $3^6 + 4^1 + 3^7 + 2^9$
3435 := $3^1 + 4^3 + 3^5 + 5^5$

3436 := $3^2 + 4^5 + 3^7 + 6^3$
3437 := $3^1 + 4^5 + 3^2 + 7^4$
3453 := $3^4 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 3^5$
3454 := $3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 4^4$
3457 := $3^3 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2$
3474 := $3^7 + 4^4 + 7^1 + 4^5$
3475 := $3^1 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 5^5$
3476 := $3^7 + 4^5 + 7^2 + 6^3$
3477 := $3^1 + 4^5 + 7^2 + 7^4$
3492 := $3^7 + 4^3 + 9^3 + 2^9$
3496 := $3^7 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 6^4$
3523 := $3^3 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 3^5$
3525 := $3^5 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 5^5$
3527 := $3^3 + 5^5 + 2^5 + 7^3$
3543 := $3^4 + 5^5 + 4^4 + 3^4$
3566 := $3^2 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 6^3$
3569 := $3^7 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 9^2$
3612 := $3^7 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 2^7$
3625 := $3^5 + 6^0 + 2^8 + 5^5$
3635 := $3^3 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 5^3$
3652 := $3^2 + 6^1 + 5^5 + 2^9$
3657 := $3^7 + 6^4 + 5^3 + 7^2$
3674 := $3^5 + 6^1 + 7^4 + 4^5$
3678 := $3^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 + 8^3$
3692 := $3^7 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 2^7$
3706 := $3^2 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 6^4$
3723 := $3^4 + 7^4 + 2^9 + 3^6$
3724 := $3^7 + 7^0 + 2^9 + 4^5$
3725 := $3^4 + 7^1 + 2^9 + 5^5$
3726 := $3^3 + 7^4 + 2^1 + 6^4$
3746 := $3^7 + 7^1 + 4^4 + 6^4$
3749 := $3^5 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 9^2$
3756 := $3^6 + 7^4 + 5^4 + 6^0$
3764 := $3^1 + 7^4 + 6^4 + 4^3$
3765 := $3^4 + 7^3 + 6^3 + 5^5$
3786 := $3^4 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 6^4$

3856 := $3^1 + 8^3 + 5^5 + 6^3$
3940 := $3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 0^1$
3941 := $3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 1^0$
3942 := $3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 2^1$
3943 := $3^1 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 3^7$
3944 := $3^7 + 9^3 + 4^1 + 4^5$
3945 := $3^3 + 9^3 + 4^3 + 5^5$
3946 := $3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 6^1$
3947 := $3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 7^1$
3948 := $3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 8^1$
3949 := $3^7 + 9^1 + 4^5 + 9^3$
4098 := $4^6 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 8^0$
4099 := $4^6 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 9^0$
4102 := $4^6 + 1^0 + 0^0 + 2^2$
4114 := $4^2 + 1^0 + 1^0 + 4^6$
4132 := $4^6 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 2^5$
4133 := $4^6 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 3^3$
4136 := $4^6 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 6^2$
4147 := $4^6 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 7^2$
4150 := $4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 0^1$
4151 := $4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 1^0$
4152 := $4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 2^1$
4153 := $4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 3^1$
4154 := $4^1 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 4^5$
4155 := $4^5 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 5^5$
4156 := $4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 6^1$
4157 := $4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 7^1$
4158 := $4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 8^1$
4159 := $4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 9^1$
4162 := $4^6 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 2^6$
4173 := $4^6 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 3^3$
4179 := $4^6 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 9^2$
4194 := $4^2 + 1^0 + 9^2 + 4^6$
4209 := $4^6 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 9^2$
4224 := $4^3 + 2^5 + 2^5 + 4^6$
4225 := $4^6 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 5^3$

4226 := $4^6 + 2^0 + 2^7 + 6^0$
4227 := $4^6 + 2^1 + 2^7 + 7^0$
4228 := $4^1 + 2^6 + 2^6 + 8^4$
4229 := $4^6 + 2^2 + 2^7 + 9^0$
4234 := $4^6 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^0$
4240 := $4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 0^1$
4241 := $4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 1^0$
4242 := $4^2 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 2^7$
4243 := $4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 3^1$
4244 := $4^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 4^6$
4245 := $4^2 + 2^3 + 4^6 + 5^3$
4246 := $4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^1$
4247 := $4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 7^1$
4248 := $4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 8^1$
4249 := $4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 9^1$
4250 := $4^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 0^0$
4254 := $4^6 + 2^5 + 5^3 + 4^0$
4260 := $4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 0^1$
4261 := $4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 1^0$
4262 := $4^6 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 2^7$
4263 := $4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 3^1$
4264 := $4^1 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 4^6$
4265 := $4^6 + 2^3 + 6^2 + 5^3$
4266 := $4^6 + 2^7 + 6^1 + 6^2$
4267 := $4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 7^1$
4268 := $4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 8^1$
4269 := $4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 9^1$
4274 := $4^6 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 4^0$
4285 := $4^5 + 2^7 + 8^1 + 5^5$
4288 := $4^3 + 2^6 + 8^2 + 8^4$
4289 := $4^3 + 2^7 + 8^4 + 9^0$
4316 := $4^6 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 6^3$
4332 := $4^6 + 3^3 + 3^4 + 2^7$
4339 := $4^6 + 3^4 + 3^4 + 9^2$
4340 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 0^1$
4341 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 1^0$

4342 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 2^1$
4343 := $4^6 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 3^5$
4344 := $4^1 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 4^6$
4345 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^1$
4346 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 6^1$
4347 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 7^1$
4348 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 8^1$
4349 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 9^1$
4352 := $4^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 2^7$
4353 := $4^4 + 3^5 + 5^5 + 3^6$
4354 := $4^4 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 4^6$
4355 := $4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5$
4358 := $4^4 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 8^4$
4362 := $4^6 + 3^2 + 6^0 + 2^8$
4365 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 5^2$
4372 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 2^5$
4373 := $4^6 + 3^3 + 7^1 + 3^5$
4376 := $4^6 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 6^2$
4380 := $4^4 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 0^0$
4396 := $4^6 + 3^1 + 9^2 + 6^3$
4397 := $4^5 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 7^4$
4403 := $4^3 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 3^5$
4405 := $4^4 + 4^5 + 0^1 + 5^5$
4424 := $4^3 + 4^4 + 2^3 + 4^6$
4434 := $4^4 + 4^0 + 3^4 + 4^6$
4443 := $4^3 + 4^4 + 4^6 + 3^3$
4447 := $4^1 + 4^1 + 4^6 + 7^3$
4449 := $4^2 + 4^4 + 4^6 + 9^2$
4469 := $4^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^2$
4472 := $4^6 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 2^5$
4476 := $4^6 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 6^2$
4485 := $4^4 + 4^6 + 8^1 + 5^3$
4572 := $4^6 + 5^1 + 7^3 + 2^7$
4573 := $4^5 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 3^4$
4574 := $4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 + 4^5$
4599 := $4^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 9^3$

4622 := $4^6 + 6^1 + 2^3 + 2^9$
4623 := $4^6 + 6^1 + 2^9 + 3^2$
4644 := $4^4 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 4^6$
4648 := $4^1 + 6^2 + 4^6 + 8^3$
4649 := $4^4 + 6^3 + 4^6 + 9^2$
4685 := $4^4 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 5^5$
4732 := $4^2 + 7^4 + 3^7 + 2^7$
4733 := $4^2 + 7^3 + 3^7 + 3^7$
4735 := $4^5 + 7^3 + 3^5 + 5^5$
4736 := $4^6 + 7^3 + 3^4 + 6^3$
4738 := $4^6 + 7^2 + 3^4 + 8^3$
4826 := $4^6 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 6^3$
4830 := $4^1 + 8^4 + 3^6 + 0^0$
4834 := $4^6 + 8^1 + 3^6 + 4^0$
4849 := $4^2 + 8^1 + 4^6 + 9^3$
4869 := $4^6 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 9^3$
4890 := $4^3 + 8^4 + 9^3 + 0^0$
4932 := $4^6 + 9^2 + 3^5 + 2^9$
4933 := $4^6 + 9^2 + 3^3 + 3^6$
4950 := $4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 0^1$
4951 := $4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 1^0$
4952 := $4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 2^1$
4953 := $4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 3^1$
4954 := $4^1 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 4^6$
4955 := $4^6 + 9^3 + 5^1 + 5^3$
4956 := $4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 6^1$
4957 := $4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 7^1$
4958 := $4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 8^1$
4959 := $4^5 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 9^3$
5234 := $5^4 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^6$
5258 := $5^2 + 2^9 + 5^4 + 8^4$
5276 := $5^5 + 2^9 + 7^3 + 6^4$
5314 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 4^0$
5320 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 0^1$
5321 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 1^0$
5322 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 2^1 + 2^3$

5323 := $5^5 + 3^1 + 2^3 + 3^7$
5324 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 4^1$
5325 := $5^1 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 5^5$
5326 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 6^1$
5327 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 7^1$
5328 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 8^1$
5329 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 9^1$
5342 := $5^1 + 3^6 + 4^6 + 2^9$
5343 := $5^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 3^7$
5344 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 4^2$
5364 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 4^2$
5366 := $5^5 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 6^4$
5367 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 6^1 + 7^2$
5384 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 8^1 + 4^3$
5394 := $5^5 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 4^0$
5446 := $5^5 + 4^0 + 4^5 + 6^4$
5453 := $5^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 3^7$
5547 := $5^1 + 5^5 + 4^2 + 7^4$
5567 := $5^1 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4$
5653 := $5^3 + 6^3 + 5^5 + 3^7$
5657 := $5^3 + 6^1 + 5^5 + 7^4$
5746 := $5^5 + 7^4 + 4^1 + 6^3$
5766 := $5^5 + 7^2 + 6^4 + 6^4$
5832 := $5^5 + 8^1 + 3^7 + 2^9$
5833 := $5^5 + 8^3 + 3^2 + 3^7$
5858 := $5^4 + 8^3 + 5^4 + 8^4$
5873 := $5^5 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 3^7$
5877 := $5^5 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 7^4$
6247 := $6^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 7^3$
6249 := $6^4 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 9^3$
6424 := $6^4 + 4^5 + 2^3 + 4^6$
6443 := $6^4 + 4^5 + 4^6 + 3^3$
6569 := $6^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 9^4$
6573 := $6^1 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 3^8$
6579 := $6^1 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 9^4$
6593 := $6^1 + 5^2 + 9^0 + 3^8$

$6599 := 6^2 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 9^4$	$7836 := 7^2 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 6^5$	$9027 := 9^4 + 0^0 + 2^6 + 7^4$
$6603 := 6^1 + 6^2 + 0^1 + 3^8$	$7906 := 7^2 + 9^2 + 0^1 + 6^5$	$9236 := 9^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^5$
$6632 := 6^1 + 6^0 + 3^8 + 2^6$	$7928 := 7^3 + 9^4 + 2^9 + 8^3$	$9237 := 9^4 + 2^5 + 3^5 + 7^4$
$6634 := 6^2 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 4^0$	$7944 := 7^3 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 4^5$	$9324 := 9^4 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 4^3$
$6649 := 6^2 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$7962 := 7^2 + 9^1 + 6^5 + 2^7$	$9347 := 9^4 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3$
$6669 := 6^2 + 6^2 + 6^2 + 9^4$	$7964 := 7^3 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 4^5$	$9362 := 9^3 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 2^7$
$6689 := 6^4 + 6^4 + 8^4 + 9^0$	$8194 := 8^4 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 4^6$	$9385 := 9^4 + 3^7 + 8^3 + 5^3$
$6714 := 6^3 + 7^4 + 1^0 + 4^6$	$8208 := 8^4 + 2^4 + 0^1 + 8^4$	$9474 := 9^4 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 4^4$
$6732 := 6^2 + 7^1 + 3^8 + 2^7$	$8224 := 8^4 + 2^4 + 2^4 + 4^6$	$9478 := 9^4 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3$
$6779 := 6^3 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 9^4$	$8228 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 2^5 + 8^4$	$9493 := 9^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 3^7$
$6792 := 6^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 + 2^3$	$8245 := 8^3 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5$	$9654 := 9^3 + 6^5 + 5^3 + 4^5$
$6793 := 6^3 + 7^1 + 9^1 + 3^8$	$8283 := 8^4 + 2^6 + 8^4 + 3^3$	$9693 := 9^3 + 6^3 + 9^4 + 3^7$
$6794 := 6^3 + 7^0 + 9^4 + 4^2$	$8288 := 8^2 + 2^5 + 8^4 + 8^4$	$9697 := 9^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 + 7^4$
$6849 := 6^3 + 8^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$8289 := 8^4 + 2^4 + 8^4 + 9^2$	$9723 := 9^3 + 7^4 + 2^5 + 3^8$
$6932 := 6^3 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 2^7$	$8316 := 8^3 + 3^3 + 1^0 + 6^5$	$9725 := 9^4 + 7^1 + 2^5 + 5^5$
$6934 := 6^2 + 9^2 + 3^8 + 4^4$	$8376 := 8^3 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 6^5$	$9947 := 9^3 + 9^4 + 4^4 + 7^4$
$6935 := 6^1 + 9^4 + 3^5 + 5^3$	$8396 := 8^3 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 6^5$	$9963 := 9^3 + 9^3 + 6^5 + 3^6$
$6937 := 6^1 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 7^3$	$8436 := 8^4 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 6^0$	
$6939 := 6^3 + 9^2 + 3^4 + 9^4$	$8443 := 8^1 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 3^5$	$10693 := 1^1 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 + 3^7$
$6972 := 6^2 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 2^5$	$8449 := 8^4 + 4^4 + 4^6 + 9^0$	$10694 := 1^1 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 + 4^6$
$6974 := 6^1 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 4^3$	$8536 := 8^3 + 5^1 + 3^5 + 6^5$	$12367 := 1^1 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$6976 := 6^2 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 6^2$	$8647 := 8^3 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 7^3$	$12386 := 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 6^5$
$7032 := 7^3 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 2^7$	$8667 := 8^3 + 6^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$12634 := 1^1 + 2^5 + 6^5 + 3^6 + 4^6$
$7123 := 7^2 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 3^8$	$8756 := 8^3 + 7^3 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$13132 := 1^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 2^3$
$7234 := 7^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^6$	$8825 := 8^4 + 8^4 + 2^3 + 5^4$	$13133 := 1^1 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 3^8$
$7279 := 7^3 + 2^5 + 7^3 + 9^4$	$8864 := 8^3 + 8^3 + 6^5 + 4^3$	$13173 := 1^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 3^8$
$7296 := 7^1 + 2^9 + 9^4 + 6^3$	$8970 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 0^1$	$13332 := 1^1 + 3^4 + 3^8 + 3^8 + 2^7$
$7299 := 7^1 + 2^1 + 9^3 + 9^4$	$8971 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 1^0$	$13337 := 1^1 + 3^7 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 7^4$
$7323 := 7^1 + 3^5 + 2^9 + 3^8$	$8972 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 2^1$	$13373 := 1^1 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 3^8$
$7329 := 7^1 + 3^6 + 2^5 + 9^4$	$8973 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 3^1$	$13393 := 1^1 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 9^4 + 3^8$
$7343 := 7^2 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 3^8$	$8974 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 4^1$	$13443 := 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 3^8$
$7363 := 7^3 + 3^5 + 6^3 + 3^8$	$8975 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 5^1$	$13933 := 1^1 + 3^4 + 9^3 + 3^8 + 3^8$
$7432 := 7^3 + 4^2 + 3^8 + 2^9$	$8976 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 6^1$	$13978 := 1^1 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 8^3$
$7530 := 7^3 + 5^4 + 3^8 + 0^0$	$8977 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^1 + 7^4$	$14276 := 1^1 + 4^6 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 6^5$
$7632 := 7^3 + 6^3 + 3^8 + 2^9$	$8978 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 8^1$	$14295 := 1^1 + 4^6 + 2^9 + 9^4 + 5^5$
$7639 := 7^3 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 9^4$	$8979 := 8^1 + 9^1 + 7^4 + 9^4$	$14346 := 1^1 + 4^1 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^5$
		$14362 := 1^1 + 4^2 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 2^3$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| 14363 := $1^1 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 6^5 + 3^8$ | 15964 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^2 + 6^0 + 4^4$ | 16475 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 5^1$ |
| 14369 := $1^1 + 4^1 + 3^3 + 6^5 + 9^4$ | 15970 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 0^1$ | 16476 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 6^2$ |
| 14697 := $1^1 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 9^4 + 7^3$ | 15971 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 1^0$ | 16477 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 7^2$ |
| 14786 := $1^1 + 4^6 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 6^5$ | 15972 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 2^1$ | 16478 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1$ |
| 15629 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 9^0$ | 15973 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 3^1$ | 16479 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^2$ |
| 15630 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 0^1$ | 15974 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 4^1$ | 16482 := $1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 8^2 + 2^5$ |
| 15631 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 1^0$ | 15975 := $1^1 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 5^6$ | 16486 := $1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 8^2 + 6^2$ |
| 15632 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^2$ | 15976 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 6^1$ | 16494 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^3 + 9^1 + 4^7$ |
| 15633 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 3^1$ | 15977 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 7^3$ | 16524 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 2^7 + 4^7$ |
| 15634 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 4^1$ | 15978 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 8^1$ | 16543 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 3^3$ |
| 15635 := $1^1 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 5^6$ | 15979 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 9^1$ | 16547 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 7^0$ |
| 15636 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 6^1$ | 16346 := $1^1 + 6^5 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^5$ | 16634 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 6^3 + 3^3 + 4^7$ |
| 15637 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 7^1$ | 16357 := $1^1 + 6^0 + 3^6 + 5^6 + 7^0$ | 16742 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 2^3$ |
| 15638 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 8^1$ | 16359 := $1^1 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 9^3$ | 16743 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 3^2$ |
| 15639 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 9^1$ | 16363 := $1^1 + 6^4 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 3^8$ | 16754 := $1^1 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 5^2 + 4^7$ |
| 15644 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 4^2$ | 16402 := $1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 2^4$ | 16837 := $1^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 7^5$ |
| 15649 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 9^0$ | 16422 := $1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^2 + 2^5$ | 16857 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 7^5$ |
| 15653 := $1^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 3^0$ | 16423 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 2^0 + 3^0$ | 16874 := $1^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 4^3$ |
| 15658 := $1^1 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 5^6 + 8^0$ | 16424 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^5 + 4^7$ | 16879 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 8^2 + 7^5 + 9^0$ |
| 15664 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 6^2 + 4^0$ | 16426 := $1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^2 + 6^2$ | 16925 := $1^1 + 6^4 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 5^6$ |
| 15669 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 9^0$ | 16430 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 0^1$ | 16927 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 9^2 + 2^5 + 7^5$ |
| 15670 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 0^0$ | 16431 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 1^0$ | 16942 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 4^7 + 2^9$ |
| 15677 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 7^2$ | 16432 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 2^5$ | 16984 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 9^2 + 8^3 + 4^7$ |
| 15686 := $1^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 6^5$ | 16433 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^1 + 3^2$ | 17026 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 6^3$ |
| 15692 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 2^6$ | 16434 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 3^3 + 4^7$ | 17053 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 3^5$ |
| 15703 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 7^2 + 0^0 + 3^3$ | 16435 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 5^1$ | 17072 := $1^1 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 2^8$ |
| 15709 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 9^2$ | 16436 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 6^2$ | 17133 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 3^4 + 3^5$ |
| 15740 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 7^2 + 4^3 + 0^0$ | 16437 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 7^1$ | 17157 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 7^5$ |
| 15753 := $1^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 5^6 + 3^0$ | 16438 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 8^1$ | 17224 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 2^7 + 4^4$ |
| 15759 := $1^1 + 5^3 + 7^1 + 5^6 + 9^0$ | 16439 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 9^1$ | 17240 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 0^1$ |
| 15762 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 2^7$ | 16453 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 3^3$ | 17241 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 1^0$ |
| 15822 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 2^2 + 2^7$ | 16470 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 0^1$ | 17242 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 2^9$ |
| 15882 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 2^7$ | 16471 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 1^0$ | 17243 := $1^1 + 7^0 + 2^7 + 4^7 + 3^6$ |
| 15884 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 4^4$ | 16472 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 2^5$ | 17244 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 4^7$ |
| 15892 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 2^8$ | 16473 := $1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 3^4$ | 17245 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^1$ |
| 15934 := $1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 4^3$ | 16474 := $1^1 + 6^2 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 4^7$ | 17246 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^1$ |

17247 := $1^1 + 7^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^3$	17834 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 4^5$	20325 := $2^2 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 5^3$
17248 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 8^3$	17840 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 0^1$	20328 := $2^2 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^7 + 8^3$
17249 := $1^1 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 4^7 + 9^3$	17841 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 1^0$	20332 := $2^7 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 2^9$
17287 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 8^1 + 7^5$	17842 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 2^1$	20345 := $2^5 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^4$
17322 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 2^9$	17843 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 3^1$	20347 := $2^6 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 7^3$
17324 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 4^0$	17844 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 4^5$	20352 := $2^5 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 2^9$
17332 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 2^9$	17845 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 5^1$	20356 := $2^9 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^2$
17334 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^4$	17846 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 6^1$	20372 := $2^7 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 2^9$
17338 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 8^3$	17847 := $1^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 7^5$	20377 := $2^3 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 7^3$
17348 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 8^3$	17848 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 8^1$	20385 := $2^6 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^3 + 5^3$
17352 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 2^9$	17849 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 9^1$	20388 := $2^7 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 8^3$
17354 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 3^0 + 5^4 + 4^7$	17868 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 8^3$	20433 := $2^2 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 3^6 + 3^9$
17357 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$	17914 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 1^0 + 4^5$	20453 := $2^1 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 5^6 + 3^6$
17372 := $1^1 + 7^2 + 3^1 + 7^5 + 2^9$	17994 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 9^2 + 4^5$	20459 := $2^3 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 5^6 + 9^3$
17376 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 6^3$	18347 := $1^1 + 8^3 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 7^5$	20483 := $2^1 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 3^0$
17378 := $1^1 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 8^3$	18436 := $1^1 + 8^3 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 6^4$	20484 := $2^1 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 8^4 + 4^7$
17407 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 4^4 + 0^1 + 7^5$	18472 := $1^1 + 8^3 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 2^7$	20485 := $2^2 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 5^0$
17424 := $1^1 + 7^1 + 4^5 + 2^3 + 4^7$	18617 := $1^1 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 7^5$	20486 := $2^2 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 6^0$
17435 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 5^4$	18697 := $1^1 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 7^5$	20489 := $2^3 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 9^0$
17442 := $1^1 + 7^0 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 2^5$	18946 := $1^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 6^5$	20493 := $2^4 + 0^0 + 4^3 + 9^3 + 3^9$
17443 := $1^1 + 7^1 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 3^3$	19732 := $1^1 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 3^9 + 2^5$	20494 := $2^2 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 9^1 + 4^7$
17445 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 4^4 + 5^3$	19733 := $1^1 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 3^7$	20495 := $2^8 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 9^3 + 5^5$
17446 := $1^1 + 7^0 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 6^2$	19735 := $1^1 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 5^0$	20498 := $2^3 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^4$
17448 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 8^3$	19736 := $1^1 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 3^9 + 6^2$	20536 := $2^9 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 6^3$
17450 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 0^0$	19743 := $1^1 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 4^0 + 3^9$	20539 := $2^1 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 9^3$
17463 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 3^6$	19773 := $1^1 + 9^2 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 3^9$	20572 := $2^7 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 2^9$
17464 := $1^1 + 7^2 + 4^5 + 6^1 + 4^7$	19830 := $1^1 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 3^9 + 0^0$	20633 := $2^2 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 3^6 + 3^9$
17483 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 3^5$	20203 := $2^3 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 0^1 + 3^9$	20644 := $2^7 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 4^6 + 4^7$
17539 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 9^3$	20213 := $2^4 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 1^0 + 3^9$	20653 := $2^7 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 5^4 + 3^9$
17543 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 3^6$	20232 := $2^2 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 2^9$	20693 := $2^6 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 9^3 + 3^9$
17559 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 5^4 + 9^0$	20236 := $2^2 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 6^2$	20744 := $2^8 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 4^6 + 4^7$
17562 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 2^7$	20243 := $2^5 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 3^9$	20843 := $2^7 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 3^9$
17563 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 3^6$	20253 := $2^5 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 3^9$	20853 := $2^5 + 0^0 + 8^3 + 5^4 + 3^9$
17650 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 6^3 + 5^4 + 0^0$	20263 := $2^5 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 3^9$	20932 := $2^3 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 2^9$
17737 := $1^1 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 3^5 + 7^5$	20293 := $2^4 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 9^2 + 3^9$	20933 := $2^9 + 0^1 + 9^1 + 3^6 + 3^9$
17794 := $1^1 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 4^4$	20324 := $2^6 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 4^3$	20963 := $2^6 + 0^0 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 3^8$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| 20973 := $2^9 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 7^2 + 3^9$ | 22597 := $2^2 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 9^4 + 7^3$ | 23343 := $2^7 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^8$ |
| 20987 := $2^1 + 0^0 + 9^2 + 8^4 + 7^5$ | 22643 := $2^7 + 2^9 + 6^4 + 4^5 + 3^9$ | 23345 := $2^5 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^3$ |
| 21236 := $2^7 + 1^0 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 6^4$ | 22659 := $2^8 + 2^0 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 9^4$ | 23347 := $2^5 + 3^3 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3$ |
| 21345 := $2^9 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3$ | 22732 := $2^3 + 2^7 + 7^4 + 3^9 + 2^9$ | 23365 := $2^9 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 5^5$ |
| 21348 := $2^7 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^3$ | 22733 := $2^3 + 2^9 + 7^3 + 3^7 + 3^9$ | 23372 := $2^1 + 3^0 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 2^0$ |
| 21364 := $2^7 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 6^4 + 4^4$ | 22753 := $2^5 + 2^9 + 7^4 + 5^3 + 3^9$ | 23374 := $2^1 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 4^0$ |
| 21417 := $2^9 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 1^0 + 7^5$ | 22773 := $2^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 7^4 + 3^9$ | 23376 := $2^2 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 6^0$ |
| 21436 := $2^9 + 1^0 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 6^3$ | 22855 := $2^3 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 5^5 + 5^6$ | 23378 := $2^3 + 3^0 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 8^0$ |
| 21439 := $2^1 + 1^0 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 9^3$ | 22935 := $2^2 + 2^4 + 9^3 + 3^8 + 5^6$ | 23385 := $2^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 8^3 + 5^5$ |
| 21497 := $2^9 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 9^2 + 7^5$ | 22949 := $2^1 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 4^7 + 9^4$ | 23387 := $2^1 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 7^5$ |
| 21785 := $2^8 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 + 5^4$ | 22953 := $2^3 + 2^7 + 9^1 + 5^5 + 3^9$ | 23417 := $2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 1^0 + 7^5$ |
| 22195 := $2^2 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 5^6$ | 22954 := $2^1 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 4^7$ | 23433 := $2^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 3^8$ |
| 22235 := $2^4 + 2^0 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^6$ | 22955 := $2^4 + 2^7 + 9^4 + 5^4 + 5^6$ | 23435 := $2^7 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 3^9 + 5^5$ |
| 22243 := $2^9 + 2^9 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 3^9$ | 22958 := $2^2 + 2^8 + 9^4 + 5^6 + 8^3$ | 23436 := $2^5 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 6^3$ |
| 22253 := $2^1 + 2^0 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 3^8$ | 22964 := $2^1 + 2^4 + 9^4 + 6^0 + 4^7$ | 23437 := $2^1 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 3^8 + 7^5$ |
| 22259 := $2^3 + 2^0 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 9^4$ | 22973 := $2^5 + 2^7 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 3^9$ | 23438 := $2^5 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 8^3$ |
| 22315 := $2^6 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 5^6$ | 22994 := $2^3 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 9^4 + 4^7$ | 23439 := $2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 9^4$ |
| 22335 := $2^2 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 3^8 + 5^6$ | 22995 := $2^4 + 2^6 + 9^3 + 9^4 + 5^6$ | 23452 := $2^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 2^9$ |
| 22337 := $2^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 7^4$ | 23034 := $2^3 + 3^4 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 4^7$ | 23454 := $2^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 4^7$ |
| 22355 := $2^4 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 5^6$ | 23042 := $2^5 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 2^6$ | 23459 := $2^9 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 9^4$ |
| 22357 := $2^4 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 5^0 + 7^4$ | 23043 := $2^4 + 3^4 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 3^8$ | 23462 := $2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 2^9$ |
| 22372 := $2^4 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 2^8$ | 23046 := $2^6 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 6^2$ | 23464 := $2^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 4^7$ |
| 22373 := $2^5 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 3^9$ | 23053 := $2^1 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 3^9$ | 23472 := $2^3 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 2^5$ |
| 22374 := $2^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 4^4$ | 23056 := $2^5 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 6^3$ | 23473 := $2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 7^5 + 3^8$ |
| 22375 := $2^7 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 7^5 + 5^5$ | 23065 := $2^8 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 5^5$ | 23474 := $2^7 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 4^6$ |
| 22376 := $2^7 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 6^2$ | 23074 := $2^7 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 4^7$ | 23476 := $2^3 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 6^2$ |
| 22383 := $2^8 + 2^8 + 3^7 + 8^0 + 3^9$ | 23164 := $2^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 6^3 + 4^7$ | 23492 := $2^3 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 2^9$ |
| 22393 := $2^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 9^1 + 3^9$ | 23204 := $2^1 + 3^8 + 2^8 + 0^0 + 4^7$ | 23493 := $2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 3^3$ |
| 22395 := $2^6 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 9^4 + 5^6$ | 23234 := $2^5 + 3^0 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 4^7$ | 23496 := $2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 6^2$ |
| 22447 := $2^3 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 4^6 + 7^5$ | 23235 := $2^6 + 3^6 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 5^6$ | 23497 := $2^5 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 7^5$ |
| 22459 := $2^4 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 9^4$ | 23237 := $2^9 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 7^3$ | 23498 := $2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 8^3$ |
| 22533 := $2^6 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 3^3 + 3^8$ | 23239 := $2^7 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 9^3$ | 23527 := $2^1 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 7^5$ |
| 22537 := $2^2 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 7^3$ | 23324 := $2^3 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 2^7 + 4^7$ | 23529 := $2^7 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 2^9 + 9^2$ |
| 22538 := $2^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 8^2$ | 23325 := $2^1 + 3^1 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 5^5$ | 23543 := $2^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 4^1 + 3^9$ |
| 22539 := $2^4 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 9^4$ | 23326 := $2^5 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 2^7 + 6^4$ | 23546 := $2^7 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 4^2 + 6^5$ |
| 22595 := $2^7 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 9^4 + 5^6$ | 23327 := $2^1 + 3^6 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 7^4$ | 23548 := $2^8 + 3^7 + 5^4 + 4^7 + 8^4$ |

23549 := $2^3 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 4^1 + 9^3$	23828 := $2^4 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 2^5 + 8^4$	24164 := $2^1 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 6^5 + 4^7$
23562 := $2^4 + 3^4 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 2^6$	23835 := $2^2 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 3^9 + 5^2$	24166 := $2^2 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 6^5$
23563 := $2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 3^9$	23837 := $2^3 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 3^9 + 7^2$	24176 := $2^3 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 7^1 + 6^5$
23566 := $2^7 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 6^5$	23839 := $2^5 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 3^9 + 9^0$	24226 := $2^1 + 4^7 + 2^5 + 2^5 + 6^5$
23568 := $2^5 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^3$	23845 := $2^6 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 4^6 + 5^0$	24245 := $2^7 + 4^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5$
23584 := $2^1 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 4^7$	23846 := $2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 4^6 + 6^0$	24264 := $2^3 + 4^3 + 2^5 + 6^5 + 4^7$
23617 := $2^5 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 1^0 + 7^5$	23848 := $2^2 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 4^3 + 8^4$	24265 := $2^4 + 4^7 + 2^6 + 6^5 + 5^2$
23627 := $2^1 + 3^8 + 6^0 + 2^8 + 7^5$	23852 := $2^2 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 5^1 + 2^6$	24293 := $2^9 + 4^6 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^9$
23637 := $2^7 + 3^7 + 6^4 + 3^9 + 7^3$	23853 := $2^6 + 3^2 + 8^4 + 5^0 + 3^9$	24306 := $2^6 + 4^7 + 3^4 + 0^0 + 6^5$
23652 := $2^2 + 3^5 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 2^2$	23856 := $2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 5^2 + 6^2$	24308 := $2^4 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 8^3$
23653 := $2^3 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 3^5$	23857 := $2^2 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 5^2 + 7^2$	24316 := $2^7 + 4^7 + 3^3 + 1^0 + 6^5$
23655 := $2^7 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 5^3 + 5^6$	23858 := $2^5 + 3^2 + 8^4 + 5^6 + 8^4$	24324 := $2^5 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 4^6$
23657 := $2^7 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$	23863 := $2^1 + 3^4 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 3^9$	24332 := $2^5 + 4^6 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 2^9$
23659 := $2^8 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 9^0$	23869 := $2^3 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 9^2$	24334 := $2^9 + 4^2 + 3^3 + 3^9 + 4^6$
23673 := $2^3 + 3^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 3^8$	23875 := $2^6 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 7^1 + 5^2$	24336 := $2^9 + 4^6 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 6^2$
23674 := $2^9 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 7^0 + 4^7$	23892 := $2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 9^2 + 2^4$	24337 := $2^1 + 4^3 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 7^4$
23679 := $2^5 + 3^5 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 9^4$	23893 := $2^5 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 9^2 + 3^9$	24345 := $2^9 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^5$
23685 := $2^8 + 3^3 + 6^5 + 8^0 + 5^6$	23897 := $2^3 + 3^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 + 7^5$	24352 := $2^3 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 2^9$
23697 := $2^5 + 3^4 + 6^3 + 9^4 + 7^5$	23907 := $2^9 + 3^3 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 7^5$	24353 := $2^9 + 4^5 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 3^9$
23727 := $2^3 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 2^3 + 7^5$	23908 := $2^7 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 8^4$	24372 := $2^5 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 2^9$
23743 := $2^7 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 3^8$	23924 := $2^3 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 2^7 + 4^6$	24373 := $2^3 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 3^9$
23745 := $2^9 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 5^3$	23928 := $2^2 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 2^6 + 8^4$	24375 := $2^7 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 5^3$
23747 := $2^5 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 4^1 + 7^5$	23943 := $2^1 + 3^4 + 9^2 + 4^6 + 3^9$	24376 := $2^7 + 4^7 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 6^5$
23748 := $2^7 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 8^3$	23945 := $2^5 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 4^6 + 5^3$	24379 := $2^8 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 9^0$
23749 := $2^9 + 3^5 + 7^2 + 4^7 + 9^4$	23947 := $2^7 + 3^7 + 9^3 + 4^6 + 7^5$	24396 := $2^7 + 4^7 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 6^5$
23750 := $2^8 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 0^0$	23949 := $2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 4^6 + 9^2$	24397 := $2^1 + 4^5 + 3^1 + 9^4 + 7^5$
23764 := $2^7 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 6^4 + 4^4$	23967 := $2^9 + 3^4 + 9^4 + 6^1 + 7^5$	24423 := $2^7 + 4^1 + 4^6 + 2^9 + 3^9$
23776 := $2^6 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 7^5 + 6^0$	23988 := $2^6 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 8^4$	24426 := $2^1 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 6^5$
23783 := $2^1 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 8^4 + 3^9$	23989 := $2^7 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 8^4 + 9^2$	24436 := $2^5 + 4^0 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 6^5$
23785 := $2^2 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 8^4 + 5^0$	24034 := $2^6 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^7$	24464 := $2^5 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 6^5 + 4^7$
23789 := $2^1 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 8^4 + 9^0$	24036 := $2^8 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 6^0$	24467 := $2^1 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 7^2$
23804 := $2^3 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 0^0 + 4^2$	24037 := $2^8 + 4^6 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 7^0$	24483 := $2^1 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 3^8$
23812 := $2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 1^0 + 2^4$	24038 := $2^1 + 4^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^4$	24489 := $2^3 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 9^4$
23813 := $2^5 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 1^0 + 3^9$	24043 := $2^3 + 4^4 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 3^9$	24532 := $2^6 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 3^9 + 2^6$
23820 := $2^3 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 2^5 + 0^0$	24137 := $2^9 + 4^4 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 7^5$	24533 := $2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 3^0 + 3^9$
23823 := $2^4 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 2^0 + 3^9$	24157 := $2^7 + 4^6 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 7^5$	24536 := $2^3 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 3^5 + 6^5$

24572 := $2^5 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 2^9$	24845 := $2^2 + 4^5 + 8^4 + 4^6 + 5^6$	26493 := $2^5 + 6^3 + 4^0 + 9^4 + 3^9$
24576 := $2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 6^2$	24848 := $2^4 + 4^4 + 8^4 + 4^7 + 8^4$	26533 := $2^7 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 3^8 + 3^9$
24593 := $2^5 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 3^9$	24864 := $2^7 + 4^3 + 8^3 + 6^5 + 4^7$	26535 := $2^3 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 3^0 + 5^6$
24607 := $2^3 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 7^5$	24865 := $2^4 + 4^7 + 8^2 + 6^5 + 5^4$	26537 := $2^3 + 6^2 + 5^5 + 3^8 + 7^5$
24617 := $2^5 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 1^0 + 7^5$	24868 := $2^8 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 6^2 + 8^4$	26555 := $2^2 + 6^5 + 5^2 + 5^5 + 5^6$
24627 := $2^3 + 4^1 + 6^5 + 2^5 + 7^5$	24883 := $2^4 + 4^5 + 8^2 + 8^4 + 3^9$	26559 := $2^5 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 9^0$
24644 := $2^5 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 4^6 + 4^7$	24906 := $2^4 + 4^7 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 6^5$	26574 := $2^3 + 6^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 + 4^7$
24647 := $2^5 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 7^5$	24976 := $2^7 + 4^4 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 6^5$	26593 := $2^3 + 6^3 + 5^3 + 9^4 + 3^9$
24664 := $2^5 + 4^4 + 6^3 + 6^5 + 4^7$	24996 := $2^1 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 6^5$	26647 := $2^9 + 6^4 + 6^5 + 4^4 + 7^5$
24667 := $2^5 + 4^2 + 6^2 + 6^5 + 7^5$	25273 := $2^5 + 5^5 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 3^9$	26655 := $2^7 + 6^0 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 5^6$
24673 := $2^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 3^8$	25276 := $2^2 + 5^4 + 2^6 + 7^5 + 6^5$	26736 := $2^7 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 6^5$
24674 := $2^9 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 4^7$	25366 := $2^7 + 5^5 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 6^5$	26773 := $2^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 3^7$
24680 := $2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 0^1$	25389 := $2^8 + 5^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 9^3$	26793 := $2^9 + 6^2 + 7^0 + 9^4 + 3^9$
24681 := $2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 1^0$	25473 := $2^1 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 3^8$	26973 := $2^9 + 6^3 + 9^4 + 7^0 + 3^9$
24682 := $2^1 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 2^9$	25476 := $2^9 + 5^3 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 6^5$	27346 := $2^9 + 7^5 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 6^5$
24683 := $2^1 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 3^2$	25479 := $2^3 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^4$	27349 := $2^5 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 9^4$
24684 := $2^3 + 4^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 4^7$	25547 := $2^9 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 4^7 + 7^4$	27363 := $2^9 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 6^5 + 3^7$
24685 := $2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 5^1$	25653 := $2^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 3^7$	27463 := $2^1 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 3^9$
24686 := $2^3 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 8^3 + 6^5$	25723 := $2^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 2^9 + 3^9$	27469 := $2^2 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4$
24687 := $2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 7^1$	25764 := $2^5 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 4^5$	27473 := $2^1 + 7^1 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 3^8$
24688 := $2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 8^3$	25867 := $2^6 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 6^5 + 7^4$	27479 := $2^3 + 7^1 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 9^4$
24689 := $2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 9^1$	26247 := $2^7 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 7^5$	27493 := $2^1 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 3^3$
24697 := $2^5 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 9^4 + 7^5$	26293 := $2^4 + 6^0 + 2^5 + 9^4 + 3^9$	27497 := $2^5 + 7^0 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 7^5$
24716 := $2^7 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 6^5$	26309 := $2^6 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 9^4$	27549 := $2^5 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 4^5 + 9^4$
24736 := $2^3 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 6^5$	26313 := $2^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 3^9$	27568 := $2^6 + 7^1 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 8^4$
24737 := $2^1 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 3^8 + 7^5$	26333 := $2^1 + 6^1 + 3^4 + 3^8 + 3^9$	27635 := $2^1 + 7^2 + 6^5 + 3^9 + 5^3$
24756 := $2^5 + 4^2 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 6^5$	26337 := $2^3 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 7^2$	27637 := $2^7 + 7^0 + 6^5 + 3^9 + 7^2$
24759 := $2^1 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 9^3$	26339 := $2^3 + 6^1 + 3^4 + 3^9 + 9^4$	27749 := $2^1 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 9^4$
24760 := $2^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 6^5 + 0^0$	26354 := $2^1 + 6^5 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 4^7$	27765 := $2^3 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 5^5$
24773 := $2^5 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 3^9$	26364 := $2^4 + 6^0 + 3^7 + 6^5 + 4^7$	27856 := $2^4 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 5^6 + 6^5$
24776 := $2^7 + 4^2 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 6^5$	26379 := $2^7 + 6^1 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 9^4$	27965 := $2^8 + 7^5 + 9^0 + 6^5 + 5^5$
24796 := $2^7 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 6^5$	26393 := $2^5 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 9^4 + 3^9$	27984 := $2^3 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 4^6$
24803 := $2^9 + 4^6 + 8^3 + 0^1 + 3^9$	26394 := $2^7 + 6^1 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 4^2$	28036 := $2^6 + 8^3 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 6^5$
24823 := $2^2 + 4^5 + 8^4 + 2^4 + 3^9$	26437 := $2^8 + 6^0 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^4$	28264 := $2^2 + 8^4 + 2^2 + 6^5 + 4^7$
24836 := $2^5 + 4^5 + 8^4 + 3^9 + 6^0$	26443 := $2^5 + 6^5 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 3^7$	28265 := $2^8 + 8^4 + 2^9 + 6^5 + 5^6$
24843 := $2^5 + 4^5 + 8^1 + 4^6 + 3^9$	26483 := $2^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 8^1 + 3^7$	28388 := $2^9 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 8^4$

28533 := $2^6 + 8^4 + 5^6 + 3^7 + 3^8$	32743 := $3^8 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 4^6 + 3^9$	32828 := $3^3 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 2^4 + 8^5$
29259 := $2^8 + 9^4 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 9^4$	32749 := $3^9 + 2^3 + 7^4 + 4^6 + 9^4$	32829 := $3^3 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 9^0$
29385 := $2^3 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 5^5$	32780 := $3^1 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 0^0$	32830 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 0^1$
29435 := $2^1 + 9^4 + 4^3 + 3^9 + 5^5$	32781 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 1^0$	32831 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 1^0$
29474 := $2^5 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 7^4 + 4^7$	32782 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 8^5 + 2^3$	32832 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 2^5$
29543 := $2^5 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 4^7 + 3^8$	32783 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 8^5 + 3^2$	32833 := $3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 3^3$
29947 := $2^1 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 7^5$	32784 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 4^1$	32834 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^1$
29965 := $2^1 + 9^0 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 5^6$	32785 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 5^1$	32835 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 5^1$
29967 := $2^1 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 7^5$	32786 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 6^1$	32836 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 6^2$
30340 := $3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 0^1$	32787 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 7^1$	32837 := $3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 7^2$
30341 := $3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 1^0$	32788 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 8^5$	32838 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 8^2 + 3^0 + 8^5$
30342 := $3^8 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 2^0$	32789 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 9^1$	32839 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 9^1$
30343 := $3^1 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 3^9$	32798 := $3^3 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 8^5$	32840 := $3^1 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 0^0$
30344 := $3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 4^6$	32800 := $3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 0^1$	32842 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 2^5$
30345 := $3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 5^1$	32801 := $3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 1^0$	32843 := $3^2 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 3^0$
30346 := $3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^1$	32802 := $3^2 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 2^4$	32844 := $3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 4^3$
30347 := $3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 7^1$	32803 := $3^1 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 3^3$	32846 := $3^2 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 6^0$
30348 := $3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 8^1$	32804 := $3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 4^2$	32847 := $3^3 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 7^2$
30349 := $3^2 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 9^4$	32805 := $3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 5^2$	32852 := $3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 5^0 + 2^6$
30586 := $3^9 + 0^0 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 6^5$	32806 := $3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 6^1$	32853 := $3^3 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 3^0$
30867 := $3^7 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 + 7^5$	32807 := $3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 7^1$	32854 := $3^2 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 4^3$
30935 := $3^7 + 0^0 + 9^4 + 3^8 + 5^6$	32808 := $3^3 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 0^0 + 8^5$	32855 := $3^4 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 5^0 + 5^0$
30964 := $3^5 + 0^1 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 4^7$	32809 := $3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 9^1$	32856 := $3^4 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 6^0$
31255 := $3^1 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 5^6$	32810 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 0^1$	32857 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 7^2$
31558 := $3^5 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 8^2$	32811 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 1^0$	32858 := $3^2 + 2^4 + 8^2 + 5^0 + 8^5$
32045 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 5^6$	32812 := $3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 2^5$	32859 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 9^2$
32068 := $3^9 + 2^9 + 0^0 + 6^5 + 8^4$	32813 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 3^2$	32860 := $3^3 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 0^1$
32254 := $3^5 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 4^7$	32814 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^1$	32861 := $3^3 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 1^0$
32524 := $3^1 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 2^8 + 4^7$	32815 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 5^1$	32862 := $3^3 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 2^6$
32527 := $3^3 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 2^6 + 7^5$	32816 := $3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 6^2$	32863 := $3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 3^3$
32549 := $3^3 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 4^7 + 9^0$	32817 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 7^1$	32864 := $3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 4^3$
32556 := $3^2 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 6^4$	32818 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 1^0 + 8^5$	32865 := $3^3 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^1$
32565 := $3^1 + 2^4 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 5^6$	32819 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 9^1$	32866 := $3^3 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 6^1$
32570 := $3^2 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 7^5 + 0^0$	32820 := $3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 0^0$	32867 := $3^3 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 7^1$
32578 := $3^4 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 7^5 + 8^2$	32825 := $3^3 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^2 + 5^2$	32868 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 8^2 + 6^0 + 8^5$
32587 := $3^3 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 7^5$	32826 := $3^2 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 6^0$	32869 := $3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 9^2$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| 32872 := $3^4 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 2^3$ | 33068 := $3^1 + 3^4 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 8^5$ | 33775 := $3^2 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 5^3$ |
| 32873 := $3^2 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 3^4$ | 33084 := $3^2 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 4^3$ | 33777 := $3^4 + 3^4 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 7^5$ |
| 32874 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 4^3$ | 33087 := $3^3 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^2$ | 33778 := $3^4 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 8^5$ |
| 32877 := $3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 7^2$ | 33228 := $3^4 + 3^5 + 2^3 + 2^7 + 8^5$ | 33779 := $3^1 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 9^2$ |
| 32879 := $3^3 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 9^2$ | 33247 := $3^3 + 3^3 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^5$ | 33798 := $3^2 + 3^5 + 7^2 + 9^3 + 8^5$ |
| 32882 := $3^4 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 2^4$ | 33268 := $3^2 + 3^5 + 2^5 + 6^3 + 8^5$ | 33804 := $3^1 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 4^5$ |
| 32883 := $3^4 + 2^5 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 3^0$ | 33274 := $3^4 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 7^5 + 4^7$ | 33822 := $3^1 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 2^9$ |
| 32885 := $3^3 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 8^5 + 5^2$ | 33283 := $3^3 + 3^5 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^5$ | 33823 := $3^4 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 3^6$ |
| 32890 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 0^1$ | 33284 := $3^1 + 3^0 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 4^4$ | 33824 := $3^1 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 4^5$ |
| 32891 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 1^0$ | 33285 := $3^1 + 3^0 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 5^0$ | 33826 := $3^4 + 3^6 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 6^3$ |
| 32892 := $3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 2^5$ | 33286 := $3^3 + 3^5 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 6^3$ | 33828 := $3^2 + 3^3 + 8^3 + 2^9 + 8^5$ |
| 32893 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^1 + 3^4$ | 33287 := $3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 7^0$ | 33829 := $3^4 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 9^3$ |
| 32894 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 4^1$ | 33288 := $3^1 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 8^3 + 8^5$ | 33842 := $3^2 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 2^5$ |
| 32895 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 5^1$ | 33318 := $3^8 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 8^3$ | 33843 := $3^2 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 4^4 + 3^6$ |
| 32896 := $3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 6^2$ | 33338 := $3^1 + 3^4 + 3^5 + 3^5 + 8^5$ | 33844 := $3^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 4^5$ |
| 32897 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 7^1$ | 33398 := $3^4 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 8^3$ | 33845 := $3^3 + 3^0 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 5^2$ |
| 32898 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 8^5$ | 33427 := $3^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 7^5$ | 33846 := $3^2 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 6^2$ |
| 32899 := $3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^1 + 9^2$ | 33428 := $3^1 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 2^9 + 8^5$ | 33847 := $3^1 + 3^1 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 7^2$ |
| 32908 := $3^1 + 2^7 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 8^5$ | 33442 := $3^4 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 2^9$ | 33864 := $3^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 4^5$ |
| 32928 := $3^3 + 2^2 + 9^0 + 2^7 + 8^5$ | 33447 := $3^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 7^5$ | 33865 := $3^3 + 3^6 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 5^3$ |
| 32934 := $3^8 + 2^7 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 4^0$ | 33467 := $3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^5$ | 33882 := $3^2 + 3^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 2^9$ |
| 32948 := $3^1 + 2^5 + 9^2 + 4^3 + 8^5$ | 33485 := $3^3 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 5^4$ | 33884 := $3^1 + 3^4 + 8^1 + 8^5 + 4^5$ |
| 32949 := $3^9 + 2^7 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 9^4$ | 33486 := $3^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^3$ | 33954 := $3^8 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 5^3 + 4^5$ |
| 32968 := $3^3 + 2^7 + 9^1 + 6^2 + 8^5$ | 33508 := $3^2 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 8^5$ | 33957 := $3^7 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 5^5 + 7^4$ |
| 32969 := $3^9 + 2^7 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 9^4$ | 33538 := $3^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 3^6 + 8^5$ | 33974 := $3^3 + 3^3 + 9^3 + 7^5 + 4^7$ |
| 32980 := $3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 0^1$ | 33539 := $3^6 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 9^4$ | 33984 := $3^5 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 4^0$ |
| 32981 := $3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 1^0$ | 33578 := $3^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 8^5$ | 34036 := $3^8 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 6^5$ |
| 32982 := $3^1 + 2^1 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 2^7$ | 33580 := $3^4 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 8^5 + 0^0$ | 34038 := $3^1 + 4^5 + 0^1 + 3^5 + 8^5$ |
| 32983 := $3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 3^1$ | 33584 := $3^4 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 4^0$ | 34068 := $3^1 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 8^5$ |
| 32984 := $3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^1$ | 33648 := $3^4 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 4^3 + 8^5$ | 34146 := $3^4 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 6^4$ |
| 32985 := $3^1 + 2^3 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 5^3$ | 33685 := $3^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 5^3$ | 34205 := $3^7 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 0^0 + 5^6$ |
| 32986 := $3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 6^1$ | 33686 := $3^5 + 3^5 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 6^3$ | 34234 := $3^6 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7$ |
| 32987 := $3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 7^1$ | 33748 := $3^5 + 3^6 + 7^1 + 4^0 + 8^5$ | 34238 := $3^6 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 8^5$ |
| 32988 := $3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^1 + 8^5$ | 33756 := $3^3 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$ | 34274 := $3^3 + 4^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 4^7$ |
| 32989 := $3^1 + 2^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^2$ | 33757 := $3^2 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 7^5$ | 34298 := $3^6 + 4^3 + 2^3 + 9^3 + 8^5$ |
| 33028 := $3^1 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 2^8 + 8^5$ | 33772 := $3^1 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 2^7$ | 34325 := $3^7 + 4^7 + 3^0 + 2^7 + 5^6$ |

$34366 := 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^7 + 6^5 + 6^5$	$34981 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$35317 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 7^1$
$34367 := 3^8 + 4^1 + 3^9 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$34982 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 2^1$	$35318 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 8^1$
$34387 := 3^2 + 4^5 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 7^3$	$34983 := 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^7$	$35319 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 9^0$
$34388 := 3^1 + 4^5 + 3^4 + 8^3 + 8^5$	$34984 := 3^7 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 4^2$	$35320 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^3 + 0^0$
$34437 := 3^8 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^0$	$34985 := 3^7 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 5^2$	$35322 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^0 + 2^2$
$34439 := 3^1 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 9^4$	$34986 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 6^1$	$35326 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^3 + 6^0$
$34453 := 3^7 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 3^0$	$34987 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 7^1$	$35328 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^4 + 8^0$
$34474 := 3^1 + 4^4 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$34988 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 8^5$	$35334 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 4^2$
$34483 := 3^6 + 4^0 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 3^6$	$34989 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^1$	$35335 := 3^9 + 5^2 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 5^6$
$34498 := 3^6 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$34993 := 3^7 + 4^0 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$35337 := 3^3 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 7^0$
$34525 := 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 2^6 + 5^6$	$35038 := 3^4 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 3^7 + 8^5$	$35339 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^3 + 3^9 + 9^0$
$34528 := 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 8^5$	$35077 := 3^5 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 7^4 + 7^5$	$35340 := 3^3 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 0^0$
$34568 := 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$35080 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 0^1$	$35342 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 2^5$
$34638 := 3^4 + 4^5 + 6^2 + 3^6 + 8^5$	$35081 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$35346 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 6^2$
$34674 := 3^5 + 4^5 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$35082 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^0$	$35352 := 3^1 + 5^2 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 2^4$
$34677 := 3^1 + 4^5 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 7^5$	$35083 := 3^1 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 3^7$	$35358 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 8^4$
$34698 := 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$35084 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 4^1$	$35363 := 3^3 + 5^6 + 3^3 + 6^0 + 3^9$
$34727 := 3^4 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 7^5$	$35085 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$35367 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 7^2$
$34728 := 3^4 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 8^5$	$35086 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 6^1$	$35374 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 4^3$
$34746 := 3^1 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 6^4$	$35087 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^1$	$35378 := 3^1 + 5^3 + 3^4 + 7^4 + 8^5$
$34762 := 3^5 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 2^5$	$35088 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 8^5$	$35382 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 2^6$
$34766 := 3^5 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 6^2 + 6^4$	$35089 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 9^1$	$35390 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 0^1$
$34784 := 3^6 + 4^4 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 4^5$	$35178 := 3^1 + 5^1 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$35391 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 1^0$
$34786 := 3^6 + 4^5 + 7^2 + 8^5 + 6^3$	$35208 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$35392 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 2^1$
$34826 := 3^6 + 4^0 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 6^4$	$35228 := 3^7 + 5^0 + 2^4 + 2^8 + 8^5$	$35393 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 9^2 + 3^9$
$34834 := 3^2 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 4^5$	$35248 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 8^5$	$35394 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 4^1$
$34836 := 3^3 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 6^4$	$35287 := 3^4 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$35395 := 3^4 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 5^6$
$34844 := 3^3 + 4^0 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 4^5$	$35289 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 9^2$	$35396 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 6^1$
$34872 := 3^6 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 2^3$	$35309 := 3^8 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 9^4$	$35397 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 7^1$
$34873 := 3^2 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 3^6$	$35310 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 0^1$	$35398 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 8^1$
$34874 := 3^2 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 4^5$	$35311 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 1^0$	$35399 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 9^2$
$34892 := 3^5 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 2^7$	$35312 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 2^1$	$35435 := 3^9 + 5^3 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 5^6$
$34947 := 3^1 + 4^5 + 9^3 + 4^7 + 7^5$	$35313 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 3^9$	$35447 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 7^5$
$34948 := 3^9 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 8^3$	$35314 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 4^1$	$35450 := 3^9 + 5^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 0^0$
$34958 := 3^7 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 8^5$	$35315 := 3^9 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 5^6$	$35487 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 7^3$
$34980 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 0^1$	$35316 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 6^1$	$35488 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 8^5$

$35526 := 3^9 + 5^0 + 5^6 + 2^0 + 6^3$	$35934 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 4^1$	$36468 := 3^7 + 6^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 8^5$
$35553 := 3^5 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$35935 := 3^8 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 5^5$	$36473 := 3^3 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 3^9$
$35559 := 3^9 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 5^6 + 9^0$	$35936 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 6^1$	$36474 := 3^2 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 4^7$
$35562 := 3^9 + 5^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^7$	$35937 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 7^1$	$36478 := 3^2 + 6^4 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^5$
$35567 := 3^2 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^5$	$35938 := 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 + 3^3 + 8^5$	$36492 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 2^7$
$35572 := 3^9 + 5^0 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 2^8$	$35939 := 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 9^4$	$36497 := 3^9 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 7^3$
$35582 := 3^7 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 8^5 + 2^0$	$35978 := 3^1 + 5^5 + 9^2 + 7^0 + 8^5$	$36517 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 5^2 + 1^0 + 7^5$
$35586 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 5^4 + 8^5 + 6^0$	$35979 := 3^9 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 7^2 + 9^4$	$36544 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 5^1 + 4^4 + 4^7$
$35598 := 3^5 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 9^1 + 8^4$	$35984 := 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^0$	$36547 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 5^1 + 4^2 + 7^5$
$35625 := 3^9 + 5^2 + 6^2 + 2^8 + 5^6$	$35994 := 3^9 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 4^3$	$36549 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 4^5 + 9^0$
$35628 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 8^5$	$36074 := 3^9 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 4^7$	$36567 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5$
$35633 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^5 + 3^9$	$36104 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 1^0 + 0^1 + 4^7$	$36568 := 3^5 + 6^3 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^5$
$35650 := 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 0^0$	$36234 := 3^1 + 6^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^7$	$36573 := 3^4 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 3^9$
$35657 := 3^9 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 7^3$	$36239 := 3^7 + 6^5 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 9^4$	$36597 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 5^2 + 9^2 + 7^5$
$35688 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 8^3 + 8^5$	$36258 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 8^5$	$36605 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 6^4 + 0^1 + 5^6$
$35733 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 7^3 + 3^0 + 3^9$	$36268 := 3^7 + 6^0 + 2^4 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$36637 := 3^8 + 6^3 + 6^5 + 3^9 + 7^4$
$35738 := 3^6 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 3^7 + 8^5$	$36284 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 4^0$	$36656 := 3^9 + 6^4 + 6^5 + 5^3 + 6^5$
$35798 := 3^1 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$36294 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 2^1 + 9^1 + 4^7$	$36657 := 3^9 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$35809 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 9^3$	$36324 := 3^2 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 2^5 + 4^7$	$36693 := 3^6 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 9^3 + 3^9$
$35822 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 2^9$	$36342 := 3^3 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 2^5$	$36707 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 7^5$
$35823 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 3^0$	$36343 := 3^3 + 6^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^9$	$36708 := 3^5 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 8^5$
$35825 := 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^3 + 2^2 + 5^6$	$36346 := 3^3 + 6^2 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 6^3$	$36722 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 2^3$
$35829 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^1 + 2^9 + 9^0$	$36347 := 3^5 + 6^2 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$36723 := 3^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 3^9$
$35830 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 0^0$	$36348 := 3^4 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 8^5$	$36724 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 2^1 + 4^2$
$35845 := 3^5 + 5^6 + 8^4 + 4^4 + 5^6$	$36368 := 3^4 + 6^2 + 3^7 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$36734 := 3^3 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 4^0$
$35848 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 8^5$	$36382 := 3^1 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 2^7$	$36735 := 3^5 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 5^0$
$35870 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 0^0$	$36385 := 3^2 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$36742 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 2^5$
$35876 := 3^4 + 5^4 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 6^0$	$36412 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 2^7$	$36743 := 3^5 + 6^1 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 3^9$
$35885 := 3^3 + 5^6 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 5^6$	$36417 := 3^9 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 7^3$	$36746 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 6^3$
$35887 := 3^4 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$36427 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 7^3$	$36748 := 3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 4^4 + 8^5$
$35898 := 3^1 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$36435 := 3^3 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 3^9 + 5^3$	$36752 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 5^1 + 2^8$
$35902 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 9^2 + 0^0 + 2^9$	$36437 := 3^8 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 3^9 + 7^4$	$36789 := 3^5 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 9^2$
$35930 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 0^1$	$36438 := 3^5 + 6^3 + 4^5 + 3^7 + 8^5$	$36837 := 3^5 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 7^3$
$35931 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 1^0$	$36447 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 4^0 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$36845 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 8^3 + 4^5 + 5^6$
$35932 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 2^1$	$36454 := 3^9 + 6^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 4^7$	$36854 := 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 5^5 + 4^2$
$35933 := 3^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^8 + 3^9$	$36457 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^2$	$36874 := 3^1 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 4^6$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| 36877 := $3^9 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 7^5$ | 37358 := $3^6 + 7^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 8^5$ | 37953 := $3^5 + 7^4 + 9^0 + 5^6 + 3^9$ |
| 36880 := $3^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 0^0$ | 37359 := $3^5 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 9^0$ | 37997 := $3^9 + 7^2 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 7^5$ |
| 36882 := $3^2 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 2^3$ | 37372 := $3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 7^5 + 2^9$ | 38145 := $3^7 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^3 + 5^5$ |
| 36883 := $3^2 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 3^2$ | 37384 := $3^3 + 7^4 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 4^0$ | 38164 := $3^1 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 6^4 + 4^6$ |
| 36884 := $3^1 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 4^2$ | 37393 := $3^7 + 7^4 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 3^9$ | 38235 := $3^3 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 5^5$ |
| 36898 := $3^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 + 9^0 + 8^5$ | 37424 := $3^2 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 2^7 + 4^7$ | 38257 := $3^7 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$ |
| 36980 := $3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 0^1$ | 37428 := $3^1 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 2^9 + 8^5$ | 38324 := $3^6 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 2^1 + 4^6$ |
| 36981 := $3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 1^0$ | 37436 := $3^6 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 6^3$ | 38325 := $3^5 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 2^1 + 5^5$ |
| 36982 := $3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 2^1$ | 37438 := $3^4 + 7^4 + 4^0 + 3^7 + 8^5$ | 38343 := $3^4 + 8^1 + 3^7 + 4^7 + 3^9$ |
| 36983 := $3^1 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 3^7$ | 37442 := $3^3 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 2^7$ | 38345 := $3^2 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5$ |
| 36984 := $3^1 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^6$ | 37443 := $3^2 + 7^3 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 3^9$ | 38348 := $3^5 + 8^3 + 3^6 + 4^6 + 8^5$ |
| 36985 := $3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 5^1$ | 37449 := $3^4 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 9^2$ | 38349 := $3^3 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 4^6 + 9^3$ |
| 36986 := $3^7 + 6^1 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 6^4$ | 37482 := $3^5 + 7^3 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 2^5$ | 38383 := $3^6 + 8^3 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 3^7$ |
| 36987 := $3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 7^1$ | 37483 := $3^6 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 3^9$ | 38456 := $3^5 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 6^4$ |
| 36988 := $3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^1 + 8^5$ | 37484 := $3^7 + 7^4 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 4^3$ | 38470 := $3^9 + 8^0 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 0^0$ |
| 36989 := $3^7 + 6^4 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3$ | 37485 := $3^7 + 7^4 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 5^3$ | 38474 := $3^5 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 4^6$ |
| 37002 := $3^9 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 0^1 + 2^9$ | 37486 := $3^5 + 7^3 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 6^2$ | 38477 := $3^9 + 8^1 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 7^4$ |
| 37045 := $3^6 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 5^5$ | 37503 := $3^7 + 7^1 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 3^9$ | 38563 := $3^7 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 3^7$ |
| 37083 := $3^4 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 8^3 + 3^9$ | 37540 := $3^9 + 7^5 + 5^2 + 4^5 + 0^0$ | 38566 := $3^4 + 8^5 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 6^4$ |
| 37177 := $3^9 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 7^3 + 7^5$ | 37578 := $3^1 + 7^4 + 5^1 + 7^4 + 8^5$ | 38657 := $3^7 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 5^1 + 7^4$ |
| 37223 := $3^6 + 7^5 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 3^9$ | 37645 := $3^9 + 7^5 + 6^1 + 4^5 + 5^3$ | 38746 := $3^5 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 4^6 + 6^4$ |
| 37226 := $3^9 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 2^9 + 6^3$ | 37648 := $3^6 + 7^2 + 6^1 + 4^6 + 8^5$ | 38834 := $3^6 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 4^6$ |
| 37229 := $3^9 + 7^5 + 2^1 + 2^3 + 9^3$ | 37663 := $3^3 + 7^4 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 3^9$ | 38835 := $3^5 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 5^5$ |
| 37236 := $3^6 + 7^5 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 6^0$ | 37687 := $3^4 + 7^4 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 7^4$ | 39075 := $3^4 + 9^4 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 5^6$ |
| 37243 := $3^6 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 4^2 + 3^9$ | 37714 := $3^1 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 4^6$ | 39338 := $3^1 + 9^4 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 8^5$ |
| 37248 := $3^2 + 7^3 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 8^5$ | 37732 := $3^6 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 2^9$ | 39348 := $3^2 + 9^1 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^5$ |
| 37258 := $3^6 + 7^5 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 8^4$ | 37738 := $3^3 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 3^0 + 8^4$ | 39354 := $3^4 + 9^2 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 4^7$ |
| 37263 := $3^6 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 6^2 + 3^9$ | 37759 := $3^9 + 7^2 + 7^4 + 5^6 + 9^0$ | 39358 := $3^1 + 9^0 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 8^5$ |
| 37264 := $3^9 + 7^5 + 2^9 + 6^1 + 4^4$ | 37794 := $3^1 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 4^6$ | 39369 := $3^9 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 9^0$ |
| 37267 := $3^9 + 7^2 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 7^5$ | 37796 := $3^9 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 9^1 + 6^4$ | 39372 := $3^9 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 2^2$ |
| 37284 := $3^5 + 7^2 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 4^6$ | 37826 := $3^9 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 6^4$ | 39373 := $3^8 + 9^4 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 3^9$ |
| 37332 := $3^4 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 3^9 + 2^5$ | 37827 := $3^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 7^4$ | 39375 := $3^9 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 5^0$ |
| 37336 := $3^4 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 3^9 + 6^2$ | 37843 := $3^5 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 3^6$ | 39377 := $3^9 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 7^0$ |
| 37345 := $3^6 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^3$ | 37867 := $3^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 7^4$ | 39384 := $3^3 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 4^0$ |
| 37352 := $3^6 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 2^7$ | 37884 := $3^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 4^2$ | 39392 := $3^9 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 2^4$ |
| 37353 := $3^2 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 3^9$ | 37949 := $3^9 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 4^0 + 9^3$ | 39393 := $3^2 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 3^9$ |

39405 := $3^9 + 9^0 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 5^6$	39825 := $3^5 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 5^3$	43438 := $4^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 3^8 + 8^5$
39423 := $3^9 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 2^5 + 3^9$	39827 := $3^3 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 7^3$	43473 := $4^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 7^1 + 3^9$
39428 := $3^1 + 9^4 + 4^3 + 2^5 + 8^5$	39829 := $3^5 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 2^8 + 9^4$	43474 := $4^6 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 4^7$
39432 := $3^9 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 2^6$	39842 := $3^8 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 4^4 + 2^8$	43478 := $4^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 7^2 + 8^5$
39438 := $3^3 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 3^8 + 8^5$	39844 := $3^1 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 4^7 + 4^7$	43498 := $4^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 8^5$
39442 := $3^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 2^5$	39848 := $3^1 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 4^1 + 8^5$	43523 := $4^5 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 2^3 + 3^9$
39443 := $3^9 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 3^9$	39864 := $3^5 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 4^4$	43544 := $4^4 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 4^6 + 4^7$
39446 := $3^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 6^2$	39869 := $3^5 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 9^4$	43582 := $4^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 2^5$
39453 := $3^9 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 3^9$	39882 := $3^2 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 2^5$	43586 := $4^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 6^2$
39458 := $3^1 + 9^4 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 8^5$	39884 := $3^3 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 4^2$	43674 := $4^7 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 4^7$
39469 := $3^7 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 9^4$	39886 := $3^2 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 6^2$	43678 := $4^1 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 8^5$
39482 := $3^2 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 2^7$	39958 := $3^1 + 9^0 + 9^4 + 5^4 + 8^5$	43682 := $4^6 + 3^8 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 2^8$
39483 := $3^2 + 9^2 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 3^8$	40358 := $4^5 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^5$	43784 := $4^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 4^6$
39484 := $3^3 + 9^4 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 4^3$	40546 := $4^7 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 4^7 + 6^5$	43836 := $4^5 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 6^5$
39485 := $3^3 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 5^3$	40586 := $4^2 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 6^5$	43856 := $4^7 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 6^5$
39532 := $3^9 + 9^1 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 2^5$	40608 := $4^3 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 8^5$	43926 := $4^7 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 2^1 + 6^5$
39533 := $3^4 + 9^2 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 3^9$	40685 := $4^2 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 5^3$	43983 := $4^6 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 8^3 + 3^9$
39536 := $3^9 + 9^1 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 6^2$	40689 := $4^3 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 9^4$	44085 := $4^6 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 5^5$
39538 := $3^1 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 3^8 + 8^5$	40733 := $4^5 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 3^9$	44449 := $4^5 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 9^4$
39573 := $3^9 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 3^9$	40864 := $4^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 4^4$	44640 := $4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 0^1$
39578 := $3^5 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 8^5$	40893 := $4^7 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 9^3 + 3^9$	44641 := $4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 1^0$
39598 := $3^5 + 9^0 + 5^2 + 9^4 + 8^5$	40976 := $4^7 + 0^1 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 6^5$	44642 := $4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 2^1$
39608 := $3^5 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 0^1 + 8^5$	41697 := $4^7 + 1^0 + 6^5 + 9^3 + 7^5$	44643 := $4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 3^1$
39623 := $3^9 + 9^1 + 6^3 + 2^5 + 3^9$	41987 := $4^4 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 7^4$	44644 := $4^1 + 4^6 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 4^7$
39628 := $3^4 + 9^4 + 6^3 + 2^1 + 8^5$	42598 := $4^2 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 8^5$	44645 := $4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 5^1$
39632 := $3^9 + 9^1 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 2^8$	42633 := $4^7 + 2^2 + 6^0 + 3^8 + 3^9$	44646 := $4^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 6^5$
39648 := $3^3 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 8^5$	42693 := $4^7 + 2^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 + 3^9$	44647 := $4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 7^1$
39682 := $3^2 + 9^4 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 2^7$	42863 := $4^1 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 3^7$	44648 := $4^1 + 4^1 + 6^5 + 4^6 + 8^5$
39687 := $3^2 + 9^4 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 7^3$	42866 := $4^5 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 6^5$	44649 := $4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 9^1$
39689 := $3^5 + 9^2 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 9^4$	42973 := $4^7 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 3^9$	44683 := $4^2 + 4^6 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 3^3$
39734 := $3^9 + 9^1 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 4^2$	43148 := $4^6 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 8^5$	44735 := $4^5 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 5^5$
39735 := $3^9 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 5^2$	43307 := $4^4 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 7^5$	45583 := $4^1 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 3^8$
39752 := $3^9 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 2^7$	43363 := $4^7 + 3^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 3^9$	45835 := $4^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 3^8 + 5^5$
39754 := $3^8 + 9^0 + 7^5 + 5^0 + 4^7$	43383 := $4^7 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 3^9$	45879 := $4^5 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 9^4$
39758 := $3^4 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 5^1 + 8^5$	43428 := $4^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 8^5$	45899 := $4^1 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 9^4$
39823 := $3^5 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 3^5$	43434 := $4^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 4^7$	46372 := $4^7 + 6^5 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 2^7$

- | | | |
|--|--|--|
| $46373 := 4^7 + 6^5 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 3^9$ | $46739 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 9^1$ | $46825 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 5^3$ |
| $46663 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^0$ | $46742 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 4^0 + 2^5$ | $46843 := 4^2 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 3^7$ |
| $46668 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^0$ | $46743 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 3^4$ | $46849 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 4^3 + 9^0$ |
| $46672 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^2$ | $46744 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 4^0 + 4^3$ | $46850 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 5^3 + 0^0$ |
| $46674 := 4^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 4^0$ | $46746 := 4^1 + 6^2 + 7^2 + 4^0 + 6^6$ | $46854 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 5^3 + 4^0$ |
| $46675 := 4^2 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 5^0$ | $46749 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 4^0 + 9^2$ | $46862 := 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 2^7$ |
| $46680 := 4^2 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 0^0$ | $46753 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 3^4$ | $46863 := 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 3^7$ |
| $46682 := 4^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^3$ | $46759 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 9^2$ | $46913 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 3^5$ |
| $46683 := 4^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 3^2$ | $46764 := 4^3 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 4^0$ | $46915 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 5^0$ |
| $46687 := 4^2 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 7^0$ | $46770 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 0^1$ | $46922 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 2^3$ |
| $46695 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 5^2$ | $46771 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 1^0$ | $46923 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 3^2$ |
| $46698 := 4^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 8^0$ | $46772 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 2^1$ | $46924 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 2^1 + 4^0$ |
| $46705 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 5^2$ | $46773 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 3^1$ | $46926 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 2^8 + 6^6$ |
| $46710 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 0^1$ | $46774 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 7^2 + 4^3$ | $46930 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 0^1$ |
| $46711 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 1^0$ | $46775 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 5^1$ | $46931 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 1^0$ |
| $46712 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 2^1$ | $46776 := 4^2 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 6^6$ | $46932 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 2^8$ |
| $46713 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 3^1$ | $46777 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 7^2$ | $46933 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 3^5$ |
| $46714 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 4^1$ | $46778 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 8^1$ | $46934 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 4^4$ |
| $46715 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 5^1$ | $46779 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 9^1$ | $46935 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^4 + 5^3$ |
| $46716 := 4^1 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 6^6$ | $46786 := 4^2 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 8^2 + 6^6$ | $46936 := 4^4 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 6^6$ |
| $46717 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 7^2$ | $46790 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 0^1$ | $46937 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 7^1$ |
| $46718 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 8^1$ | $46791 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 1^0$ | $46938 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 8^1$ |
| $46719 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 9^1$ | $46792 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 2^1$ | $46939 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 9^1$ |
| $46723 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 2^0 + 3^0$ | $46793 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 3^1$ | $46946 := 4^3 + 6^3 + 9^1 + 4^0 + 6^6$ |
| $46724 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 2^1 + 4^0$ | $46794 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 4^1$ | $46953 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 3^3$ |
| $46726 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 2^6 + 6^6$ | $46795 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 5^3$ | $46954 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 5^2 + 4^4$ |
| $46729 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^0 + 9^0$ | $46796 := 4^1 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 6^6$ | $46959 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 9^2$ |
| $46730 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 0^1$ | $46797 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 9^2 + 7^2$ | $46970 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 0^1$ |
| $46731 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 1^0$ | $46798 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 8^1$ | $46971 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 1^0$ |
| $46732 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 2^6$ | $46799 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^1 + 9^2$ | $46972 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 2^1$ |
| $46733 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 3^3 + 3^3$ | $46802 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 2^7$ | $46973 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 3^5$ |
| $46734 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 3^2 + 4^3$ | $46803 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 3^4$ | $46974 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 4^4$ |
| $46735 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 5^2$ | $46805 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 0^1 + 5^3$ | $46975 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 7^2 + 5^3$ |
| $46736 := 4^2 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 6^6$ | $46809 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 0^1 + 9^2$ | $46976 := 4^2 + 6^3 + 9^2 + 7^1 + 6^6$ |
| $46737 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 3^3 + 7^2$ | $46823 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 3^3$ | $46977 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 7^2$ |
| $46738 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 8^2$ | $46824 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 4^2$ | $46978 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 8^2$ |

$46979 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 9^1$	$47690 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 0^1$	$48539 := 4^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 9^2$
$46986 := 4^4 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 8^2 + 6^6$	$47691 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 1^0$	$48562 := 4^5 + 8^0 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 2^8$
$46993 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 9^2 + 3^5$	$47692 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 2^1$	$48625 := 4^5 + 8^2 + 6^6 + 2^8 + 5^4$
$46994 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 4^4$	$47693 := 4^2 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 3^5$	$48650 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 0^1$
$46995 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 9^2 + 5^0$	$47694 := 4^1 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 4^5$	$48651 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 1^0$
$47016 := 4^2 + 7^3 + 0^1 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$47695 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 5^1$	$48652 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 2^1$
$47026 := 4^3 + 7^2 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 6^6$	$47696 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^1 + 9^3 + 6^6$	$48653 := 4^2 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 3^5$
$47064 := 4^3 + 7^3 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$47697 := 4^4 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 7^2$	$48654 := 4^1 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 4^4$
$47065 := 4^3 + 7^3 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 5^0$	$47698 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 8^1$	$48655 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 5^6$
$47068 := 4^1 + 7^3 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 8^2$	$47699 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 9^3$	$48656 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$47096 := 4^2 + 7^3 + 0^1 + 9^2 + 6^6$	$47726 := 4^4 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 6^6$	$48657 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 7^1$
$47163 := 4^4 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 3^5$	$47746 := 4^2 + 7^0 + 7^2 + 4^5 + 6^6$	$48658 := 4^4 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 8^5$
$47186 := 4^2 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 8^3 + 6^6$	$47762 := 4^5 + 7^0 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 2^5$	$48659 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 9^1$
$47236 := 4^2 + 7^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 6^6$	$47763 := 4^5 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 3^4$	$48664 := 4^4 + 8^3 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 4^5$
$47256 := 4^1 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 5^3 + 6^6$	$47766 := 4^5 + 7^0 + 7^2 + 6^2 + 6^6$	$48667 := 4^1 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 7^3$
$47260 := 4^1 + 7^3 + 2^8 + 6^6 + 0^0$	$47768 := 4^4 + 7^0 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 8^3$	$48753 := 4^2 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 3^0$
$47264 := 4^4 + 7^3 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$47769 := 4^5 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 9^2$	$48863 := 4^1 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 3^7$
$47296 := 4^4 + 7^3 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 6^6$	$47786 := 4^5 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 6^6$	$48936 := 4^1 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 3^7 + 6^6$
$47306 := 4^3 + 7^3 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$47944 := 4^6 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 4^7$	$49168 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 8^5$
$47346 := 4^3 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^6$	$47946 := 4^4 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 4^5 + 6^6$	$49218 := 4^7 + 9^0 + 2^6 + 1^0 + 8^5$
$47362 := 4^3 + 7^2 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 2^9$	$47962 := 4^2 + 7^2 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 2^9$	$49236 := 4^4 + 9^1 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 6^6$
$47363 := 4^4 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 3^4$	$47966 := 4^1 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 6^4 + 6^6$	$49238 := 4^7 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 8^5$
$47367 := 4^2 + 7^3 + 3^2 + 6^6 + 7^3$	$47967 := 4^2 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 7^5$	$49282 := 4^7 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^7$
$47368 := 4^4 + 7^1 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 8^5$	$47968 := 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 8^3$	$49298 := 4^7 + 9^0 + 2^6 + 9^2 + 8^5$
$47426 := 4^4 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^9 + 6^6$	$48226 := 4^5 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 6^6$	$49364 := 4^4 + 9^1 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 4^4$
$47563 := 4^1 + 7^2 + 5^3 + 6^6 + 3^6$	$48264 := 4^3 + 8^1 + 2^9 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$49368 := 4^1 + 9^1 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 8^3$
$47633 := 4^1 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 3^6$	$48333 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 3^8$	$49385 := 4^7 + 9^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 5^3$
$47639 := 4^1 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 9^3$	$48396 := 4^4 + 8^3 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^6$	$49386 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 6^3$
$47643 := 4^4 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 3^6$	$48436 := 4^5 + 8^3 + 4^0 + 3^5 + 6^6$	$49418 := 4^4 + 9^1 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 8^5$
$47649 := 4^4 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 9^3$	$48458 := 4^7 + 8^0 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 8^2$	$49436 := 4^4 + 9^2 + 4^4 + 3^7 + 6^6$
$47652 := 4^2 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 2^9$	$48459 := 4^3 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 9^0$	$49498 := 4^4 + 9^1 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 8^5$
$47653 := 4^4 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 3^6$	$48464 := 4^2 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$49637 := 4^2 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 7^2$
$47673 := 4^6 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 3^7$	$48507 := 4^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 7^2$	$49678 := 4^2 + 9^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 + 8^5$
$47679 := 4^4 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 9^2$	$48522 := 4^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 2^0 + 2^6$	$49728 := 4^2 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 2^7 + 8^5$
$47683 := 4^5 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 3^0$	$48526 := 4^1 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 2^7 + 6^0$	$49784 := 4^3 + 9^2 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 4^3$
$47689 := 4^5 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 9^0$	$48535 := 4^2 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 3^0 + 5^6$	$49785 := 4^1 + 9^2 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 5^3$

49836 := $4^4 + 9^3 + 8^1 + 3^7 + 6^6$	52833 := $5^3 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 3^0 + 3^9$	53956 := $5^1 + 3^6 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 6^6$
49857 := $4^4 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 7^5$	52834 := $5^3 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 4^4$	54259 := $5^6 + 4^7 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 9^4$
49859 := $4^7 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 5^4 + 9^2$	52837 := $5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 7^5$	54363 := $5^5 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 3^5$
49872 := $4^4 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 2^5$	52857 := $5^3 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 5^5 + 7^5$	54367 := $5^3 + 4^5 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 7^0$
49876 := $4^1 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 6^3$	52877 := $5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 7^5$	54369 := $5^3 + 4^5 + 3^1 + 6^6 + 9^4$
49883 := $4^7 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 3^6$	53064 := $5^3 + 3^7 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 4^6$	54476 := $5^5 + 4^4 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 6^6$
49890 := $4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 0^1$	53078 := $5^4 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 8^5$	54566 := $5^1 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 6^6$
49891 := $4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 1^0$	53088 := $5^3 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 8^3 + 8^5$	54632 := $5^5 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 2^9$
49892 := $4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 2^1$	53226 := $5^1 + 3^8 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 6^6$	54633 := $5^5 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 3^3 + 3^6$
49893 := $4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 3^1$	53246 := $5^1 + 3^8 + 2^3 + 4^2 + 6^6$	54655 := $5^6 + 4^1 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 5^6$
49894 := $4^1 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 4^7$	53262 := $5^1 + 3^8 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 2^5$	54659 := $5^5 + 4^5 + 6^6 + 5^5 + 9^3$
49895 := $4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 5^1$	53263 := $5^1 + 3^2 + 2^5 + 6^6 + 3^8$	54748 := $5^5 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 4^5 + 8^5$
49896 := $4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 6^1$	53266 := $5^1 + 3^8 + 2^3 + 6^2 + 6^6$	54855 := $5^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 5^6 + 5^6$
49897 := $4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 7^1$	53346 := $5^3 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 6^6$	54873 := $5^1 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 3^9$
49898 := $4^7 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 9^3 + 8^5$	53356 := $5^1 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^6$	55336 := $5^5 + 5^5 + 3^5 + 3^7 + 6^6$
49899 := $4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^1 + 9^3$	53376 := $5^3 + 3^3 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 6^6$	55426 := $5^6 + 5^6 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 6^5$
49968 := $4^7 + 9^2 + 9^3 + 6^1 + 8^5$	53396 := $5^3 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 9^4 + 6^6$	55466 := $5^1 + 5^1 + 4^5 + 6^5 + 6^6$
49987 := $4^6 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 7^0$	53406 := $5^3 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 0^1 + 6^6$	55483 := $5^5 + 5^5 + 4^7 + 8^5 + 3^4$
50367 := $5^5 + 0^1 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^3$	53469 := $5^1 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^4$	55827 := $5^5 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 7^5$
50536 := $5^2 + 0^0 + 5^5 + 3^6 + 6^6$	53480 := $5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 0^1$	55843 := $5^1 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 3^8$
50635 := $5^3 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 5^5$	53481 := $5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 1^0$	56258 := $5^2 + 6^5 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 8^5$
50764 := $5^1 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 4^6$	53482 := $5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 2^1$	56298 := $5^6 + 6^5 + 2^7 + 9^0 + 8^5$
50827 := $5^6 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 7^4$	53483 := $5^1 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^9$	56344 := $5^5 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 4^0$
50876 := $5^1 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 6^4$	53484 := $5^1 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 4^5$	56347 := $5^5 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^0$
50886 := $5^3 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 8^4 + 6^6$	53485 := $5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 5^1$	56349 := $5^5 + 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 9^4$
50935 := $5^6 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 5^6$	53486 := $5^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 6^6$	56364 := $5^5 + 6^1 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 4^2$
52372 := $5^6 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 7^5 + 2^8$	53487 := $5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 7^1$	56382 := $5^5 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 2^5$
52498 := $5^6 + 2^3 + 4^6 + 9^0 + 8^5$	53488 := $5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^1 + 8^5$	56386 := $5^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 6^6$
52583 := $5^1 + 2^1 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 3^9$	53489 := $5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 9^1$	56433 := $5^1 + 6^6 + 4^5 + 3^7 + 3^8$
52708 := $5^5 + 2^3 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 8^5$	53628 := $5^4 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 2^6 + 8^4$	56439 := $5^5 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 3^4 + 9^4$
52726 := $5^5 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 2^9 + 6^6$	53647 := $5^3 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 4^4 + 7^2$	56563 := $5^1 + 6^3 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 3^8$
52748 := $5^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 4^2 + 8^5$	53649 := $5^3 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 9^4$	56632 := $5^1 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 2^3$
52768 := $5^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 6^2 + 8^5$	53843 := $5^3 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 3^9$	56633 := $5^1 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 3^7$
52783 := $5^5 + 2^1 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 3^4$	53862 := $5^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 6^6 + 2^7$	56634 := $5^5 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 4^4$
52789 := $5^5 + 2^3 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 9^2$	53863 := $5^3 + 3^2 + 8^3 + 6^6 + 3^8$	56639 := $5^5 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 3^4 + 9^4$
52832 := $5^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 2^7$	53886 := $5^5 + 3^0 + 8^1 + 8^4 + 6^6$	56673 := $5^1 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^7$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| 56682 := $5^6 + 6^0 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 2^9$ | 59138 := $5^3 + 9^4 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 8^5$ | 59312 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 2^8$ |
| 56749 := $5^5 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 4^3 + 9^4$ | 59139 := $5^1 + 9^2 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 9^5$ | 59314 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 4^4$ |
| 56858 := $5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 + 5^6 + 8^5$ | 59140 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 4^3 + 0^0$ | 59319 := $5^2 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 1^0 + 9^5$ |
| 56859 := $5^1 + 6^6 + 8^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$ | 59177 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 7^0$ | 59320 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 2^8 + 0^0$ |
| 56873 := $5^5 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 3^9$ | 59184 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 4^0$ | 59322 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 2^0 + 2^2$ |
| 56899 := $5^6 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 9^3$ | 59192 := $5^1 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 2^7$ | 59326 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 2^3 + 6^0$ |
| 56967 := $5^3 + 6^5 + 9^1 + 6^6 + 7^4$ | 59193 := $5^3 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 3^2$ | 59332 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^5 + 2^5$ |
| 56982 := $5^5 + 6^6 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 2^7$ | 59202 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 0^1 + 2^6$ | 59333 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 3^3 + 3^5$ |
| 57378 := $5^3 + 7^4 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 8^5$ | 59203 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 3^0$ | 59334 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 4^4$ |
| 57393 := $5^6 + 7^4 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 3^9$ | 59204 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 0^0 + 4^0$ | 59335 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 3^3 + 5^3$ |
| 57606 := $5^5 + 7^2 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$ | 59207 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 7^0$ | 59336 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^5 + 6^2$ |
| 57868 := $5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 6^5 + 8^5$ | 59208 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 0^0 + 8^0$ | 59337 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 3^4 + 7^0$ |
| 58563 := $5^4 + 8^4 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 3^8$ | 59222 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 2^5 + 2^7$ | 59339 := $5^3 + 9^2 + 3^1 + 3^4 + 9^5$ |
| 59038 := $5^2 + 9^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^5$ | 59223 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 2^7 + 3^2$ | 59340 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 0^0$ |
| 59056 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 6^0$ | 59224 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 4^2$ | 59347 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 7^2$ |
| 59057 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 7^0$ | 59226 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 2^7 + 6^2$ | 59353 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 5^3 + 3^3$ |
| 59060 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 0^1$ | 59227 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 7^2$ | 59356 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 5^1 + 6^3$ |
| 59061 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 1^0$ | 59230 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 0^0$ | 59357 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^2$ |
| 59062 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 2^0$ | 59234 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^0$ | 59362 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 2^6$ |
| 59063 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 3^1$ | 59240 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 4^3 + 0^0$ | 59367 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 7^2$ |
| 59064 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 4^1$ | 59241 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 1^0$ | 59373 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 7^2 + 3^5$ |
| 59065 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 5^1$ | 59242 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 2^1$ | 59375 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 7^2 + 5^3$ |
| 59066 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 6^1$ | 59243 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 3^1$ | 59379 := $5^1 + 9^2 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 9^5$ |
| 59067 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 7^1$ | 59244 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 4^3$ | 59382 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 8^0 + 2^6$ |
| 59068 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 8^1$ | 59245 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 5^3$ | 59392 := $5^1 + 9^0 + 3^4 + 9^5 + 2^8$ |
| 59069 := $5^1 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 9^5$ | 59246 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 6^1$ | 59394 := $5^1 + 9^2 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 4^4$ |
| 59072 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 2^4$ | 59247 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^2$ | 59399 := $5^2 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 9^2 + 9^5$ |
| 59076 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 6^0$ | 59248 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 8^1$ | 59406 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 6^3$ |
| 59077 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 7^0$ | 59249 := $5^3 + 9^1 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 9^5$ | 59423 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 2^5 + 3^4$ |
| 59083 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^3$ | 59263 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 6^1 + 3^4$ | 59426 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 2^5 + 6^3$ |
| 59084 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 4^0$ | 59267 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 7^2$ | 59432 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^8$ |
| 59092 := $5^2 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 9^5 + 2^4$ | 59269 := $5^1 + 9^2 + 2^7 + 6^1 + 9^5$ | 59434 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 4^4$ |
| 59093 := $5^2 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 9^5 + 3^2$ | 59282 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 2^4 + 8^2 + 2^7$ | 59442 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 4^4 + 2^7$ |
| 59103 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 0^0 + 3^3$ | 59283 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 8^2 + 3^4$ | 59443 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 4^4 + 3^2$ |
| 59120 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 2^6 + 0^0$ | 59286 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 8^1 + 6^3$ | 59447 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 7^0$ |
| 59137 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 3^4 + 7^0$ | 59302 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 0^0 + 2^2$ | 59456 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^0$ |

59462 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^3 + 2^7$	59733 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 3^2$	59913 := $5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 3^6$
59463 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^3 + 3^2$	59734 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 3^4 + 4^4$	59920 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 2^4 + 0^0$
59467 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 7^3$	59736 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 3^1 + 6^3$	59930 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 0^1$
59479 := $5^1 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 9^5$	59738 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 3^1 + 8^3$	59931 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 1^0$
59487 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 7^2$	59740 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 4^3 + 0^0$	59932 := $5^2 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 3^6 + 2^7$
59516 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 1^0 + 6^3$	59746 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 4^3 + 6^0$	59933 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^3$
59543 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 4^0 + 3^5$	59752 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 5^4 + 2^2$	59934 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 4^1$
59552 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 2^7$	59760 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 6^2 + 0^0$	59935 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 5^3$
59568 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 8^3$	59763 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 3^4$	59936 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 6^1$
59572 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 2^9$	59772 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 2^5$	59937 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 7^1$
59578 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 8^3$	59773 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 3^0$	59938 := $5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 8^3$
59588 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 8^3$	59774 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 7^3 + 4^4$	59939 := $5^3 + 9^1 + 9^3 + 3^3 + 9^5$
59592 := $5^1 + 9^0 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 2^9$	59776 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 6^2$	59940 := $5^4 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 0^0$
59596 := $5^3 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 6^3$	59788 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 8^0 + 8^2$	59957 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^2$
59602 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 0^1 + 2^9$	59790 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 0^1$	59968 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 8^2$
59606 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 6^3$	59791 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 1^0$	59974 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 4^3$
59622 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 2^8 + 2^8$	59792 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 2^3$	59992 := $5^1 + 9^2 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 2^7$
59623 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 3^0$	59793 := $5^1 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 3^6$	59993 := $5^3 + 9^1 + 9^2 + 9^5 + 3^6$
59634 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 3^5 + 4^0$	59794 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 4^1$	60289 := $6^3 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 8^3 + 9^5$
59638 := $5^4 + 9^4 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 8^5$	59795 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 5^1$	60294 := $6^3 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 4^5$
59647 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 4^4 + 7^0$	59796 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 6^1$	60349 := $6^4 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 9^5$
59674 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 4^4$	59797 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 7^1$	60359 := $6^4 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 9^5$
59677 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 7^0$	59798 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 8^1$	60379 := $6^4 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 7^1 + 9^5$
59682 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 8^0 + 2^0$	59799 := $5^1 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 9^3 + 9^5$	60397 := $6^4 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 7^2$
59683 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 8^3 + 3^4$	59802 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 0^1 + 2^6$	60409 := $6^4 + 0^1 + 4^3 + 0^1 + 9^5$
59684 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 4^0$	59822 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 2^7 + 2^7$	60483 := $6^5 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 3^9$
59688 := $5^3 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 8^3$	59823 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 3^6$	60593 := $6^4 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^5$
59689 := $5^4 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 9^5$	59824 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 4^4$	60595 := $6^4 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 5^3$
59690 := $5^4 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 0^0$	59830 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 3^5 + 0^0$	60853 := $6^5 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 5^4 + 3^9$
59692 := $5^4 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 2^4$	59843 := $5^2 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 3^0$	60859 := $6^4 + 0^0 + 8^3 + 5^0 + 9^5$
59693 := $5^4 + 9^1 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 3^2$	59846 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 4^3 + 6^3$	60922 := $6^4 + 0^0 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 2^9$
59703 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 3^3$	59863 := $5^1 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 6^3 + 3^4$	60938 := $6^4 + 0^1 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 8^3$
59725 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 2^0 + 5^0$	59883 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 3^4$	61495 := $6^4 + 1^0 + 4^5 + 9^5 + 5^3$
59726 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 2^1 + 6^0$	59904 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 4^0$	61654 := $6^5 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 5^5 + 4^6$
59728 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 2^2 + 8^0$	59905 := $5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^0$	62179 := $6^3 + 2^9 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 9^5$
59732 := $5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 2^3$	59912 := $5^1 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 2^7$	62285 := $6^6 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 8^0 + 5^6$

$62295 := 6^6 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 9^1 + 5^6$	$62759 := 6^4 + 2^3 + 7^4 + 5^1 + 9^5$	$63474 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 4^1$
$62315 := 6^6 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 5^6$	$62779 := 6^4 + 2^5 + 7^0 + 7^4 + 9^5$	$63475 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 5^1$
$62325 := 6^6 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 2^4 + 5^6$	$62794 := 6^4 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 4^2$	$63476 := 6^1 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 6^6$
$62352 := 6^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 2^6$	$62795 := 6^6 + 2^9 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 5^6$	$63477 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^1 + 7^5$
$62354 := 6^6 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 4^3$	$62797 := 6^4 + 2^1 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 7^4$	$63478 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 8^1$
$62355 := 6^6 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 5^6$	$62825 := 6^6 + 2^4 + 8^3 + 2^4 + 5^6$	$63479 := 6^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 9^5$
$62358 := 6^6 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 8^2$	$62858 := 6^6 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 5^6 + 8^3$	$63492 := 6^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 2^7$
$62365 := 6^6 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 6^0 + 5^6$	$62935 := 6^1 + 2^9 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 5^5$	$63493 := 6^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 9^5 + 3^7$
$62394 := 6^1 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 9^5 + 4^5$	$63042 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 2^0$	$63495 := 6^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 5^3$
$62395 := 6^3 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$63043 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 3^0$	$63497 := 6^1 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 7^3$
$62396 := 6^4 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 6^4$	$63044 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 4^7$	$63498 := 6^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 8^5$
$62397 := 6^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 7^4$	$63045 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 5^0$	$63522 := 6^6 + 3^6 + 5^6 + 2^8 + 2^8$
$62425 := 6^6 + 2^4 + 4^3 + 2^6 + 5^6$	$63054 := 6^6 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 4^7$	$63523 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 2^9 + 3^6$
$62466 := 6^5 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 6^5 + 6^6$	$63074 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 4^7$	$63527 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 7^5$
$62506 := 6^3 + 2^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 6^6$	$63124 := 6^6 + 3^4 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 4^7$	$63529 := 6^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 2^5 + 9^5$
$62519 := 6^3 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 1^0 + 9^5$	$63149 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 9^2$	$63544 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 4^4 + 4^7$
$62532 := 6^6 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 3^5 + 2^2$	$63234 := 6^6 + 3^4 + 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^7$	$63549 := 6^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 4^6 + 9^5$
$62533 := 6^6 + 2^3 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^5$	$63254 := 6^6 + 3^4 + 2^3 + 5^3 + 4^7$	$63568 := 6^3 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 8^5$
$62535 := 6^6 + 2^7 + 5^3 + 3^0 + 5^6$	$63293 := 6^4 + 3^6 + 2^5 + 9^5 + 3^7$	$63570 := 6^6 + 3^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 0^0$
$62539 := 6^4 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 3^7 + 9^5$	$63294 := 6^2 + 3^4 + 2^5 + 9^5 + 4^6$	$63584 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 8^3 + 4^7$
$62540 := 6^6 + 2^1 + 5^6 + 4^4 + 0^0$	$63324 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 2^8 + 4^7$	$63586 := 6^4 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 8^1 + 6^6$
$62542 := 6^6 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 4^1 + 2^8$	$63342 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 2^5$	$63605 := 6^4 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 0^0 + 5^6$
$62546 := 6^6 + 2^3 + 5^6 + 4^4 + 6^0$	$63346 := 6^2 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 6^6$	$63637 := 6^5 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 7^4$
$62553 := 6^6 + 2^2 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 3^5$	$63348 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 8^2$	$63659 := 6^4 + 3^0 + 6^6 + 5^6 + 9^2$
$62554 := 6^6 + 2^4 + 5^0 + 5^6 + 4^4$	$63364 := 6^3 + 3^3 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 4^7$	$63675 := 6^1 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 5^3$
$62562 := 6^3 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 6^6 + 2^6$	$63389 := 6^3 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$63679 := 6^1 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 + 9^5$
$62587 := 6^6 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 7^2$	$63412 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 2^7$	$63692 := 6^5 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 9^4 + 2^9$
$62594 := 6^2 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 4^4$	$63435 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 5^3$	$63695 := 6^3 + 3^2 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 5^5$
$62599 := 6^3 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 9^2 + 9^5$	$63436 := 6^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 3^8 + 6^6$	$63697 := 6^3 + 3^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^5$
$62625 := 6^3 + 2^6 + 6^6 + 2^6 + 5^6$	$63437 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 3^3 + 7^3$	$63706 := 6^3 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$
$62653 := 6^6 + 2^7 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 3^5$	$63438 := 6^5 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 8^5$	$63707 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 7^5$
$62657 := 6^6 + 2^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 7^3$	$63457 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^2$	$63708 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 8^0$
$62688 := 6^5 + 2^6 + 6^6 + 8^4 + 8^4$	$63470 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 0^1$	$63720 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 0^1$
$62749 := 6^4 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 4^0 + 9^5$	$63471 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 1^0$	$63721 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 1^0$
$62752 := 6^6 + 2^6 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 2^6$	$63472 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 2^2$	$63722 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^1 + 2^8$
$62753 := 6^6 + 2^7 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 3^0$	$63473 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 3^1$	$63723 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^4 + 3^5$

$63724 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^2 + 4^4$	$64283 := 6^6 + 4^7 + 2^1 + 8^3 + 3^6$	$64738 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 8^1$
$63725 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 5^1$	$64289 := 6^6 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 8^3 + 9^3$	$64739 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 9^1$
$63726 := 6^1 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 6^6$	$64334 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7$	$64744 := 6^6 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 4^5$
$63727 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 2^8 + 7^5$	$64337 := 6^6 + 4^3 + 3^4 + 3^6 + 7^5$	$64760 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 0^1$
$63728 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 8^1$	$64346 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^6$	$64761 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 1^0$
$63729 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 9^1$	$64364 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 4^7$	$64762 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 2^1$
$63734 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 4^0$	$64392 := 6^1 + 4^6 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 2^9$	$64763 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 3^1$
$63742 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 2^5$	$64394 := 6^3 + 4^5 + 3^2 + 9^5 + 4^6$	$64764 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 4^1$
$63744 := 6^6 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 4^2 + 4^4$	$64395 := 6^6 + 4^7 + 3^0 + 9^3 + 5^4$	$64765 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 5^1$
$63745 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	$64407 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 7^3$	$64766 := 6^1 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 6^6$
$63746 := 6^2 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 6^6$	$64445 := 6^6 + 4^4 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 5^3$	$64767 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 7^5$
$63747 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 4^4 + 7^5$	$64449 := 6^3 + 4^3 + 4^5 + 4^6 + 9^5$	$64768 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 8^1$
$63760 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 0^1$	$64464 := 6^4 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 4^7$	$64769 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 9^1$
$63761 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 1^0$	$64465 := 6^4 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 6^6 + 5^3$	$64776 := 6^4 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 6^6$
$63762 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 2^1$	$64487 := 6^6 + 4^4 + 4^4 + 8^3 + 7^5$	$64792 := 6^4 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 2^3$
$63763 := 6^3 + 3^1 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 3^4$	$64495 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 4^5 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$64793 := 6^4 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 3^2$
$63764 := 6^2 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 4^4$	$64497 := 6^6 + 4^0 + 4^5 + 9^1 + 7^5$	$64794 := 6^4 + 4^5 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 4^5$
$63765 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 5^1$	$64499 := 6^6 + 4^0 + 4^7 + 9^3 + 9^3$	$64795 := 6^3 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 5^5$
$63766 := 6^1 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^3 + 6^6$	$64533 := 6^6 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^7$	$64864 := 6^4 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 6^6 + 4^7$
$63767 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$64534 := 6^6 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 3^8 + 4^6$	$64934 := 6^2 + 4^5 + 9^5 + 3^6 + 4^6$
$63768 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 8^1$	$64555 := 6^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 5^6$	$64937 := 6^4 + 4^1 + 9^5 + 3^7 + 7^4$
$63769 := 6^3 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 9^2$	$64573 := 6^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 3^6$	$64958 := 6^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 8^3$
$63784 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 8^2 + 4^4$	$64593 := 6^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 3^7$	$65234 := 6^6 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^7$
$63834 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 3^6 + 4^7$	$64597 := 6^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 7^4$	$65276 := 6^4 + 5^1 + 2^9 + 7^5 + 6^6$
$63924 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 9^3 + 2^7 + 4^7$	$64624 := 6^4 + 4^4 + 6^6 + 2^5 + 4^7$	$65433 := 6^6 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 3^4 + 3^7$
$63942 := 6^2 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 2^5$	$64643 := 6^4 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 4^7 + 3^5$	$65447 := 6^6 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$63944 := 6^1 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 4^6$	$64687 := 6^4 + 4^7 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 7^3$	$65467 := 6^6 + 5^2 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^4$
$63946 := 6^2 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 6^2$	$64698 := 6^4 + 4^4 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 8^4$	$65473 := 6^6 + 5^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 3^3$
$63947 := 6^3 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 7^3$	$64730 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 0^1$	$65493 := 6^2 + 5^3 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 3^7$
$63985 := 6^4 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 5^5$	$64731 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 1^0$	$65545 := 6^1 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 4^8 + 5^0$
$63987 := 6^4 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 7^4$	$64732 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 2^1$	$65549 := 6^1 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 9^0$
$64035 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 3^6 + 5^6$	$64733 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^1 + 3^5$	$65604 := 6^1 + 5^2 + 6^2 + 0^0 + 4^8$
$64197 := 6^6 + 4^1 + 1^0 + 9^3 + 7^5$	$64734 := 6^6 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 4^5$	$65614 := 6^2 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 1^0 + 4^8$
$64224 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 2^5 + 2^7 + 4^7$	$64735 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 5^1$	$65634 := 6^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 3^4 + 4^8$
$64247 := 6^6 + 4^2 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 7^5$	$64736 := 6^1 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 6^6$	$65642 := 6^2 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 2^6$
$64267 := 6^2 + 4^4 + 2^9 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$64737 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^1 + 3^5 + 7^5$	$65647 := 6^2 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 7^2$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| 65649 := $6^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 9^2$ | 66351 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 1^0$ | 66536 := $6^2 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 6^6$ |
| 65674 := $6^1 + 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^0 + 4^8$ | 66352 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 2^1$ | 66594 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 5^4 + 9^0 + 4^8$ |
| 65676 := $6^5 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 6^6$ | 66353 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 3^9$ | 66623 := $6^2 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 2^5 + 3^9$ |
| 65693 := $6^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 3^7$ | 66354 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 4^1$ | 66632 := $6^2 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 2^8$ |
| 65694 := $6^2 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 4^8$ | 66355 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 5^1$ | 66647 := $6^5 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 4^6 + 7^3$ |
| 65704 := $6^2 + 5^3 + 7^1 + 0^1 + 4^8$ | 66356 := $6^1 + 6^1 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 6^6$ | 66732 := $6^3 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 2^7$ |
| 65724 := $6^1 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 2^7 + 4^8$ | 66357 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 7^1$ | 66734 := $6^2 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 4^2$ |
| 65743 := $6^1 + 5^3 + 7^2 + 4^8 + 3^3$ | 66358 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 8^1$ | 66737 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 7^3$ |
| 65747 := $6^2 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 4^8 + 7^2$ | 66359 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^1$ | 66752 := $6^2 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 2^7$ |
| 65749 := $6^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 4^8 + 9^2$ | 66362 := $6^1 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 6^6 + 2^4$ | 66829 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 9^5$ |
| 65750 := $6^6 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 0^0$ | 66373 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 3^9$ | 66840 := $6^1 + 6^4 + 8^0 + 4^8 + 0^0$ |
| 65764 := $6^1 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 6^3 + 4^8$ | 66374 := $6^2 + 6^3 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 4^8$ | 66842 := $6^4 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 4^8 + 2^3$ |
| 65783 := $6^6 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 3^7$ | 66377 := $6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 7^0$ | 66843 := $6^4 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 4^8 + 3^2$ |
| 65824 := $6^1 + 5^2 + 8^0 + 2^8 + 4^8$ | 66378 := $6^3 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 7^5 + 8^3$ | 66847 := $6^1 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 7^0$ |
| 65838 := $6^3 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 3^4 + 8^5$ | 66384 := $6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 4^0$ | 66849 := $6^2 + 6^2 + 8^3 + 4^8 + 9^3$ |
| 65839 := $6^3 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 3^8 + 9^5$ | 66392 := $6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 2^4$ | 66853 := $6^6 + 6^0 + 8^3 + 5^0 + 3^9$ |
| 65842 := $6^3 + 5^2 + 8^0 + 4^8 + 2^6$ | 66393 := $6^2 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 9^1 + 3^9$ | 66858 := $6^4 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 8^5$ |
| 65877 := $6^6 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 7^5$ | 66423 := $6^2 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 2^5 + 3^9$ | 66859 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 9^5$ |
| 65878 := $6^3 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 8^5$ | 66425 := $6^2 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 2^9 + 5^3$ | 66863 := $6^1 + 6^1 + 8^3 + 6^6 + 3^9$ |
| 65879 := $6^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 9^5$ | 66428 := $6^2 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 8^3$ | 66884 := $6^2 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 4^8$ |
| 65894 := $6^3 + 5^3 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 4^8$ | 66443 := $6^2 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 3^9$ | 66887 := $6^1 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 7^2$ |
| 65924 := $6^1 + 5^3 + 9^0 + 2^8 + 4^8$ | 66445 := $6^3 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 5^5$ | 66890 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 0^1$ |
| 65942 := $6^3 + 5^3 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 2^6$ | 66454 := $6^2 + 6^0 + 4^4 + 5^4 + 4^8$ | 66891 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 1^0$ |
| 65964 := $6^1 + 5^3 + 9^2 + 6^3 + 4^8$ | 66459 := $6^3 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 9^2$ | 66892 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 2^1$ |
| 66044 := $6^2 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 4^8$ | 66480 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 0^1$ | 66893 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 3^1$ |
| 66049 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 9^2$ | 66481 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 1^0$ | 66894 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 4^1$ |
| 66224 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 2^7 + 2^7 + 4^8$ | 66482 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 2^1$ | 66895 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 5^1$ |
| 66243 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 2^5 + 4^8 + 3^5$ | 66483 := $6^3 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 8^0 + 3^6$ | 66896 := $6^1 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 6^5$ |
| 66245 := $6^2 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 4^8 + 5^3$ | 66484 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 4^8$ | 66897 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 7^1$ |
| 66248 := $6^2 + 6^2 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 8^3$ | 66485 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 5^1$ | 66898 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 8^2$ |
| 66249 := $6^4 + 6^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 9^5$ | 66486 := $6^1 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 6^3$ | 66899 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^1 + 9^5$ |
| 66334 := $6^1 + 6^2 + 3^3 + 3^6 + 4^8$ | 66487 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 7^1$ | 66913 := $6^1 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 3^8$ |
| 66342 := $6^6 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 2^0$ | 66488 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^1 + 8^3$ | 66922 := $6^5 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 2^6$ |
| 66345 := $6^6 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^0$ | 66489 := $6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 9^1$ | 66923 := $6^4 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 2^4 + 3^8$ |
| 66347 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 7^0$ | 66532 := $6^2 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 2^5$ | 66926 := $6^2 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 6^5$ |
| 66350 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 0^1$ | 66534 := $6^1 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 4^3$ | 66934 := $6^2 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 4^3$ |

- | | | |
|--|--|--|
| $66937 := 6^2 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 7^2$ | $67639 := 6^2 + 7^2 + 6^5 + 3^6 + 9^5$ | $68754 := 6^2 + 8^1 + 7^2 + 5^5 + 4^8$ |
| $66938 := 6^1 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 3^9 + 8^3$ | $67643 := 6^4 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 3^9$ | $68777 := 6^6 + 8^3 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 7^5$ |
| $66939 := 6^1 + 6^4 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 9^5$ | $67672 := 6^4 + 7^4 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 2^9$ | $68825 := 6^2 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 5^5$ |
| $66943 := 6^2 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^8$ | $67685 := 6^6 + 7^5 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 5^3$ | $68885 := 6^3 + 8^1 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 5^5$ |
| $66952 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 2^0$ | $67693 := 6^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^9$ | $68958 := 6^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 8^5$ |
| $66953 := 6^4 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 5^5 + 3^7$ | $67729 := 6^5 + 7^2 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 9^5$ | $68959 := 6^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 + 5^5 + 9^5$ |
| $66954 := 6^2 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 5^1 + 4^8$ | $67743 := 6^1 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 3^7$ | $68976 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 6^5$ |
| $66957 := 6^1 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^0$ | $67803 := 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^4 + 0^0 + 3^5$ | $69013 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 1^0 + 3^7$ |
| $66974 := 6^2 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 4^3$ | $67896 := 6^3 + 7^3 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 6^5$ | $69093 := 6^4 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 9^5 + 3^7$ |
| $66993 := 6^1 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 9^5 + 3^8$ | $67898 := 6^5 + 7^2 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 8^3$ | $69146 := 6^4 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 4^5 + 6^5$ |
| $66995 := 6^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 5^3$ | $67904 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 0^1 + 4^8$ | $69236 := 6^3 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 6^5$ |
| $67144 := 6^6 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 4^7$ | $67923 := 6^5 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 3^5$ | $69237 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 7^4$ |
| $67184 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 4^8$ | $67929 := 6^5 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 2^5 + 9^5$ | $69253 := 6^1 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 3^8$ |
| $67234 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^8$ | $67944 := 6^4 + 7^1 + 9^2 + 4^5 + 4^8$ | $69274 := 6^4 + 9^1 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 4^8$ |
| $67240 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 2^6 + 4^8 + 0^0$ | $67945 := 6^1 + 7^4 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 5^0$ | $69277 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 7^2 + 7^4$ |
| $67295 := 6^5 + 7^3 + 2^1 + 9^5 + 5^3$ | $67947 := 6^5 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 7^2$ | $69307 := 6^4 + 9^5 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 7^4$ |
| $67297 := 6^5 + 7^0 + 2^7 + 9^5 + 7^3$ | $67965 := 6^4 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 6^6 + 5^5$ | $69343 := 6^4 + 9^2 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 3^7$ |
| $67322 := 6^6 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 2^7 + 2^9$ | $67984 := 6^4 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 4^7$ | $69349 := 6^4 + 9^4 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 9^5$ |
| $67325 := 6^6 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 2^3 + 5^5$ | $68072 := 6^6 + 8^4 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 2^9$ | $69362 := 6^4 + 9^5 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 2^9$ |
| $67343 := 6^1 + 7^3 + 3^6 + 4^8 + 3^6$ | $68243 := 6^1 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 4^8 + 3^7$ | $69434 := 6^1 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 3^7 + 4^6$ |
| $67344 := 6^1 + 7^2 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 4^8$ | $68264 := 6^4 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 6^4 + 4^8$ | $69435 := 6^2 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 3^6 + 5^5$ |
| $67348 := 6^4 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 8^3$ | $68449 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 9^2$ | $69453 := 6^2 + 9^3 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 3^3$ |
| $67389 := 6^5 + 7^2 + 3^1 + 8^3 + 9^5$ | $68574 := 6^6 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 4^7$ | $69473 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 3^5$ |
| $67413 := 6^6 + 7^2 + 4^5 + 1^0 + 3^9$ | $68640 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 0^1$ | $69475 := 6^2 + 9^3 + 4^8 + 7^2 + 5^5$ |
| $67432 := 6^4 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 2^9$ | $68641 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 1^0$ | $69524 := 6^1 + 9^3 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 4^8$ |
| $67434 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 4^2 + 3^5 + 4^8$ | $68642 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1$ | $69567 := 6^3 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4$ |
| $67459 := 6^4 + 7^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 9^0$ | $68643 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 3^1$ | $69634 := 6^1 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 3^3 + 4^7$ |
| $67465 := 6^4 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 6^0 + 5^4$ | $68644 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^1 + 4^8$ | $69648 := 6^1 + 9^1 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 8^4$ |
| $67480 := 6^6 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 0^0$ | $68645 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 5^1$ | $69742 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 7^4 + 4^1 + 2^9$ |
| $67493 := 6^6 + 7^2 + 4^5 + 9^2 + 3^9$ | $68646 := 6^1 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 6^4$ | $69743 := 6^2 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 4^6 + 3^8$ |
| $67543 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 3^5$ | $68647 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 7^1$ | $69749 := 6^2 + 9^4 + 7^1 + 4^6 + 9^5$ |
| $67549 := 6^5 + 7^3 + 5^3 + 4^4 + 9^5$ | $68648 := 6^4 + 8^1 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 8^3$ | $69787 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 8^3 + 7^4$ |
| $67585 := 6^6 + 7^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 + 5^2$ | $68649 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 9^1$ | $69854 := 6^3 + 9^0 + 8^4 + 5^1 + 4^8$ |
| $67624 := 6^6 + 7^5 + 6^0 + 2^6 + 4^6$ | $68669 := 6^2 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 6^5 + 9^5$ | $69924 := 6^3 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^6$ |
| $67634 := 6^1 + 7^4 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 4^7$ | $68739 := 6^3 + 8^3 + 7^4 + 3^8 + 9^5$ | $69952 := 6^5 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 5^5 + 2^0$ |
| $67637 := 6^4 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 7^0$ | $68753 := 6^6 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 5^1 + 3^9$ | $69965 := 6^1 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 5^5$ |

70347 := $7^4 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 4^8 + 7^4$	74293 := $7^1 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 3^7$	75974 := $7^2 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^5 + 4^3$
70367 := $7^3 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 7^5$	74323 := $7^1 + 4^8 + 3^7 + 2^5 + 3^8$	75983 := $7^5 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 3^0$
70478 := $7^5 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 8^5$	74334 := $7^2 + 4^0 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 4^8$	75990 := $7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 0^1$
70488 := $7^3 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 8^4$	74345 := $7^4 + 4^6 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 5^3$	75991 := $7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 1^0$
70685 := $7^5 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 8^4 + 5^5$	74346 := $7^1 + 4^5 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 6^5$	75992 := $7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 2^1$
72149 := $7^2 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 9^4$	74349 := $7^2 + 4^2 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 9^4$	75993 := $7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 3^1$
72234 := $7^1 + 2^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^8$	74363 := $7^5 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 3^8$	75994 := $7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 4^1$
72343 := $7^4 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 3^7$	74369 := $7^2 + 4^8 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 9^4$	75995 := $7^5 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 5^3$
72349 := $7^1 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 9^4$	74436 := $7^4 + 4^6 + 4^8 + 3^7 + 6^3$	75996 := $7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 6^1$
72364 := $7^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 4^8$	74437 := $7^4 + 4^6 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 7^4$	75997 := $7^1 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 7^5$
72385 := $7^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^5 + 5^5$	74498 := $7^4 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 8^5$	75998 := $7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 8^1$
72403 := $7^2 + 2^8 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 3^8$	74503 := $7^4 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 3^8$	75999 := $7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 9^5$
72434 := $7^2 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 3^8 + 4^8$	74616 := $7^1 + 4^8 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 6^5$	76079 := $7^1 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 7^5 + 9^5$
72443 := $7^3 + 2^1 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 3^8$	74632 := $7^4 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 3^8 + 2^7$	76149 := $7^5 + 6^2 + 1^0 + 4^4 + 9^5$
72449 := $7^3 + 2^3 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 9^4$	74633 := $7^3 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 3^7 + 3^8$	76234 := $7^4 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^8$
72453 := $7^3 + 2^3 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 3^8$	74659 := $7^4 + 4^8 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 9^4$	76274 := $7^2 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 7^4 + 4^8$
72473 := $7^3 + 2^5 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 3^8$	74696 := $7^1 + 4^8 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 6^5$	76294 := $7^3 + 6^1 + 2^9 + 9^5 + 4^7$
72479 := $7^1 + 2^5 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 9^4$	74763 := $7^2 + 4^8 + 7^4 + 6^3 + 3^8$	76296 := $7^5 + 6^3 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 6^3$
72497 := $7^2 + 2^3 + 4^8 + 9^4 + 7^3$	74896 := $7^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 9^3 + 6^5$	76299 := $7^4 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 9^4 + 9^5$
72694 := $7^2 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^4 + 4^8$	75019 := $7^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 1^0 + 9^5$	76329 := $7^5 + 6^3 + 3^0 + 2^8 + 9^5$
72747 := $7^4 + 2^3 + 7^4 + 4^8 + 7^4$	75099 := $7^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 9^2 + 9^5$	76369 := $7^5 + 6^3 + 3^4 + 6^3 + 9^5$
72984 := $7^3 + 2^5 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 4^8$	75336 := $7^5 + 5^5 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 6^6$	76443 := $7^4 + 6^5 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 3^6$
73396 := $7^1 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 6^5$	75354 := $7^1 + 5^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 4^8$	76445 := $7^1 + 6^5 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^5$
73426 := $7^2 + 3^0 + 4^8 + 2^6 + 6^5$	75449 := $7^1 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 9^5$	76452 := $7^1 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 2^3$
73446 := $7^2 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 6^5$	75846 := $7^4 + 5^3 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 6^5$	76453 := $7^1 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 3^2$
73464 := $7^1 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 6^5 + 4^8$	75859 := $7^5 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 9^5$	76454 := $7^4 + 6^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 4^8$
73465 := $7^4 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 5^5$	75890 := $7^5 + 5^2 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 0^0$	76479 := $7^3 + 6^3 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 9^5$
73469 := $7^2 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 6^4 + 9^4$	75907 := $7^2 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 7^5$	76495 := $7^2 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 9^1 + 5^5$
73482 := $7^5 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 2^7$	75922 := $7^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 2^6$	76529 := $7^5 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 2^9 + 9^5$
73604 := $7^2 + 3^5 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 4^8$	75926 := $7^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 6^0$	76589 := $7^5 + 6^3 + 5^1 + 8^3 + 9^5$
73643 := $7^1 + 3^4 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 3^5$	75934 := $7^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 4^3$	76744 := $7^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 4^8$
73644 := $7^2 + 3^3 + 6^5 + 4^4 + 4^8$	75937 := $7^2 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 7^5$	76765 := $7^4 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 5^5$
73649 := $7^1 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 4^4 + 9^5$	75939 := $7^5 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 3^4 + 9^5$	76894 := $7^5 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 4^5$
73664 := $7^3 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 6^5 + 4^8$	75943 := $7^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^4$	76924 := $7^5 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 4^5$
73667 := $7^4 + 3^3 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 7^5$	75946 := $7^5 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^0$	76927 := $7^3 + 6^3 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 7^5$
74168 := $7^3 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 6^5 + 8^3$	75963 := $7^5 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 3^4$	76929 := $7^5 + 6^3 + 9^3 + 2^7 + 9^5$

76943 := $7^5 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 3^3$	78546 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 6^1$	79486 := $7^2 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 6^6$
77396 := $7^5 + 7^0 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 6^4$	78547 := $7^1 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 7^3$	79534 := $7^3 + 9^2 + 5^7 + 3^6 + 4^4$
77464 := $7^1 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 6^5 + 4^8$	78548 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 8^1$	79536 := $7^1 + 9^2 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 6^4$
77496 := $7^3 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 9^5 + 6^4$	78549 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 9^1$	79556 := $7^2 + 9^2 + 5^1 + 5^7 + 6^4$
77849 := $7^1 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 4^7 + 9^5$	78558 := $7^3 + 8^0 + 5^2 + 5^7 + 8^2$	79572 := $7^3 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 2^5$
78135 := $7^1 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 5^7$	78563 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 6^1 + 3^4$	79574 := $7^3 + 9^2 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 4^5$
78145 := $7^1 + 8^1 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 5^7$	78569 := $7^3 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 6^2 + 9^0$	79576 := $7^3 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 6^2$
78205 := $7^1 + 8^1 + 2^6 + 0^0 + 5^7$	78595 := $7^3 + 8^0 + 5^3 + 9^0 + 5^7$	79590 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 0^1$
78215 := $7^2 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 1^0 + 5^7$	78650 := $7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 0^1$	79591 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 1^0$
78253 := $7^1 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 3^4$	78651 := $7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 1^0$	79592 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 2^1$
78254 := $7^2 + 8^1 + 2^3 + 5^7 + 4^3$	78652 := $7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 2^1$	79593 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 3^9$
78255 := $7^2 + 8^2 + 2^4 + 5^0 + 5^7$	78653 := $7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 3^1$	79594 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 4^1$
78275 := $7^1 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 7^1 + 5^7$	78654 := $7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 4^1$	79595 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 5^1 + 9^3 + 5^7$
78295 := $7^2 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 9^2 + 5^7$	78655 := $7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 5^7$	79596 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 6^1$
78297 := $7^4 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 9^5 + 7^5$	78656 := $7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 6^1$	79597 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 7^1$
78325 := $7^1 + 8^2 + 3^0 + 2^7 + 5^7$	78657 := $7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 7^1$	79598 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 8^1$
78349 := $7^4 + 8^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 9^5$	78658 := $7^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 8^3$	79599 := $7^1 + 9^1 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 9^3$
78365 := $7^1 + 8^1 + 3^2 + 6^3 + 5^7$	78659 := $7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 9^1$	79623 := $7^3 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 3^9$
78453 := $7^1 + 8^2 + 4^4 + 5^7 + 3^0$	78725 := $7^1 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 2^5 + 5^7$	79642 := $7^4 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 2^9$
78454 := $7^2 + 8^1 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 4^4$	78852 := $7^3 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^8$	79682 := $7^2 + 9^2 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 2^7$
78485 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 5^7$	78905 := $7^2 + 8^0 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 5^7$	79683 := $7^1 + 9^1 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 3^5$
78495 := $7^2 + 8^2 + 4^4 + 9^0 + 5^7$	78963 := $7^1 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 3^9$	79756 := $7^3 + 9^3 + 7^3 + 5^7 + 6^3$
78502 := $7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 2^5$	79045 := $7^5 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 4^3 + 5^5$	79758 := $7^2 + 9^3 + 7^3 + 5^7 + 8^3$
78503 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 3^3$	79083 := $7^3 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 3^9$	79759 := $7^2 + 9^3 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 9^5$
78506 := $7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 6^2$	79203 := $7^3 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 3^9$	79843 := $7^3 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 3^9$
78524 := $7^1 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^7 + 4^4$	79205 := $7^3 + 9^3 + 2^3 + 0^1 + 5^7$	79864 := $7^3 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 6^6 + 4^2$
78526 := $7^2 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^7 + 6^3$	79245 := $7^1 + 9^2 + 2^3 + 4^5 + 5^7$	79885 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 8^3 + 8^3 + 5^7$
78527 := $7^2 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 7^3$	79265 := $7^3 + 9^3 + 2^5 + 6^2 + 5^7$	79932 := $7^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 2^7$
78534 := $7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^0 + 4^3$	79283 := $7^1 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 8^3 + 3^9$	79935 := $7^3 + 9^1 + 9^3 + 3^6 + 5^7$
78536 := $7^3 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 3^1 + 6^0$	79332 := $7^1 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 3^9 + 2^9$	79953 := $7^3 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 3^3$
78540 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 0^1$	79334 := $7^3 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^9 + 4^4$	79954 := $7^5 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 4^6$
78541 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 1^0$	79352 := $7^3 + 9^3 + 3^3 + 5^7 + 2^7$	79958 := $7^5 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 8^4$
78542 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 2^1$	79359 := $7^3 + 9^2 + 3^4 + 5^7 + 9^3$	79975 := $7^2 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 7^3 + 5^7$
78543 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 3^1$	79365 := $7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 5^4$	79996 := $7^2 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 6^5$
78544 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^1 + 4^3$	79394 := $7^1 + 9^3 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 4^8$	80325 := $8^1 + 0^0 + 3^7 + 2^2 + 5^7$
78545 := $7^3 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 4^3 + 5^7$	79454 := $7^3 + 9^3 + 4^0 + 5^7 + 4^4$	80352 := $8^1 + 0^1 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^5$

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|--|--|--|
| $80356 := 8^1 + 0^1 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 6^2$ | $82378 := 8^5 + 2^3 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 8^5$ | $82753 := 8^1 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 5^7 + 3^7$ |
| $80385 := 8^1 + 0^0 + 3^7 + 8^2 + 5^7$ | $82427 := 8^2 + 2^2 + 4^8 + 2^4 + 7^5$ | $82774 := 8^5 + 2^3 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 4^7$ |
| $80396 := 8^5 + 0^1 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^6$ | $82434 := 8^3 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 3^0 + 4^8$ | $82855 := 8^1 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 5^4 + 5^7$ |
| $80464 := 8^5 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 6^6 + 4^5$ | $82440 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 0^1$ | $82887 := 8^3 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 7^5$ |
| $80536 := 8^1 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 3^7 + 6^3$ | $82441 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 1^0$ | $82893 := 8^2 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 9^5 + 3^9$ |
| $80537 := 8^1 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 3^1 + 7^4$ | $82442 := 8^1 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 2^9$ | $82937 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 9^5 + 3^8 + 7^5$ |
| $80562 := 8^5 + 0^0 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 2^9$ | $82443 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 3^1$ | $82952 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 2^0$ |
| $80664 := 8^5 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 4^5$ | $82444 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 4^8$ | $82953 := 8^4 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 5^7 + 3^6$ |
| $81345 := 8^1 + 1^0 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^7$ | $82445 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 5^1$ | $82955 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 9^3 + 5^0 + 5^7$ |
| $81613 := 8^5 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 3^7$ | $82446 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 6^1$ | $82959 := 8^4 + 2^3 + 9^0 + 5^7 + 9^3$ |
| $81693 := 8^5 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 3^7$ | $82447 := 8^1 + 2^5 + 4^3 + 4^8 + 7^5$ | $83254 := 8^3 + 3^2 + 2^9 + 5^7 + 4^6$ |
| $82048 := 8^5 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 8^5$ | $82448 := 8^1 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 8^3$ | $83257 := 8^3 + 3^7 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 7^4$ |
| $82225 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 5^7$ | $82449 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 9^1$ | $83349 := 8^3 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 9^5$ |
| $82235 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 5^7$ | $82468 := 8^5 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 8^5$ | $83364 := 8^5 + 3^6 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 4^5$ |
| $82244 := 8^2 + 2^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 4^8$ | $82472 := 8^2 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 7^5 + 2^6$ | $83523 := 8^3 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^9 + 3^7$ |
| $82245 := 8^1 + 2^3 + 2^3 + 4^6 + 5^7$ | $82487 := 8^1 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 8^1 + 7^5$ | $83526 := 8^4 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 2^3 + 6^4$ |
| $82253 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 5^7 + 3^3$ | $82527 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 5^7 + 2^8 + 7^2$ | $83543 := 8^3 + 3^4 + 5^7 + 4^6 + 3^6$ |
| $82254 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^4 + 5^7 + 4^2$ | $82532 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 2^6$ | $83546 := 8^5 + 3^0 + 5^2 + 4^6 + 6^6$ |
| $82255 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^3 + 5^2 + 5^7$ | $82542 := 8^2 + 2^0 + 5^7 + 4^6 + 2^8$ | $83567 := 8^4 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 6^4 + 7^2$ |
| $82256 := 8^4 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 6^0$ | $82553 := 8^4 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 5^7 + 3^5$ | $83636 := 8^5 + 3^6 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 6^6$ |
| $82258 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 8^0$ | $82554 := 8^3 + 2^8 + 5^4 + 5^6 + 4^8$ | $83654 := 8^5 + 3^2 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 4^6$ |
| $82265 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 6^2 + 5^7$ | $82556 := 8^1 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 5^7 + 6^4$ | $83674 := 8^1 + 3^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 4^8$ |
| $82275 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 7^2 + 5^7$ | $82559 := 8^4 + 2^8 + 5^0 + 5^7 + 9^2$ | $83697 := 8^2 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 7^5$ |
| $82295 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^6 + 9^1 + 5^7$ | $82566 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 6^3$ | $83745 := 8^1 + 3^7 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 5^7$ |
| $82305 := 8^4 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 0^0 + 5^7$ | $82567 := 8^4 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 7^3$ | $83764 := 8^5 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 4^6$ |
| $82335 := 8^4 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 3^4 + 5^7$ | $82572 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 2^2$ | $83946 := 8^1 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 6^5$ |
| $82350 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 0^1$ | $82573 := 8^4 + 2^3 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 3^0$ | $83964 := 8^3 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 4^7$ |
| $82351 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 1^0$ | $82574 := 8^1 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 4^6$ | $84075 := 8^3 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 7^4 + 5^6$ |
| $82352 := 8^4 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 2^7$ | $82593 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 3^5$ | $84243 := 8^1 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 3^7$ |
| $82353 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 3^1$ | $82597 := 8^4 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 7^3$ | $84376 := 8^1 + 4^8 + 3^6 + 7^5 + 6^4$ |
| $82354 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 4^1$ | $82643 := 8^5 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 4^5 + 3^7$ | $84755 := 8^1 + 4^6 + 7^4 + 5^3 + 5^7$ |
| $82355 := 8^3 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 5^5 + 5^7$ | $82645 := 8^5 + 2^5 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 5^5$ | $84757 := 8^1 + 4^8 + 7^4 + 5^1 + 7^5$ |
| $82356 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 6^1$ | $82648 := 8^5 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 8^5$ | $84759 := 8^1 + 4^2 + 7^2 + 5^7 + 9^4$ |
| $82357 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 7^1$ | $82685 := 8^1 + 2^7 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 5^5$ | $84950 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 0^1$ |
| $82358 := 8^1 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 8^4$ | $82687 := 8^5 + 2^7 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 7^5$ | $84951 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 1^0$ |
| $82359 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 9^1$ | $82735 := 8^4 + 2^9 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 5^7$ | $84952 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 2^1$ |

84953 := $8^1 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 3^5$	85433 := $8^1 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 3^9$	86485 := $8^1 + 6^5 + 4^3 + 8^3 + 5^7$
84954 := $8^1 + 4^1 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 4^4$	85435 := $8^1 + 5^5 + 4^6 + 3^4 + 5^7$	86495 := $8^3 + 6^4 + 4^0 + 9^4 + 5^7$
84955 := $8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 5^7$	85439 := $8^1 + 5^7 + 4^2 + 3^6 + 9^4$	86498 := $8^3 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 9^4 + 8^5$
84956 := $8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 6^1$	85459 := $8^3 + 5^1 + 4^4 + 5^7 + 9^4$	86534 := $8^4 + 6^3 + 5^7 + 3^0 + 4^6$
84957 := $8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 7^1$	85477 := $8^1 + 5^5 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 7^5$	86535 := $8^1 + 6^5 + 5^4 + 3^0 + 5^7$
84958 := $8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 8^1$	85563 := $8^4 + 5^5 + 5^7 + 6^3 + 3^0$	86542 := $8^3 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 4^0 + 2^7$
84959 := $8^1 + 4^4 + 9^1 + 5^7 + 9^4$	85639 := $8^1 + 5^7 + 6^3 + 3^6 + 9^4$	86554 := $8^3 + 6^5 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 4^2$
85037 := $8^1 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 7^3$	85647 := $8^4 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 4^5 + 7^4$	86558 := $8^4 + 6^3 + 5^2 + 5^7 + 8^4$
85203 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 3^8$	85675 := $8^5 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 5^5$	86645 := $8^3 + 6^3 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 5^7$
85230 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 0^1$	85679 := $8^5 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^4 + 9^3$	86665 := $8^3 + 6^2 + 6^3 + 6^5 + 5^7$
85231 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 1^0$	85743 := $8^3 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 3^9$	86695 := $8^2 + 6^0 + 6^5 + 9^3 + 5^7$
85232 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 2^5$	85835 := $8^3 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 3^8 + 5^7$	86757 := $8^3 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 7^3$
85233 := $8^1 + 5^7 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 3^8$	85859 := $8^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 + 5^7 + 9^0$	87095 := $8^1 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 9^4 + 5^7$
85234 := $8^1 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^8$	85926 := $8^1 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 6^5$	87454 := $8^1 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 4^8$
85235 := $8^3 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^7$	85929 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 2^1 + 9^4$	87464 := $8^4 + 7^5 + 4^5 + 6^0 + 4^8$
85236 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^2$	85943 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 4^2 + 3^8$	87634 := $8^1 + 7^4 + 6^1 + 3^9 + 4^8$
85237 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 7^1$	85963 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 6^2 + 3^8$	87635 := $8^3 + 7^4 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 5^7$
85238 := $8^1 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 8^3$	85967 := $8^1 + 5^7 + 9^1 + 6^5 + 7^2$	87836 := $8^5 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 6^3$
85239 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 9^4$	86049 := $8^5 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	88345 := $8^5 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^5$
85263 := $8^2 + 5^7 + 2^9 + 6^0 + 3^8$	86153 := $8^1 + 6^5 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 3^5$	88352 := $8^5 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 2^3$
85264 := $8^4 + 5^6 + 2^0 + 6^1 + 4^8$	86225 := $8^2 + 6^5 + 2^2 + 2^8 + 5^7$	88353 := $8^5 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 3^9$
85274 := $8^4 + 5^6 + 2^4 + 7^0 + 4^8$	86243 := $8^5 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 3^8$	88489 := $8^1 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 8^5 + 9^4$
85279 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 7^2 + 9^4$	86249 := $8^5 + 6^6 + 2^3 + 4^4 + 9^4$	89295 := $8^4 + 9^0 + 2^9 + 9^4 + 5^7$
85294 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 9^4 + 4^3$	86285 := $8^2 + 6^5 + 2^8 + 8^2 + 5^7$	89324 := $8^4 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 2^3 + 4^8$
85324 := $8^2 + 5^2 + 3^9 + 2^4 + 4^8$	86337 := $8^5 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 7^3$	89343 := $8^4 + 9^0 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 3^9$
85325 := $8^3 + 5^3 + 3^8 + 2^1 + 5^7$	86345 := $8^4 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^7$	89390 := $8^4 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 0^0$
85327 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 2^7 + 7^0$	86353 := $8^5 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 3^8$	89417 := $8^3 + 9^4 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 7^5$
85329 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 3^1 + 2^7 + 9^4$	86354 := $8^4 + 6^2 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 4^6$	89497 := $8^3 + 9^2 + 4^8 + 9^4 + 7^5$
85342 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 2^7$	86373 := $8^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 3^9$	91820 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^0 + 0^0$
85343 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 3^8$	86377 := $8^5 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 7^3$	91821 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 1^0$
85344 := $8^5 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 4^7$	86415 := $8^3 + 6^5 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 5^7$	91822 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 2^1$
85348 := $8^2 + 5^0 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 8^2$	86425 := $8^1 + 6^5 + 4^1 + 2^9 + 5^7$	91823 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 3^1$
85350 := $8^4 + 5^5 + 3^1 + 5^7 + 0^0$	86445 := $8^3 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 5^7$	91824 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 4^1$
85356 := $8^4 + 5^5 + 3^2 + 5^7 + 6^0$	86465 := $8^3 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 5^7$	91825 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 5^1$
85362 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 2^7$	86472 := $8^4 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 7^5 + 2^5$	91826 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 6^1$
85432 := $8^3 + 5^7 + 4^6 + 3^7 + 2^9$	86476 := $8^4 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 7^5 + 6^2$	91827 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 7^1$

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|---|---|---|
| 91828 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 8^5$ | 92897 := $9^3 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 7^3$ | 94592 := $9^2 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 2^0$ |
| 91829 := $9^1 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 9^5$ | 93069 := $9^4 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 9^5$ | 94635 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 5^7$ |
| 91842 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 2^3$ | 93084 := $9^5 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 4^5$ | 94652 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 2^7$ |
| 91843 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 3^2$ | 93268 := $9^5 + 3^3 + 2^7 + 6^4 + 8^5$ | 94653 := $9^2 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 3^3$ |
| 91862 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 2^3$ | 93283 := $9^5 + 3^6 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 3^6$ | 94675 := $9^2 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^2 + 5^7$ |
| 91863 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^2$ | 93435 := $9^4 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 3^8 + 5^7$ | 94677 := $9^5 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 + 7^5$ |
| 91883 := $9^5 + 1^0 + 8^2 + 8^5 + 3^0$ | 93466 := $9^1 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 6^6$ | 94725 := $9^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 5^7$ |
| 92082 := $9^5 + 2^3 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^8$ | 93559 := $9^4 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 9^4$ | 94854 := $9^2 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^7$ |
| 92083 := $9^5 + 2^8 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 3^2$ | 93628 := $9^5 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 2^9 + 8^5$ | 94947 := $9^3 + 4^7 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 7^4$ |
| 92274 := $9^5 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 4^7$ | 93663 := $9^2 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 3^5$ | 95056 := $9^1 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 6^4$ |
| 92324 := $9^4 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 4^8$ | 93667 := $9^1 + 3^1 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 7^3$ | 95078 := $9^2 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 8^2$ |
| 92348 := $9^5 + 2^5 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 8^5$ | 93846 := $9^5 + 3^6 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 6^4$ | 95240 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 0^0$ |
| 92368 := $9^5 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 6^2 + 8^5$ | 93868 := $9^5 + 3^5 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 8^5$ | 95241 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 1^0$ |
| 92383 := $9^5 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 3^3$ | 93869 := $9^3 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 9^5$ | 95242 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 2^1$ |
| 92387 := $9^5 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 7^2$ | 94236 := $9^3 + 4^8 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 6^5$ | 95243 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 3^1$ |
| 92388 := $9^5 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 8^3 + 8^5$ | 94347 := $9^5 + 4^7 + 3^7 + 4^7 + 7^3$ | 95244 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 4^7$ |
| 92454 := $9^5 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 4^7$ | 94359 := $9^5 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 9^0$ | 95245 := $9^3 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^7$ |
| 92458 := $9^5 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^5$ | 94385 := $9^5 + 4^4 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 5^3$ | 95246 := $9^1 + 5^7 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^3$ |
| 92465 := $9^4 + 2^1 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 5^7$ | 94437 := $9^4 + 4^4 + 4^8 + 3^9 + 7^4$ | 95247 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^1$ |
| 92497 := $9^5 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 9^0 + 7^5$ | 94474 := $9^5 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 4^7$ | 95248 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 8^1$ |
| 92526 := $9^4 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 6^5$ | 94478 := $9^5 + 4^1 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 8^5$ | 95249 := $9^1 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 9^3$ |
| 92582 := $9^5 + 2^7 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 2^9$ | 94520 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^0 + 0^0$ | 95270 := $9^2 + 5^7 + 2^8 + 7^5 + 0^0$ |
| 92583 := $9^5 + 2^5 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 3^6$ | 94521 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 1^0$ | 95286 := $9^5 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 6^3$ |
| 92654 := $9^4 + 2^7 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 4^3$ | 94522 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 2^1$ | 95287 := $9^5 + 5^5 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 7^3$ |
| 92677 := $9^5 + 2^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 + 7^5$ | 94523 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 3^1$ | 95337 := $9^2 + 5^7 + 3^4 + 3^5 + 7^5$ |
| 92678 := $9^5 + 2^9 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^5$ | 94524 := $9^1 + 4^1 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7$ | 95344 := $9^4 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 4^6$ |
| 92727 := $9^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 7^5$ | 94525 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 5^7$ | 95374 := $9^5 + 5^5 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 4^7$ |
| 92784 := $9^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 4^7$ | 94526 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 6^1$ | 95462 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 2^3$ |
| 92803 := $9^5 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 3^6$ | 94527 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 7^1$ | 95463 := $9^1 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 3^6$ |
| 92834 := $9^5 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 4^4$ | 94528 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 8^1$ | 95504 := $9^3 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 4^5$ |
| 92842 := $9^5 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 2^9$ | 94529 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 9^1$ | 95567 := $9^1 + 5^4 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 7^5$ |
| 92843 := $9^5 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 3^0$ | 94542 := $9^1 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 2^3$ | 95568 := $9^5 + 5^4 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 8^5$ |
| 92844 := $9^5 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 4^5$ | 94543 := $9^1 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 3^2$ | 95578 := $9^1 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^3$ |
| 92846 := $9^5 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 6^0$ | 94562 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 6^2 + 2^3$ | 95596 := $9^1 + 5^5 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 6^5$ |
| 92854 := $9^5 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 4^5$ | 94563 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 6^2 + 3^2$ | 95726 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 2^6 + 6^0$ |
| 92874 := $9^5 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 4^5$ | 94583 := $9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 3^0$ | 95734 := $9^1 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 4^3$ |

95737 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 3^3 + 7^5$	98343 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 3^3$	98654 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 5^3 + 4^8$
95743 := $9^2 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 3^6$	98344 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 4^8$	98723 := $9^5 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 2^1 + 3^8$
95774 := $9^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 4^3$	98345 := $9^1 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^7$	98729 := $9^4 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 2^3 + 9^5$
95795 := $9^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 5^7$	98346 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 6^1$	98744 := $9^1 + 8^1 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 4^8$
95797 := $9^1 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 9^5 + 7^5$	98347 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 7^1$	98764 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 6^2 + 4^8$
95974 := $9^1 + 5^7 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 4^5$	98348 := $9^1 + 8^1 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 8^5$	98834 := $9^1 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 4^8$
96236 := $9^3 + 6^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 6^6$	98349 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 9^1$	98874 := $9^1 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 4^8$
96413 := $9^5 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 3^9$	98365 := $9^1 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 5^7$	98890 := $9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 0^1$
96493 := $9^2 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 9^5 + 3^9$	98380 := $9^5 + 8^0 + 3^8 + 8^5 + 0^0$	98891 := $9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 1^0$
96526 := $9^2 + 6^6 + 5^5 + 2^3 + 6^6$	98387 := $9^5 + 8^1 + 3^8 + 8^5 + 7^0$	98892 := $9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 2^1$
96542 := $9^3 + 6^4 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 2^3$	98388 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 8^5 + 8^5$	98893 := $9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 3^1$
96543 := $9^1 + 6^4 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 3^6$	98389 := $9^4 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 8^5 + 9^5$	98894 := $9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 4^1$
96564 := $9^4 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 6^5 + 4^6$	98402 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 2^4$	98895 := $9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 5^1$
96567 := $9^2 + 6^6 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^2$	98413 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 3^3$	98896 := $9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 6^1$
96744 := $9^4 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 4^3 + 4^8$	98437 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 7^2$	98897 := $9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 7^1$
96746 := $9^1 + 6^6 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 6^6$	98442 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 2^7$	98898 := $9^4 + 8^1 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 8^5$
97443 := $9^4 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 3^8$	98443 := $9^5 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 4^3 + 3^8$	98899 := $9^1 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 9^5$
97466 := $9^1 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 6^6$	98454 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 4^8$	98922 := $9^4 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 2^9$
97645 := $9^3 + 7^4 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 5^7$	98473 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 3^4$	98926 := $9^4 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 6^2$
97689 := $9^3 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 9^3$	98493 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 9^2 + 3^3$	99483 := $9^2 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^8$
97733 := $9^5 + 7^1 + 7^5 + 3^7 + 3^9$	98503 := $9^5 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 3^8$	99682 := $9^2 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 2^3$
97757 := $9^2 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 5^7 + 7^5$	98539 := $9^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^9 + 9^0$	99683 := $9^1 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 3^8$
98324 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 2^3 + 4^8$	98542 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 2^5$	99758 := $9^3 + 9^0 + 7^5 + 5^7 + 8^4$
98340 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 0^1$	98546 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 6^2$	99843 := $9^2 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 3^6$
98341 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 1^0$	98634 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 3^5 + 4^8$	
98342 := $9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 2^1$	98642 := $9^2 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 2^8$	

3 Flexible Powers: Positive and Negative Coefficients

This section brings flexible powers narcissistic-type numbers with positive-negative coefficients. It is understood that $0^a = 1, a \neq 0$ and $0^0 = 1$.

23 := $-2^2 + 3^3$	152 := $-1^1 + 5^2 + 2^7$	236 := $-2^3 + 3^5 + 6^0$
48 := $-4^2 + 8^2$	222 := $-2^1 - 2^5 + 2^8$	238 := $-2^2 + 3^5 - 8^0$
125 := $-1^1 + 2^0 + 5^3$	223 := $-2^2 - 2^4 + 3^5$	240 := $-2^4 + 4^4 + 0^1$
126 := $-1^1 + 2^7 - 6^0$	224 := $-2^4 - 2^4 + 4^4$	241 := $-2^4 + 4^4 + 1^0$
128 := $-1^1 + 2^7 + 8^0$	225 := $-2^5 + 2^8 + 5^0$	242 := $-2^4 + 4^4 + 2^1$
	234 := $-2^3 + 3^5 - 4^0$	243 := $-2^2 + 4^1 + 3^5$

$$\begin{aligned} 244 &:= -2^3 - 4^1 + 4^4 \\ 245 &:= -2^4 + 4^4 + 5^1 \\ 246 &:= -2^2 + 4^4 - 6^1 \\ 247 &:= -2^1 + 4^4 - 7^1 \\ 248 &:= -2^3 - 4^4 + 8^3 \\ 249 &:= -2^3 + 4^4 + 9^0 \\ 262 &:= -2^8 + 6^1 + 2^9 \\ 263 &:= -2^4 + 6^2 + 3^5 \\ 264 &:= -2^3 + 6^4 - 4^5 \\ 278 &:= -2^6 + 7^3 - 8^0 \\ 283 &:= -2^8 + 8^3 + 3^3 \\ 287 &:= -2^6 + 8^1 + 7^3 \\ 317 &:= -3^3 + 1^0 + 7^3 \\ 334 &:= -3^1 + 3^4 + 4^4 \\ 337 &:= -3^1 - 3^1 + 7^3 \\ 354 &:= -3^3 + 5^3 + 4^4 \\ 372 &:= -3^1 + 7^3 + 2^5 \\ 375 &:= -3^5 - 7^1 + 5^4 \\ 376 &:= -3^1 + 7^3 + 6^2 \\ 392 &:= -3^4 + 9^3 - 2^8 \\ 397 &:= -3^3 + 9^2 + 7^3 \\ 427 &:= -4^7 + 2^2 + 7^5 \\ 448 &:= -4^3 + 4^5 - 8^3 \\ 487 &:= -4^7 + 8^2 + 7^5 \\ 488 &:= -4^2 - 8^1 + 8^3 \\ 508 &:= -5^1 + 0^0 + 8^3 \\ 557 &:= -5^4 - 5^6 + 7^5 \\ 574 &:= -5^2 + 7^3 + 4^4 \\ 597 &:= -5^3 + 9^3 - 7^1 \\ 629 &:= -6^2 - 2^6 + 9^3 \\ 665 &:= -6^1 + 6^4 - 5^4 \\ 692 &:= -6^2 + 9^3 - 2^0 \\ 694 &:= -6^2 + 9^3 + 4^0 \\ 723 &:= -7^1 + 2^0 + 3^6 \\ 725 &:= -7^4 + 2^0 + 5^5 \\ 934 &:= -9^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 936 &:= -9^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 \\ 942 &:= -9^2 + 4^5 - 2^0 \\ 944 &:= -9^2 + 4^0 + 4^5 \\ 1022 &:= -1^1 - 0^0 + 2^9 + 2^9 \\ 1024 &:= -1^1 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 4^5 \\ 1232 &:= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 2^9 \\ 1234 &:= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^5 + 4^5 \\ 1236 &:= -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 6^4 \\ 1238 &:= -1^1 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 8^3 \\ 1239 &:= -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 9^3 \\ 1254 &:= -1^1 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 4^5 \\ 1256 &:= -1^1 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\ 1262 &:= -1^1 - 2^0 + 6^4 - 2^5 \\ 1264 &:= -1^1 - 2^5 + 6^4 + 4^0 \\ 1286 &:= -1^1 - 2^0 - 8^1 + 6^4 \\ 1296 &:= -1^1 + 2^1 - 9^0 + 6^4 \\ 1326 &:= -1^1 - 3^0 + 2^5 + 6^4 \\ 1327 &:= -1^1 + 3^6 + 2^8 + 7^3 \\ 1329 &:= -1^1 + 3^6 - 2^7 + 9^3 \\ 1354 &:= -1^1 + 3^6 + 5^4 + 4^0 \\ 1362 &:= -1^1 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 2^6 \\ 1368 &:= -1^1 + 3^2 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\ 1386 &:= -1^1 + 3^3 + 8^2 + 6^4 \\ 1526 &:= -1^1 - 5^2 + 2^8 + 6^4 \\ 1546 &:= -1^1 - 5^1 + 4^4 + 6^4 \\ 1563 &:= -1^1 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 3^5 \\ 1569 &:= -1^1 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 9^3 \\ 1584 &:= -1^1 + 5^4 - 8^2 + 4^5 \\ 1632 &:= -1^1 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 2^8 \\ 1637 &:= -1^1 + 6^4 - 3^0 + 7^3 \\ 1638 &:= -1^1 - 6^2 + 3^7 - 8^3 \\ 1654 &:= -1^1 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5 \\ 1672 &:= -1^1 - 6^3 + 7^4 - 2^9 \\ 1723 &:= -1^1 + 7^2 - 2^9 + 3^7 \\ 1806 &:= -1^1 + 8^3 - 0^0 + 6^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1856 &:= -1^1 - 8^2 + 5^4 + 6^4 \\ 1872 &:= -1^1 - 8^3 + 7^4 - 2^4 \\ 1879 &:= -1^1 - 8^3 + 7^4 - 9^1 \\ 1887 &:= -1^1 - 8^0 - 8^3 + 7^4 \\ 1897 &:= -1^1 - 8^3 + 9^1 + 7^4 \\ 1927 &:= -1^1 - 9^3 + 2^8 + 7^4 \\ 2033 &:= -2^7 + 0^0 - 3^3 + 3^7 \\ 2043 &:= -2^7 + 0^1 - 4^2 + 3^7 \\ 2044 &:= -2^2 + 0^1 + 4^5 + 4^5 \\ 2053 &:= -2^3 - 0^0 - 5^3 + 3^7 \\ 2064 &:= -2^8 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 4^5 \\ 2073 &:= -2^6 - 0^0 - 7^2 + 3^7 \\ 2123 &:= -2^6 + 1^0 - 2^0 + 3^7 \\ 2132 &:= -2^6 + 1^0 + 3^7 + 2^3 \\ 2133 &:= -2^6 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 3^7 \\ 2137 &:= -2^8 + 1^0 - 3^2 + 7^4 \\ 2139 &:= -2^7 - 1^0 + 3^7 + 9^2 \\ 2147 &:= -2^8 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 7^4 \\ 2153 &:= -2^3 - 1^0 - 5^2 + 3^7 \\ 2173 &:= -2^3 + 1^0 - 7^1 + 3^7 \\ 2176 &:= -2^3 - 1^0 + 7^4 - 6^3 \\ 2183 &:= -2^1 - 1^0 - 8^0 + 3^7 \\ 2193 &:= -2^1 - 1^0 + 9^1 + 3^7 \\ 2203 &:= -2^4 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 3^7 \\ 2223 &:= -2^2 + 2^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 \\ 2234 &:= -2^4 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 \\ 2236 &:= -2^4 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^0 \\ 2243 &:= -2^2 - 2^2 + 4^3 + 3^7 \\ 2249 &:= -2^4 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 9^3 \\ 2263 &:= -2^4 + 2^7 - 6^2 + 3^7 \\ 2264 &:= -2^6 + 2^3 + 6^4 + 4^5 \\ 2267 &:= -2^6 - 2^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\ 2270 &:= -2^1 - 2^7 + 7^4 - 0^0 \\ 2271 &:= -2^7 - 2^0 + 7^4 - 1^0 \\ 2272 &:= -2^1 - 2^7 + 7^4 + 2^0 \\ 2273 &:= -2^7 - 2^0 + 7^4 + 3^0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2274 &:= -2^6 - 2^6 + 7^4 + 4^0 \\ 2275 &:= -2^7 + 2^0 + 7^4 + 5^0 \\ 2276 &:= -2^7 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 6^0 \\ 2278 &:= -2^7 + 2^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 \\ 2283 &:= -2^5 + 2^6 + 8^2 + 3^7 \\ 2286 &:= -2^1 - 2^9 + 8^4 - 6^4 \\ 2303 &:= -2^7 + 3^5 + 0^0 + 3^7 \\ 2305 &:= -2^3 + 3^7 + 0^0 + 5^3 \\ 2312 &:= -2^1 + 3^7 - 1^0 + 2^7 \\ 2314 &:= -2^7 + 3^7 - 1^0 + 4^4 \\ 2317 &:= -2^1 - 3^4 - 1^0 + 7^4 \\ 2327 &:= -2^6 - 3^2 - 2^0 + 7^4 \\ 2332 &:= -2^6 + 3^4 + 3^7 + 2^7 \\ 2333 &:= -2^4 + 3^4 + 3^4 + 3^7 \\ 2334 &:= -2^7 - 3^1 + 3^8 - 4^6 \\ 2335 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 + 3^7 + 5^3 \\ 2336 &:= -2^6 - 3^1 + 3^7 + 6^3 \\ 2337 &:= -2^6 + 3^0 - 3^0 + 7^4 \\ 2337 &:= -2^6 - 3^0 + 3^0 + 7^4 \\ 2347 &:= -2^6 + 3^2 + 4^0 + 7^4 \\ 2353 &:= -2^4 - 3^3 + 5^5 - 3^6 \\ 2354 &:= -2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 4^4 \\ 2355 &:= -2^4 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 5^5 \\ 2356 &:= -2^2 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\ 2357 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 \\ 2365 &:= -2^5 - 3^6 + 6^0 + 5^5 \\ 2367 &:= -2^3 - 3^3 + 6^0 + 7^4 \\ 2370 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 7^4 + 0^1 \\ 2371 &:= -2^1 - 3^3 + 7^4 - 1^0 \\ 2372 &:= -2^2 - 3^2 + 7^4 - 2^4 \\ 2373 &:= -2^1 - 3^3 + 7^4 + 3^0 \\ 2374 &:= -2^1 - 3^2 + 7^4 - 4^2 \\ 2375 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 7^4 + 5^1 \\ 2376 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 7^4 + 6^1 \\ 2377 &:= -2^1 + 3^3 - 7^2 + 7^4 \\ 2378 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2379 &:= -2^2 - 3^2 + 7^4 - 9^1 \\ 2386 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 - 8^0 + 6^3 \\ 2387 &:= -2^2 - 3^2 - 8^0 + 7^4 \\ 2392 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 2^7 \\ 2395 &:= -2^1 + 3^0 - 9^3 + 5^5 \\ 2396 &:= -2^3 + 3^7 + 9^0 + 6^3 \\ 2397 &:= -2^1 - 3^0 - 9^0 + 7^4 \\ 2398 &:= -2^6 - 3^1 + 9^4 - 8^4 \\ 2423 &:= -2^2 - 4^2 + 2^8 + 3^7 \\ 2427 &:= -2^1 - 4^1 + 2^5 + 7^4 \\ 2429 &:= -2^2 - 4^6 - 2^5 + 9^4 \\ 2432 &:= -2^5 - 4^6 + 3^8 - 2^0 \\ 2434 &:= -2^3 - 4^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 \\ 2436 &:= -2^3 + 4^4 + 3^7 + 6^0 \\ 2443 &:= -2^2 + 4^1 + 4^4 + 3^7 \\ 2445 &:= -2^1 - 4^5 + 4^6 - 5^4 \\ 2447 &:= -2^1 - 4^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 \\ 2449 &:= -2^5 + 4^2 - 4^6 + 9^4 \\ 2463 &:= -2^2 + 4^3 + 6^3 + 3^7 \\ 2464 &:= -2^5 - 4^7 - 6^6 + 4^8 \\ 2467 &:= -2^2 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\ 2469 &:= -2^1 - 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\ 2473 &:= -2^3 - 4^0 + 7^4 + 3^4 \\ 2479 &:= -2^1 - 4^0 + 7^4 + 9^2 \\ 2485 &:= -2^6 - 4^3 - 8^3 + 5^5 \\ 2517 &:= -2^3 + 5^3 - 1^0 + 7^4 \\ 2533 &:= -2^9 + 5^5 - 3^4 + 3^0 \\ 2537 &:= -2^4 + 5^3 + 3^3 + 7^4 \\ 2552 &:= -2^9 - 5^3 + 5^5 + 2^6 \\ 2572 &:= -2^9 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 2^3 \\ 2573 &:= -2^9 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 3^2 \\ 2574 &:= -2^4 + 5^3 + 7^4 + 4^3 \\ 2576 &:= -2^4 - 5^2 + 7^4 + 6^3 \\ 2578 &:= -2^9 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\ 2582 &:= -2^5 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 2^0 \\ 2596 &:= -2^4 + 5^5 - 9^3 + 6^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2615 &:= -2^9 + 6^0 + 1^0 + 5^5 \\ 2637 &:= -2^3 + 6^0 + 3^5 + 7^4 \\ 2643 &:= -2^4 + 6^3 + 4^4 + 3^7 \\ 2645 &:= -2^3 - 6^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\ 2647 &:= -2^2 - 6^1 + 4^4 + 7^4 \\ 2649 &:= -2^5 + 6^3 - 4^6 + 9^4 \\ 2650 &:= -2^9 + 6^2 + 5^5 + 0^0 \\ 2652 &:= -2^8 - 6^3 + 5^5 - 2^0 \\ 2654 &:= -2^8 - 6^3 + 5^5 + 4^0 \\ 2669 &:= -2^2 + 6^4 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\ 2687 &:= -2^6 - 6^4 + 8^4 - 7^2 \\ 2695 &:= -2^9 + 6^0 + 9^2 + 5^5 \\ 2727 &:= -2^4 + 7^3 - 2^0 + 7^4 \\ 2732 &:= -2^4 + 7^2 + 3^7 + 2^9 \\ 2734 &:= -2^2 + 7^4 + 3^4 + 4^4 \\ 2735 &:= -2^2 + 7^3 - 3^6 + 5^5 \\ 2736 &:= -2^7 - 7^4 + 3^8 - 6^4 \\ 2737 &:= -2^2 + 7^3 - 3^1 + 7^4 \\ 2738 &:= -2^8 + 7^4 + 3^4 + 8^3 \\ 2739 &:= -2^7 - 7^2 + 3^7 + 9^3 \\ 2750 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 0^1 \\ 2751 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 1^0 \\ 2752 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 2^1 \\ 2753 &:= -2^1 - 7^3 + 5^5 - 3^3 \\ 2754 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 4^1 \\ 2755 &:= -2^1 - 7^3 - 5^2 + 5^5 \\ 2756 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\ 2757 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\ 2758 &:= -2^4 - 7^3 + 5^5 - 8^1 \\ 2759 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 2765 &:= -2^4 - 7^3 - 6^0 + 5^5 \\ 2772 &:= -2^2 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 2^5 \\ 2775 &:= -2^3 + 7^0 - 7^3 + 5^5 \\ 2776 &:= -2^2 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 6^2 \\ 2777 &:= -2^4 + 7^2 + 7^3 + 7^4 \\ 2778 &:= -2^7 - 7^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2779 &:= -2^3 - 7^3 + 7^4 + 9^3 \\ 2786 &:= -2^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 6^0 \\ 2793 &:= -2^1 - 7^5 - 9^2 + 3^9 \\ 2795 &:= -2^8 + 7^1 - 9^2 + 5^5 \\ 2805 &:= -2^8 - 8^2 + 0^1 + 5^5 \\ 2823 &:= -2^2 + 8^3 + 2^7 + 3^7 \\ 2843 &:= -2^8 + 8^4 - 4^5 + 3^3 \\ 2845 &:= -2^4 - 8^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\ 2847 &:= -2^1 + 8^3 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\ 2849 &:= -2^7 + 8^3 - 4^6 + 9^4 \\ 2852 &:= -2^4 - 8^0 + 5^5 - 2^8 \\ 2859 &:= -2^8 - 8^0 + 5^5 - 9^1 \\ 2862 &:= -2^1 + 8^4 - 6^4 + 2^6 \\ 2873 &:= -2^1 - 8^0 - 7^5 + 3^9 \\ 2875 &:= -2^8 - 8^0 + 7^1 + 5^5 \\ 2885 &:= -2^8 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 5^5 \\ 2913 &:= -2^1 + 9^3 - 1^0 + 3^7 \\ 2915 &:= -2^7 - 9^2 - 1^0 + 5^5 \\ 2932 &:= -2^4 + 9^3 + 3^7 + 2^5 \\ 2933 &:= -2^6 + 9^2 + 3^6 + 3^7 \\ 2936 &:= -2^4 + 9^3 + 3^7 + 6^2 \\ 2950 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 0^1 \\ 2951 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 1^0 \\ 2952 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 2^1 \\ 2953 &:= -2^6 - 9^2 + 5^5 - 3^3 \\ 2954 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 4^1 \\ 2955 &:= -2^6 - 9^2 - 5^2 + 5^5 \\ 2956 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\ 2957 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\ 2958 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\ 2959 &:= -2^2 - 9^2 + 5^5 - 9^2 \\ 2978 &:= -2^4 + 9^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\ 2993 &:= -2^2 + 9^2 + 9^3 + 3^7 \\ 2995 &:= -2^7 - 9^0 - 9^0 + 5^5 \\ 3035 &:= -3^2 + 0^1 - 3^4 + 5^5 \\ 3044 &:= -3^3 - 0^0 - 4^5 + 4^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3045 &:= -3^4 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 5^5 \\ 3052 &:= -3^2 + 0^1 + 5^5 - 2^6 \\ 3053 &:= -3^4 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 3^2 \\ 3058 &:= -3^1 + 0^1 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\ 3125 &:= -3^1 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 5^5 \\ 3185 &:= -3^1 - 1^0 + 8^2 + 5^5 \\ 3225 &:= -3^3 - 2^0 + 2^7 + 5^5 \\ 3234 &:= -3^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^5 \\ 3235 &:= -3^1 + 2^5 + 3^4 + 5^5 \\ 3236 &:= -3^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 6^4 \\ 3238 &:= -3^6 - 2^7 - 3^0 + 8^4 \\ 3240 &:= -3^6 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 0^0 \\ 3245 &:= -3^2 + 2^7 + 4^0 + 5^5 \\ 3250 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 0^1 \\ 3251 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 1^0 \\ 3252 &:= -3^1 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 2^7 \\ 3253 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 3^1 \\ 3254 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 4^1 \\ 3255 &:= -3^1 + 2^3 + 5^3 + 5^5 \\ 3256 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\ 3257 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\ 3258 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\ 3259 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3275 &:= -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5 \\ 3294 &:= -3^2 - 2^6 - 9^3 + 4^6 \\ 3324 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 - 2^4 + 4^6 \\ 3325 &:= -3^2 + 3^4 + 2^7 + 5^5 \\ 3340 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 0^1 \\ 3341 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 1^0 \\ 3342 &:= -3^2 - 3^6 + 4^6 - 2^4 \\ 3343 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 3^1 \\ 3344 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 4^6 \\ 3345 &:= -3^2 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^5 \\ 3346 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\ 3347 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 7^1 \\ 3348 &:= -3^1 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 8^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3349 &:= -3^2 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 9^3 \\ 3356 &:= -3^4 + 3^8 - 5^5 + 6^0 \\ 3364 &:= -3^2 - 3^6 + 6^1 + 4^6 \\ 3365 &:= -3^1 + 3^3 + 6^3 + 5^5 \\ 3366 &:= -3^4 + 3^7 - 6^2 + 6^4 \\ 3382 &:= -3^6 - 3^0 + 8^4 + 2^4 \\ 3384 &:= -3^6 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 4^2 \\ 3385 &:= -3^2 - 3^5 + 8^3 + 5^5 \\ 3417 &:= -3^2 + 4^5 + 1^0 + 7^4 \\ 3432 &:= -3^6 + 4^6 + 3^0 + 2^6 \\ 3434 &:= -3^6 + 4^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 \\ 3435 &:= -3^3 + 4^4 + 3^4 + 5^5 \\ 3436 &:= -3^5 - 4^6 - 3^0 + 6^5 \\ 3439 &:= -3^2 + 4^6 - 3^6 + 9^2 \\ 3449 &:= -3^6 + 4^0 + 4^6 + 9^2 \\ 3452 &:= -3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 2^3 \\ 3453 &:= -3^2 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 3^4 \\ 3454 &:= -3^4 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 \\ 3456 &:= -3^6 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\ 3457 &:= -3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\ 3458 &:= -3^2 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 8^4 \\ 3459 &:= -3^1 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 9^2 \\ 3472 &:= -3^4 + 4^5 + 7^4 + 2^7 \\ 3473 &:= -3^4 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 3^7 \\ 3475 &:= -3^2 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 5^5 \\ 3479 &:= -3^3 + 4^5 + 7^4 + 9^2 \\ 3492 &:= -3^1 + 4^6 - 9^3 + 2^7 \\ 3497 &:= -3^2 + 4^5 + 9^2 + 7^4 \\ 3522 &:= -3^5 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 2^9 \\ 3524 &:= -3^6 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 4^6 \\ 3528 &:= -3^4 + 5^2 - 2^9 + 8^4 \\ 3543 &:= -3^2 - 5^4 + 4^6 + 3^4 \\ 3545 &:= -3^6 + 5^3 + 4^5 + 5^5 \\ 3546 &:= -3^2 - 5^3 - 4^6 + 6^5 \\ 3547 &:= -3^1 + 5^3 + 4^5 + 7^4 \\ 3549 &:= -3^1 - 5^4 + 4^6 + 9^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3562 &:= -3^4 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 2^9 \\ 3583 &:= -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 + 3^3 \\ 3585 &:= -3^3 - 5^2 + 8^3 + 5^5 \\ 3617 &:= -3^4 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 7^4 \\ 3624 &:= -3^6 + 6^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 \\ 3634 &:= -3^1 - 6^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 \\ 3635 &:= -3^1 - 6^3 + 3^6 + 5^5 \\ 3638 &:= -3^5 - 6^3 + 3^0 + 8^4 \\ 3639 &:= -3^6 - 6^1 - 3^7 + 9^4 \\ 3656 &:= -3^6 - 6^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\ 3657 &:= -3^3 + 6^3 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\ 3670 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 0^1 \\ 3671 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 1^0 \\ 3672 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 2^1 \\ 3673 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 3^1 \\ 3674 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 4^1 \\ 3675 &:= -3^2 + 6^3 + 7^3 + 5^5 \\ 3676 &:= -3^3 + 6^1 + 7^4 + 6^4 \\ 3677 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 7^4 \\ 3678 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\ 3679 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\ 3687 &:= -3^2 + 6^4 - 8^0 + 7^4 \\ 3697 &:= -3^2 + 6^4 + 9^1 + 7^4 \\ 3724 &:= -3^3 - 7^3 - 2^1 + 4^6 \\ 3726 &:= -3^1 + 7^4 + 2^5 + 6^4 \\ 3728 &:= -3^2 - 7^3 - 2^4 + 8^4 \\ 3742 &:= -3^1 - 7^3 + 4^6 - 2^3 \\ 3743 &:= -3^2 - 7^3 + 4^6 - 3^0 \\ 3745 &:= -3^1 - 7^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 \\ 3746 &:= -3^6 + 7^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 \\ 3748 &:= -3^2 - 7^3 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\ 3749 &:= -3^1 - 7^3 + 4^6 - 9^0 \\ 3766 &:= -3^8 + 7^5 - 6^5 + 6^4 \\ 3768 &:= -3^5 - 7^2 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\ 3769 &:= -3^2 + 7^4 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\ 3782 &:= -3^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 + 2^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3786 &:= -3^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 + 6^2 \\ 3788 &:= -3^5 - 7^0 - 8^2 + 8^4 \\ 3822 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 - 2^5 + 2^0 \\ 3834 &:= -3^3 + 8^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 \\ 3835 &:= -3^3 + 8^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 \\ 3843 &:= -3^2 - 8^0 + 4^6 - 3^5 \\ 3844 &:= -3^5 - 8^1 - 4^0 + 4^6 \\ 3846 &:= -3^5 - 8^0 + 4^6 - 6^1 \\ 3848 &:= -3^5 - 8^0 - 4^1 + 8^4 \\ 3852 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 - 5^1 + 2^2 \\ 3853 &:= -3^2 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 3^6 \\ 3854 &:= -3^6 + 8^3 - 5^2 + 4^6 \\ 3855 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 + 5^0 + 5^0 \\ 3859 &:= -3^1 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 9^3 \\ 3860 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 + 6^1 + 0^0 \\ 3862 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 2^3 \\ 3863 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 3^2 \\ 3872 &:= -3^2 + 8^4 - 7^3 + 2^7 \\ 3873 &:= -3^2 + 8^4 - 7^4 + 3^7 \\ 3875 &:= -3^1 + 8^4 - 7^3 + 5^3 \\ 3878 &:= -3^6 + 8^3 - 7^0 + 8^4 \\ 3880 &:= -3^6 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 0^0 \\ 3924 &:= -3^3 - 9^2 - 2^6 + 4^6 \\ 3942 &:= -3^2 - 9^2 + 4^6 - 2^6 \\ 3943 &:= -3^4 - 9^2 + 4^6 + 3^2 \\ 3948 &:= -3^1 - 9^2 - 4^3 + 8^4 \\ 3964 &:= -3^3 - 9^5 + 6^6 + 4^7 \\ 3982 &:= -3^4 - 9^0 + 8^4 - 2^5 \\ 3984 &:= -3^3 - 9^2 + 8^4 - 4^1 \\ 3987 &:= -3^3 - 9^2 + 8^4 - 7^0 \\ 3989 &:= -3^3 - 9^2 + 8^4 + 9^0 \\ 4024 &:= -4^3 + 0^1 - 2^3 + 4^6 \\ 4028 &:= -4^1 + 0^1 - 2^6 + 8^4 \\ 4034 &:= -4^3 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 4^6 \\ 4048 &:= -4^3 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\ 4053 &:= -4^1 - 0^0 - 5^6 + 3^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4054 &:= -4^2 - 0^0 - 5^2 + 4^6 \\ 4058 &:= -4^3 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\ 4068 &:= -4^3 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\ 4074 &:= -4^2 + 0^0 - 7^1 + 4^6 \\ 4078 &:= -4^2 - 0^0 - 7^0 + 8^4 \\ 4080 &:= -4^2 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 0^0 \\ 4081 &:= -4^2 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 1^0 \\ 4082 &:= -4^2 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 2^0 \\ 4083 &:= -4^1 + 0^1 + 8^4 - 3^2 \\ 4084 &:= -4^1 + 0^1 - 8^1 + 4^6 \\ 4085 &:= -4^2 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 5^1 \\ 4086 &:= -4^1 + 0^1 + 8^4 - 6^1 \\ 4087 &:= -4^2 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 7^1 \\ 4088 &:= -4^2 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 8^4 \\ 4089 &:= -4^2 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\ 4094 &:= -4^1 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 4^6 \\ 4158 &:= -4^3 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\ 4208 &:= -4^2 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 8^4 \\ 4224 &:= -4^1 + 2^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 \\ 4228 &:= -4^1 + 2^3 + 2^7 + 8^4 \\ 4243 &:= -4^3 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 3^5 \\ 4245 &:= -4^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^2 \\ 4246 &:= -4^3 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\ 4247 &:= -4^3 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 7^3 \\ 4249 &:= -4^3 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 9^3 \\ 4264 &:= -4^2 - 2^5 + 6^3 + 4^6 \\ 4265 &:= -4^6 + 2^9 - 6^5 + 5^6 \\ 4283 &:= -4^3 + 2^3 + 8^4 + 3^5 \\ 4284 &:= -4^1 - 2^6 + 8^4 + 4^4 \\ 4285 &:= -4^3 + 2^7 + 8^4 + 5^3 \\ 4288 &:= -4^3 - 2^8 + 8^3 + 8^4 \\ 4289 &:= -4^2 + 2^7 + 8^4 + 9^2 \\ 4309 &:= -4^3 - 3^7 - 0^0 + 9^4 \\ 4324 &:= -4^2 + 3^5 + 2^0 + 4^6 \\ 4334 &:= -4^1 - 3^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 \\ 4335 &:= -4^3 + 3^7 + 3^7 + 5^2 \end{aligned}$$

4338 := $-4^1 + 3^1 + 3^5 + 8^4$
4352 := $-4^5 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 2^6$
4353 := $-4^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 3^7$
4356 := $-4^3 - 3^0 + 5^5 + 6^4$
4357 := $-4^4 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$
4359 := $-4^2 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 9^4$
4369 := $-4^1 - 3^7 - 6^0 + 9^4$
4374 := $-4^3 - 3^0 + 7^3 + 4^6$
4378 := $-4^3 + 3^1 + 7^3 + 8^4$
4395 := $-4^1 - 3^7 + 9^4 + 5^2$
4427 := $-4^1 + 4^6 - 2^3 + 7^3$
4429 := $-4^1 + 4^6 + 2^8 + 9^2$
4449 := $-4^3 - 4^5 - 4^5 + 9^4$
4487 := $-4^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 7^3$
4553 := $-4^7 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 3^7$
4573 := $-4^2 + 5^0 + 7^4 + 3^7$
4586 := $-4^3 - 5^5 - 8^0 + 6^5$
4594 := $-4^4 + 5^2 + 9^3 + 4^6$
4596 := $-4^3 - 5^5 + 9^1 + 6^5$
4624 := $-4^4 + 6^4 - 2^9 + 4^6$
4628 := $-4^2 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 8^4$
4648 := $-4^4 - 6^3 + 4^5 + 8^4$
4658 := $-4^3 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 8^4$
4689 := $-4^3 - 6^4 - 8^3 + 9^4$
4737 := $-4^3 + 7^4 - 3^0 + 7^4$
4754 := $-4^2 + 7^2 + 5^4 + 4^6$
4776 := $-4^4 - 7^3 - 7^4 + 6^5$
4778 := $-4^1 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 8^4$
4787 := $-4^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 7^4$
4797 := $-4^1 + 7^4 - 9^0 + 7^4$
4809 := $-4^2 + 8^4 + 0^1 + 9^3$
4823 := $-4^1 + 8^4 + 2^1 + 3^6$
4829 := $-4^1 + 8^4 + 2^3 + 9^3$
4848 := $-4^2 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 8^4$
4864 := $-4^2 - 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^6$
4887 := $-4^3 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 7^3$

4935 := $-4^3 + 9^4 - 3^7 + 5^4$
4952 := $-4^6 - 9^4 + 5^6 - 2^4$
4959 := $-4^6 - 9^1 + 5^6 - 9^4$
4975 := $-4^6 - 9^4 + 7^1 + 5^6$
5162 := $-5^5 - 1^0 + 6^5 + 2^9$
5236 := $-5^2 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^4$
5239 := $-5^4 + 2^5 - 3^6 + 9^4$
5268 := $-5^3 + 2^0 + 6^4 + 8^4$
5274 := $-5^6 - 2^2 + 7^5 + 4^6$
5295 := $-5^4 - 2^4 + 9^4 - 5^4$
5347 := $-5^6 + 3^7 + 4^7 + 7^4$
5362 := $-5^6 + 3^9 + 6^4 + 2^3$
5363 := $-5^6 + 3^2 + 6^4 + 3^9$
5364 := $-5^2 - 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^6$
5365 := $-5^2 + 3^8 - 6^4 + 5^3$
5367 := $-5^1 - 3^1 + 6^5 - 7^4$
5368 := $-5^2 + 3^0 + 6^4 + 8^4$
5369 := $-5^4 + 3^6 - 6^4 + 9^4$
5386 := $-5^1 - 3^0 + 8^4 + 6^4$
5413 := $-5^3 - 4^5 + 1^0 + 3^8$
5423 := $-5^4 - 4^0 - 2^9 + 3^8$
5439 := $-5^3 - 4^5 + 3^3 + 9^4$
5457 := $-5^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4$
5463 := $-5^3 - 4^0 + 6^5 - 3^7$
5493 := $-5^3 - 4^5 + 9^2 + 3^8$
5496 := $-5^1 - 4^5 + 9^4 - 6^2$
5543 := $-5^2 + 5^5 + 4^4 + 3^7$
5563 := $-5^2 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 3^7$
5639 := $-5^4 - 6^3 - 3^4 + 9^4$
5674 := $-5^5 + 6^5 - 7^0 + 4^5$
5693 := $-5^4 - 6^3 + 9^4 - 3^3$
5695 := $-5^2 - 6^3 + 9^4 - 5^4$
5729 := $-5^4 + 7^2 - 2^8 + 9^4$
5762 := $-5^3 - 7^4 + 6^5 + 2^9$
5769 := $-5^4 + 7^2 - 6^3 + 9^4$
5836 := $-5^4 - 8^2 + 3^8 - 6^2$

5873 := $-5^4 - 8^2 + 7^0 + 3^8$
5879 := $-5^4 - 8^1 - 7^2 + 9^4$
5892 := $-5^3 - 8^3 + 9^4 - 2^5$
5920 := $-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 0^1$
5921 := $-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 1^0$
5922 := $-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 2^1$
5923 := $-5^3 - 9^0 - 2^9 + 3^8$
5924 := $-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 4^1$
5925 := $-5^3 + 9^4 - 2^9 + 5^0$
5926 := $-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 6^1$
5927 := $-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 7^1$
5928 := $-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 8^1$
5929 := $-5^4 + 9^0 - 2^3 + 9^4$
5934 := $-5^4 - 9^0 + 3^8 - 4^0$
5936 := $-5^4 - 9^0 + 3^8 + 6^0$
5938 := $-5^4 + 9^0 + 3^8 + 8^0$
5940 := $-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 0^1$
5941 := $-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 1^0$
5942 := $-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 2^1$
5943 := $-5^4 - 9^1 + 4^2 + 3^8$
5944 := $-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 4^1$
5945 := $-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 5^1$
5946 := $-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 6^1$
5947 := $-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 7^1$
5948 := $-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 8^1$
5949 := $-5^4 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 9^4$
5962 := $-5^4 + 9^4 - 6^1 + 2^5$
5963 := $-5^4 - 9^1 + 6^2 + 3^8$
5964 := $-5^4 + 9^4 - 6^2 + 4^3$
5966 := $-5^4 + 9^4 - 6^1 + 6^2$
5969 := $-5^2 + 9^3 - 6^4 + 9^4$
5988 := $-5^3 + 9^4 - 8^3 + 8^2$
6226 := $-6^4 + 2^1 - 2^8 + 6^5$
6236 := $-6^4 - 2^0 - 3^5 + 6^5$
6243 := $-6^2 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 3^7$
6249 := $-6^3 - 2^5 - 4^3 + 9^4$

$$\begin{aligned} 6263 &:= -6^1 - 2^8 - 6^2 + 3^8 \\ 6266 &:= -6^3 + 2^1 - 6^4 + 6^5 \\ 6283 &:= -6^3 + 2^1 - 8^2 + 3^8 \\ 6289 &:= -6^3 + 2^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\ 6298 &:= -6^1 - 2^8 + 9^4 - 8^0 \\ 6313 &:= -6^1 - 3^5 + 1^0 + 3^8 \\ 6319 &:= -6^3 - 3^3 + 1^0 + 9^4 \\ 6332 &:= -6^3 - 3^2 + 3^8 - 2^2 \\ 6333 &:= -6^3 - 3^1 - 3^2 + 3^8 \\ 6334 &:= -6^3 - 3^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 \\ 6335 &:= -6^3 - 3^2 + 3^8 - 5^0 \\ 6336 &:= -6^1 - 3^1 + 3^8 - 6^3 \\ 6337 &:= -6^3 - 3^0 + 3^8 - 7^1 \\ 6338 &:= -6^1 - 3^6 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\ 6339 &:= -6^1 + 3^3 - 3^5 + 9^4 \\ 6342 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 2^0 \\ 6343 &:= -6^3 - 3^0 - 4^0 + 3^8 \\ 6345 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^0 \\ 6347 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^0 \\ 6349 &:= -6^3 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 9^4 \\ 6350 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 0^1 \\ 6351 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 1^0 \\ 6352 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 - 5^0 + 2^3 \\ 6353 &:= -6^3 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 3^8 \\ 6354 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 4^1 \\ 6355 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 5^1 \\ 6356 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^1 \\ 6357 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^1 \\ 6358 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^1 \\ 6359 &:= -6^3 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\ 6362 &:= -6^3 + 3^8 + 6^0 + 2^4 \\ 6373 &:= -6^3 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 3^8 \\ 6379 &:= -6^3 + 3^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\ 6392 &:= -6^3 - 3^4 + 9^4 + 2^7 \\ 6393 &:= -6^1 - 3^4 - 9^2 + 3^8 \\ 6396 &:= -6^4 - 3^1 - 9^2 + 6^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6397 &:= -6^3 + 3^1 + 9^4 + 7^2 \\ 6399 &:= -6^3 - 3^3 + 9^2 + 9^4 \\ 6409 &:= -6^3 + 4^3 + 0^1 + 9^4 \\ 6423 &:= -6^1 - 4^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 \\ 6427 &:= -6^1 + 4^6 - 2^6 + 7^4 \\ 6429 &:= -6^2 - 4^3 - 2^5 + 9^4 \\ 6456 &:= -6^4 + 4^0 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\ 6462 &:= -6^4 - 4^2 + 6^5 - 2^1 \\ 6463 &:= -6^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 3^7 \\ 6465 &:= -6^4 - 4^2 + 6^5 + 5^0 \\ 6467 &:= -6^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\ 6468 &:= -6^4 - 4^1 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\ 6483 &:= -6^1 - 4^3 - 8^1 + 3^8 \\ 6487 &:= -6^1 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 7^4 \\ 6490 &:= -6^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 - 0^0 \\ 6492 &:= -6^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 + 2^0 \\ 6506 &:= -6^4 + 5^2 + 0^0 + 6^5 \\ 6519 &:= -6^2 - 5^1 - 1^0 + 9^4 \\ 6523 &:= -6^2 - 5^0 - 2^0 + 3^8 \\ 6529 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 - 2^0 + 9^4 \\ 6530 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 0^1 \\ 6531 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 1^0 \\ 6532 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 2^1 \\ 6533 &:= -6^1 + 5^1 - 3^3 + 3^8 \\ 6534 &:= -6^1 - 5^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 \\ 6535 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 5^1 \\ 6536 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 6^1 \\ 6537 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 7^1 \\ 6538 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 \\ 6539 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^2 + 9^4 \\ 6549 &:= -6^1 - 5^1 - 4^0 + 9^4 \\ 6553 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 3^8 \\ 6557 &:= -6^2 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\ 6559 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\ 6573 &:= -6^1 + 5^2 - 7^1 + 3^8 \\ 6579 &:= -6^1 + 5^2 - 7^0 + 9^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6592 &:= -6^1 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 2^5 \\ 6593 &:= -6^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 3^5 \\ 6594 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 9^4 + 4^3 \\ 6595 &:= -6^3 + 5^3 + 9^4 + 5^3 \\ 6596 &:= -6^1 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 6^2 \\ 6599 &:= -6^1 + 5^3 - 9^2 + 9^4 \\ 6605 &:= -6^4 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 5^3 \\ 6623 &:= -6^1 + 6^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 \\ 6624 &:= -6^4 + 6^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 \\ 6732 &:= -6^1 + 7^2 + 3^8 + 2^7 \\ 6734 &:= -6^1 + 7^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 \\ 6737 &:= -6^3 + 7^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 \\ 6739 &:= -6^2 + 7^4 - 3^7 + 9^4 \\ 6773 &:= -6^3 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 3^7 \\ 6794 &:= -6^2 + 7^3 - 9^5 + 4^8 \\ 6825 &:= -6^5 - 8^3 - 2^9 + 5^6 \\ 6863 &:= -6^3 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 3^8 \\ 6888 &:= -6^4 - 8^1 + 8^4 + 8^4 \\ 6897 &:= -6^1 - 8^0 + 9^4 + 7^3 \\ 6937 &:= -6^4 - 9^3 + 3^8 + 7^4 \\ 6938 &:= -6^3 + 9^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\ 6954 &:= -6^1 + 9^4 - 5^4 + 4^5 \\ 6956 &:= -6^3 - 9^3 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\ 6979 &:= -6^1 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 \\ 6993 &:= -6^3 - 9^2 + 9^3 + 3^8 \\ 7023 &:= -7^2 - 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 \\ 7216 &:= -7^2 - 2^9 + 1^0 + 6^5 \\ 7233 &:= -7^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 3^8 \\ 7234 &:= -7^3 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 \\ 7239 &:= -7^2 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 9^4 \\ 7243 &:= -7^3 + 2^0 + 4^5 + 3^8 \\ 7253 &:= -7^4 - 2^5 + 5^5 + 3^8 \\ 7256 &:= -7^1 - 2^9 - 5^0 + 6^5 \\ 7294 &:= -7^4 - 2^7 - 9^4 + 4^7 \\ 7296 &:= -7^1 + 2^8 - 9^3 + 6^5 \\ 7299 &:= -7^1 + 2^4 + 9^3 + 9^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7322 &:= -7^1 + 3^8 + 2^8 + 2^9 \\ 7368 &:= -7^3 - 3^0 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\ 7416 &:= -7^3 - 4^2 - 1^0 + 6^5 \\ 7426 &:= -7^3 + 4^0 - 2^3 + 6^5 \\ 7435 &:= -7^1 + 4^4 + 3^8 + 5^4 \\ 7436 &:= -7^3 + 4^1 - 3^0 + 6^5 \\ 7453 &:= -7^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 3^8 \\ 7496 &:= -7^3 + 4^3 - 9^0 + 6^5 \\ 7526 &:= -7^3 + 5^3 - 2^5 + 6^5 \\ 7562 &:= -7^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 2^7 \\ 7563 &:= -7^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 3^4 \\ 7564 &:= -7^3 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 4^4 \\ 7566 &:= -7^2 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 6^5 \\ 7635 &:= -7^4 - 6^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 \\ 7652 &:= -7^1 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 2^3 \\ 7653 &:= -7^1 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 3^2 \\ 7662 &:= -7^2 - 6^0 + 6^5 - 2^6 \\ 7679 &:= -7^2 + 6^5 - 7^2 + 9^0 \\ 7692 &:= -7^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 + 2^2 \\ 7726 &:= -7^2 + 7^0 - 2^1 + 6^5 \\ 7746 &:= -7^1 - 7^1 - 4^2 + 6^5 \\ 7761 &:= -7^1 - 7^1 + 6^5 - 1^0 \\ 7763 &:= -7^1 - 7^1 + 6^5 + 3^0 \\ 7764 &:= -7^1 - 7^0 + 6^5 - 4^1 \\ 7767 &:= -7^1 - 7^0 + 6^5 - 7^0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7769 &:= -7^1 - 7^0 + 6^5 + 9^0 \\ 7786 &:= -7^1 + 7^4 + 8^4 + 6^4 \\ 7836 &:= -7^1 + 8^2 + 3^1 + 6^5 \\ 7837 &:= -7^4 - 8^1 - 3^8 + 7^5 \\ 7848 &:= -7^3 - 8^0 + 4^6 + 8^4 \\ 7854 &:= -7^3 + 8^4 + 5^1 + 4^6 \\ 7893 &:= -7^3 - 8^3 + 9^4 + 3^7 \\ 7986 &:= -7^1 + 9^3 - 8^3 + 6^5 \\ 8226 &:= -8^2 + 2^1 + 2^9 + 6^5 \\ 8248 &:= -8^1 + 2^6 + 4^6 + 8^4 \\ 8265 &:= -8^1 - 2^7 + 6^5 + 5^4 \\ 8296 &:= -8^4 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 6^6 \\ 8337 &:= -8^4 - 3^7 - 3^7 + 7^5 \\ 8485 &:= -8^1 - 4^8 - 8^4 + 5^7 \\ 8496 &:= -8^1 - 4^0 + 9^3 + 6^5 \\ 8733 &:= -8^1 - 7^1 + 3^7 + 3^8 \\ 8739 &:= -8^1 - 7^0 + 3^7 + 9^4 \\ 8897 &:= -8^2 - 8^0 + 9^4 + 7^4 \\ 8979 &:= -8^2 + 9^2 + 7^4 + 9^4 \\ 9057 &:= -9^4 + 0^1 + 5^6 - 7^1 \\ 9065 &:= -9^4 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 5^6 \\ 9094 &:= -9^3 + 0^1 - 9^4 + 4^7 \\ 9236 &:= -9^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 6^5 \\ 9324 &:= -9^4 - 3^5 - 2^8 + 4^7 \\ 9362 &:= -9^3 + 3^7 + 6^5 + 2^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9364 &:= -9^4 - 3^5 - 6^3 + 4^7 \\ 9367 &:= -9^2 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\ 9437 &:= -9^3 + 4^7 - 3^8 + 7^3 \\ 9454 &:= -9^4 + 4^4 - 5^4 + 4^7 \\ 9455 &:= -9^1 - 4^8 - 5^5 + 5^7 \\ 9478 &:= -9^4 - 4^4 + 7^5 - 8^3 \\ 9542 &:= -9^4 - 5^2 + 4^7 - 2^8 \\ 9569 &:= -9^2 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\ 9634 &:= -9^4 - 6^3 + 3^3 + 4^7 \\ 9657 &:= -9^4 + 6^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\ 9679 &:= -9^2 - 6^5 + 7^5 + 9^3 \\ 9727 &:= -9^4 - 7^1 - 2^9 + 7^5 \\ 9742 &:= -9^4 - 7^2 + 4^7 - 2^5 \\ 9745 &:= -9^4 - 7^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 \\ 9814 &:= -9^4 - 8^1 - 1^0 + 4^7 \\ 9824 &:= -9^4 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 4^7 \\ 9834 &:= -9^4 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 4^7 \\ 9879 &:= -9^3 + 8^4 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\ 9904 &:= -9^4 + 9^2 + 0^1 + 4^7 \\ 9924 &:= -9^3 + 9^4 - 2^2 + 4^6 \\ 9942 &:= -9^1 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 2^7 \\ 9944 &:= -9^3 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 4^6 \\ 9963 &:= -9^1 + 9^1 + 6^5 + 3^7 \\ 9964 &:= -9^3 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 4^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10176 &:= -1^1 - 0^0 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 6^5 \\ 10237 &:= -1^1 + 0^1 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 7^5 \\ 10372 &:= -1^1 - 0^0 - 3^8 + 7^5 + 2^7 \\ 10649 &:= -1^1 - 0^0 - 6^1 + 4^6 + 9^4 \\ 10687 &:= -1^1 - 0^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 7^4 \\ 10846 &:= -1^1 - 0^0 + 8^4 - 4^5 + 6^5 \\ 10933 &:= -1^1 - 0^0 + 9^4 + 3^7 + 3^7 \\ 10973 &:= -1^1 - 0^0 + 9^3 + 7^5 - 3^8 \\ 11528 &:= -1^1 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 2^0 - 8^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11538 &:= -1^1 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 3^2 - 8^4 \\ 11554 &:= -1^1 + 1^0 + 5^2 + 5^6 - 4^6 \\ 11578 &:= -1^1 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\ 11862 &:= -1^1 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 2^3 \\ 11863 &:= -1^1 + 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 3^2 \\ 11864 &:= -1^1 + 1^0 - 8^1 + 6^5 + 4^6 \\ 11865 &:= -1^1 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 5^1 \\ 11866 &:= -1^1 + 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 6^1 \\ 11869 &:= -1^1 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 9^0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12284 &:= -1^1 - 2^0 - 2^1 - 8^4 + 4^7 \\ 12296 &:= -1^1 - 2^5 - 2^6 + 9^5 - 6^6 \\ 12348 &:= -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 8^4 \\ 12367 &:= -1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\ 12369 &:= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\ 12386 &:= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 8^3 - 6^5 \\ 12393 &:= -1^1 + 2^0 - 3^6 + 9^4 + 3^8 \\ 12396 &:= -1^1 + 2^0 + 3^1 + 9^5 - 6^6 \\ 12435 &:= -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 3^8 + 5^5 \end{aligned}$$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| $12452 := -1^1 - 2^3 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 2^7$ | $12896 := -1^1 - 2^3 + 8^3 + 9^5 - 6^6$ | $13357 := -1^1 - 3^4 - 3^5 - 5^5 + 7^5$ |
| $12453 := -1^1 - 2^3 - 4^6 - 5^5 + 3^9$ | $12929 := -1^1 - 2^6 + 9^4 - 2^7 + 9^4$ | $13359 := -1^1 + 3^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 9^2$ |
| $12455 := -1^1 - 2^3 - 4^8 - 5^3 + 5^7$ | $12945 := -1^1 - 2^1 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 5^5$ | $13363 := -1^1 - 3^8 + 3^5 - 6^0 + 3^9$ |
| $12456 := -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^6 - 6^5$ | $12984 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 9^3 - 8^4 + 4^7$ | $13378 := -1^1 - 3^6 - 3^7 + 7^5 - 8^3$ |
| $12457 := -1^1 - 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 + 7^5$ | $12992 := -1^1 - 2^0 + 9^4 + 9^4 - 2^7$ | $13398 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 3^9 - 9^0 - 8^4$ |
| $12459 := -1^1 - 2^7 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 9^0$ | $12994 := -1^1 - 2^7 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 4^0$ | $13425 := -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^1 - 2^3 + 5^6$ |
| $12475 := -1^1 - 2^6 - 4^8 - 7^2 + 5^7$ | $12995 := -1^1 - 2^0 + 9^4 + 9^4 - 5^3$ | $13428 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^7 - 2^8 - 8^3$ |
| $12479 := -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^4$ | $13039 := -1^1 - 3^4 - 0^0 + 3^8 + 9^4$ | $13435 := -1^1 - 3^0 - 4^0 - 3^7 + 5^6$ |
| $12524 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 5^7 - 2^5 - 4^8$ | $13058 := -1^1 - 3^9 - 0^0 - 5^2 + 8^5$ | $13445 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 5^6$ |
| $12544 := -1^1 - 2^3 + 5^6 + 4^5 - 4^6$ | $13073 := -1^1 - 3^8 + 0^0 - 7^2 + 3^9$ | $13452 := -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 2^4$ |
| $12548 := -1^1 - 2^2 + 5^6 + 4^5 - 8^4$ | $13078 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 0^0 - 7^1 + 8^5$ | $13454 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 4^2$ |
| $12568 := -1^1 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^4$ | $13082 := -1^1 - 3^9 - 0^0 + 8^5 - 2^0$ | $13465 := -1^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 5^5$ |
| $12587 := -1^1 - 2^7 + 5^1 - 8^4 + 7^5$ | $13083 := -1^1 - 3^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^9$ | $13467 := -1^1 + 3^1 - 4^7 + 6^6 - 7^5$ |
| $12633 := -1^1 - 2^1 - 6^5 + 3^6 + 3^9$ | $13084 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 0^0 + 8^5 - 4^0$ | $13468 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 8^3$ |
| $12639 := -1^1 + 2^2 - 6^5 + 3^9 + 9^3$ | $13085 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 5^0$ | $13485 := -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 8^2 + 5^6$ |
| $12647 := -1^1 - 2^6 + 6^0 - 4^6 + 7^5$ | $13086 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 6^0$ | $13502 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 2^6$ |
| $12649 := -1^1 + 2^0 - 6^6 + 4^4 + 9^5$ | $13093 := -1^1 - 3^3 - 0^0 + 9^4 + 3^8$ | $13519 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 1^0 + 9^2$ |
| $12653 := -1^1 + 2^9 - 6^4 + 5^6 - 3^7$ | $13095 := -1^1 + 3^8 - 0^0 + 9^4 - 5^2$ | $13534 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 4^2$ |
| $12675 := -1^1 - 2^9 - 6^2 - 7^4 + 5^6$ | $13123 := -1^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 3^8$ | $13535 := -1^1 - 3^3 + 5^3 - 3^7 + 5^6$ |
| $12678 := -1^1 + 2^2 - 6^2 + 7^5 - 8^4$ | $13158 := -1^1 - 3^8 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 8^4$ | $13537 := -1^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 3^7 + 7^3$ |
| $12697 := -1^1 + 2^8 - 6^6 + 9^5 + 7^2$ | $13194 := -1^1 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 9^5 - 4^8$ | $13538 := -1^1 - 3^5 + 5^5 + 3^8 + 8^4$ |
| $12708 := -1^1 - 2^0 + 7^5 - 0^0 - 8^4$ | $13228 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 2^4 + 2^7 + 8^5$ | $13553 := -1^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 5^6 - 3^7$ |
| $12724 := -1^1 - 2^1 + 7^5 + 2^4 - 4^6$ | $13245 := -1^1 + 3^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5$ | $13556 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$ |
| $12728 := -1^1 + 2^1 + 7^5 + 2^4 - 8^4$ | $13249 := -1^1 + 3^8 + 2^6 + 4^3 + 9^4$ | $13572 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 2^7$ |
| $12738 := -1^1 + 2^0 + 7^5 + 3^3 - 8^4$ | $13254 := -1^1 - 3^1 - 2^0 - 5^5 + 4^7$ | $13573 := -1^1 - 3^3 - 5^5 + 7^5 - 3^4$ |
| $12742 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 7^5 - 4^6 + 2^6$ | $13266 := -1^1 + 3^9 + 2^6 + 6^4 - 6^5$ | $13574 := -1^1 - 3^3 - 5^5 + 7^3 + 4^7$ |
| $12745 := -1^1 - 2^9 - 7^0 + 4^7 - 5^5$ | $13268 := -1^1 - 3^9 - 2^5 + 6^3 + 8^5$ | $13575 := -1^1 - 3^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 5^5$ |
| $12783 := -1^1 - 2^3 + 7^5 - 8^4 + 3^4$ | $13286 := -1^1 - 3^6 + 2^7 - 8^5 + 6^6$ | $13578 := -1^1 + 3^5 + 5^4 + 7^5 - 8^4$ |
| $12789 := -1^1 - 2^1 + 7^5 - 8^4 + 9^2$ | $13328 := -1^1 + 3^5 - 3^9 + 2^0 + 8^5$ | $13596 := -1^1 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 9^3 - 6^4$ |
| $12832 := -1^1 - 2^8 + 8^5 - 3^9 + 2^2$ | $13332 := -1^1 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 3^8 - 2^5$ | $13597 := -1^1 - 3^1 - 5^5 - 9^2 + 7^5$ |
| $12833 := -1^1 - 2^3 + 8^5 - 3^5 - 3^9$ | $13336 := -1^1 - 3^0 + 3^8 + 3^8 + 6^3$ | $13599 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 9^2 + 9^2$ |
| $12836 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 8^5 - 3^9 - 6^3$ | $13338 := -1^1 + 3^6 + 3^8 + 3^8 - 8^3$ | $13623 := -1^1 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 2^4 + 3^8$ |
| $12839 := -1^1 - 2^2 + 8^4 + 3^7 + 9^4$ | $13352 := -1^1 - 3^4 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 2^2$ | $13628 := -1^1 - 3^1 + 6^6 - 2^8 - 8^5$ |
| $12853 := -1^1 - 2^8 + 8^5 + 5^2 - 3^9$ | $13353 := -1^1 - 3^1 - 3^4 + 5^6 - 3^7$ | $13632 := -1^1 + 3^8 - 6^0 + 3^8 + 2^9$ |
| $12856 := -1^1 + 2^5 - 8^4 + 5^6 + 6^4$ | $13355 := -1^1 - 3^4 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 5^6$ | $13644 := -1^1 - 3^5 + 6^6 - 4^7 - 4^7$ |
| $12864 := -1^1 + 2^0 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 4^5$ | $13356 := -1^1 - 3^5 - 3^6 + 5^6 - 6^4$ | $13648 := -1^1 - 3^5 + 6^6 + 4^1 - 8^5$ |

- | | | |
|--|--|--|
| 13652 := $-1^1 - 3^7 + 6^3 + 5^6 - 2^0$ | 14265 := $-1^1 - 4^3 + 2^0 - 6^4 + 5^6$ | 14598 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 9^0 - 8^0$ |
| 13654 := $-1^1 - 3^7 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 4^0$ | 14276 := $-1^1 + 4^6 + 2^2 + 7^4 + 6^5$ | 14605 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 6^1 - 0^0 + 5^6$ |
| 13665 := $-1^1 + 3^8 - 6^4 + 6^5 + 5^4$ | 14277 := $-1^1 - 4^3 - 2^6 - 7^4 + 7^5$ | 14635 := $-1^1 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 3^5 + 5^6$ |
| 13668 := $-1^1 - 3^1 - 6^3 + 6^6 - 8^5$ | 14293 := $-1^1 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 9^2 - 3^7$ | 14645 := $-1^1 - 4^0 + 6^6 - 4^7 - 5^6$ |
| 13677 := $-1^1 - 3^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 + 7^5$ | 14322 := $-1^1 + 4^7 - 3^7 + 2^7 - 2^1$ | 14652 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 6^2 + 5^6 + 2^4$ |
| 13735 := $-1^1 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 3^3 - 5^5$ | 14323 := $-1^1 + 4^7 - 3^0 + 2^7 - 3^7$ | 14657 := $-1^1 - 4^1 - 6^6 + 5^7 - 7^5$ |
| 13740 := $-1^1 - 3^5 - 7^4 + 4^7 + 0^0$ | 14324 := $-1^1 + 4^3 - 3^7 + 2^6 + 4^7$ | 14658 := $-1^1 - 4^5 - 6^1 + 5^6 + 8^2$ |
| 13753 := $-1^1 - 3^2 + 7^5 - 5^5 + 3^4$ | 14325 := $-1^1 - 4^5 - 3^5 - 2^5 + 5^6$ | 14665 := $-1^1 - 4^9 - 6^0 + 6^7 - 5^5$ |
| 13755 := $-1^1 - 3^7 + 7^3 - 5^2 + 5^6$ | 14336 := $-1^1 + 4^0 - 3^0 + 3^8 + 6^5$ | 14675 := $-1^1 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 7^3 + 5^6$ |
| 13758 := $-1^1 - 3^9 + 7^2 + 5^4 + 8^5$ | 14336 := $-1^1 - 4^0 + 3^0 + 3^8 + 6^5$ | 14677 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 6^4 - 7^4 + 7^5$ |
| 13759 := $-1^1 - 3^1 + 7^5 - 5^5 + 9^2$ | 14344 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 4^7$ | 14705 := $-1^1 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 0^1 - 5^5$ |
| 13795 := $-1^1 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 9^4 + 5^4$ | 14345 := $-1^1 - 4^4 + 3^0 - 4^5 + 5^6$ | 14742 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 7^5 - 4^5 - 2^4$ |
| 13806 := $-1^1 - 3^4 - 8^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$ | 14346 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3$ | 14749 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 7^5 - 4^5 - 9^1$ |
| 13826 := $-1^1 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 2^1 + 6^5$ | 14347 := $-1^1 - 4^2 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 7^5$ | 14764 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 7^5 + 6^1 - 4^5$ |
| 13829 := $-1^1 - 3^9 + 8^5 + 2^4 + 9^3$ | 14356 := $-1^1 + 4^0 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$ | 14765 := $-1^1 - 4^9 - 7^4 + 6^7 - 5^4$ |
| 13845 := $-1^1 - 3^5 - 8^3 - 4^5 + 5^6$ | 14358 := $-1^1 - 4^5 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 8^0$ | 14833 := $-1^1 + 4^6 + 8^4 + 3^4 + 3^8$ |
| 13846 := $-1^1 - 3^6 - 8^3 + 4^7 - 6^4$ | 14365 := $-1^1 + 4^1 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 5^2$ | 14835 := $-1^1 - 4^5 - 8^1 + 3^5 + 5^6$ |
| 13860 := $-1^1 - 3^3 - 8^5 + 6^6 + 0^1$ | 14377 := $-1^1 - 4^0 - 3^3 - 7^4 + 7^5$ | 14846 := $-1^1 - 4^5 - 8^3 + 4^7 - 6^0$ |
| 13861 := $-1^1 - 3^3 - 8^5 + 6^6 + 1^0$ | 14385 := $-1^1 + 4^7 - 3^7 + 8^2 + 5^3$ | 14848 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 8^0 + 4^7 - 8^3$ |
| 13862 := $-1^1 - 3^2 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 2^4$ | 14453 := $-1^1 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 3^7$ | 14852 := $-1^1 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 5^6 - 2^8$ |
| 13863 := $-1^1 + 3^1 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 3^3$ | 14456 := $-1^1 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$ | 14853 := $-1^1 - 4^2 - 8^3 + 5^6 - 3^5$ |
| 13864 := $-1^1 - 3^3 - 8^5 + 6^6 + 4^1$ | 14473 := $-1^1 - 4^6 + 4^7 - 7^0 + 3^7$ | 14855 := $-1^1 - 4^4 - 8^3 - 5^0 + 5^6$ |
| 13865 := $-1^1 + 3^1 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 5^2$ | 14478 := $-1^1 - 4^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^3$ | 14856 := $-1^1 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$ |
| 13866 := $-1^1 - 3^3 - 8^5 + 6^1 + 6^6$ | 14523 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 2^2 - 3^4$ | 14857 := $-1^1 - 4^4 - 8^3 + 5^6 + 7^0$ |
| 13867 := $-1^1 - 3^3 - 8^5 + 6^6 + 7^1$ | 14525 := $-1^1 - 4^6 + 5^5 - 2^7 + 5^6$ | 14872 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 8^5 - 7^5 - 2^6$ |
| 13868 := $-1^1 - 3^3 + 8^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$ | 14526 := $-1^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 2^6 - 6^4$ | 14895 := $-1^1 - 4^0 + 8^0 - 9^3 + 5^6$ |
| 13869 := $-1^1 - 3^2 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 9^1$ | 14528 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 2^3 - 8^2$ | 14929 := $-1^1 + 4^7 - 9^3 + 2^2 - 9^3$ |
| 13885 := $-1^1 - 3^7 - 8^2 + 8^3 + 5^6$ | 14543 := $-1^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 4^7 - 3^8$ | 14958 := $-1^1 - 4^0 - 9^3 + 5^6 + 8^2$ |
| 13886 := $-1^1 - 3^2 + 8^1 - 8^5 + 6^6$ | 14547 := $-1^1 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 4^5 - 7^2$ | 14965 := $-1^1 + 4^1 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 5^4$ |
| 13958 := $-1^1 - 3^7 + 9^1 + 5^6 + 8^3$ | 14562 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 2^5$ | 14968 := $-1^1 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 6^3 + 8^4$ |
| 13974 := $-1^1 - 3^2 + 9^0 - 7^4 + 4^7$ | 14563 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 3^0$ | 14989 := $-1^1 + 4^7 - 9^3 + 8^2 - 9^3$ |
| 14047 := $-1^1 + 4^3 + 0^0 + 4^7 - 7^4$ | 14565 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 6^2 + 5^6$ | 15023 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 0^1 + 2^7 - 3^6$ |
| 14064 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 0^0 - 6^4 + 4^7$ | 14583 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 8^1 - 3^2$ | 15112 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 1^0 + 1^0 - 2^9$ |
| 14213 := $-1^1 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 1^0 - 3^7$ | 14586 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 8^1 - 6^1$ | 15138 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 1^0 + 3^3 - 8^3$ |
| 14253 := $-1^1 + 4^7 + 2^5 + 5^2 - 3^7$ | 14590 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 9^1 - 0^0$ | 15139 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 1^0 + 3^5 - 9^3$ |
| 14256 := $-1^1 - 4^3 - 2^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$ | 14592 := $-1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 2^0$ | 15157 := $-1^1 - 5^3 + 1^0 + 5^6 - 7^3$ |

15192 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 1^0 + 9^2 - 2^9$	15390 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 0^1$	15533 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 3^2 - 3^4$
15224 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 2^9 + 2^7 - 4^2$	15391 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 1^0$	15534 := $-1^1 + 5^0 - 5^5 + 3^9 - 4^5$
15242 := $-1^1 - 5^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 2^9$	15392 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 2^1$	15536 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 3^4 - 6^1$
15243 := $-1^1 - 5^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 3^1$	15393 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 3^1 + 9^1 - 3^5$	15537 := $-1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 3^4 - 7^0$
15244 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 4^4$	15394 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 4^1$	15538 := $-1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 + 3^1 - 8^2$
15245 := $-1^1 - 5^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^4$	15395 := $-1^1 + 5^1 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 5^6$	15539 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 3^1 - 9^2$
15247 := $-1^1 - 5^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^0$	15396 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 6^1$	15543 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 + 4^0 - 3^4$
15248 := $-1^1 - 5^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 8^3$	15397 := $-1^1 - 5^3 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 7^4$	15547 := $-1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 - 4^0 + 7^2$
15254 := $-1^1 - 5^4 - 2^0 + 5^6 + 4^4$	15398 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 8^1$	15549 := $-1^1 + 5^1 + 5^6 + 4^0 - 9^2$
15256 := $-1^1 - 5^4 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^0$	15399 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 9^1$	15553 := $-1^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 5^6 - 3^4$
15257 := $-1^1 - 5^2 + 2^0 + 5^6 - 7^3$	15423 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 4^2 + 2^9 - 3^6$	15554 := $-1^1 - 5^0 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 4^3$
15263 := $-1^1 - 5^5 + 2^1 - 6^4 + 3^9$	15424 := $-1^1 + 5^0 - 4^5 + 2^6 + 4^7$	15557 := $-1^1 - 5^4 + 5^0 - 5^4 + 7^5$
15264 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 2^9 + 6^3 - 4^3$	15425 := $-1^1 + 5^2 - 4^4 + 2^5 + 5^6$	15558 := $-1^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 8^2$
15275 := $-1^1 - 5^1 - 2^0 - 7^3 + 5^6$	15426 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 4^2 + 2^1 - 6^3$	15562 := $-1^1 + 5^0 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 2^6$
15287 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 2^1 + 8^1 - 7^3$	15428 := $-1^1 + 5^5 + 4^7 + 2^4 - 8^4$	15564 := $-1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 4^0$
15318 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 1^0 - 8^2$	15436 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 4^0 + 3^3 - 6^3$	15569 := $-1^1 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^2$
15333 := $-1^1 + 5^2 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 3^8$	15448 := $-1^1 + 5^2 - 4^5 + 4^7 + 8^2$	15570 := $-1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 7^2 + 0^1$
15336 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^4 + 3^2 - 6^3$	15462 := $-1^1 - 5^4 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 2^9$	15571 := $-1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 7^2 + 1^0$
15338 := $-1^1 - 5^1 - 3^5 + 3^9 - 8^4$	15468 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^2$	15572 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 7^2 - 2^1$
15342 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^3 + 4^0 - 2^8$	15484 := $-1^1 + 5^3 - 4^5 + 8^5 - 4^7$	15573 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 7^2 - 3^0$
15346 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 4^0 - 6^2$	15500 := $-1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 0^1$	15574 := $-1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 7^2 + 4^1$
15352 := $-1^1 - 5^2 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 2^8$	15501 := $-1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 1^0$	15575 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 5^0 - 7^2 + 5^6$
15353 := $-1^1 - 5^0 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 3^5$	15502 := $-1^1 + 5^1 + 5^6 + 0^0 - 2^7$	15576 := $-1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 7^1 - 6^2$
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15356 := $-1^1 - 5^2 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^3$	15505 := $-1^1 + 5^1 - 5^3 + 0^0 + 5^6$	15579 := $-1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 7^2 + 9^1$
15357 := $-1^1 - 5^1 + 3^4 + 5^6 - 7^3$	15506 := $-1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 6^1$	15582 := $-1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 8^0 - 2^4$
15372 := $-1^1 + 5^4 - 3^7 + 7^5 + 2^7$	15507 := $-1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 7^1$	15584 := $-1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 + 8^0 - 4^2$
15373 := $-1^1 + 5^2 - 3^6 + 7^5 - 3^6$	15508 := $-1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 8^1$	15586 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 8^0 - 6^2$
15374 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^0 + 7^1 - 4^4$	15509 := $-1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 9^1$	15589 := $-1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 8^0 - 9^1$
15375 := $-1^1 - 5^1 - 3^5 - 7^0 + 5^6$	15512 := $-1^1 - 5^4 + 5^6 + 1^0 + 2^9$	15590 := $-1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 0^1$
15376 := $-1^1 - 5^3 - 3^2 + 7^5 - 6^4$	15514 := $-1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 - 1^0 + 4^2$	15591 := $-1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 1^0$
15379 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 7^1 - 9^1$	15519 := $-1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 + 1^0 - 9^2$	15592 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 + 9^0 - 2^5$
15381 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 8^0 - 1^0$	15522 := $-1^1 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 2^0 - 2^7$	15593 := $-1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 - 3^3$
15383 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 8^0 - 3^5$	15525 := $-1^1 + 5^2 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 5^6$	15594 := $-1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 9^1 - 4^2$
15388 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 8^1 - 8^0$	15532 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 3^3 - 2^6$	15595 := $-1^1 - 5^1 - 5^2 + 9^0 + 5^6$

$15596 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 + 9^1 - 6^2$	$15647 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 7^0$	$15732 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 7^1 + 3^5 - 2^7$
$15597 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 9^0 - 7^0$	$15648 := -1^1 + 5^4 - 6^4 + 4^7 - 8^2$	$15733 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^0 + 3^3 + 3^4$
$15598 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 8^1$	$15649 := -1^1 + 5^0 - 6^1 + 4^7 - 9^3$	$15735 := -1^1 - 5^3 - 7^1 + 3^5 + 5^6$
$15599 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 9^0 + 9^0$	$15650 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 0^1$	$15736 := -1^1 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 3^6 - 6^3$
$15602 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 0^1 - 2^4$	$15651 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 1^0$	$15738 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 8^2$
$15603 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 0^1 - 3^3$	$15652 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 2^5$	$15739 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 3^3 + 9^2$
$15604 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 0^1 + 4^2$	$15653 := -1^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 3^3$	$15750 := -1^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 5^6 + 0^1$
$15605 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 5^6$	$15654 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 6^2 + 5^6 - 4^0$	$15751 := -1^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 5^6 + 1^0$
$15609 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 0^1 - 9^1$	$15655 := -1^1 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 5^2 + 5^6$	$15752 := -1^1 + 5^0 - 7^0 + 5^6 + 2^7$
$15617 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 1^0 - 7^1$	$15656 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15753 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 7^2 + 5^6 + 3^4$
$15618 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 1^0 - 8^1$	$15657 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 7^1$	$15754 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 7^0 - 5^4 + 4^7$
$15620 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 2^0 + 0^0$	$15658 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 5^6 - 8^0$	$15755 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 7^1 + 5^3 + 5^6$
$15621 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 2^1 + 1^0$	$15659 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 9^1$	$15756 := -1^1 + 5^1 + 7^3 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15622 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 2^0 - 2^1$	$15660 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 6^2 - 0^0$	$15757 := -1^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 5^6 + 7^1$
$15623 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 2^0 - 3^0$	$15660 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 6^2 + 0^0$	$15758 := -1^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 5^6 + 8^1$
$15624 := -1^1 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 2^9 + 4^7$	$15662 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 6^2 + 2^0$	$15759 := -1^1 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 5^6 + 9^2$
$15625 := -1^1 + 5^0 - 6^0 + 2^0 + 5^6$	$15663 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 3^3$	$15764 := -1^1 - 5^4 + 7^1 - 6^0 + 4^7$
$15625 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 5^6$	$15665 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 5^6$	$15773 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^2 + 7^3 - 3^5$
$15626 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^1 - 6^0$	$15667 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 7^0$	$15774 := -1^1 - 5^0 - 7^1 + 7^5 - 4^5$
$15626 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 2^1 + 6^0$	$15668 := -1^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 6^5 - 8^1$	$15784 := -1^1 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^0 - 4^5$
$15627 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0$	$15671 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 - 1^0$	$15792 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 7^2 + 9^3 - 2^9$
$15628 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 8^0$	$15672 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 - 2^1$	$15793 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 9^2 + 3^4$
$15629 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 2^1 + 9^1$	$15673 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 - 3^0$	$15803 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 8^2 + 0^1 + 3^5$
$15630 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 3^0 - 0^0$	$15673 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 + 3^0$	$15824 := -1^1 - 5^4 + 8^2 + 2^1 + 4^7$
$15631 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 3^2 - 1^0$	$15675 := -1^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 5^6$	$15827 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 8^5 - 2^7 - 7^5$
$15632 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^3$	$15678 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 - 8^0$	$15832 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 8^0 + 3^4 + 2^7$
$15633 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 3^2$	$15681 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 - 1^0$	$15842 := -1^1 - 5^2 - 8^3 + 4^7 - 2^2$
$15634 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 3^3 - 4^2$	$15683 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 + 3^0$	$15843 := -1^1 - 5^0 - 8^3 + 4^7 - 3^3$
$15635 := -1^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 3^2 + 5^6$	$15684 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 4^2$	$15845 := -1^1 - 5^0 - 8^3 + 4^7 - 5^2$
$15638 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 3^2 - 8^0$	$15686 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^2 - 6^0$	$15846 := -1^1 - 5^6 - 8^5 + 4^8 - 6^4$
$15640 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 4^2 - 0^0$	$15687 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 7^2$	$15847 := -1^1 - 5^2 - 8^3 + 4^7 + 7^0$
$15640 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 4^2 + 0^0$	$15688 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^0 + 8^2$	$15854 := -1^1 - 5^2 - 8^0 + 5^6 + 4^4$
$15642 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 2^4$	$15697 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^2 - 7^1$	$15862 := -1^1 - 5^6 + 8^5 - 6^4 + 2^4$
$15643 := -1^1 - 5^1 - 6^1 + 4^7 - 3^6$	$15698 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 8^2$	$15864 := -1^1 - 5^0 - 8^3 - 6^1 + 4^7$
$15645 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 5^6$	$15712 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^3 + 1^0 - 2^8$	$15873 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 8^0 + 7^1 + 3^5$
$15646 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 4^3 - 6^2$	$15713 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 3^4$	$15882 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 2^8$

15883 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 3^5$	16255 := $-1^1 - 6^1 + 2^9 + 5^3 + 5^6$	16385 := $-1^1 + 6^1 + 3^5 + 8^3 + 5^6$
15884 := $-1^1 + 5^1 - 8^3 + 8^1 + 4^7$	16257 := $-1^1 - 6^2 - 2^9 - 5^0 + 7^5$	16394 := $-1^1 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 4^7$
15932 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 2^6$	16258 := $-1^1 - 6^1 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 8^3$	16403 := $-1^1 - 6^1 + 4^7 - 0^0 + 3^3$
15933 := $-1^1 + 5^4 + 9^4 + 3^7 + 3^8$	16272 := $-1^1 - 6^1 - 2^4 + 7^5 - 2^9$	16404 := $-1^1 + 6^2 - 4^2 + 0^0 + 4^7$
15934 := $-1^1 - 5^3 - 9^2 - 3^5 + 4^7$	16273 := $-1^1 + 6^1 - 2^9 + 7^5 - 3^3$	16412 := $-1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 1^0 - 2^3$
15937 := $-1^1 - 5^4 - 9^0 - 3^5 + 7^5$	16274 := $-1^1 - 6^2 - 2^9 + 7^5 + 4^2$	16415 := $-1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 5^2$
15939 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 3^5 + 9^2$	16275 := $-1^1 + 6^1 - 2^9 + 7^5 - 5^2$	16419 := $-1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 1^0 - 9^0$
15950 := $-1^1 - 5^5 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 0^1$	16278 := $-1^1 - 6^4 + 2^8 + 7^5 + 8^3$	16420 := $-1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 2^5 - 0^0$
15951 := $-1^1 - 5^5 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 1^0$	16279 := $-1^1 - 6^1 - 2^9 + 7^5 - 9^1$	16421 := $-1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 2^0 + 1^0$
15952 := $-1^1 - 5^5 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 2^1$	16284 := $-1^1 - 6^2 + 2^0 - 8^2 + 4^7$	16422 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 2^5$
15953 := $-1^1 + 5^1 + 9^2 + 5^6 + 3^5$	16287 := $-1^1 - 6^1 - 2^0 - 8^3 + 7^5$	16423 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^5 + 3^2$
15954 := $-1^1 + 5^4 + 9^3 + 5^6 - 4^5$	16294 := $-1^1 - 6^1 - 2^1 - 9^2 + 4^7$	16424 := $-1^1 + 6^2 + 4^0 + 2^2 + 4^7$
15955 := $-1^1 + 5^1 - 9^5 + 5^7 - 5^5$	16295 := $-1^1 + 6^1 - 2^6 + 9^3 + 5^6$	16425 := $-1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 5^2$
15956 := $-1^1 + 5^3 - 9^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	16296 := $-1^1 + 6^5 + 2^4 + 9^3 + 6^5$	16426 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 6^2$
15957 := $-1^1 - 5^0 - 9^1 + 5^6 + 7^3$	16297 := $-1^1 - 6^1 - 2^9 + 9^1 + 7^5$	16427 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 - 2^2 + 7^2$
15958 := $-1^1 - 5^5 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 8^1$	16304 := $-1^1 + 6^0 - 3^4 + 0^0 + 4^7$	16428 := $-1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 2^0 + 8^1$
15959 := $-1^1 - 5^5 + 9^1 + 5^7 - 9^5$	16324 := $-1^1 + 6^1 - 3^4 + 2^4 + 4^7$	16429 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^7 - 9^2$
15962 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 9^2 + 6^0 + 2^8$	16325 := $-1^1 - 6^2 + 3^6 + 2^3 + 5^6$	16432 := $-1^1 - 6^1 + 4^7 - 3^2 + 2^6$
15967 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 9^0 + 6^0 + 7^3$	16327 := $-1^1 - 6^1 - 3^6 + 2^8 + 7^5$	16435 := $-1^1 - 6^3 + 4^5 + 3^1 + 5^6$
15972 := $-1^1 - 5^4 - 9^2 + 7^5 - 2^7$	16342 := $-1^1 - 6^1 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 2^5$	16438 := $-1^1 - 6^1 + 4^7 - 3^1 + 8^2$
15973 := $-1^1 + 5^4 - 9^3 + 7^5 - 3^6$	16343 := $-1^1 - 6^2 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 3^1$	16440 := $-1^1 - 6^1 + 4^3 + 4^7 - 0^0$
15974 := $-1^1 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 7^3 + 4^2$	16344 := $-1^1 - 6^2 + 3^0 - 4^1 + 4^7$	16442 := $-1^1 - 6^0 - 4^1 + 4^7 + 2^6$
15975 := $-1^1 - 5^0 + 9^1 + 7^3 + 5^6$	16345 := $-1^1 - 6^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^1$	16443 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 4^3 + 4^7 - 3^1$
15977 := $-1^1 + 5^6 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 7^3$	16347 := $-1^1 - 6^2 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^0$	16444 := $-1^1 + 6^0 - 4^1 + 4^3 + 4^7$
16047 := $-1^1 + 6^1 + 0^0 + 4^7 - 7^3$	16348 := $-1^1 - 6^2 + 3^0 - 4^7 + 8^5$	16445 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 4^3 + 4^7 - 5^0$
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16062 := $-1^1 + 6^5 - 0^0 + 6^5 + 2^9$	16351 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 3^6 + 5^6 - 1^0$	16448 := $-1^1 + 6^0 - 4^7 + 4^3 + 8^5$
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16237 := $-1^1 - 6^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 7^5$	16355 := $-1^1 + 6^0 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 5^6$	16454 := $-1^1 + 6^1 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 4^7$
16247 := $-1^1 - 6^0 - 2^7 + 4^7 - 7^1$	16358 := $-1^1 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 5^6 - 8^0$	16456 := $-1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 6^2$
16248 := $-1^1 + 6^0 - 2^7 + 4^7 - 8^1$	16365 := $-1^1 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 5^6$	16458 := $-1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 8^2$
16249 := $-1^1 - 6^3 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 9^2$	16374 := $-1^1 - 6^0 - 3^0 - 7^1 + 4^7$	16459 := $-1^1 - 6^1 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 9^2$
16253 := $-1^1 - 6^2 - 2^6 + 5^6 + 3^6$	16384 := $-1^1 + 6^0 - 3^0 + 8^0 + 4^7$	16467 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^2$
16254 := $-1^1 - 6^1 + 2^1 - 5^3 + 4^7$	16384 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 4^7$	16469 := $-1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 9^2$

$16472 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 2^2$	$16729 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 - 2^5 - 9^1$	$16807 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 8^0 + 0^0 + 7^5$
$16474 := -1^1 - 6^6 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 4^8$	$16732 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 3^2 - 2^6$	$16807 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 7^5$
$16475 := -1^1 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 5^3$	$16733 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 + 3^2 - 3^4$	$16827 := -1^1 + 6^1 - 8^0 + 2^4 + 7^5$
$16477 := -1^1 - 6^3 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 7^5$	$16734 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^3 + 3^2 + 4^7$	$16834 := -1^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 3^5 + 4^7$
$16479 := -1^1 - 6^6 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 9^0$	$16736 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^4 + 3^8 + 6^5$	$16837 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 8^2 - 3^3 + 7^5$
$16482 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 8^2 - 2^0$	$16738 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 3^1 - 8^2$	$16843 := -1^1 + 6^3 + 8^0 + 4^7 + 3^5$
$16484 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^0 + 8^2 + 4^7$	$16740 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 4^3 - 0^0$	$16847 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 8^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$
$16489 := -1^1 - 6^6 + 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$16742 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 + 4^0 - 2^6$	$16852 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 8^2 + 5^6 - 2^2$
$16492 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 9^1 + 2^6$	$16744 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 4^0 - 4^3$	$16853 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 8^3 - 5^5 + 3^9$
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$16496 := -1^1 - 6^4 - 4^9 + 9^0 + 6^7$	$16747 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 7^2 - 4^1 + 7^5$	$16855 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 8^2 + 5^6 - 5^0$
$16499 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 9^2 - 9^0$	$16753 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 5^2 - 3^3$	$16857 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 8^2 + 5^6 + 7^0$
$16523 := -1^1 - 6^2 - 5^5 + 2^1 + 3^9$	$16755 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 5^2 - 5^2$	$16859 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 8^3 + 5^6 + 9^3$
$16527 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 5^0 - 2^6 + 7^5$	$16757 := -1^1 - 6^0 - 7^2 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$16870 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 8^2 + 7^5 + 0^0$
$16534 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 5^3 + 3^3 + 4^7$	$16762 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 6^1 - 2^5$	$16872 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 2^6$
$16537 := -1^1 - 6^0 - 5^2 - 3^5 + 7^5$	$16763 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 6^2 - 3^0$	$16873 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 8^1 + 7^5 + 3^4$
$16542 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 5^2 + 4^7 + 2^7$	$16765 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 6^2 + 5^0$	$16875 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 8^2 + 7^5 - 5^0$
$16543 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 4^7 - 3^0$	$16768 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 6^2 - 8^0$	$16877 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 8^2 + 7^0 + 7^5$
$16545 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 5^0 + 4^7 + 5^3$	$16770 := -1^1 - 6^2 - 7^0 + 7^5 + 0^0$	$16883 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 8^4 + 8^0 + 3^9$
$16548 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 5^6 + 4^5 - 8^2$	$16772 := -1^1 - 6^0 - 7^0 + 7^5 - 2^5$	$16925 := -1^1 + 6^4 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 5^6$
$16563 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 3^6$	$16773 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 7^1 + 7^5 - 3^3$	$16927 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 9^0 + 2^7 + 7^5$
$16564 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 4^7$	$16774 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^2 + 7^3 + 4^7$	$16942 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 9^3 + 4^7 - 2^3$
$16568 := -1^1 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^3$	$16775 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 7^1 + 7^5 - 5^2$	$16945 := -1^1 + 6^3 + 9^2 + 4^5 + 5^6$
$16574 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 4^4$	$16776 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^1 + 7^5 - 6^2$	$16949 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 9^0 + 4^7 - 9^3$
$16576 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 5^6 - 7^3 + 6^4$	$16778 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 7^1 + 7^5 + 8^0$	$16965 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 6^4 + 5^6$
$16587 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 5^1 - 8^1 + 7^5$	$16782 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 2^2$	$16985 := -1^1 + 6^4 + 9^0 + 8^2 + 5^6$
$16627 := -1^1 + 6^2 - 6^3 + 2^0 + 7^5$	$16783 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 8^1 - 3^2$	$16987 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 7^5$
$16644 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 6^1 + 4^4 + 4^7$	$16784 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^2 + 4^7$	$17026 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 6^3$
$16647 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 7^2$	$16786 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 8^1 - 6^1$	$17032 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 3^5 - 2^4$
$16695 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 6^4 - 9^1 + 5^6$	$16790 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 9^1 - 0^0$	$17034 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 3^5 - 4^2$
$16722 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 2^3 - 2^7$	$16792 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 9^0 - 2^4$	$17039 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 3^5 - 9^1$
$16723 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 2^0 - 3^4$	$16793 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 9^1 - 3^1$	$17053 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 5^1 + 3^5$
$16724 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^3 - 2^0 + 4^7$	$16795 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 9^1 - 5^0$	$17055 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 5^3 + 5^3$
$16725 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 2^3 - 5^3$	$16797 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^0 - 9^1 + 7^5$	$17062 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 2^8$
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$16728 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 2^3 - 8^2$	$16799 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 9^0 - 9^1$	$17086 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 6^3$

17175 := $-1^1 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 5^2$	17351 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 3^4 + 5^4 + 1^0$	17593 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 5^4 + 9^2 + 3^4$
17222 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 2^7 + 2^8$	17352 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 5^2 + 2^9$	17594 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 9^3 + 4^3$
17225 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 2^9 - 5^3$	17353 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 3^1 + 5^4 - 3^4$	17596 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 5^2 + 9^3 + 6^2$
17226 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 2^7 + 2^8 + 6^2$	17354 := $-1^1 + 7^3 + 3^1 + 5^4 + 4^7$	17598 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^0 + 9^3 + 8^2$
17229 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 2^3 + 2^9 - 9^2$	17355 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 3^4 + 5^1 + 5^4$	17622 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 2^5 - 2^9$
17242 := $-1^1 + 7^3 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 2^9$	17356 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 3^4 + 5^4 + 6^1$	17629 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 2^8 - 9^3$
17246 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 6^3$	17357 := $-1^1 + 7^1 - 3^4 + 5^4 + 7^5$	17659 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 6^0 + 5^3 + 9^3$
17247 := $-1^1 - 7^1 + 2^9 - 4^3 + 7^5$	17358 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 3^2 + 5^4 - 8^2$	17664 := $-1^1 - 7^3 + 6^3 + 6^7 - 4^9$
17262 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 2^4 + 6^3 + 2^8$	17359 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 5^4 - 9^2$	17760 := $-1^1 - 7^3 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 0^0$
17263 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 2^1 + 6^3 + 3^5$	17363 := $-1^1 - 7^4 + 3^4 + 6^0 + 3^9$	17774 := $-1^1 - 7^1 - 7^2 + 7^5 + 4^5$
17265 := $-1^1 + 7^3 + 2^1 + 6^4 + 5^6$	17398 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 3^0 + 9^2 + 8^3$	17775 := $-1^1 + 7^0 + 7^3 + 7^5 + 5^4$
17269 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 6^3 - 9^1$	17424 := $-1^1 + 7^0 + 4^5 + 2^4 + 4^7$	17792 := $-1^1 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 2^8$
17270 := $-1^1 - 7^2 + 2^9 + 7^5 + 0^0$	17435 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 5^4$	17822 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 8^1 + 2^9 + 2^9$
17273 := $-1^1 - 7^1 - 2^0 - 7^4 + 3^9$	17448 := $-1^1 + 7^2 + 4^5 + 4^7 - 8^1$	17824 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 8^1 + 2^1 + 4^5$
17275 := $-1^1 + 7^3 + 2^0 + 7^5 + 5^3$	17455 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 5^4$	17825 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 2^9 - 5^1$
17276 := $-1^1 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 7^5 - 6^0$	17464 := $-1^1 - 7^3 + 4^2 + 6^7 - 4^9$	17829 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 2^9 - 9^0$
17278 := $-1^1 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 7^5 + 8^0$	17486 := $-1^1 - 7^2 - 4^4 - 8^6 + 6^7$	17834 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 4^5$
17282 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 2^2 + 8^3 - 2^5$	17513 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 5^4 + 1^0 + 3^4$	17842 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 2^2$
17283 := $-1^1 - 7^4 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 3^9$	17530 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6 + 0^1$	17846 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 + 4^4 + 6^4$
17285 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 2^3 + 8^3 - 5^2$	17531 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6 + 1^0$	17854 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 8^0 + 5^2 + 4^5$
17286 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 2^2 + 8^3 - 6^2$	17532 := $-1^1 - 7^3 + 5^6 + 3^7 + 2^6$	17862 := $-1^1 + 7^1 - 8^6 + 6^7 + 2^6$
17287 := $-1^1 + 7^0 - 2^5 + 8^3 + 7^5$	17533 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^0 + 3^6 - 3^0$	17865 := $-1^1 + 7^2 - 8^6 + 6^7 + 5^2$
17293 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 2^0 + 9^3 - 3^5$	17534 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6 + 4^1$	17879 := $-1^1 + 7^3 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 9^3$
17305 := $-1^1 - 7^4 + 3^9 - 0^0 + 5^2$	17535 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 5^0 + 3^6 - 5^0$	17945 := $-1^1 + 7^4 - 9^2 + 4^0 + 5^6$
17312 := $-1^1 - 7^4 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 2^5$	17535 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^0 + 3^6 + 5^0$	17952 := $-1^1 + 7^4 - 9^1 + 5^6 - 2^6$
17316 := $-1^1 - 7^4 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 6^2$	17536 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6 + 6^1$	17953 := $-1^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 5^6 - 3^4$
17318 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 3^0 + 1^0 + 8^3$	17537 := $-1^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 3^6 + 7^5$	17954 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 9^0 + 5^3 + 4^5$
17320 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 3^0 + 2^9 + 0^0$	17538 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6 + 8^1$	17975 := $-1^1 - 7^2 - 9^0 + 7^4 + 5^6$
17322 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 2^9$	17539 := $-1^1 + 7^4 + 5^6 + 3^5 - 9^3$	18046 := $-1^1 - 8^6 - 0^0 + 4^4 + 6^7$
17326 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 2^9 - 6^0$	17552 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 5^4 - 2^2$	18167 := $-1^1 + 8^2 + 1^0 + 6^4 + 7^5$
17328 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 2^0 + 8^3$	17553 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 5^4 - 3^1$	18274 := $-1^1 - 8^3 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 4^7$
17332 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 2^8$	17555 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^0 + 5^3 + 5^4$	18324 := $-1^1 + 8^4 - 3^7 + 2^5 + 4^7$
17335 := $-1^1 + 7^2 + 3^6 + 3^9 - 5^5$	17557 := $-1^1 + 7^0 + 5^3 + 5^4 + 7^5$	18325 := $-1^1 + 8^3 + 3^7 + 2^1 + 5^6$
17344 := $-1^1 - 7^4 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 4^3$	17559 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 5^0 + 5^2 + 9^3$	18326 := $-1^1 - 8^2 + 3^9 + 2^2 - 6^4$
17346 := $-1^1 - 7^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^0$	17579 := $-1^1 + 7^2 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^3$	18345 := $-1^1 - 8^4 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^6$
17350 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 3^4 + 5^4 + 0^1$	17592 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 5^2 + 9^3 + 2^5$	18346 := $-1^1 - 8^1 + 3^7 + 4^7 - 6^3$

- 18362** := $-1^1 - 8^1 + 3^9 - 6^4 - 2^4$ **19075** := $-1^1 - 9^5 - 0^0 + 7^0 + 5^7$ **19646** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 6^5 + 4^6 + 6^5$
18364 := $-1^1 - 8^3 - 3^1 - 6^6 + 4^8$ **19243** := $-1^1 + 9^1 - 2^9 + 4^3 + 3^9$ **19673** := $-1^1 - 9^0 - 6^0 - 7^1 + 3^9$
18365 := $-1^1 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 6^4 - 5^5$ **19332** := $-1^1 + 9^2 + 3^4 + 3^9 - 2^9$ **19683** := $-1^1 + 9^0 - 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^9$
18368 := $-1^1 - 8^2 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 8^4$ **19335** := $-1^1 - 9^3 - 3^5 + 3^9 + 5^4$ **19685** := $-1^1 + 9^0 - 6^2 + 8^4 + 5^6$
18369 := $-1^1 - 8^1 + 3^9 - 6^4 - 9^1$ **19337** := $-1^1 - 9^0 - 3^0 + 3^9 - 7^3$ **19687** := $-1^1 + 9^2 - 6^4 + 8^4 + 7^5$
18386 := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 3^9 + 8^0 - 6^4$ **19344** := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 4^4$ **19693** := $-1^1 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 3^9$
18396 := $-1^1 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^1 - 6^4$ **19346** := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^0$ **19723** := $-1^1 - 9^1 + 7^2 + 2^0 + 3^9$
18436 := $-1^1 + 8^4 + 4^1 + 3^8 + 6^5$ **19353** := $-1^1 - 9^2 - 3^5 - 5^1 + 3^9$ **19730** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 0^1$
18453 := $-1^1 + 8^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 3^5$ **19386** := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 3^9 + 8^0 - 6^3$ **19731** := $-1^1 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 - 1^0$
18456 := $-1^1 + 8^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$ **19392** := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 3^9 - 9^2 - 2^7$ **19732** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 2^1$
18496 := $-1^1 + 8^2 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 6^5$ **19395** := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 3^9 - 9^2 - 5^3$ **19733** := $-1^1 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 3^9$
18534 := $-1^1 + 8^0 - 5^3 + 3^9 - 4^5$ **19423** := $-1^1 - 9^0 - 4^4 - 2^1 + 3^9$ **19734** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 4^1$
18539 := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 5^6 + 3^7 + 9^3$ **19425** := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 4^7 - 2^1 + 5^5$ **19735** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 5^1$
18544 := $-1^1 + 8^3 + 5^4 + 4^5 + 4^7$ **19434** := $-1^1 + 9^1 - 4^0 + 3^9 - 4^4$ **19736** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 6^1$
18569 := $-1^1 - 8^3 + 5^7 + 6^1 - 9^5$ **19436** := $-1^1 + 9^1 - 4^4 + 3^9 + 6^0$ **19737** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 7^1 + 3^9 + 7^2$
18634 := $-1^1 - 8^1 - 6^4 + 3^9 + 4^4$ **19443** := $-1^1 + 9^0 - 4^4 + 4^2 + 3^9$ **19738** := $-1^1 - 9^0 - 7^1 + 3^9 + 8^2$
18643 := $-1^1 + 8^0 - 6^4 + 4^4 + 3^9$ **19445** := $-1^1 + 9^0 - 4^3 + 4^7 + 5^5$ **19739** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$
18678 := $-1^1 + 8^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 8^3$ **19463** := $-1^1 + 9^0 - 4^4 + 6^2 + 3^9$ **19752** := $-1^1 + 9^4 - 7^4 + 5^6 - 2^5$
18723 := $-1^1 + 8^4 + 7^5 + 2^3 - 3^7$ **19532** := $-1^1 - 9^1 - 5^3 + 3^9 - 2^4$ **19763** := $-1^1 + 9^2 - 7^0 + 6^0 + 3^9$
18724 := $-1^1 - 8^2 + 7^4 + 2^2 + 4^7$ **19534** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 5^5 + 3^3 + 4^7$ **19785** := $-1^1 + 9^4 - 7^4 + 8^0 + 5^6$
18727 := $-1^1 - 8^3 + 7^4 + 2^5 + 7^5$ **19537** := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 5^4 + 3^7 + 7^5$ **19843** := $-1^1 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 4^2 + 3^9$
18745 := $-1^1 - 8^2 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 5^2$ **19538** := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 5^0 + 3^9 - 8^2$ **19845** := $-1^1 - 9^1 + 8^4 + 4^7 - 5^4$
18753 := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 7^4 + 5^6 + 3^6$ **19539** := $-1^1 - 9^1 - 5^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$ **19862** := $-1^1 - 9^5 + 8^5 + 6^6 - 2^9$
18755 := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 7^1 + 5^5 + 5^6$ **19553** := $-1^1 - 9^1 + 5^1 - 5^3 + 3^9$ **19863** := $-1^1 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 6^2 + 3^9$
18784 := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 4^7$ **19559** := $-1^1 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 9^3$ **19933** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 9^1 + 3^5 + 3^9$
18794 := $-1^1 + 8^0 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^7$ **19573** := $-1^1 + 9^1 - 5^3 + 7^1 + 3^9$
18835 := $-1^1 + 8^3 + 8^3 + 3^7 + 5^6$ **19586** := $-1^1 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 8^3 - 6^0$ **20053** := $-2^8 + 0^0 + 0^1 + 5^4 + 3^9$
18847 := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 8^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$ **19588** := $-1^1 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 8^0 + 8^3$ **20132** := $-2^6 + 0^1 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 2^9$
18849 := $-1^1 + 8^0 - 8^4 + 4^7 + 9^4$ **19593** := $-1^1 - 9^1 + 5^0 - 9^2 + 3^9$ **20223** := $-2^2 + 0^1 + 2^5 + 2^9 + 3^9$
18923 := $-1^1 - 8^3 + 9^1 - 2^8 + 3^9$ **19603** := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 6^0 + 0^0 + 3^9$ **20235** := $-2^3 - 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^4$
18953 := $-1^1 - 8^0 - 9^3 + 5^0 + 3^9$ **19623** := $-1^1 - 9^0 + 6^1 - 2^6 + 3^9$ **20237** := $-2^3 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 7^2$
18963 := $-1^1 - 8^3 + 9^1 - 6^3 + 3^9$ **19624** := $-1^1 + 9^3 - 6^6 + 2^4 + 4^8$ **20243** := $-2^4 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 4^3 + 3^9$
18985 := $-1^1 - 8^4 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 5^5$ **19632** := $-1^1 - 9^2 - 6^0 + 3^9 + 2^5$ **20253** := $-2^6 + 0^0 + 2^3 + 5^4 + 3^9$
19033 := $-1^1 + 9^2 - 0^0 + 3^9 - 3^6$ **19636** := $-1^1 - 9^1 - 6^0 + 3^9 - 6^2$ **20273** := $-2^3 - 0^0 + 2^8 + 7^3 + 3^9$
19073 := $-1^1 + 9^2 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 3^7$ **19638** := $-1^1 - 9^1 - 6^2 + 3^9 + 8^0$ **20293** := $-2^7 + 0^0 + 2^3 + 9^3 + 3^9$
19075 := $-1^1 - 9^5 + 0^0 - 7^0 + 5^7$ **19645** := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 6^1 + 4^6 + 5^6$ **20305** := $-2^1 - 0^0 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 5^4$
20322 := $-2^1 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^7 + 2^9$

20324 := $-2^7 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 4^4$	20447 := $-2^5 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 4^7 - 7^0$	20864 := $-2^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 6^5 - 4^6$
20325 := $-2^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^5 + 5^4$	20448 := $-2^4 + 0^1 - 4^2 + 4^7 + 8^4$	20870 := $-2^5 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 + 0^1$
20332 := $-2^4 + 0^1 + 3^6 + 3^9 - 2^6$	20449 := $-2^5 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 9^0$	20871 := $-2^5 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 1^0$
20334 := $-2^9 + 0^1 + 3^7 + 3^9 - 4^5$	20453 := $-2^7 - 0^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 3^9$	20872 := $-2^4 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 2^4$
20339 := $-2^6 + 0^1 - 3^2 + 3^9 + 9^3$	20454 := $-2^5 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 4^7$	20873 := $-2^1 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 3^3$
20343 := $-2^2 - 0^0 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 3^9$	20458 := $-2^4 - 0^0 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 8^4$	20874 := $-2^5 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 + 4^1$
20344 := $-2^7 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 4^7$	20463 := $-2^9 + 0^1 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 3^9$	20875 := $-2^1 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 5^2$
20347 := $-2^4 - 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 7^3$	20464 := $-2^4 - 0^0 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 4^7$	20876 := $-2^5 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 + 6^1$
20348 := $-2^7 - 0^0 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 8^4$	20473 := $-2^9 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 3^4$	20877 := $-2^5 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^1 + 7^5$
20349 := $-2^6 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 9^3$	20474 := $-2^2 - 0^0 + 4^6 - 7^0 + 4^7$	20878 := $-2^4 - 0^0 - 8^1 + 7^5 + 8^4$
20353 := $-2^6 + 0^1 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 3^9$	20478 := $-2^1 - 0^0 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 8^4$	20879 := $-2^4 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 9^1$
20373 := $-2^5 + 0^1 + 3^6 - 7^1 + 3^9$	20479 := $-2^6 - 0^0 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^4$	20887 := $-2^3 + 0^1 - 8^1 + 8^4 + 7^5$
20375 := $-2^5 + 0^1 + 3^9 - 7^4 + 5^5$	20480 := $-2^1 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 0^0$	20893 := $-2^5 + 0^0 + 8^3 + 9^3 + 3^9$
20379 := $-2^5 + 0^1 + 3^9 - 7^0 + 9^3$	20482 := $-2^1 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 2^2$	20897 := $-2^2 - 0^0 + 8^4 - 9^0 + 7^5$
20384 := $-2^4 + 0^0 - 3^4 + 8^4 + 4^7$	20484 := $-2^2 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 8^1 + 4^7$	20923 := $-2^1 + 0^0 + 9^3 + 2^9 + 3^9$
20385 := $-2^6 - 0^0 + 3^6 + 8^4 + 5^6$	20498 := $-2^6 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 8^4$	20963 := $-2^3 + 0^0 - 9^1 + 6^4 + 3^9$
20387 := $-2^9 - 0^0 - 3^1 + 8^4 + 7^5$	20532 := $-2^5 + 0^1 + 5^4 + 3^9 + 2^8$	21236 := $-2^8 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 6^4$
20389 := $-2^5 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 9^3$	20533 := $-2^2 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 3^6 + 3^9$	21347 := $-2^5 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 7^4$
20392 := $-2^2 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 9^3 - 2^4$	20597 := $-2^6 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 7^5$	21362 := $-2^7 - 1^0 + 3^9 + 6^4 + 2^9$
20393 := $-2^4 + 0^1 - 3^1 + 9^3 + 3^9$	20635 := $-2^8 + 0^0 - 6^4 + 3^8 + 5^6$	21363 := $-2^9 - 1^0 + 3^7 + 6^1 + 3^9$
20394 := $-2^1 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 9^3 - 4^2$	20636 := $-2^7 + 0^0 - 6^3 + 3^9 + 6^4$	21433 := $-2^1 - 1^0 + 4^5 + 3^6 + 3^9$
20395 := $-2^4 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 9^3 - 5^0$	20643 := $-2^6 + 0^0 - 6^0 + 4^5 + 3^9$	21634 := $-2^4 + 1^0 - 6^4 + 3^8 + 4^7$
20396 := $-2^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 9^3 - 6^0$	20647 := $-2^8 + 0^0 - 6^0 + 4^6 + 7^5$	21693 := $-2^4 + 1^0 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 3^9$
20397 := $-2^3 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 9^3 - 7^1$	20673 := $-2^8 - 0^0 + 6^4 - 7^2 + 3^9$	21837 := $-2^8 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 3^9 + 7^4$
20398 := $-2^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 9^3 + 8^0$	20678 := $-2^3 - 0^0 - 6^3 + 7^5 + 8^4$	21893 := $-2^8 + 1^0 - 8^4 + 9^4 + 3^9$
20399 := $-2^2 + 0^1 + 3^9 - 9^1 + 9^3$	20739 := $-2^4 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^3$	21925 := $-2^2 - 1^0 + 9^4 - 2^8 + 5^6$
20414 := $-2^6 - 0^0 + 4^6 - 1^0 + 4^7$	20742 := $-2^5 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 4^6 - 2^7$	21945 := $-2^8 - 1^0 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 5^6$
20418 := $-2^6 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 8^4$	20745 := $-2^5 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 4^6 - 5^3$	21965 := $-2^2 - 1^0 + 9^4 - 6^3 + 5^6$
20424 := $-2^6 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 2^3 + 4^7$	20768 := $-2^7 - 0^0 + 7^5 - 6^1 + 8^4$	21984 := $-2^7 + 1^0 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 4^6$
20433 := $-2^5 + 0^0 + 4^5 + 3^9 - 3^5$	20774 := $-2^7 + 0^1 - 7^0 + 7^5 + 4^6$	22037 := $-2^4 - 2^5 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 7^4$
20434 := $-2^4 - 0^0 - 4^4 + 3^9 + 4^5$	20782 := $-2^7 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 + 2^3$	22053 := $-2^2 - 2^7 - 0^0 + 5^6 + 3^8$
20435 := $-2^3 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 3^9 - 5^6$	20783 := $-2^7 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 + 3^2$	22059 := $-2^6 - 2^6 + 0^0 + 5^6 + 9^4$
20438 := $-2^5 - 0^0 + 4^7 - 3^2 + 8^4$	20784 := $-2^7 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^6$	22073 := $-2^1 - 2^3 - 0^0 + 7^4 + 3^9$
20443 := $-2^3 + 0^1 - 4^4 + 4^5 + 3^9$	20789 := $-2^5 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 - 9^2$	22153 := $-2^1 - 2^5 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 3^8$
20444 := $-2^5 + 0^1 - 4^1 + 4^6 + 4^7$	20837 := $-2^6 - 0^0 + 8^4 - 3^0 + 7^5$	22159 := $-2^5 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 9^4$
20446 := $-2^5 - 0^0 + 4^6 + 4^7 - 6^0$	20847 := $-2^6 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 4^6 + 7^5$	22195 := $-2^3 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 5^6$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| $22235 := -2^4 + 2^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^6$ | $22449 := -2^8 + 2^4 - 4^4 + 4^7 + 9^4$ | $22729 := -2^7 - 2^9 + 7^5 + 2^0 + 9^4$ |
| $22243 := -2^9 - 2^9 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 3^9$ | $22459 := -2^9 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 9^4$ | $22732 := -2^7 + 2^2 + 7^5 + 3^8 - 2^9$ |
| $22304 := -2^7 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 0^0 + 4^7$ | $22463 := -2^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 3^9$ | $22733 := -2^4 - 2^6 + 7^4 + 3^6 + 3^9$ |
| $22305 := -2^9 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 5^5$ | $22464 := -2^8 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^6 + 4^8$ | $22734 := -2^2 - 2^8 + 7^2 + 3^8 + 4^7$ |
| $22315 := -2^7 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 5^6$ | $22466 := -2^5 + 2^1 - 4^7 + 6^6 - 6^5$ | $22735 := -2^1 - 2^6 - 7^1 + 3^9 + 5^5$ |
| $22334 := -2^5 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 3^9 - 4^2$ | $22469 := -2^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 9^4$ | $22737 := -2^5 - 2^8 - 7^3 + 3^8 + 7^5$ |
| $22335 := -2^5 - 2^7 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 5^4$ | $22473 := -2^7 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 3^8$ | $22753 := -2^1 - 2^2 - 7^2 + 5^5 + 3^9$ |
| $22337 := -2^1 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 3^9 + 7^4$ | $22483 := -2^4 - 2^8 - 4^5 + 8^4 + 3^9$ | $22773 := -2^8 + 2^2 - 7^3 + 7^5 + 3^8$ |
| $22339 := -2^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 9^3$ | $22489 := -2^3 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 8^2 + 9^4$ | $22791 := -2^6 - 2^9 + 7^5 + 9^4 - 1^0$ |
| $22347 := -2^8 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3$ | $22496 := -2^9 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 9^4 - 6^0$ | $22792 := -2^5 - 2^5 + 7^5 + 9^4 - 2^9$ |
| $22352 := -2^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^5 - 2^9$ | $22498 := -2^9 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 8^2$ | $22793 := -2^2 - 2^4 + 7^4 + 9^3 + 3^9$ |
| $22353 := -2^3 + 2^8 - 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^8$ | $22532 := -2^2 - 2^4 + 5^5 + 3^9 - 2^8$ | $22794 := -2^4 - 2^7 - 7^1 + 9^4 + 4^7$ |
| $22355 := -2^9 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^5 - 5^1$ | $22533 := -2^4 - 2^4 + 5^5 - 3^5 + 3^9$ | $22795 := -2^9 + 2^6 + 7^5 + 9^4 - 5^3$ |
| $22357 := -2^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 7^4$ | $22534 := -2^1 - 2^4 + 5^5 + 3^9 - 4^4$ | $22834 := -2^7 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 3^8 + 4^7$ |
| $22358 := -2^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^5 - 8^3$ | $22535 := -2^4 - 2^8 - 5^0 + 3^9 + 5^5$ | $22835 := -2^2 + 2^5 - 8^0 + 3^9 + 5^5$ |
| $22359 := -2^1 + 2^8 - 3^4 + 5^6 + 9^4$ | $22536 := -2^3 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 3^6 + 6^5$ | $22846 := -2^1 - 2^7 + 8^4 + 4^8 - 6^6$ |
| $22364 := -2^9 - 2^0 - 3^9 + 6^6 - 4^6$ | $22537 := -2^3 + 2^4 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 7^3$ | $22847 := -2^1 - 2^5 + 8^4 + 4^7 + 7^4$ |
| $22372 := -2^5 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 2^8$ | $22538 := -2^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 8^3$ | $22849 := -2^4 - 2^4 - 8^2 + 4^7 + 9^4$ |
| $22373 := -2^4 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^1 + 3^9$ | $22539 := -2^2 - 2^8 + 5^5 + 3^9 - 9^1$ | $22856 := -2^5 - 2^0 - 8^3 + 5^6 + 6^5$ |
| $22374 := -2^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 4^5$ | $22543 := -2^3 - 2^0 + 5^5 - 4^4 + 3^9$ | $22863 := -2^4 + 2^1 - 8^4 + 6^6 - 3^9$ |
| $22375 := -2^7 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 5^5$ | $22553 := -2^1 - 2^7 - 5^3 + 5^5 + 3^9$ | $22865 := -2^3 - 2^4 - 8^3 + 6^5 + 5^6$ |
| $22376 := -2^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 + 7^5 + 6^5$ | $22554 := -2^4 - 2^6 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 4^7$ | $22873 := -2^9 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 3^8$ |
| $22378 := -2^4 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^5 + 8^5$ | $22558 := -2^5 - 2^8 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 8^4$ | $22874 := -2^3 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 7^4 + 4^7$ |
| $22379 := -2^2 - 2^8 - 3^6 + 7^5 + 9^4$ | $22559 := -2^3 + 2^8 + 5^3 + 5^6 + 9^4$ | $22883 := -2^7 - 2^8 - 8^3 + 8^4 + 3^9$ |
| $22395 := -2^1 - 2^5 + 3^5 + 9^4 + 5^6$ | $22573 := -2^3 - 2^7 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 3^9$ | $22904 := -2^3 - 2^5 + 9^4 - 0^0 + 4^7$ |
| $22423 := -2^1 - 2^3 + 4^7 - 2^9 + 3^8$ | $22593 := -2^8 + 2^5 + 5^5 + 9^1 + 3^9$ | $22914 := -2^4 - 2^4 + 9^4 + 1^0 + 4^7$ |
| $22429 := -2^1 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 2^9 + 9^4$ | $22595 := -2^7 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 9^4 + 5^6$ | $22924 := -2^2 - 2^0 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 4^7$ |
| $22430 := -2^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 3^8 - 0^0$ | $22624 := -2^9 - 2^9 + 6^5 - 2^9 + 4^7$ | $22934 := -2^1 - 2^3 - 9^0 + 3^8 + 4^7$ |
| $22431 := -2^9 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 3^8 - 1^0$ | $22625 := -2^3 - 2^8 + 6^5 - 2^9 + 5^6$ | $22935 := -2^1 + 2^7 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 5^5$ |
| $22432 := -2^1 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 3^8 - 2^9$ | $22635 := -2^6 + 2^9 + 6^0 + 3^8 + 5^6$ | $22937 := -2^2 + 2^7 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 7^4$ |
| $22433 := -2^9 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 3^0 + 3^8$ | $22647 := -2^6 + 2^9 + 6^4 + 4^6 + 7^5$ | $22938 := -2^7 + 2^4 - 9^3 + 3^9 + 8^4$ |
| $22434 := -2^8 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 3^8 + 4^7$ | $22649 := -2^2 - 2^8 - 6^2 + 4^7 + 9^4$ | $22940 := -2^1 - 2^1 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 0^0$ |
| $22435 := -2^3 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 3^8 + 5^6$ | $22665 := -2^3 - 2^9 - 6^3 + 6^5 + 5^6$ | $22941 := -2^1 - 2^0 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 1^0$ |
| $22436 := -2^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 6^0$ | $22687 := -2^5 + 2^7 - 6^5 + 8^5 - 7^4$ | $22942 := -2^1 + 2^0 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 2^1$ |
| $22438 := -2^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 8^0$ | $22694 := -2^8 - 2^0 + 6^1 + 9^4 + 4^7$ | $22943 := -2^1 + 2^0 - 9^0 + 4^7 + 3^8$ |
| $22443 := -2^8 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 3^7$ | $22695 := -2^1 + 2^9 - 6^0 + 9^4 + 5^6$ | $22944 := -2^1 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 4^0$ |

$22945 := -2^1 + 2^0 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 5^0$	$23256 := -2^3 - 3^2 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^5$	$23376 := -2^1 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 6^0$
$22946 := -2^1 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 6^0$	$23257 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$23378 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 8^0$
$22947 := -2^2 - 2^0 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$23258 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$23382 := -2^7 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 8^4 - 2^9$
$22948 := -2^1 + 2^2 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 8^0$	$23264 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 2^9 + 6^0 + 4^6$	$23384 := -2^6 - 3^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 4^7$
$22949 := -2^2 - 2^0 + 9^1 + 4^7 + 9^4$	$23265 := -2^7 - 3^2 + 2^0 + 6^5 + 5^6$	$23385 := -2^4 + 3^4 + 3^9 + 8^3 + 5^5$
$22952 := -2^1 + 2^8 + 9^4 + 5^6 + 2^9$	$23268 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 2^8 + 6^0 + 8^4$	$23387 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 7^5$
$22953 := -2^6 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 3^9$	$23271 := -2^5 + 3^8 - 2^6 + 7^5 - 1^0$	$23406 := -2^9 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 0^0 + 6^5$
$22954 := -2^2 + 2^3 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 4^7$	$23272 := -2^4 + 3^8 - 2^4 + 7^5 - 2^6$	$23416 := -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 6^5$
$22964 := -2^4 - 2^0 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 4^7$	$23273 := -2^2 - 3^3 - 2^6 + 7^5 + 3^8$	$23417 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 1^0 + 7^5$
$22974 := -2^2 - 2^4 + 9^4 + 7^2 + 4^7$	$23274 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 2^1 + 7^3 + 4^7$	$23419 := -2^8 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 9^4$
$22975 := -2^6 - 2^7 + 9^6 - 7^6 - 5^8$	$23275 := -2^2 + 3^8 - 2^6 + 7^5 - 5^2$	$23424 := -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 2^9 + 4^7$
$22977 := -2^4 - 2^5 + 9^4 - 7^3 + 7^5$	$23276 := -2^2 - 3^8 - 2^3 - 7^5 + 6^6$	$23426 := -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 2^0 + 6^5$
$22994 := -2^4 - 2^4 + 9^2 + 9^4 + 4^7$	$23277 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 2^8 + 7^5 - 7^3$	$23427 := -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 2^6 + 7^5$
$23034 := -2^4 - 3^6 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6$	$23278 := -2^4 - 3^8 - 2^9 - 7^4 + 8^5$	$23432 := -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 2^9$
$23035 := -2^4 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 5^5$	$23279 := -2^2 - 3^4 - 2^2 + 7^5 + 9^4$	$23433 := -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 3^4 + 3^9$
$23042 := -2^5 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 2^7$	$23282 := -2^9 + 3^9 - 2^0 + 8^4 + 2^4$	$23434 := -2^3 - 3^4 - 4^4 + 3^9 + 4^6$
$23043 := -2^3 - 3^6 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 3^9$	$23284 := -2^9 + 3^9 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 4^2$	$23436 := -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 6^5$
$23049 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 4^6 - 9^3$	$23297 := -2^2 - 3^1 - 2^6 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$23437 := -2^1 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 3^9 - 7^3$
$23054 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 4^7$	$23307 := -2^6 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$23438 := -2^2 - 3^4 - 4^4 + 3^9 + 8^4$
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$23087 := -2^1 + 3^7 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5$	$23342 := -2^6 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 2^9$	$23448 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 4^7 + 8^3$
$23127 := -2^8 + 3^8 - 1^0 + 2^4 + 7^5$	$23344 := -2^7 - 3^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 4^6$	$23456 := -2^3 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5$
$23145 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 4^6 - 5^4$	$23345 := -2^8 + 3^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^5$	$23457 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 7^3$
$23146 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 6^3$	$23346 := -2^2 - 3^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^5$	$23458 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 8^3$
$23163 := -2^1 + 3^7 - 1^0 + 6^4 + 3^9$	$23347 := -2^1 - 3^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^5$	$23465 := -2^4 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 6^5 + 5^6$
$23204 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 2^9 + 0^0 + 4^6$	$23349 := -2^9 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 9^2$	$23472 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^5 + 2^7$
$23234 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^7$	$23364 := -2^1 + 3^1 + 3^9 + 6^5 - 4^6$	$23473 := -2^6 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 7^0 + 3^9$
$23235 := -2^2 - 3^4 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 5^5$	$23365 := -2^3 - 3^0 - 3^3 + 6^5 + 5^6$	$23475 := -2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^5 + 5^3$
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$23238 := -2^1 - 3^3 - 2^9 + 3^9 + 8^4$	$23367 := -2^1 + 3^4 - 3^8 + 6^6 - 7^5$	$23477 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 7^5$
$23252 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 2^6 + 5^5 + 2^9$	$23368 := -2^2 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 6^5 - 8^4$	$23479 := -2^6 - 3^4 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 9^4$
$23253 := -2^6 - 3^1 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 3^9$	$23370 := -2^1 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 0^0$	$23486 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 8^4 - 6^2$
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$23255 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 5^5 - 5^0$	$23374 := -2^1 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 4^0$	$23494 := -2^9 - 3^9 + 4^5 + 9^5 - 4^7$

$23496 := -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 6^5$	$23643 := -2^5 + 3^6 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 3^8$	$23742 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 7^0 + 4^6 - 2^5$
$23497 := -2^4 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$23644 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 6^1 + 4^6 - 4^0$	$23743 := -2^1 - 3^3 - 7^1 + 4^6 + 3^9$
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$23526 := -2^1 - 3^0 + 5^6 + 2^7 + 6^5$	$23649 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 6^0 + 4^6 - 9^0$	$23747 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 4^6 - 7^0$
$23528 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 2^1 + 8^4$	$23652 := -2^1 - 3^1 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 2^8$	$23747 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 7^0 + 4^6 + 7^0$
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$23530 := -2^3 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 3^9 + 0^0$	$23655 := -2^7 - 3^5 + 6^5 + 5^4 + 5^6$	$23749 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 4^6 + 9^0$
$23532 := -2^2 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 3^9 - 2^0$	$23656 := -2^6 + 3^3 - 6^5 + 5^7 - 6^6$	$23763 := -2^6 - 3^3 + 7^5 + 6^5 - 3^6$
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$23546 := -2^4 + 3^3 - 5^4 + 4^7 + 6^5$	$23676 := -2^4 - 3^7 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$23782 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 8^4 + 2^2$
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$23564 := -2^4 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 4^3$	$23680 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 + 8^4 + 0^0$	$23786 := -2^2 - 3^6 + 7^5 - 8^2 + 6^5$
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$23569 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^3$	$23683 := -2^4 - 3^4 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 3^9$	$23789 := -2^3 - 3^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 - 9^4$
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$23583 := -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 8^4 + 3^7$	$23686 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 6^0 + 8^4 + 6^2$	$23812 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 1^0 + 2^6$
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$23586 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^4 - 6^3$	$23694 := -2^3 - 3^2 + 6^6 - 9^4 - 4^7$	$23827 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 2^0 + 7^2$
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$23636 := -2^4 + 3^8 - 6^4 + 3^9 - 6^4$	$23727 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 2^5 + 7^5$	$23837 := -2^4 - 3^3 + 8^3 + 3^8 + 7^5$
$23639 := -2^8 + 3^7 + 6^4 + 3^9 + 9^3$	$23728 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 2^1 + 8^4$	$23838 := -2^1 - 3^1 + 8^2 + 3^9 + 8^4$
$23640 := -2^9 - 3^2 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 0^0$	$23740 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 7^1 + 4^6 + 0^1$	$23839 := -2^8 - 3^7 - 8^5 + 3^0 + 9^5$
$23642 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 6^0 + 4^6 - 2^7$	$23741 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 7^1 + 4^6 + 1^0$	$23840 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 4^6 - 0^0$

23842 := $-2^1 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 4^6 + 2^6$	23986 := $-2^3 + 3^9 - 9^0 + 8^4 + 6^3$	24346 := $-2^3 - 4^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 6^7$
23843 := $-2^4 + 3^4 - 8^0 + 4^6 + 3^9$	23987 := $-2^5 - 3^7 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 7^0$	24352 := $-2^6 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 2^9$
23852 := $-2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 5^2 + 2^6$	23988 := $-2^3 + 3^9 + 9^3 + 8^4 - 8^3$	24353 := $-2^2 - 4^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 3^8$
23853 := $-2^3 + 3^4 + 8^4 + 5^0 + 3^9$	23989 := $-2^5 - 3^7 + 9^0 + 8^5 - 9^4$	24356 := $-2^1 - 4^9 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^7$
23856 := $-2^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 6^4$	24032 := $-2^1 + 4^6 - 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^8$	24358 := $-2^8 - 4^6 - 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^5$
23857 := $-2^7 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 5^4 + 7^5$	24034 := $-2^1 + 4^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^6$	24372 := $-2^2 + 4^5 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 2^4$
23859 := $-2^1 + 3^7 - 8^3 + 5^6 + 9^4$	24036 := $-2^7 + 4^7 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 6^5$	24373 := $-2^4 + 4^5 - 3^1 + 7^5 + 3^8$
23866 := $-2^7 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 6^3 - 6^0$	24056 := $-2^7 + 4^7 - 0^0 + 5^2 + 6^5$	24374 := $-2^1 - 4^2 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 4^5$
23867 := $-2^8 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 7^3$	24063 := $-2^4 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 6^5 - 3^4$	24375 := $-2^4 + 4^5 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 5^0$
23868 := $-2^7 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 6^3 + 8^4$	24064 := $-2^5 - 4^3 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 4^7$	24376 := $-2^5 - 4^4 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^5$
23871 := $-2^3 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 7^5 - 1^0$	24067 := $-2^9 - 4^1 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 7^5$	24377 := $-2^3 + 4^5 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 7^1$
23872 := $-2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 7^5 - 2^2$	24076 := $-2^9 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 6^5$	24378 := $-2^8 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 8^3$
23873 := $-2^2 - 3^1 + 8^3 + 7^5 + 3^8$	24096 := $-2^6 + 4^7 - 0^0 + 9^0 + 6^5$	24379 := $-2^2 + 4^5 - 3^2 + 7^5 + 9^4$
23874 := $-2^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 7^5 - 4^1$	24136 := $-2^5 + 4^7 - 1^0 + 3^2 + 6^5$	24395 := $-2^8 - 4^6 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 5^6$
23875 := $-2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 7^5 - 5^0$	24137 := $-2^8 + 4^5 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 7^5$	24396 := $-2^3 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 9^0 + 6^5$
23876 := $-2^4 + 3^9 + 8^3 + 7^4 + 6^4$	24146 := $-2^4 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 6^5$	24397 := $-2^2 + 4^5 + 3^2 + 9^4 + 7^5$
23877 := $-2^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 7^5 - 7^0$	24156 := $-2^2 + 4^7 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 6^5$	24399 := $-2^2 + 4^7 + 3^6 + 9^3 + 9^4$
23879 := $-2^1 + 3^0 + 8^3 + 7^5 + 9^4$	24160 := $-2^1 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 6^5 + 0^0$	24444 := $-2^7 - 4^1 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 4^7$
23891 := $-2^7 - 3^7 + 8^5 - 9^4 - 1^0$	24176 := $-2^5 + 4^7 - 1^0 + 7^2 + 6^5$	24445 := $-2^8 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 5^3$
23892 := $-2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 9^0 + 2^7$	24223 := $-2^2 + 4^6 - 2^6 + 2^9 + 3^9$	24447 := $-2^7 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 4^7 - 7^0$
23893 := $-2^7 - 3^7 + 8^5 + 9^0 - 3^8$	24226 := $-2^1 + 4^7 + 2^2 + 2^6 + 6^5$	24448 := $-2^6 - 4^3 - 4^6 - 4^6 + 8^5$
23897 := $-2^6 + 3^4 + 8^3 + 9^4 + 7^5$	24236 := $-2^2 + 4^7 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 6^5$	24449 := $-2^7 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 9^0$
23924 := $-2^6 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 2^7 + 4^6$	24243 := $-2^5 - 4^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 3^9$	24463 := $-2^2 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 3^5$
23925 := $-2^9 + 3^7 + 9^4 + 2^6 + 5^6$	24263 := $-2^4 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 6^5 - 3^2$	24464 := $-2^4 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 6^5 + 4^7$
23930 := $-2^7 - 3^7 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 0^0$	24264 := $-2^3 - 4^2 + 2^7 + 6^5 + 4^7$	24465 := $-2^6 - 4^4 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 5^4$
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23964 := $-2^5 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 6^3 + 4^6$	24283 := $-2^2 - 4^1 + 2^9 + 8^4 + 3^9$	24489 := $-2^9 - 4^4 - 4^5 - 8^5 + 9^5$
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23985 := $-2^6 + 3^9 + 9^3 + 8^3 + 5^5$	24339 := $-2^6 + 4^7 + 3^6 + 3^6 + 9^4$	24576 := $-2^1 - 4^1 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 6^5$

$24579 := -2^2 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 7^4 + 9^4$	$24763 := -2^6 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 3^5$	$25237 := -2^2 + 5^5 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 7^4$
$24593 := -2^1 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$24766 := -2^5 - 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^3 + 6^5$	$25273 := -2^6 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 7^4 + 3^9$
$24608 := -2^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 8^3$	$24776 := -2^6 + 4^4 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$25295 := -2^3 + 5^5 - 2^3 + 9^4 + 5^6$
$24624 := -2^5 - 4^2 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 4^7$	$24786 := -2^8 + 4^0 + 7^2 + 8^5 - 6^5$	$25324 := -2^7 + 5^6 - 3^8 + 2^2 + 4^7$
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$24634 := -2^8 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 3^6 + 4^7$	$24828 := -2^2 - 4^6 - 8^4 + 2^8 + 8^5$	$25345 := -2^7 + 5^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^6$
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$24649 := -2^5 - 4^6 - 6^6 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$24862 := -2^1 - 4^3 + 8^5 - 6^5 - 2^6$	$25384 := -2^6 + 5^6 - 3^8 + 8^5 - 4^7$
$24653 := -2^8 + 4^0 - 6^6 + 5^7 - 3^8$	$24863 := -2^1 - 4^9 + 8^3 + 6^7 + 3^8$	$25389 := -2^6 - 5^2 - 3^6 + 8^5 - 9^4$
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$24662 := -2^2 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 6^5 + 2^9$	$24866 := -2^7 + 4^0 + 8^5 + 6^0 - 6^5$	$25435 := -2^3 - 5^1 + 4^7 - 3^8 + 5^6$
$24663 := -2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 6^5 - 3^6$	$24867 := -2^7 - 4^1 + 8^5 - 6^5 + 7^1$	$25436 := -2^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 3^8 - 6^6$
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$24675 := -2^5 - 4^0 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 5^3$	$24887 := -2^5 - 4^6 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 7^3$	$25475 := -2^9 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 7^6 + 5^7$
$24683 := -2^1 - 4^3 - 6^5 + 8^5 - 3^5$	$24928 := -2^8 - 4^5 - 9^4 + 2^0 + 8^5$	$25476 := -2^6 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 7^5 - 6^5$
$24684 := -2^2 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 4^7$	$24932 := -2^5 - 4^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 - 2^8$	$25477 := -2^6 - 5^7 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 7^6$
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$24756 := -2^4 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$25086 := -2^5 + 5^3 + 0^0 + 8^5 - 6^5$	$25673 := -2^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 - 3^0$

$25674 := -2^6 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 - 4^3$	$25982 := -2^8 - 5^0 - 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^5$	$26393 := -2^6 + 6^3 - 3^1 + 9^4 + 3^9$
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$25689 := -2^9 - 5^1 - 6^0 + 8^5 - 9^4$	$25984 := -2^4 - 5^2 + 9^5 - 8^5 - 4^4$	$26395 := -2^6 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 9^4 - 5^0$
$25694 := -2^9 - 5^6 + 6^6 - 9^3 - 4^6$	$25986 := -2^2 - 5^0 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 6^3$	$26397 := -2^6 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 7^0$
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$25762 := -2^3 + 5^6 + 7^4 + 6^5 - 2^5$	$26193 := -2^4 - 6^2 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$26425 := -2^9 + 6^6 - 4^6 + 2^1 - 5^6$
$25765 := -2^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 + 6^5 + 5^6$	$26198 := -2^1 - 6^1 - 1^0 - 9^4 + 8^5$	$26428 := -2^2 + 6^6 - 4^7 + 2^8 - 8^4$
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$25834 := -2^2 - 5^4 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 4^4$	$26268 := -2^2 - 6^5 - 2^4 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$26443 := -2^3 + 6^5 - 4^5 + 4^2 + 3^9$
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$25853 := -2^4 + 5^5 - 8^2 + 5^5 + 3^9$	$26289 := -2^1 - 6^1 + 2^4 - 8^5 + 9^5$	$26464 := -2^4 + 6^4 + 4^5 + 6^5 + 4^7$
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$25893 := -2^9 + 5^3 - 8^5 + 9^5 - 3^0$	$26332 := -2^2 - 6^2 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 2^7$	$26538 := -2^4 - 6^5 - 5^4 + 3^7 + 8^5$
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$25928 := -2^8 - 5^2 - 9^4 + 2^1 + 8^5$	$26344 := -2^1 + 6^5 + 3^7 + 4^7 - 4^0$	$26640 := -2^4 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 0^1$
$25941 := -2^7 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 1^0$	$26345 := -2^2 + 6^6 - 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^4$	$26641 := -2^4 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 1^0$
$25942 := -2^6 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 2^6$	$26346 := -2^1 + 6^0 + 3^7 + 4^7 + 6^5$	$26642 := -2^4 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 2^1$
$25943 := -2^7 + 5^5 + 9^0 + 4^7 + 3^8$	$26353 := -2^4 + 6^6 - 3^6 + 5^3 - 3^9$	$26643 := -2^2 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 - 3^2$
$25945 := -2^7 + 5^4 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 5^6$	$26358 := -2^7 + 6^6 - 3^9 + 5^2 - 8^3$	$26644 := -2^3 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 - 4^1$
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$25948 := -2^1 - 5^0 - 9^4 - 4^4 + 8^5$	$26376 := -2^9 - 6^2 - 3^9 - 7^2 + 6^6$	$26646 := -2^2 - 6^1 + 6^5 + 4^8 - 6^6$
$25963 := -2^6 - 5^0 + 9^4 - 6^3 + 3^9$	$26392 := -2^2 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 9^4 - 2^6$	$26647 := -2^1 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 - 7^1$

$26648 := -2^4 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 8^1$	$27236 := -2^3 - 7^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 6^5$	$27630 := -2^5 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^7 + 0^1$
$26649 := -2^3 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 9^0$	$27258 := -2^4 - 7^4 + 2^5 - 5^5 + 8^5$	$27631 := -2^5 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^7 + 1^0$
$26732 := -2^7 + 6^5 - 7^3 + 3^9 - 2^8$	$27326 := -2^2 - 7^0 + 3^9 - 2^7 + 6^5$	$27632 := -2^2 + 7^2 + 6^5 + 3^9 + 2^7$
$26733 := -2^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 + 3^9 - 3^6$	$27343 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 3^8$	$27633 := -2^1 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^3 - 3^7$
$26734 := -2^5 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 3^7 - 4^1$	$27346 := -2^7 - 7^0 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^5$	$27634 := -2^5 - 7^2 + 6^5 + 3^9 + 4^4$
$26735 := -2^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 + 3^3 - 5^5$	$27362 := -2^4 - 7^2 + 3^9 + 6^5 - 2^5$	$27635 := -2^1 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^7 - 5^2$
$26737 := -2^5 + 6^5 - 7^0 + 3^7 + 7^5$	$27363 := -2^3 - 7^1 - 3^4 + 6^5 + 3^9$	$27636 := -2^5 - 7^1 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 6^5$
$26738 := -2^4 + 6^7 + 7^4 + 3^8 - 8^6$	$27364 := -2^3 - 7^3 + 3^9 + 6^5 + 4^4$	$27637 := -2^5 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^7 + 7^1$
$26739 := -2^5 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 3^7 + 9^0$	$27366 := -2^3 - 7^2 + 3^9 - 6^2 + 6^5$	$27638 := -2^4 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^7 - 8^1$
$26753 := -2^1 + 6^6 - 7^3 + 5^3 - 3^9$	$27368 := -2^4 - 7^5 - 3^8 + 6^6 + 8^4$	$27639 := -2^5 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^7 + 9^1$
$26763 := -2^3 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 3^7$	$27369 := -2^1 - 7^1 + 3^9 + 6^5 - 9^2$	$27645 := -2^6 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 4^0 + 5^5$
$26773 := -2^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 + 7^5 + 3^7$	$27384 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 3^8 + 8^4 - 4^3$	$27652 := -2^6 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 2^3$
$26777 := -2^8 + 6^5 + 7^2 + 7^4 + 7^5$	$27385 := -2^2 + 7^5 - 3^8 + 8^5 - 5^6$	$27653 := -2^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 5^1 - 3^7$
$26778 := -2^5 - 6^2 - 7^6 - 7^6 + 8^6$	$27386 := -2^1 - 7^1 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 6^5$	$27656 := -2^4 + 7^5 - 6^2 + 5^5 + 6^5$
$26797 := -2^1 - 6^6 - 7^4 + 9^5 + 7^5$	$27431 := -2^5 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 3^8 - 1^0$	$27657 := -2^1 - 7^2 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 7^5$
$26823 := -2^7 + 6^5 - 8^3 + 2^2 + 3^9$	$27432 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 3^8 - 2^4$	$27658 := -2^4 - 7^6 + 6^4 - 5^9 + 8^7$
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$26843 := -2^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 4^7 + 3^7$	$27435 := -2^2 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 3^8 - 5^2$	$27672 := -2^5 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 + 2^8$
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$26865 := -2^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 + 6^6 - 5^6$	$27449 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 4^6 + 9^4$	$27693 := -2^1 - 7^1 + 6^6 + 9^3 - 3^9$
$26883 := -2^7 + 6^5 - 8^3 + 8^2 + 3^9$	$27453 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 3^8$	$27696 := -2^7 - 7^5 - 6^4 - 9^3 + 6^6$
$26932 := -2^4 + 6^5 + 9^0 + 3^9 - 2^9$	$27455 := -2^8 + 7^5 - 4^6 + 5^6 - 5^4$	$27697 := -2^4 + 7^4 + 6^5 + 9^3 + 7^5$
$26933 := -2^2 - 6^2 + 9^3 + 3^8 + 3^9$	$27456 := -2^8 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^5$	$27743 := -2^2 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 3^8$
$26934 := -2^9 + 6^5 - 9^1 + 3^9 - 4^1$	$27458 := -2^5 - 7^5 - 4^6 + 5^6 + 8^5$	$27763 := -2^5 - 7^1 + 7^3 + 6^5 + 3^9$
$26936 := -2^1 - 6^2 + 9^0 - 3^9 + 6^6$	$27463 := -2^1 + 7^1 - 4^0 + 6^5 + 3^9$	$27767 := -2^6 - 7^5 - 7^6 + 6^7 - 7^6$
$26937 := -2^9 + 6^5 - 9^1 + 3^9 - 7^0$	$27492 := -2^2 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 2^5$	$27818 := -2^9 - 7^3 - 8^4 + 1^0 + 8^5$
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$26943 := -2^5 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 4^0 - 3^9$	$27497 := -2^4 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$27836 := -2^5 - 7^5 + 8^5 + 3^9 - 6^5$
$26953 := -2^4 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 5^1 - 3^9$	$27563 := -2^6 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 6^5 - 3^4$	$27837 := -2^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 - 3^0 - 7^4$
$26963 := -2^1 + 6^0 - 9^1 + 6^6 - 3^9$	$27564 := -2^6 + 7^3 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 4^7$	$27838 := -2^6 - 7^4 + 8^4 - 3^8 + 8^5$
$26973 := -2^1 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 7^0 - 3^9$	$27568 := -2^1 + 7^5 - 5^5 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$27864 := -2^3 - 7^4 + 8^0 + 6^6 - 4^7$
$26975 := -2^2 + 6^5 - 9^3 + 7^5 + 5^5$	$27569 := -2^2 - 7^1 - 5^7 + 6^6 + 9^5$	$27894 := -2^3 - 7^4 + 8^5 - 9^4 + 4^6$
$26977 := -2^3 + 6^5 + 9^0 + 7^4 + 7^5$	$27584 := -2^9 + 7^2 - 5^4 + 8^5 - 4^6$	$27898 := -2^2 - 7^4 + 8^4 - 9^4 + 8^5$
$26993 := -2^4 + 6^2 + 9^3 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$27614 := -2^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 1^0 - 4^7$	$27946 := -2^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 + 4^6 + 6^5$

$27965 := -2^2 - 7^2 + 9^5 - 6^6 + 5^6$	$28398 := -2^5 - 8^4 - 3^5 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$28517 := -2^5 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 1^0 - 7^5$
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$28158 := -2^9 - 8^4 - 1^0 - 5^0 + 8^5$	$28416 := -2^8 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 1^0 - 6^0$	$28537 := -2^2 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 3^2 - 7^5$
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$28246 := -2^1 + 8^4 - 2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5$	$28421 := -2^8 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^2 + 1^0$	$28547 := -2^1 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^0 - 7^5$
$28264 := -2^3 + 8^4 + 2^4 + 6^5 + 4^7$	$28422 := -2^1 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^3 - 2^8$	$28548 := -2^7 - 8^0 + 5^1 - 4^6 + 8^5$
$28284 := -2^2 - 8^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 - 4^6$	$28423 := -2^3 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^1 - 3^5$	$28553 := -2^5 + 8^5 - 5^3 + 5^6 - 3^9$
$28285 := -2^8 - 8^4 - 2^8 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$28424 := -2^3 + 8^5 - 4^4 + 2^4 - 4^6$	$28554 := -2^7 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 5^1 - 4^6$
$28287 := -2^7 - 8^4 - 2^8 + 8^5 - 7^0$	$28425 := -2^8 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^2 + 5^1$	$28558 := -2^6 - 8^4 - 5^2 - 5^2 + 8^5$
$28288 := -2^6 - 8^2 - 2^8 - 8^4 + 8^5$	$28426 := -2^5 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^1 - 6^3$	$28567 := -2^6 + 8^0 - 5^6 + 6^6 - 7^4$
$28289 := -2^7 - 8^4 - 2^8 + 8^5 + 9^0$	$28427 := -2^8 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^2 + 7^1$	$28568 := -2^7 - 8^4 + 5^2 - 6^0 + 8^5$
$28330 := -2^6 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 3^7 + 0^1$	$28428 := -2^2 - 8^4 + 4^2 - 2^8 + 8^5$	$28573 := -2^2 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 7^5 + 3^3$
$28331 := -2^6 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 3^7 + 1^0$	$28429 := -2^8 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$28576 := -2^7 + 8^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 6^5$
$28332 := -2^6 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 3^7 + 2^1$	$28443 := -2^1 + 8^5 - 4^5 + 4^7 - 3^9$	$28579 := -2^2 + 8^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 - 9^4$
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$28334 := -2^6 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 3^7 + 4^1$	$28448 := -2^5 - 8^4 + 4^3 - 4^4 + 8^5$	$28583 := -2^7 + 8^0 + 5^6 + 8^5 - 3^9$
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$28672 := -2^3 + 8^4 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 2^0$	$28974 := -2^5 + 8^5 - 9^1 + 7^3 - 4^6$	$29499 := -2^3 + 9^0 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 9^4$
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$28843 := -2^2 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 4^4 - 3^4$	$29447 := -2^9 - 9^6 + 4^0 - 4^9 + 7^7$	$29678 := -2^6 - 9^6 - 6^3 + 7^7 - 8^6$
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$28866 := -2^4 - 8^4 + 8^5 - 6^1 + 6^3$	$29492 := -2^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 2^1$	$29749 := -2^7 - 9^2 + 7^7 - 4^9 - 9^6$
$28887 := -2^6 - 8^2 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 7^3$	$29493 := -2^2 - 9^1 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 3^8$	$29760 := -2^3 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 + 0^1$
$28890 := -2^9 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 0^0$	$29494 := -2^3 + 9^4 - 4^1 + 9^4 + 4^7$	$29761 := -2^3 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 + 1^0$
$28895 := -2^9 + 8^0 - 8^5 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$29495 := -2^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 5^1$	$29762 := -2^1 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 2^2$
$28957 := -2^5 + 8^5 - 9^4 + 5^5 - 7^3$	$29496 := -2^2 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 9^4 - 6^1$	$29763 := -2^1 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^1$
$28958 := -2^9 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 5^5 - 8^5$	$29497 := -2^1 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 9^4 - 7^1$	$29764 := -2^3 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 + 4^1$
$28973 := -2^8 - 8^6 - 9^6 + 7^7 - 3^6$	$29498 := -2^3 + 9^4 - 4^7 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$29765 := -2^1 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 5^0$

$29766 := -2^3 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^1 + 6^6$	$30368 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 3^1 - 6^3 + 8^5$	$30833 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 3^5$
$29767 := -2^1 - 9^2 + 7^0 + 6^6 - 7^5$	$30384 := -3^8 + 0^1 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 4^6$	$30834 := -3^1 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^7 + 4^4$
$29768 := -2^3 - 9^1 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 8^2$	$30387 := -3^5 + 0^1 - 3^7 + 8^5 + 7^2$	$30842 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 2^8$
$29769 := -2^3 + 9^1 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 9^2$	$30446 := -3^4 - 0^0 + 4^4 - 4^7 + 6^6$	$30857 := -3^6 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 5^6 - 7^5$
$29782 := -2^6 - 9^1 - 7^4 + 8^5 - 2^9$	$30483 := -3^4 - 0^0 - 4^2 + 8^5 - 3^7$	$30862 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 2^6$
$29783 := -2^8 - 9^6 + 7^7 - 8^6 + 3^4$	$30486 := -3^6 - 0^0 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 6^4$	$30873 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 3^5$
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$29786 := -2^7 + 9^0 - 7^5 + 8^2 + 6^6$	$30525 := -3^6 + 0^1 + 5^6 + 2^2 + 5^6$	$30975 := -3^6 + 0^0 - 9^3 + 7^5 + 5^6$
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$29833 := -2^4 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 3^1 - 3^7$	$30552 := -3^6 - 0^0 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 2^5$	$31283 := -3^5 - 1^0 - 2^9 + 8^5 - 3^6$
$29834 := -2^1 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 3^7 - 4^2$	$30556 := -3^6 - 0^0 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$31285 := -3^6 - 1^0 - 2^7 + 8^5 - 5^4$
$29835 := -2^4 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 3^7 - 5^0$	$30558 := -3^7 + 0^0 - 5^2 + 5^0 + 8^5$	$31308 := -3^6 - 1^0 - 3^6 - 0^0 + 8^5$
$29837 := -2^3 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 3^7 - 7^1$	$30578 := -3^7 - 0^0 - 5^0 - 7^0 + 8^5$	$31338 := -3^6 + 1^0 - 3^6 + 3^3 + 8^5$
$29839 := -2^2 - 9^1 + 8^5 - 3^7 - 9^3$	$30580 := -3^7 + 0^0 - 5^0 + 8^5 - 0^0$	$31446 := -3^3 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 4^7 - 6^4$
$29843 := -2^3 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 4^0 - 3^7$	$30580 := -3^7 - 0^0 - 5^0 + 8^5 + 0^0$	$31468 := -3^1 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 6^4 - 8^5$
$29847 := -2^9 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 - 7^4$	$30581 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 1^0$	$31484 := -3^1 - 1^0 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 4^5$
$29853 := -2^2 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 5^1 - 3^7$	$30582 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 2^0$	$31486 := -3^1 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 8^5 - 6^4$
$29856 := -2^1 - 9^0 + 8^5 - 5^5 + 6^3$	$30583 := -3^1 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 8^5 - 3^7$	$31596 := -3^9 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 9^5 - 6^5$
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$29859 := -2^9 - 9^0 + 8^5 - 5^5 + 9^3$	$30585 := -3^6 + 0^1 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 5^6$	$31648 := -3^4 + 1^0 - 6^4 + 4^4 + 8^5$
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$29877 := -2^5 - 9^6 - 8^6 - 7^2 + 7^7$	$30588 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 8^5$	$31687 := -3^7 + 1^0 - 6^4 + 8^5 + 7^4$
$29878 := -2^4 - 9^6 - 8^2 + 7^7 - 8^6$	$30589 := -3^7 + 0^1 - 5^0 + 8^5 + 9^1$	$31705 := -3^6 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 5^6$
$29927 := -2^2 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 2^1 + 7^5$	$30618 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 1^0 + 8^5$	$31734 := -3^7 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 4^7$
$29947 := -2^1 - 9^1 - 9^6 - 4^9 + 7^7$	$30654 := -3^5 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 5^4 - 4^7$	$31776 := -3^9 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 6^6$
$29965 := -2^8 - 9^2 - 9^3 + 6^6 - 5^6$	$30659 := -3^4 + 0^1 - 6^6 + 5^7 - 9^3$	$31823 := -3^6 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^9 - 3^6$
$30245 := -3^9 + 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^8 - 5^6$	$30682 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 2^6$	$31826 := -3^6 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 - 6^3$
$30246 := -3^2 - 0^0 - 2^4 - 4^7 + 6^6$	$30694 := -3^3 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 9^4 + 4^7$	$31829 := -3^4 - 1^0 + 8^5 - 2^7 - 9^3$
$30264 := -3^1 - 0^0 - 2^2 + 6^6 - 4^7$	$30698 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 8^5$	$31862 := -3^7 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 6^4 - 2^4$
$30278 := -3^4 + 0^1 - 2^3 - 7^4 + 8^5$	$30758 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 5^6 + 8^3$	$31868 := -3^7 - 1^0 - 8^1 + 6^4 + 8^5$
$30286 := -3^7 + 0^0 - 2^9 + 8^5 + 6^3$	$30822 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^8 - 2^4$	$31869 := -3^7 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 6^4 - 9^1$
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$30288 := -3^8 + 0^0 - 2^4 + 8^4 + 8^5$	$30828 := -3^7 - 0^0 - 8^1 + 2^8 + 8^5$	$31887 := -3^3 + 1^0 - 8^3 + 8^5 - 7^3$
$30328 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 3^1 - 2^8 + 8^5$	$30829 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^8 - 9^1$	$31956 := -3^5 + 1^0 + 9^3 + 5^7 - 6^6$
$30338 := -3^1 + 0^0 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 8^4$	$30832 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 3^5 + 2^3$	$31958 := -3^4 - 1^0 - 9^3 + 5^0 + 8^5$

$32008 := -3^6 - 2^5 + 0^0 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$32288 := -3^6 + 2^0 + 2^8 + 8^5 - 8^1$	$32465 := -3^3 - 2^0 + 4^5 - 6^6 + 5^7$
$32028 := -3^5 - 2^9 - 0^0 + 2^4 + 8^5$	$32293 := -3^8 - 2^8 - 2^8 + 9^5 - 3^9$	$32467 := -3^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^5$
$32038 := -3^6 - 2^0 + 0^0 - 3^0 + 8^5$	$32298 := -3^6 + 2^1 + 2^8 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$32468 := -3^1 - 2^9 - 4^0 + 6^3 + 8^5$
$32044 := -3^6 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 4^7$	$32308 := -3^5 + 2^9 - 3^6 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$32470 := -3^6 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 0^1$
$32045 := -3^3 + 2^6 - 0^0 + 4^7 + 5^6$	$32328 := -3^2 - 2^8 + 3^4 - 2^8 + 8^5$	$32471 := -3^6 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 1^0$
$32048 := -3^6 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 4^1 + 8^5$	$32344 := -3^7 - 2^9 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 4^7$	$32472 := -3^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 2^3$
$32058 := -3^4 - 2^2 + 0^1 - 5^4 + 8^5$	$32346 := -3^4 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^7 + 6^6$	$32473 := -3^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 3^2$
$32068 := -3^6 - 2^3 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 8^5$	$32347 := -3^4 - 2^1 - 3^9 - 4^8 + 7^6$	$32474 := -3^5 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 4^7$
$32078 := -3^6 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 8^5$	$32348 := -3^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 8^5$	$32475 := -3^3 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 7^5 - 5^4$
$32083 := -3^6 + 2^4 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 3^3$	$32358 := -3^3 - 2^0 + 3^5 - 5^4 + 8^5$	$32476 := -3^5 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^5 - 6^3$
$32085 := -3^3 - 2^5 + 0^0 + 8^5 - 5^4$	$32366 := -3^4 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 6^6 - 6^5$	$32477 := -3^4 - 2^5 - 4^5 + 7^5 + 7^5$
$32087 := -3^4 - 2^8 - 0^0 + 8^5 - 7^3$	$32368 := -3^2 - 2^8 + 3^4 - 6^3 + 8^5$	$32478 := -3^1 - 2^3 + 4^3 - 7^3 + 8^5$
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$32182 := -3^2 - 2^6 - 1^0 + 8^5 - 2^9$	$32382 := -3^1 - 2^7 + 3^0 + 8^5 - 2^8$	$32483 := -3^1 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 3^3$
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$32187 := -3^5 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 8^5 - 7^3$	$32385 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 8^5 - 5^4$	$32486 := -3^1 + 2^0 - 4^3 + 8^5 - 6^3$
$32188 := -3^1 - 2^6 - 1^0 - 8^3 + 8^5$	$32386 := -3^1 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 8^5 + 6^4$	$32487 := -3^1 + 2^0 + 4^3 + 8^5 - 7^3$
$32189 := -3^5 - 2^8 + 1^0 + 8^5 - 9^2$	$32387 := -3^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^4 + 7^5$	$32488 := -3^2 - 2^4 - 4^4 + 8^0 + 8^5$
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$32578 := -3^5 - 2^0 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 8^5$	$32718 := -3^1 + 2^0 - 7^2 + 1^0 + 8^5$	$32817 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 7^2$
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$32634 := -3^4 + 2^8 + 6^6 + 3^7 - 4^7$	$32781 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$32830 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 3^4 + 0^1$
$32638 := -3^1 + 2^3 - 6^3 + 3^4 + 8^5$	$32782 := -3^1 + 2^1 - 7^0 + 8^5 + 2^4$	$32831 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 3^4 + 1^0$
$32648 := -3^2 - 2^7 + 6^0 + 4^2 + 8^5$	$32783 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 3^2$	$32832 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^0 + 2^6$
$32653 := -3^8 - 2^8 + 6^6 - 5^4 - 3^8$	$32784 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 8^5 + 4^2$	$32833 := -3^1 - 2^2 + 8^5 - 3^2 + 3^4$
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$32674 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 4^7$	$32787 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 7^1$	$32836 := -3^1 - 2^2 + 8^5 + 3^4 - 6^1$
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$32678 := -3^1 - 2^1 - 6^2 - 7^2 + 8^5$	$32789 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 9^1$	$32838 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 8^2 + 3^0 + 8^5$
$32679 := -3^8 - 2^9 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 9^4$	$32798 := -3^1 + 2^0 - 7^2 + 9^2 + 8^5$	$32839 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^4 - 9^1$
$32680 := -3^4 - 2^0 - 6^1 + 8^5 + 0^1$	$32799 := -3^9 + 2^0 - 7^1 + 9^5 - 9^4$	$32840 := -3^2 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 0^0$
$32681 := -3^4 - 2^0 - 6^1 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$32802 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 2^5$	$32843 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 8^5 - 4^0 + 3^4$
$32682 := -3^3 - 2^0 + 6^1 + 8^5 - 2^6$	$32803 := -3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 0^0 - 3^3$	$32844 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 4^3$
$32683 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 8^5 - 3^4$	$32804 := -3^3 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 4^3$	$32845 := -3^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 4^0 - 5^2$
$32684 := -3^1 - 2^4 - 6^0 + 8^5 - 4^3$	$32805 := -3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 0^0 - 5^2$	$32846 := -3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 6^0$
$32685 := -3^3 - 2^5 + 6^0 + 8^5 - 5^2$	$32806 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 6^2$	$32847 := -3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 7^2$
$32686 := -3^2 - 2^0 - 6^2 + 8^5 - 6^2$	$32807 := -3^1 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 7^2$	$32849 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 9^2$
$32687 := -3^1 - 2^7 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 7^2$	$32808 := -3^2 - 2^4 + 8^2 + 0^0 + 8^5$	$32850 := -3^3 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 0^1$
$32688 := -3^2 - 2^0 - 6^1 - 8^2 + 8^5$	$32809 := -3^2 - 2^5 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 9^2$	$32851 := -3^2 - 2^5 + 8^5 + 5^3 - 1^0$
$32689 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 6^1 + 8^5 - 9^2$	$32812 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 - 1^0 + 2^6$	$32852 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 2^6$
$32694 := -3^7 - 2^3 - 6^5 + 9^5 - 4^7$	$32813 := -3^1 - 2^5 + 8^5 - 1^0 + 3^4$	$32853 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 3^4$
$32698 := -3^1 - 2^5 - 6^2 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$32814 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^3$	$32854 := -3^1 - 2^5 + 8^5 + 5^3 - 4^1$
$32708 := -3^1 - 2^3 - 7^2 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$32815 := -3^4 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 5^3$	$32855 := -3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 5^0 + 5^2$

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|---|---|---|
| $32856 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 5^3 - 6^2$ | $32896 := -3^1 - 2^2 + 8^5 - 9^2 + 6^3$ | $33243 := -3^8 - 3^8 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 3^9$ |
| $32857 := -3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 5^3 - 7^2$ | $32897 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 7^2$ | $33244 := -3^2 - 3^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^7$ |
| $32858 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 8^2 + 5^2 + 8^5$ | $32899 := -3^3 - 2^2 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 9^2$ | $33246 := -3^8 - 3^8 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 6^6$ |
| $32859 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 9^2$ | $32928 := -3^2 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 2^7 + 8^5$ | $33247 := -3^1 + 3^3 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 7^5$ |
| $32860 := -3^2 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 0^0$ | $32929 := -3^9 - 2^2 - 9^4 + 2^7 + 9^5$ | $33248 := -3^1 + 3^5 - 2^4 + 4^4 + 8^5$ |
| $32862 := -3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 2^6$ | $32932 := -3^8 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 2^7$ | $33250 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 0^0$ |
| $32863 := -3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 3^4$ | $32938 := -3^4 - 2^0 + 9^1 + 3^5 + 8^5$ | $33258 := -3^5 + 3^6 - 2^0 + 5^1 + 8^5$ |
| $32864 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 4^3$ | $32944 := -3^4 + 2^8 + 9^0 + 4^7 + 4^7$ | $33262 := -3^8 - 3^8 - 2^4 + 6^6 - 2^8$ |
| $32865 := -3^3 - 2^1 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^3$ | $32947 := -3^3 + 2^9 - 9^3 + 4^7 + 7^5$ | $33264 := -3^9 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 4^6$ |
| $32866 := -3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 6^2$ | $32948 := -3^1 + 2^3 - 9^2 + 4^4 + 8^5$ | $33265 := -3^4 + 3^7 + 2^7 + 6^6 - 5^6$ |
| $32867 := -3^3 - 2^0 + 8^5 - 6^3 + 7^3$ | $32949 := -3^9 + 2^7 - 9^4 + 4^2 + 9^5$ | $33268 := -3^1 - 3^1 + 2^9 - 6^1 + 8^5$ |
| $32868 := -3^5 + 2^7 - 8^0 + 6^3 + 8^5$ | $32968 := -3^1 - 2^2 - 9^1 + 6^3 + 8^5$ | $33269 := -3^2 - 3^8 - 2^8 + 6^6 - 9^4$ |
| $32869 := -3^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 6^0 - 9^0$ | $32969 := -3^9 + 2^7 - 9^4 + 6^2 + 9^5$ | $33280 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 0^1$ |
| $32870 := -3^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 0^1$ | $32981 := -3^1 - 2^9 + 9^3 + 8^5 - 1^0$ | $33281 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 1^0$ |
| $32871 := -3^2 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 7^2 - 1^0$ | $32982 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 2^7$ | $33282 := -3^1 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 2^9$ |
| $32872 := -3^2 - 2^3 + 8^5 - 7^1 + 2^7$ | $32983 := -3^1 - 2^4 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^5$ | $33283 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 3^1$ |
| $32873 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 7^3 - 3^5$ | $32984 := -3^2 - 2^5 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 4^4$ | $33284 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 4^1$ |
| $32874 := -3^1 - 2^2 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 4^3$ | $32985 := -3^3 + 2^7 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 5^3$ | $33285 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 5^1$ |
| $32875 := -3^1 - 2^3 + 8^5 - 7^1 + 5^3$ | $32986 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 6^3$ | $33286 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 6^1$ |
| $32876 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 7^3 - 6^3$ | $32987 := -3^3 - 2^4 - 9^2 + 8^5 + 7^3$ | $33287 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 7^1$ |
| $32877 := -3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 7^2 - 7^0$ | $32988 := -3^3 + 2^8 - 9^0 + 8^5 - 8^1$ | $33288 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^3 + 8^3 + 8^5$ |
| $32878 := -3^1 + 2^7 - 8^2 + 7^2 + 8^5$ | $32989 := -3^3 + 2^8 + 9^0 + 8^5 - 9^1$ | $33289 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 9^1$ |
| $32879 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 9^2$ | $33008 := -3^1 + 3^5 - 0^0 + 0^0 + 8^5$ | $33318 := -3^8 + 3^9 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 8^3$ |
| $32880 := -3^2 + 2^7 - 8^1 + 8^5 + 0^0$ | $33028 := -3^2 - 3^5 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 8^5$ | $33338 := -3^4 + 3^1 - 3^4 + 3^6 + 8^5$ |
| $32882 := -3^2 - 2^2 - 8^0 + 8^5 + 2^7$ | $33048 := -3^1 + 3^3 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 8^5$ | $33355 := -3^4 - 3^0 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 5^6$ |
| $32883 := -3^1 + 2^7 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 3^2$ | $33058 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 5^6 - 8^2$ | $33357 := -3^7 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 5^6 - 7^1$ |
| $32884 := -3^1 + 2^7 - 8^1 + 8^5 - 4^0$ | $33083 := -3^2 + 3^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 3^5$ | $33358 := -3^2 + 3^0 - 3^3 + 5^4 + 8^5$ |
| $32885 := -3^1 - 2^2 - 8^0 + 8^5 + 5^3$ | $33087 := -3^3 + 3^1 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^3$ | $33365 := -3^7 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 5^6$ |
| $32886 := -3^1 + 2^7 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 6^1$ | $33089 := -3^1 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 9^2$ | $33377 := -3^1 + 3^2 - 3^5 + 7^5 + 7^5$ |
| $32887 := -3^1 + 2^7 + 8^0 + 8^5 - 7^1$ | $33152 := -3^7 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 2^5$ | $33378 := -3^1 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 8^5$ |
| $32888 := -3^2 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 8^5$ | $33156 := -3^7 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 6^2$ | $33388 := -3^3 - 3^4 + 3^6 - 8^0 + 8^5$ |
| $32889 := -3^2 + 2^7 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 9^0$ | $33157 := -3^1 + 3^6 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 7^5$ | $33398 := -3^2 - 3^2 - 3^4 + 9^3 + 8^5$ |
| $32892 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 2^7$ | $33158 := -3^5 + 3^2 - 1^0 + 5^4 + 8^5$ | $33407 := -3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 7^5$ |
| $32893 := -3^1 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 9^0 - 3^0$ | $33174 := -3^2 - 3^2 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 4^7$ | $33418 := -3^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 8^5$ |
| $32894 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 4^3$ | $33208 := -3^4 + 3^2 + 2^9 + 0^1 + 8^5$ | $33424 := -3^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 4^7$ |
| $32895 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 5^3$ | $33228 := -3^1 - 3^4 + 2^5 + 2^9 + 8^5$ | $33427 := -3^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 2^1 + 7^5$ |

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|---|---|---|
| $33428 := -3^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 2^2 + 8^5$ | $33594 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 9^3 - 4^4$ | $33796 := -3^4 - 3^8 + 7^3 - 9^4 + 6^6$ |
| $33442 := -3^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 2^9$ | $33597 := -3^5 - 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 7^4$ | $33824 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 4^5$ |
| $33443 := -3^3 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 3^6$ | $33598 := -3^1 + 3^6 - 5^4 + 9^3 + 8^5$ | $33825 := -3^2 - 3^7 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 5^5$ |
| $33445 := -3^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 4^7 - 5^2$ | $33623 := -3^8 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 2^3 - 3^8$ | $33826 := -3^1 - 3^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 6^4$ |
| $33446 := -3^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 4^9 + 6^7$ | $33626 := -3^8 - 3^8 - 6^2 + 2^7 + 6^6$ | $33829 := -3^8 - 3^9 + 8^3 + 2^9 + 9^5$ |
| $33447 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 7^5$ | $33628 := -3^1 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 2^7 + 8^5$ | $33842 := -3^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 2^5$ |
| $33448 := -3^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 8^5$ | $33643 := -3^5 - 3^7 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 3^9$ | $33843 := -3^1 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 3^3$ |
| $33462 := -3^8 - 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^6 - 2^3$ | $33645 := -3^3 + 3^7 - 6^6 + 4^2 + 5^7$ | $33844 := -3^1 - 3^2 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 4^5$ |
| $33464 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^5 + 4^6$ | $33647 := -3^1 + 3^5 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 7^5$ | $33845 := -3^1 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 4^5 - 5^2$ |
| $33465 := -3^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 6^6 - 5^6$ | $33648 := -3^2 + 3^4 - 6^3 + 4^5 + 8^5$ | $33846 := -3^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 6^2$ |
| $33467 := -3^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^5$ | $33652 := -3^1 + 3^7 - 6^6 + 5^7 - 2^0$ | $33847 := -3^1 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 7^2$ |
| $33468 := -3^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 6^3 + 8^5$ | $33654 := -3^1 + 3^7 - 6^6 + 5^7 + 4^0$ | $33848 := -3^2 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 4^5 + 8^5$ |
| $33469 := -3^4 - 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^6 - 9^4$ | $33658 := -3^8 - 3^8 + 6^6 + 5^3 - 8^0$ | $33849 := -3^3 + 3^1 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 9^2$ |
| $33478 := -3^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 8^5$ | $33665 := -3^3 + 3^7 - 6^6 + 6^2 + 5^7$ | $33862 := -3^3 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 6^4 - 2^8$ |
| $33480 := -3^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 0^1$ | $33668 := -3^2 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 6^3 + 8^5$ | $33864 := -3^5 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 4^2$ |
| $33481 := -3^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 1^0$ | $33669 := -3^4 - 3^8 + 6^3 + 6^6 - 9^4$ | $33865 := -3^1 - 3^6 + 8^5 - 6^4 + 5^5$ |
| $33482 := -3^1 - 3^5 + 4^5 + 8^5 - 2^6$ | $33682 := -3^2 + 3^7 - 6^4 + 8^5 + 2^5$ | $33866 := -3^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 6^4 - 6^3$ |
| $33483 := -3^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 3^6$ | $33683 := -3^1 - 3^3 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 3^6$ | $33867 := -3^1 - 3^1 + 8^5 - 6^4 + 7^4$ |
| $33484 := -3^4 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 4^5$ | $33684 := -3^4 + 3^2 - 6^2 + 8^5 + 4^5$ | $33876 := -3^8 - 3^8 - 8^0 + 7^3 + 6^6$ |
| $33485 := -3^1 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 8^5 - 5^1$ | $33685 := -3^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 - 5^2$ | $33884 := -3^6 - 3^7 - 8^2 + 8^5 + 4^6$ |
| $33486 := -3^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 8^5 - 6^3$ | $33686 := -3^2 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 8^5 - 6^4$ | $33885 := -3^7 + 3^5 - 8^2 + 8^5 + 5^5$ |
| $33487 := -3^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 7^0$ | $33687 := -3^3 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 7^0$ | $33886 := -3^5 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 8^5 + 6^4$ |
| $33488 := -3^2 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 8^0 + 8^5$ | $33689 := -3^3 + 3^1 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 9^3$ | $33934 := -3^3 - 3^7 + 9^2 + 3^9 + 4^7$ |
| $33489 := -3^1 - 3^0 - 4^1 + 8^5 + 9^3$ | $33736 := -3^6 - 3^6 + 7^5 + 3^9 - 6^4$ | $33936 := -3^1 - 3^4 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 6^5$ |
| $33498 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 9^3 + 8^5$ | $33738 := -3^1 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 3^6 + 8^5$ | $33954 := -3^5 + 3^7 + 9^0 + 5^6 + 4^7$ |
| $33533 := -3^8 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 3^9 + 3^9$ | $33756 := -3^5 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 5^7 - 6^6$ | $33955 := -3^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 5^6 - 5^4$ |
| $33536 := -3^1 - 3^8 + 5^1 - 3^8 + 6^6$ | $33757 := -3^2 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 7^5$ | $33958 := -3^7 + 3^5 + 9^1 + 5^5 + 8^5$ |
| $33538 := -3^1 - 3^4 + 5^3 + 3^6 + 8^5$ | $33758 := -3^7 + 3^1 + 7^2 + 5^5 + 8^5$ | $33974 := -3^3 + 3^4 + 9^3 + 7^5 + 4^7$ |
| $33539 := -3^8 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 3^6 + 9^5$ | $33759 := -3^4 - 3^9 - 7^4 - 5^5 + 9^5$ | $33982 := -3^5 + 3^6 + 9^3 + 8^5 - 2^0$ |
| $33554 := -3^1 - 3^6 - 5^6 - 5^6 + 4^8$ | $33772 := -3^4 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 7^5 - 2^2$ | $33984 := -3^5 + 3^6 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 4^0$ |
| $33560 := -3^8 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 + 0^0$ | $33773 := -3^1 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 3^4$ | $34065 := -3^1 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 6^6 - 5^7$ |
| $33573 := -3^6 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 3^9$ | $33774 := -3^1 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 7^5 + 4^7$ | $34168 := -3^2 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 6^7 - 8^6$ |
| $33574 := -3^5 + 3^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 + 4^7$ | $33775 := -3^4 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 7^5 - 5^0$ | $34234 := -3^6 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^7$ |
| $33576 := -3^4 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 6^6$ | $33776 := -3^3 - 3^3 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 6^3$ | $34235 := -3^4 - 4^5 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^6$ |
| $33577 := -3^1 - 3^2 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 7^5$ | $33777 := -3^4 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 7^5$ | $34237 := -3^7 - 4^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 7^5$ |
| $33579 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3$ | $33792 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 7^5 + 9^0 - 2^9$ | $34238 := -3^3 + 4^4 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 8^5$ |

$34253 := -3^3 - 4^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$34569 := -3^7 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 6^4 - 9^5$	$34823 := -3^1 - 4^0 + 8^5 - 2^7 + 3^7$
$34257 := -3^7 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 7^5$	$34583 := -3^1 + 4^4 - 5^4 + 8^5 + 3^7$	$34832 := -3^3 - 4^3 + 8^5 + 3^7 - 2^5$
$34276 := -3^5 + 4^7 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 6^4$	$34586 := -3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 - 6^4$	$34834 := -3^2 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^5$
$34278 := -3^3 + 4^5 + 2^9 + 7^0 + 8^5$	$34588 := -3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 8^5$	$34835 := -3^4 - 4^3 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 5^2$
$34286 := -3^4 - 4^7 - 2^0 + 8^4 + 6^6$	$34638 := -3^7 - 4^7 + 6^6 + 3^8 - 8^1$	$34837 := -3^3 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 7^3$
$34296 := -3^4 - 4^7 - 2^9 + 9^5 - 6^5$	$34639 := -3^8 + 4^5 + 6^6 + 3^4 - 9^4$	$34839 := -3^7 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 3^4 + 9^2$
$34307 := -3^7 + 4^1 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$34653 := -3^3 + 4^5 - 6^6 + 5^7 + 3^7$	$34846 := -3^5 + 4^0 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 6^4$
$34325 := -3^6 - 4^4 + 3^9 + 2^1 + 5^6$	$34655 := -3^1 + 4^3 - 6^6 + 5^5 + 5^7$	$34852 := -3^2 - 4^5 + 8^5 + 5^5 - 2^3$
$34327 := -3^7 + 4^2 + 3^9 + 2^3 + 7^5$	$34656 := -3^1 - 4^6 - 6^5 - 5^3 + 6^6$	$34853 := -3^4 - 4^2 + 8^5 - 5^1 + 3^7$
$34328 := -3^1 + 4^5 + 3^3 + 2^9 + 8^5$	$34658 := -3^1 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 5^5 + 8^5$	$34855 := -3^2 - 4^5 + 8^5 - 5^1 + 5^5$
$34335 := -3^5 - 4^0 - 3^6 + 3^9 + 5^6$	$34669 := -3^9 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 6^6 - 9^2$	$34857 := -3^4 - 4^4 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 7^4$
$34345 := -3^1 - 4^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^6$	$34676 := -3^3 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 6^4$	$34858 := -3^1 - 4^5 - 8^1 + 5^5 + 8^5$
$34364 := -3^1 + 4^6 - 3^0 + 6^6 - 4^7$	$34678 := -3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^1 + 8^5$	$34859 := -3^2 - 4^5 + 8^5 + 5^5 - 9^0$
$34368 := -3^1 + 4^3 + 3^5 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$34682 := -3^7 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 2^2$	$34863 := -3^3 - 4^3 + 8^5 - 6^0 + 3^7$
$34375 := -3^5 - 4^0 + 3^7 + 7^5 + 5^6$	$34684 := -3^7 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 4^6$	$34865 := -3^1 - 4^5 + 8^5 - 6^0 + 5^5$
$34382 := -3^1 + 4^5 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 2^9$	$34685 := -3^1 - 4^0 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 5^4$	$34872 := -3^2 - 4^4 + 8^5 + 7^4 - 2^5$
$34383 := -3^2 + 4^7 - 3^7 + 8^3 + 3^9$	$34686 := -3^9 - 4^3 + 6^5 + 8^0 + 6^6$	$34873 := -3^4 - 4^5 - 8^3 + 7^5 + 3^9$
$34385 := -3^2 + 4^3 + 3^7 + 8^5 - 5^4$	$34692 := -3^8 + 4^9 - 6^7 + 9^5 - 2^2$	$34876 := -3^4 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 7^4 - 6^3$
$34386 := -3^2 - 4^7 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 6^6$	$34693 := -3^1 + 4^9 - 6^7 + 9^5 - 3^8$	$34877 := -3^2 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 7^4$
$34433 := -3^1 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 3^8 + 3^9$	$34695 := -3^8 + 4^9 - 6^7 + 9^5 - 5^0$	$34878 := -3^3 - 4^4 - 8^1 + 7^4 + 8^5$
$34435 := -3^7 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 3^6 + 5^5$	$34696 := -3^6 + 4^9 + 6^6 + 9^4 - 6^7$	$34883 := -3^2 + 4^0 - 8^2 + 8^5 + 3^7$
$34472 := -3^6 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 2^5$	$34697 := -3^8 + 4^9 - 6^7 + 9^5 + 7^0$	$34887 := -3^3 - 4^4 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 7^4$
$34475 := -3^7 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 7^5 - 5^4$	$34724 := -3^1 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 2^9 + 4^7$	$34894 := -3^1 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 4^5$
$34476 := -3^3 + 4^2 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 6^4$	$34728 := -3^6 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 2^5 + 8^5$	$34896 := -3^2 + 4^7 - 8^6 + 9^3 + 6^7$
$34477 := -3^4 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 7^5$	$34736 := -3^6 - 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^9 - 6^0$	$34926 := -3^3 - 4^7 + 9^5 + 2^6 - 6^5$
$34483 := -3^6 + 4^0 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 3^7$	$34738 := -3^6 - 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 8^0$	$34938 := -3^2 + 4^0 - 9^1 + 3^7 + 8^5$
$34494 := -3^3 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 9^3 + 4^7$	$34744 := -3^6 - 4^4 + 7^6 - 4^7 - 4^8$	$34943 := -3^1 + 4^7 - 9^1 + 4^7 + 3^7$
$34498 := -3^3 + 4^1 + 4^5 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$34748 := -3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 4^6 + 8^5$	$34963 := -3^4 + 4^5 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 3^9$
$34523 := -3^6 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 2^3 + 3^9$	$34766 := -3^9 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 6^5 + 6^6$	$34965 := -3^4 + 4^6 - 9^2 + 6^6 - 5^6$
$34526 := -3^6 + 4^6 - 5^6 + 2^7 + 6^6$	$34782 := -3^1 - 4^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 - 2^7$	$34968 := -3^4 + 4^4 + 9^3 + 6^4 + 8^5$
$34537 := -3^4 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 3^7 + 7^5$	$34783 := -3^4 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 3^6$	$34982 := -3^5 - 4^6 + 9^4 + 8^5 - 2^3$
$34548 := -3^1 + 4^5 - 5^6 + 4^7 + 8^5$	$34784 := -3^4 + 4^5 + 7^2 + 8^5 + 4^5$	$34983 := -3^3 + 4^3 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^7$
$34553 := -3^6 - 4^0 - 5^2 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$34785 := -3^1 - 4^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 - 5^3$	$34985 := -3^5 + 4^3 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 5^5$
$34563 := -3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 3^8$	$34787 := -3^6 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$34989 := -3^5 - 4^6 - 9^0 + 8^5 + 9^4$
$34566 := -3^5 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 6^6$	$34814 := -3^1 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^5$	$34993 := -3^9 + 4^0 - 9^4 + 9^5 + 3^7$
$34567 := -3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5$	$34816 := -3^8 + 4^7 + 8^5 + 1^0 - 6^5$	$35032 := -3^5 + 5^6 - 0^0 + 3^9 - 2^5$

$35046 := -3^4 - 5^6 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 6^6$	$35309 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 9^1$	$35446 := -3^5 + 5^6 - 4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5$
$35054 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 0^0 + 5^6 + 4^7$	$35314 := -3^6 - 5^2 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 4^7$	$35449 := -3^3 + 5^7 + 4^2 + 4^7 - 9^5$
$35073 := -3^5 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 3^9$	$35320 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^4 - 0^0$	$35462 := -3^8 - 5^2 - 4^6 + 6^6 - 2^9$
$35083 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^6$	$35322 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^0 + 2^4$	$35467 := -3^1 - 5^6 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 7^3$
$35087 := -3^4 - 5^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$35325 := -3^2 + 5^2 + 3^9 + 2^0 + 5^6$	$35469 := -3^3 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 9^5$
$35137 := -3^6 - 5^4 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 7^5$	$35331 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^3 + 3^9 - 1^0$	$35475 := -3^4 + 5^5 - 4^0 + 7^5 + 5^6$
$35158 := -3^6 - 5^1 - 1^0 + 5^5 + 8^5$	$35332 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 2^5$	$35482 := -3^3 + 5^5 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 2^7$
$35223 := -3^4 + 5^6 - 2^3 + 2^2 + 3^9$	$35333 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 3^9$	$35483 := -3^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 + 8^5 - 3^6$
$35228 := -3^6 + 5^5 + 2^5 + 2^5 + 8^5$	$35334 := -3^1 - 5^0 - 3^6 + 3^9 + 4^7$	$35484 := -3^6 + 5^5 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 4^4$
$35230 := -3^4 + 5^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 0^0$	$35336 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 6^2$	$35485 := -3^2 + 5^4 - 4^5 + 8^5 + 5^5$
$35232 := -3^4 + 5^6 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 2^2$	$35337 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 3^9 - 7^2$	$35486 := -3^4 - 5^0 + 4^6 + 8^5 - 6^4$
$35234 := -3^2 + 5^6 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^3$	$35338 := -3^5 + 5^4 + 3^0 + 3^7 + 8^5$	$35487 := -3^4 - 5^4 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 7^4$
$35236 := -3^2 + 5^6 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^0$	$35340 := -3^6 + 5^0 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 0^0$	$35532 := -3^3 - 5^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^8$
$35246 := -3^2 - 5^6 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^6$	$35342 := -3^6 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 4^7 - 2^0$	$35592 := -3^7 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 9^4 - 2^5$
$35247 := -3^6 - 5^6 - 2^9 - 4^8 + 7^6$	$35344 := -3^3 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 4^0$	$35596 := -3^3 - 5^2 - 5^6 + 9^5 - 6^5$
$35248 := -3^6 + 5^6 - 2^7 + 4^7 + 8^4$	$35346 := -3^3 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^0$	$35628 := -3^4 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 2^5 + 8^5$
$35249 := -3^5 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 9^5$	$35351 := -3^4 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 5^6 - 1^0$	$35629 := -3^1 - 5^6 - 6^5 - 2^4 + 9^5$
$35253 := -3^4 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$35353 := -3^4 + 5^3 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$35635 := -3^9 - 5^5 + 6^0 - 3^9 + 5^7$
$35258 := -3^2 - 5^4 - 2^0 + 5^5 + 8^5$	$35355 := -3^1 + 5^2 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 5^6$	$35637 := -3^6 - 5^3 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 7^5$
$35266 := -3^9 + 5^1 + 2^9 + 6^5 + 6^6$	$35357 := -3^3 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 5^6 - 7^2$	$35643 := -3^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 + 4^6 + 3^4$
$35283 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 - 3^6$	$35358 := -3^2 - 5^1 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^2$	$35644 := -3^5 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 4^7 + 4^7$
$35284 := -3^4 + 5^5 - 2^9 + 8^5 - 4^2$	$35363 := -3^3 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 6^0 + 3^9$	$35648 := -3^5 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 4^1 + 8^5$
$35285 := -3^6 + 5^3 - 2^2 + 8^5 + 5^5$	$35364 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 4^3$	$35649 := -3^1 - 5^6 - 6^5 + 4^1 + 9^5$
$35286 := -3^6 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 - 6^1$	$35374 := -3^1 - 5^0 + 3^7 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$35664 := -3^3 - 5^5 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 4^3$
$35287 := -3^1 + 5^3 - 2^2 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$35376 := -3^5 - 5^6 + 3^7 + 7^4 + 6^6$	$35667 := -3^4 - 5^5 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 7^1$
$35289 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 - 9^3$	$35378 := -3^2 - 5^2 + 3^5 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$35679 := -3^8 - 5^0 - 6^0 - 7^5 + 9^5$
$35294 := -3^9 + 5^2 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 4^6$	$35394 := -3^6 - 5^2 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 4^7$	$35682 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^5 + 2^3$
$35300 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 0^1$	$35396 := -3^2 - 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^5 - 6^5$	$35683 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^5 - 3^5$
$35301 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 1^0$	$35398 := -3^9 + 5^3 + 3^1 + 9^5 - 8^4$	$35684 := -3^2 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 8^5 + 4^6$
$35302 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 - 2^2$	$35423 := -3^1 - 5^4 + 4^7 - 2^4 + 3^9$	$35685 := -3^5 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 5^5$
$35303 := -3^1 + 5^6 - 3^1 + 0^0 + 3^9$	$35427 := -3^1 - 5^7 - 4^6 + 2^1 + 7^6$	$35686 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^5 - 6^3$
$35304 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^1 - 4^0$	$35428 := -3^6 + 5^5 + 4^4 + 2^3 + 8^5$	$35687 := -3^5 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 7^0$
$35305 := -3^1 - 5^0 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 5^6$	$35432 := -3^1 + 5^6 - 4^0 + 3^9 + 2^7$	$35732 := -3^4 + 5^6 - 7^1 + 3^9 + 2^9$
$35306 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 6^0$	$35434 := -3^2 - 5^4 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 4^7$	$35733 := -3^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 3^6 + 3^9$
$35307 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 7^0$	$35438 := -3^1 - 5^4 + 4^7 + 3^9 - 8^0$	$35735 := -3^6 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 3^9 - 5^2$
$35308 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 8^1$	$35443 := -3^1 - 5^4 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 3^9$	$35737 := -3^6 - 5^2 + 7^0 + 3^9 + 7^5$

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|---|---|---|
| $35738 := -3^4 + 5^6 - 7^0 + 3^9 + 8^3$ | $35845 := -3^3 - 5^1 + 8^5 - 4^2 + 5^5$ | $35939 := -3^9 + 5^5 - 9^4 + 3^2 + 9^5$ |
| $35739 := -3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 3^9 - 9^3$ | $35846 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^2 - 6^2$ | $35948 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 8^5$ |
| $35754 := -3^6 - 5^1 + 7^6 - 5^6 - 4^8$ | $35847 := -3^4 - 5^6 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 7^4$ | $35954 := -3^8 - 5^2 + 9^5 - 5^3 - 4^7$ |
| $35758 := -3^1 - 5^3 - 7^1 + 5^5 + 8^5$ | $35849 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^3 - 9^2$ | $35976 := -3^9 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 7^2 - 6^3$ |
| $35763 := -3^6 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 6^0 + 3^9$ | $35853 := -3^4 + 5^4 + 8^0 + 5^6 + 3^9$ | $35978 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 9^2 + 7^1 + 8^5$ |
| $35768 := -3^3 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 6^0 + 8^5$ | $35858 := -3^2 - 5^2 - 8^0 + 5^5 + 8^5$ | $35979 := -3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2 - 7^3 + 9^5$ |
| $35773 := -3^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 3^7$ | $35862 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 6^2 - 2^6$ | $35984 := -3^9 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 8^0 - 4^4$ |
| $35777 := -3^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 + 7^5 + 7^5$ | $35863 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 6^3 - 3^5$ | $35994 := -3^9 - 5^1 + 9^3 + 9^5 - 4^6$ |
| $35778 := -3^2 + 5^4 - 7^1 + 7^4 + 8^5$ | $35864 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 4^2$ | $35995 := -3^5 - 5^4 - 9^4 + 9^5 - 5^6$ |
| $35783 := -3^4 - 5^4 + 7^5 - 8^0 + 3^9$ | $35865 := -3^2 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 5^5$ | $35998 := -3^9 - 5^0 + 9^3 + 9^5 - 8^4$ |
| $35784 := -3^2 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 - 4^0$ | $35866 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 6^0 - 6^0$ | $36034 := -3^3 - 6^1 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^7$ |
| $35786 := -3^2 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 6^0$ | $35867 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 7^2$ | $36128 := -3^8 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 2^7 - 8^4$ |
| $35791 := -3^9 - 5^5 + 7^6 - 9^5 - 1^0$ | $35868 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 8^5$ | $36233 := -3^8 + 6^6 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 3^8$ |
| $35793 := -3^4 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 9^1 + 3^9$ | $35872 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 7^1 - 2^0$ | $36234 := -3^4 + 6^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^7$ |
| $35798 := -3^8 + 5^3 - 7^5 + 9^5 - 8^1$ | $35874 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 4^0$ | $36237 := -3^1 + 6^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 7^5$ |
| $35802 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 0^1 - 2^6$ | $35879 := -3^1 + 5^7 - 8^0 + 7^5 - 9^5$ | $36238 := -3^2 + 6^4 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 8^5$ |
| $35803 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 0^1 - 3^4$ | $35881 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 8^5 - 1^0$ | $36243 := -3^4 + 6^0 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 3^9$ |
| $35806 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 0^1 - 6^1$ | $35882 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 8^5 - 2^4$ | $36273 := -3^1 - 6^3 + 2^1 + 7^5 + 3^9$ |
| $35809 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 0^1 - 9^2$ | $35883 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 8^5 + 3^0$ | $36278 := -3^8 + 6^6 - 2^6 + 7^3 - 8^4$ |
| $35812 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 - 2^0$ | $35884 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 8^5 - 4^0$ | $36294 := -3^3 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 9^4 - 4^7$ |
| $35814 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^0$ | $35884 := -3^2 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 8^5 + 4^0$ | $36297 := -3^4 + 6^6 - 2^5 + 9^4 - 7^5$ |
| $35820 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 0^1$ | $35885 := -3^6 - 5^3 + 8^4 + 8^5 - 5^3$ | $36342 := -3^5 + 6^1 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 2^9$ |
| $35821 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 1^0$ | $35886 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 6^0$ | $36343 := -3^1 + 6^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^9$ |
| $35822 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^1 - 2^6$ | $35887 := -3^2 - 5^4 + 8^4 + 8^5 - 7^3$ | $36344 := -3^1 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 4^7$ |
| $35823 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 3^2$ | $35888 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 8^0$ | $36347 := -3^3 - 6^2 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 7^3$ |
| $35824 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^2 - 4^3$ | $35889 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 8^5 - 9^1$ | $36348 := -3^1 + 6^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 8^5$ |
| $35825 := -3^1 - 5^0 + 8^5 - 2^6 + 5^5$ | $35890 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 9^0 - 0^0$ | $36357 := -3^9 - 6^0 - 3^9 + 5^7 - 7^4$ |
| $35826 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 6^1$ | $35892 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 2^0$ | $36367 := -3^4 - 6^1 + 3^9 - 6^2 + 7^5$ |
| $35827 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 7^1$ | $35894 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 9^1 + 4^0$ | $36369 := -3^4 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 6^6 - 9^5$ |
| $35828 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 8^2 + 2^1 + 8^5$ | $35896 := -3^9 + 5^4 - 8^4 + 9^5 + 6^0$ | $36372 := -3^4 - 6^2 + 3^9 + 7^5 - 2^0$ |
| $35829 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 9^1$ | $35897 := -3^9 - 5^5 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 7^3$ | $36374 := -3^4 - 6^2 + 3^9 + 7^5 + 4^0$ |
| $35837 := -3^3 - 5^4 - 8^0 + 3^9 + 7^5$ | $35898 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 9^1 + 8^5$ | $36384 := -3^5 + 6^1 - 3^5 + 8^5 + 4^6$ |
| $35838 := -3^4 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 3^3 + 8^5$ | $35933 := -3^8 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 3^1 - 3^9$ | $36385 := -3^5 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 8^5 + 5^5$ |
| $35842 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^2 - 2^6$ | $35934 := -3^2 - 5^3 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 4^7$ | $36386 := -3^4 + 6^3 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 6^4$ |
| $35843 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^1 - 3^3$ | $35937 := -3^2 - 5^4 + 9^2 + 3^9 + 7^5$ | $36387 := -3^1 - 6^2 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 7^5$ |
| $35844 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 4^2$ | $35938 := -3^3 + 5^5 - 9^1 + 3^4 + 8^5$ | $36416 := -3^8 - 6^5 + 4^6 + 1^0 + 6^6$ |

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|---|---|---|
| $36436 := -3^7 - 6^5 - 4^4 - 3^0 + 6^6$ | $36686 := -3^7 - 6^1 - 6^5 - 8^0 + 6^6$ | $36883 := -3^2 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 3^3$ |
| $36437 := -3^2 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^9 + 7^3$ | $36687 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 8^0 - 7^1$ | $36885 := -3^1 - 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 5^2$ |
| $36458 := -3^5 - 6^3 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 8^5$ | $36691 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 9^0 - 1^0$ | $36887 := -3^3 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 7^2$ |
| $36473 := -3^3 + 6^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 3^9$ | $36692 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 9^0 - 2^1$ | $36892 := -3^7 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 9^4 - 2^8$ |
| $36475 := -3^6 - 6^4 - 4^5 + 7^6 - 5^7$ | $36693 := -3^2 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 9^1 - 3^7$ | $36893 := -3^5 - 6^1 + 8^5 + 9^4 - 3^7$ |
| $36478 := -3^1 + 6^4 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^5$ | $36695 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 5^0$ | $36894 := -3^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 9^4 - 4^7$ |
| $36485 := -3^9 + 6^5 - 4^0 + 8^5 + 5^6$ | $36696 := -3^7 - 6^1 - 6^5 + 9^1 + 6^6$ | $36898 := -3^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 + 9^0 + 8^5$ |
| $36496 := -3^8 - 6^5 + 4^6 + 9^2 + 6^6$ | $36703 := -3^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 3^9$ | $36924 := -3^9 + 6^6 - 9^4 + 2^7 + 4^7$ |
| $36522 := -3^8 + 6^6 - 5^5 + 2^6 - 2^9$ | $36723 := -3^5 - 6^2 + 7^5 + 2^9 + 3^9$ | $36927 := -3^9 - 6^1 + 9^5 - 2^5 - 7^4$ |
| $36547 := -3^8 + 6^6 - 5^5 + 4^7 - 7^5$ | $36726 := -3^2 - 6^5 - 7^4 + 2^8 + 6^6$ | $36928 := -3^7 - 6^3 + 9^4 + 2^1 + 8^5$ |
| $36548 := -3^2 - 6^5 + 5^7 - 4^5 - 8^5$ | $36743 := -3^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 3^9$ | $36937 := -3^3 - 6^0 + 9^5 - 3^9 - 7^4$ |
| $36562 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 2^8$ | $36746 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 7^2 + 4^1 + 6^6$ | $36948 := -3^1 + 6^1 + 9^2 + 4^6 + 8^5$ |
| $36564 := -3^7 - 6^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 4^1$ | $36748 := -3^4 - 6^2 + 7^0 + 4^6 + 8^5$ | $36963 := -3^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 + 6^6 - 3^7$ |
| $36567 := -3^7 - 6^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^0$ | $36764 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 4^3$ | $36965 := -3^8 - 6^1 + 9^0 + 6^6 - 5^5$ |
| $36569 := -3^7 - 6^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 9^0$ | $36783 := -3^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 3^9$ | $36967 := -3^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 7^5$ |
| $36583 := -3^1 - 6^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 3^6$ | $36784 := -3^4 - 6^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 4^6$ | $36972 := -3^9 - 6^0 + 9^5 - 7^4 + 2^3$ |
| $36584 := -3^5 - 6^2 - 5^0 + 8^5 + 4^6$ | $36788 := -3^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 8^4$ | $36973 := -3^9 - 6^0 + 9^5 - 7^4 + 3^2$ |
| $36585 := -3^6 + 6^4 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 5^5$ | $36798 := -3^7 - 6^0 - 7^3 + 9^4 + 8^5$ | $36976 := -3^8 - 6^0 + 9^5 - 7^5 + 6^4$ |
| $36587 := -3^1 + 6^4 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 7^4$ | $36818 := -3^2 - 6^2 + 8^4 - 1^0 + 8^5$ | $37029 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 0^1 + 2^6 + 9^5$ |
| $36589 := -3^3 - 6^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 9^3$ | $36824 := -3^1 - 6^2 + 8^5 - 2^0 + 4^6$ | $37035 := -3^4 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 5^4$ |
| $36613 := -3^4 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 1^0 - 3^7$ | $36828 := -3^1 - 6^0 + 8^4 - 2^5 + 8^5$ | $37044 := -3^5 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 4^7$ |
| $36628 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 8^2$ | $36834 := -3^1 - 6^2 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 4^6$ | $37092 := -3^9 - 7^4 - 0^0 + 9^5 + 2^7$ |
| $36632 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^1 - 2^6$ | $36835 := -3^1 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 5^5$ | $37139 := -3^4 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 9^3$ |
| $36638 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^2 - 8^2$ | $36838 := -3^5 + 6^3 + 8^4 + 3^0 + 8^5$ | $37193 := -3^3 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 9^3 + 3^9$ |
| $36639 := -3^7 - 6^4 + 6^6 + 3^3 - 9^4$ | $36842 := -3^3 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 2^2$ | $37225 := -3^7 + 7^6 - 2^7 + 2^4 - 5^7$ |
| $36652 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 5^2 - 2^4$ | $36844 := -3^1 - 6^0 + 8^5 - 4^2 + 4^6$ | $37229 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 2^3 + 2^8 + 9^5$ |
| $36653 := -3^4 - 6^4 - 6^6 + 5^7 + 3^8$ | $36847 := -3^2 - 6^0 + 8^5 + 4^6 - 7^1$ | $37244 := -3^3 + 7^5 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 4^7$ |
| $36654 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 5^2 - 4^3$ | $36848 := -3^2 + 6^0 - 8^1 + 4^6 + 8^5$ | $37246 := -3^8 - 7^4 - 2^9 + 4^3 + 6^6$ |
| $36656 := -3^7 - 6^2 - 6^5 - 5^0 + 6^6$ | $36851 := -3^6 - 6^5 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 1^0$ | $37263 := -3^8 - 7^4 - 2^9 + 6^6 + 3^4$ |
| $36659 := -3^6 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 5^5 - 9^5$ | $36852 := -3^4 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 5^5 - 2^8$ | $37283 := -3^2 + 7^4 - 2^6 + 8^5 + 3^7$ |
| $36662 := -3^7 + 6^0 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 2^5$ | $36853 := -3^6 - 6^5 - 8^5 + 5^7 + 3^0$ | $37286 := -3^6 - 7^4 - 2^7 + 8^5 + 6^5$ |
| $36673 := -3^3 - 6^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 3^9$ | $36854 := -3^1 - 6^1 + 8^5 - 5^0 + 4^6$ | $37287 := -3^3 + 7^4 - 2^8 + 8^5 + 7^4$ |
| $36675 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 7^1 - 5^2$ | $36859 := -3^2 + 6^7 - 8^6 + 5^7 - 9^5$ | $37288 := -3^4 - 7^1 + 2^9 + 8^4 + 8^5$ |
| $36678 := -3^1 + 6^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 8^5$ | $36868 := -3^1 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 6^1 + 8^5$ | $37289 := -3^6 - 7^5 - 2^7 - 8^4 + 9^5$ |
| $36683 := -3^2 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 8^0 - 3^7$ | $36874 := -3^1 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 4^6$ | $37335 := -3^1 + 7^6 - 3^7 + 3^0 - 5^7$ |
| $36684 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 8^1 - 4^0$ | $36877 := -3^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 7^4$ | $37338 := -3^2 + 7^4 - 3^2 + 3^7 + 8^5$ |

$37348 := -3^2 + 7^4 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 8^5$	$37622 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 2^3 - 2^6$	$37979 := -3^7 + 7^5 - 9^1 + 7^5 + 9^4$
$37353 := -3^7 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 3^9$	$37625 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 2^6 - 5^1$	$37996 := -3^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 + 9^2 + 6^6$
$37356 := -3^8 - 7^3 + 3^6 - 5^5 + 6^6$	$37626 := -3^1 - 7^5 + 6^5 + 2^2 + 6^6$	$37997 := -3^7 + 7^5 + 9^1 + 9^4 + 7^5$
$37357 := -3^2 - 7^3 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 7^4$	$37628 := -3^1 - 7^4 + 6^5 - 2^9 + 8^5$	$38053 := -3^3 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 3^7$
$37358 := -3^1 + 7^4 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 8^5$	$37629 := -3^4 - 7^4 + 6^6 + 2^4 - 9^4$	$38069 := -3^9 - 8^0 + 0^1 - 6^4 + 9^5$
$37365 := -3^7 + 7^6 + 3^3 + 6^0 - 5^7$	$37647 := -3^3 + 7^5 - 6^2 + 4^6 + 7^5$	$38089 := -3^6 - 8^3 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 9^4$
$37378 := -3^3 + 7^2 + 3^7 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$37662 := -3^3 - 7^5 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 2^6$	$38252 := -3^8 - 8^5 - 2^5 + 5^7 - 2^9$
$37393 := -3^7 + 7^4 - 3^7 + 9^5 - 3^9$	$37682 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 8^1 - 2^2$	$38257 := -3^5 - 8^3 - 2^9 - 5^7 + 7^6$
$37394 := -3^4 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 9^3 + 4^4$	$37683 := -3^1 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 8^1 - 3^8$	$38275 := -3^1 + 8^5 - 2^4 + 7^4 + 5^5$
$37396 := -3^7 + 7^0 - 3^9 + 9^5 + 6^3$	$37684 := -3^9 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 4^2$	$38285 := -3^8 - 8^3 + 2^0 - 8^5 + 5^7$
$37432 := -3^4 + 7^5 + 4^5 + 3^9 - 2^0$	$37685 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 8^1 - 5^0$	$38293 := -3^5 + 8^5 - 2^6 + 9^4 - 3^6$
$37434 := -3^4 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 4^5$	$37686 := -3^1 - 7^5 + 6^5 + 8^2 + 6^6$	$38294 := -3^1 + 8^5 - 2^3 + 9^4 - 4^5$
$37463 := -3^5 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 3^9$	$37687 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 7^0$	$38324 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 2^1 + 4^6$
$37485 := -3^1 - 7^0 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 5^4$	$37690 := -3^1 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 9^4 - 0^0$	$38334 := -3^2 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 4^5$
$37486 := -3^1 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 6^4$	$37692 := -3^1 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 9^4 + 2^0$	$38344 := -3^6 - 8^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 4^8$
$37489 := -3^7 + 7^3 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 9^4$	$37693 := -3^9 - 7^4 - 6^0 + 9^5 + 3^6$	$38345 := -3^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4$
$37534 := -3^4 + 7^6 - 5^7 + 3^7 - 4^6$	$37694 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 4^0$	$38346 := -3^3 + 8^5 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 6^5$
$37537 := -3^6 + 7^4 - 5^4 + 3^9 + 7^5$	$37696 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 6^6$	$38360 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 0^1$
$37538 := -3^9 - 7^5 + 5^7 - 3^0 - 8^4$	$37708 := -3^1 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 8^4$	$38361 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 1^0$
$37540 := -3^9 - 7^5 + 5^7 - 4^6 + 0^0$	$37732 := -3^7 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 3^8 - 2^8$	$38362 := -3^1 + 8^5 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 2^3$
$37553 := -3^7 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 5^5 + 3^9$	$37734 := -3^1 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 4^6$	$38363 := -3^1 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 6^5 - 3^7$
$37559 := -3^9 - 7^5 - 5^4 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$37754 := -3^2 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 4^5$	$38364 := -3^2 + 8^5 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 4^2$
$37568 := -3^8 - 7^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^0$	$37794 := -3^2 - 7^3 - 7^5 + 9^5 - 4^6$	$38365 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 5^1$
$37573 := -3^7 - 7^1 - 5^7 + 7^6 + 3^5$	$37868 := -3^5 - 7^2 + 8^4 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$38366 := -3^1 - 8^3 + 3^0 - 6^5 + 6^6$
$37576 := -3^8 - 7^4 - 5^3 + 7^1 + 6^6$	$37884 := -3^1 - 7^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 4^5$	$38367 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 7^1$
$37589 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^4 - 8^0 + 9^5$	$37904 := -3^5 - 7^5 + 9^5 + 0^0 - 4^6$	$38368 := -3^7 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 8^5$
$37590 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 0^1$	$37906 := -3^7 - 7^0 - 9^4 - 0^0 + 6^6$	$38369 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 9^1$
$37591 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$37916 := -3^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$38383 := -3^6 + 8^3 - 3^6 + 8^5 + 3^8$
$37592 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 2^1$	$37932 := -3^7 - 7^5 + 9^5 - 3^7 + 2^6$	$38386 := -3^4 - 8^4 + 3^1 - 8^4 + 6^6$
$37593 := -3^8 + 7^0 - 5^6 + 9^5 + 3^6$	$37935 := -3^8 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 3^6 - 5^6$	$38393 := -3^5 - 8^0 - 3^6 + 9^5 - 3^9$
$37594 := -3^7 + 7^6 - 5^7 + 9^0 + 4^4$	$37936 := -3^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 + 3^3 + 6^6$	$38436 := -3^3 - 8^4 - 4^6 - 3^0 + 6^6$
$37595 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 5^4$	$37939 := -3^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 9^3$	$38437 := -3^8 - 8^3 + 4^8 - 3^9 - 7^3$
$37596 := -3^1 + 7^1 - 5^6 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$37954 := -3^7 - 7^5 + 9^5 - 5^5 + 4^5$	$38456 := -3^1 - 8^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^6$
$37597 := -3^9 + 7^1 + 5^4 + 9^5 - 7^4$	$37956 := -3^4 + 7^1 + 9^4 + 5^7 - 6^6$	$38457 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 4^1 + 5^7 - 7^3$
$37598 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 8^1$	$37957 := -3^8 - 7^5 + 9^5 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$38459 := -3^4 - 8^5 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 9^4$
$37599 := -3^8 + 7^1 - 5^6 + 9^3 + 9^5$	$37972 := -3^7 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 7^5 - 2^4$	$38460 := -3^1 - 8^4 - 4^6 + 6^6 - 0^0$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| $38462 := -3^1 - 8^4 - 4^6 + 6^6 + 2^0$ | $38639 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^1 + 9^4$ | $38868 := -3^7 - 8^0 + 8^3 + 6^5 + 8^5$ |
| $38472 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 7^4 - 2^6$ | $38646 := -3^5 + 8^1 - 6^5 + 4^0 + 6^6$ | $38869 := -3^5 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 6^3 + 9^4$ |
| $38473 := -3^1 + 8^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 3^9$ | $38657 := -3^6 - 8^4 + 6^6 - 5^5 - 7^2$ | $38876 := -3^7 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 6^5$ |
| $38475 := -3^6 - 8^2 - 4^4 + 7^6 - 5^7$ | $38662 := -3^6 - 8^0 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 2^9$ | $38879 := -3^6 - 8^2 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 9^4$ |
| $38476 := -3^3 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 6^4$ | $38663 := -3^5 - 8^0 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^3$ | $38894 := -3^5 + 8^2 + 8^5 + 9^4 - 4^4$ |
| $38479 := -3^8 - 8^3 - 4^8 + 7^6 - 9^4$ | $38664 := -3^6 + 8^3 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 4^0$ | $38896 := -3^6 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^4 - 6^3$ |
| $38489 := -3^4 - 8^4 - 4^7 + 8^0 + 9^5$ | $38673 := -3^3 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 7^3 - 3^7$ | $38897 := -3^4 - 8^1 + 8^5 + 9^4 - 7^3$ |
| $38492 := -3^4 - 8^4 - 4^7 + 9^5 + 2^2$ | $38675 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 7^3 - 5^2$ | $38917 := -3^9 - 8^0 - 9^5 + 1^0 + 7^6$ |
| $38494 := -3^8 - 8^4 - 4^7 - 9^0 + 4^8$ | $38678 := -3^7 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 8^4$ | $38922 := -3^9 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 2^2 - 2^9$ |
| $38497 := -3^8 - 8^1 - 4^7 + 9^5 + 7^4$ | $38692 := -3^6 + 8^5 - 6^2 + 9^4 + 2^7$ | $38925 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 9^0 + 2^7 + 5^7$ |
| $38499 := -3^9 - 8^2 + 4^8 - 9^3 - 9^4$ | $38694 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 9^4 + 4^4$ | $38927 := -3^9 + 8^1 - 9^5 + 2^1 + 7^6$ |
| $38524 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 2^4 - 4^4$ | $38695 := -3^1 + 8^5 - 6^1 + 9^4 - 5^4$ | $38928 := -3^4 - 8^2 + 9^4 - 2^8 + 8^5$ |
| $38540 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 0^1$ | $38725 := -3^4 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 2^9 + 5^5$ | $38934 := -3^9 - 8^3 + 9^5 + 3^4 - 4^0$ |
| $38541 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 1^0$ | $38729 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 2^7 + 9^4$ | $38936 := -3^9 - 8^3 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 6^0$ |
| $38542 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 2^1$ | $38743 := -3^5 - 8^5 - 7^3 + 4^8 + 3^8$ | $38943 := -3^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 + 4^6 + 3^7$ |
| $38543 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 3^1$ | $38749 := -3^5 - 8^5 + 7^5 - 4^6 + 9^5$ | $38947 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 7^3$ |
| $38544 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 + 4^1 - 4^4$ | $38753 := -3^9 + 8^0 - 7^1 + 5^7 - 3^9$ | $38948 := -3^5 - 8^2 - 9^5 + 4^8 + 8^5$ |
| $38545 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 5^5 + 4^4 + 5^5$ | $38763 := -3^7 + 8^3 + 7^3 + 6^6 - 3^8$ | $38956 := -3^9 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 5^4 + 6^3$ |
| $38546 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 4^3 + 6^5$ | $38764 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 6^5 + 4^3$ | $38965 := -3^9 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 6^3 - 5^4$ |
| $38547 := -3^1 + 8^5 + 5^5 + 4^4 + 7^4$ | $38765 := -3^1 + 8^5 - 7^4 + 6^5 + 5^4$ | $38966 := -3^1 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 6^6 - 6^5$ |
| $38548 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 8^1$ | $38768 := -3^4 - 8^4 + 7^4 + 6^5 + 8^5$ | $38967 := -3^9 - 8^4 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 7^4$ |
| $38549 := -3^4 + 8^5 - 5^4 + 4^8 - 9^5$ | $38769 := -3^9 - 8^3 - 7^2 - 6^2 + 9^5$ | $38968 := -3^4 - 8^2 + 9^4 - 6^3 + 8^5$ |
| $38563 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 3^8$ | $38783 := -3^3 - 8^3 - 7^1 + 8^5 + 3^8$ | $38979 := -3^9 - 8^0 - 9^3 + 7^3 + 9^5$ |
| $38564 := -3^8 - 8^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 4^5$ | $38789 := -3^3 - 8^3 - 7^0 + 8^5 + 9^4$ | $38982 := -3^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 + 8^5 - 2^8$ |
| $38565 := -3^6 + 8^5 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 5^4$ | $38795 := -3^6 - 8^0 + 7^6 + 9^0 - 5^7$ | $38984 := -3^4 - 8^1 + 9^4 + 8^5 - 4^4$ |
| $38583 := -3^2 + 8^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 3^7$ | $38805 := -3^8 + 8^1 - 8^5 + 0^0 + 5^7$ | $38986 := -3^5 - 8^2 + 9^4 + 8^5 - 6^2$ |
| $38586 := -3^1 - 8^4 + 5^3 - 8^4 + 6^6$ | $38809 := -3^2 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 9^4$ | $38997 := -3^9 - 8^0 + 9^2 - 9^5 + 7^6$ |
| $38594 := -3^6 + 8^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 - 4^0$ | $38813 := -3^1 - 8^3 + 8^5 - 1^0 + 3^8$ | $39027 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 2^2 - 7^3$ |
| $38596 := -3^6 + 8^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 + 6^0$ | $38829 := -3^5 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 2^8 + 9^4$ | $39029 := -3^9 - 9^2 + 0^1 - 2^8 + 9^5$ |
| $38598 := -3^6 - 8^0 - 5^0 + 9^4 + 8^5$ | $38834 := -3^6 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 4^6$ | $39069 := -3^9 - 9^2 + 0^1 - 6^3 + 9^5$ |
| $38614 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 1^0 + 4^4$ | $38837 := -3^4 - 8^4 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 7^5$ | $39082 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 2^2$ |
| $38632 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 - 2^2$ | $38849 := -3^9 - 8^0 - 8^3 - 4^1 + 9^5$ | $39083 := -3^1 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^5$ |
| $38633 := -3^1 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 - 3^6$ | $38852 := -3^8 - 8^1 - 8^5 + 5^7 + 2^6$ | $39084 := -3^5 + 9^4 - 0^0 + 8^5 - 4^0$ |
| $38635 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 - 5^0$ | $38855 := -3^8 + 8^2 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 5^1$ | $39085 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 5^0$ |
| $38636 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^5 + 6^5$ | $38857 := -3^1 - 8^4 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 7^4$ | $39086 := -3^3 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 6^3$ |
| $38637 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 7^0$ | $38859 := -3^8 + 8^2 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 9^0$ | $39087 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^0$ |

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| $39088 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 8^5$ | $39283 := -3^1 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 8^5 - 3^3$ | $39344 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 4^1$ |
| $39112 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 1^0 - 2^8$ | $39284 := -3^1 - 9^5 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 4^8$ | $39345 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^1$ |
| $39123 := -3^5 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 2^0 - 3^9$ | $39285 := -3^1 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 8^5 - 5^2$ | $39346 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 6^1$ |
| $39133 := -3^5 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 3^9$ | $39286 := -3^1 + 9^4 - 2^2 + 8^5 - 6^2$ | $39347 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 7^1$ |
| $39156 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^1 - 6^3$ | $39287 := -3^1 + 9^4 - 2^5 + 8^5 - 7^1$ | $39348 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 8^5$ |
| $39159 := -3^9 - 9^2 - 1^0 - 5^3 + 9^5$ | $39288 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 8^5 - 8^2$ | $39349 := -3^2 - 9^1 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 9^5$ |
| $39172 := -3^9 - 9^5 - 1^0 + 7^6 + 2^8$ | $39289 := -3^2 + 9^0 - 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^4$ | $39352 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 5^1 - 2^4$ |
| $39173 := -3^5 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 7^2 - 3^9$ | $39290 := -3^9 - 9^2 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 0^0$ | $39353 := -3^1 - 9^1 + 3^9 - 5^0 + 3^9$ |
| $39174 := -3^9 - 9^5 + 1^0 + 7^6 + 4^4$ | $39292 := -3^9 - 9^1 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 2^6$ | $39354 := -3^2 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 5^0 - 4^1$ |
| $39192 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 1^0 + 9^5 - 2^8$ | $39293 := -3^4 + 9^1 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 3^9$ | $39355 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 5^1 - 5^2$ |
| $39222 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^4 + 2^7 - 2^8$ | $39294 := -3^9 - 9^1 + 2^0 + 9^5 - 4^3$ | $39356 := -3^2 - 9^3 - 3^8 - 5^0 + 6^6$ |
| $39223 := -3^4 + 9^5 - 2^6 + 2^1 - 3^9$ | $39302 := -3^4 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 0^0 + 2^4$ | $39357 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 5^0 - 7^1$ |
| $39224 := -3^9 - 9^4 - 2^2 - 2^6 + 4^8$ | $39304 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 0^0 - 4^3$ | $39358 := -3^1 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 8^5$ |
| $39225 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^5 + 2^4 - 5^3$ | $39312 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 1^0 - 2^6$ | $39359 := -3^1 - 9^1 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^5$ |
| $39229 := -3^9 - 9^0 - 2^3 - 2^7 + 9^5$ | $39313 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^3 + 1^0 - 3^9$ | $39362 := -3^1 - 9^3 - 3^8 + 6^6 - 2^0$ |
| $39238 := -3^2 - 9^2 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^5$ | $39315 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 1^0 - 5^2$ | $39363 := -3^1 - 9^0 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 3^9$ |
| $39240 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^7 + 4^0 + 0^0$ | $39317 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 3^0 + 1^0 - 7^2$ | $39364 := -3^1 - 9^3 - 3^8 + 6^6 + 4^0$ |
| $39241 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 1^0$ | $39318 := -3^1 - 9^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 8^5$ | $39365 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 6^0 + 5^0$ |
| $39242 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^6 + 4^1 - 2^6$ | $39324 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 2^0 - 4^2$ | $39366 := -3^6 - 9^0 - 3^8 + 6^0 + 6^6$ |
| $39243 := -3^4 - 9^4 + 2^5 + 4^8 - 3^9$ | $39327 := -3^6 + 9^5 - 3^7 + 2^0 - 7^5$ | $39367 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 6^0 - 7^0$ |
| $39244 := -3^4 + 9^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 4^7$ | $39328 := -3^1 + 9^0 + 3^8 + 2^0 + 8^5$ | $39367 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 3^0 + 6^0 + 7^0$ |
| $39246 := -3^4 - 9^4 + 2^8 - 4^5 + 6^6$ | $39329 := -3^3 - 9^1 - 3^9 - 2^0 + 9^5$ | $39368 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 6^1 - 8^0$ |
| $39247 := -3^8 - 9^4 + 2^8 - 4^8 + 7^6$ | $39330 := -3^3 - 9^1 + 3^9 + 3^9 + 0^1$ | $39369 := -3^9 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 9^5$ |
| $39248 := -3^1 - 9^5 - 2^2 + 4^8 + 8^5$ | $39331 := -3^3 - 9^1 + 3^9 + 3^9 + 1^0$ | $39370 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 0^1$ |
| $39249 := -3^9 - 9^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 9^5$ | $39332 := -3^1 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 2^5$ | $39371 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 1^0$ |
| $39259 := -3^9 - 9^2 - 2^0 - 5^2 + 9^5$ | $39333 := -3^2 + 9^5 - 3^3 + 3^1 - 3^9$ | $39372 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^0 + 2^3$ |
| $39262 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^6 + 6^3 - 2^8$ | $39334 := -3^3 - 9^0 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 4^1$ | $39373 := -3^1 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 3^9$ |
| $39264 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 2^3 - 6^2 + 4^8$ | $39335 := -3^2 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 3^1 - 5^2$ | $39374 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 4^1$ |
| $39266 := -3^6 - 9^4 - 2^6 - 6^2 + 6^6$ | $39336 := -3^1 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 6^2$ | $39375 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 5^1$ |
| $39267 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^7 + 6^2 - 7^1$ | $39337 := -3^3 - 9^0 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 7^0$ | $39376 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 6^1$ |
| $39268 := -3^1 + 9^4 - 2^6 + 6^1 + 8^5$ | $39338 := -3^1 + 9^1 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 8^5$ | $39377 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 7^1$ |
| $39269 := -3^4 - 9^3 - 2^4 + 6^6 - 9^4$ | $39339 := -3^2 - 9^1 - 3^2 - 3^9 + 9^5$ | $39378 := -3^1 + 9^4 + 3^1 + 7^2 + 8^5$ |
| $39279 := -3^9 - 9^2 + 2^0 - 7^1 + 9^5$ | $39340 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 0^1$ | $39379 := -3^1 + 9^1 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 9^5$ |
| $39280 := -3^4 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 0^1$ | $39341 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 1^0$ | $39382 := -3^3 + 9^2 + 3^8 + 8^5 - 2^0$ |
| $39281 := -3^4 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0$ | $39342 := -3^2 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 - 2^4$ | $39384 := -3^3 + 9^2 + 3^8 + 8^5 + 4^0$ |
| $39282 := -3^3 + 9^4 - 2^2 + 8^5 - 2^4$ | $39343 := -3^3 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 4^0 - 3^9$ | $39387 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 8^0 - 7^1$ |

$39391 := -3^9 - 9^0 + 3^3 + 9^5 - 1^0$	$39454 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 4^3$	$39578 := -3^2 - 9^0 - 5^7 + 7^6 + 8^2$
$39392 := -3^9 + 9^0 + 3^2 + 9^5 + 2^4$	$39456 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 5^3 - 6^2$	$39579 := -3^3 + 9^0 - 5^7 + 7^6 + 9^2$
$39393 := -3^2 + 9^1 + 3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9$	$39462 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 2^5$	$39593 := -3^9 + 9^1 - 5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5$
$39394 := -3^3 - 9^1 - 3^9 + 9^5 + 4^3$	$39463 := -3^1 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 3^9$	$39594 := -3^3 + 9^2 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 4^7$
$39395 := -3^3 + 9^2 - 3^9 + 9^5 - 5^2$	$39464 := -3^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 4^7$	$39595 := -3^9 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 9^5 - 5^4$
$39396 := -3^9 - 9^1 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 6^2$	$39465 := -3^2 - 9^4 + 4^1 + 6^6 - 5^4$	$39596 := -3^9 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 6^3$
$39397 := -3^2 - 9^1 - 3^9 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$39466 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 6^6$	$39597 := -3^2 + 9^0 - 5^7 + 9^2 + 7^6$
$39398 := -3^1 - 9^1 + 3^4 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$39467 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 6^2 + 7^2$	$39603 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 6^1 + 0^1 + 3^5$
$39402 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 0^1 + 2^5$	$39468 := -3^1 - 9^5 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 8^5$	$39606 := -3^1 + 9^3 - 6^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$
$39403 := -3^3 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 0^1 - 3^9$	$39469 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 9^5$	$39620 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 6^0 + 2^8 - 0^0$
$39405 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 0^1 - 5^2$	$39478 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 4^0 + 7^2 + 8^2$	$39621 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 6^6 + 2^8 - 1^0$
$39406 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 0^1 + 6^2$	$39484 := -3^3 - 9^5 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 4^8$	$39622 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 6^6 + 2^7 + 2^7$
$39417 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 7^2$	$39485 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 4^5 + 8^5 - 5^4$	$39623 := -3^5 - 9^4 + 6^6 - 2^8 + 3^3$
$39420 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 0^1$	$39486 := -3^4 - 9^4 - 4^2 - 8^3 + 6^6$	$39624 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 4^4$
$39421 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 1^0$	$39487 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 8^1 + 7^2$	$39625 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 2^7 + 5^3$
$39422 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 2^7$	$39492 := -3^9 - 9^0 - 4^0 + 9^5 + 2^7$	$39626 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 2^3 + 6^3$
$39423 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 2^6 - 3^9$	$39497 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$39627 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 2^8 - 7^0$
$39424 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^1 + 2^7 + 4^8$	$39507 := -3^2 - 9^1 - 5^7 + 0^0 + 7^6$	$39628 := -3^7 - 9^3 + 6^6 - 2^4 - 8^4$
$39425 := -3^5 + 9^5 - 4^7 + 2^7 - 5^5$	$39514 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 5^5 + 1^0 - 4^7$	$39629 := -3^9 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 2^8 + 9^5$
$39426 := -3^6 - 9^4 - 4^1 + 2^6 + 6^6$	$39517 := -3^2 + 9^0 - 5^7 + 1^0 + 7^6$	$39632 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 3^2 + 2^8$
$39427 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 7^1$	$39520 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 2^7 + 0^0$	$39635 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 3^5 + 5^2$
$39428 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 8^1$	$39522 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 2^5 - 2^0$	$39642 := -3^7 - 9^3 + 6^6 - 4^6 - 2^1$
$39429 := -3^9 - 9^0 - 4^3 + 2^7 + 9^5$	$39524 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 4^0$	$39643 := -3^1 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 4^3 - 3^9$
$39430 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 3^4 - 0^0$	$39532 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 3^2 + 2^5$	$39644 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 4^4$
$39432 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^6$	$39533 := -3^4 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 3^5 - 3^9$	$39645 := -3^4 - 9^4 + 6^6 + 4^4 - 5^4$
$39434 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$39534 := -3^2 + 9^5 - 5^5 + 3^1 - 4^7$	$39646 := -3^3 + 9^3 - 6^5 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$39438 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 4^0 + 3^2 + 8^2$	$39536 := -3^5 + 9^4 - 5^6 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$39647 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 4^2 + 7^2$
$39439 := -3^9 - 9^1 + 4^0 + 3^4 + 9^5$	$39538 := -3^2 + 9^4 - 5^2 + 3^5 + 8^5$	$39648 := -3^7 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 4^1 - 8^4$
$39442 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 4^2 + 2^6$	$39552 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 5^3 - 2^6$	$39649 := -3^9 - 9^1 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 9^5$
$39443 := -3^1 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 4^3 - 3^9$	$39554 := -3^8 - 9^0 - 5^6 + 5^7 - 4^7$	$39662 := -3^6 - 9^4 - 6^3 + 6^6 + 2^9$
$39445 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 5^3$	$39556 := -3^8 + 9^2 - 5^4 + 5^1 + 6^6$	$39663 := -3^3 + 9^2 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^6$
$39446 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 4^2 + 4^3 + 6^6$	$39572 := -3^4 + 9^0 - 5^7 + 7^6 + 2^7$	$39664 := -3^2 + 9^3 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 4^3$
$39447 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 7^2$	$39573 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 3^4$	$39667 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 6^3 + 7^2$
$39448 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 8^5$	$39574 := -3^3 + 9^2 - 5^7 + 7^6 - 4^1$	$39668 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 6^3 + 6^1 + 8^3$
$39449 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 9^5$	$39576 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^2 + 6^2$	$39669 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 6^1 + 6^3 + 9^5$
$39453 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 3^4$	$39577 := -3^3 + 9^2 - 5^7 + 7^6 - 7^0$	$39670 := -3^4 - 9^4 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 0^0$

- 39672** := $-3^4 - 9^4 + 6^6 - 7^3 + 2^0$ **39762** := $-3^8 + 9^1 - 7^3 + 6^6 + 2^0$ **39869** := $-3^2 - 9^3 + 8^3 + 6^6 - 9^4$
39674 := $-3^9 + 9^5 - 6^2 + 7^3 + 4^0$ **39772** := $-3^9 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 7^3 + 2^6$ **39878** := $-3^9 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 7^0 + 8^3$
39685 := $-3^5 + 9^1 + 6^5 + 8^5 - 5^4$ **39774** := $-3^3 + 9^4 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 4^7$ **39880** := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 8^3 + 0^0$
39687 := $-3^8 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 8^2 - 7^3$ **39778** := $-3^8 + 9^5 - 7^5 + 7^0 + 8^4$ **39882** := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 8^3 - 2^2$
39702 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 0^0 - 2^3$ **39790** := $-3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 0^1$ **39883** := $-3^1 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 8^3 - 3^9$
39705 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 0^0 - 5^1$ **39791** := $-3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 1^0$ **39885** := $-3^4 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 5^3$
39708 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 0^1 - 8^0$ **39792** := $-3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 2^1$ **39886** := $-3^4 - 9^4 - 8^2 - 8^2 + 6^6$
39709 := $-3^9 - 9^0 + 7^3 + 0^0 + 9^5$ **39793** := $-3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 3^1$ **39887** := $-3^1 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 7^2$
39710 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 0^1$ **39794** := $-3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 4^1$ **39933** := $-3^4 - 9^2 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9$
39711 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 1^0$ **39795** := $-3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 5^1$ **39936** := $-3^4 - 9^2 - 9^4 + 3^1 + 6^6$
39712 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 2^1$ **39796** := $-3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 6^1$ **39956** := $-3^5 - 9^4 + 9^3 - 5^4 + 6^6$
39713 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 3^1$ **39797** := $-3^9 + 9^2 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 7^3$ **39965** := $-3^2 + 9^5 + 9^5 + 6^0 - 5^7$
39714 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 4^1$ **39798** := $-3^9 - 9^2 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 8^3$ **39972** := $-3^7 - 9^2 + 9^5 - 7^5 - 2^1$
39715 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 5^1$ **39799** := $-3^9 + 9^1 + 7^3 + 9^2 + 9^5$ **39973** := $-3^4 - 9^0 + 9^5 - 7^5 - 3^7$
39716 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 6^1$ **39804** := $-3^9 - 9^4 + 8^3 + 0^1 + 4^8$ **39974** := $-3^9 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 4^4$
39717 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 7^3$ **39806** := $-3^2 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 6^5$ **39975** := $-3^7 - 9^2 + 9^5 - 7^5 + 5^0$
39718 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 8^1$ **39822** := $-3^1 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^9 - 2^4$ **39978** := $-3^4 + 9^3 + 9^4 + 7^0 + 8^5$
39719 := $-3^9 + 9^1 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 9^5$ **39823** := $-3^2 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 3^8$ **39986** := $-3^3 - 9^2 - 9^4 - 8^0 + 6^6$
39724 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 2^4 - 4^0$ **39824** := $-3^4 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 4^3$ **39996** := $-3^2 - 9^1 - 9^2 - 9^4 + 6^6$
39726 := $-3^3 - 9^4 - 7^3 + 2^0 + 6^6$ **39826** := $-3^2 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^9 - 6^1$
39732 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 3^3 - 2^2$ **39829** := $-3^1 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 9^4$ **40169** := $-4^8 + 0^0 - 1^0 + 6^6 + 9^5$
39733 := $-3^1 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 3^3 - 3^9$ **39842** := $-3^1 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 2^9$ **40169** := $-4^8 - 0^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 9^5$
39734 := $-3^2 - 9^1 + 7^5 + 3^8 + 4^7$ **39845** := $-3^5 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 4^7 - 5^6$ **40279** := $-4^7 - 0^0 + 2^4 - 7^4 + 9^5$
39735 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 3^5 + 5^3$ **39846** := $-3^8 - 9^0 + 8^1 - 4^4 + 6^6$ **40286** := $-4^4 - 0^0 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 6^5$
39736 := $-3^6 - 9^4 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 6^6$ **39847** := $-3^4 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 4^4 + 7^3$ **40296** := $-4^8 - 0^0 + 2^7 + 9^5 + 6^6$
39737 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 3^3 + 7^3$ **39848** := $-3^2 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 4^2 + 8^5$ **40297** := $-4^7 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 9^5 - 7^4$
39739 := $-3^9 + 9^2 + 7^2 + 3^5 + 9^5$ **39856** := $-3^5 - 9^4 - 8^0 + 5^1 + 6^6$ **40346** := $-4^1 - 0^0 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^6$
39742 := $-3^2 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 4^7 - 2^0$ **39860** := $-3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 0^1$ **40348** := $-4^1 - 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 8^5$
39744 := $-3^2 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 4^7$ **39861** := $-3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 1^0$ **40363** := $-4^6 - 0^0 - 3^2 + 6^6 - 3^7$
39746 := $-3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 4^0 + 6^2$ **39862** := $-3^4 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 2^7$ **40366** := $-4^5 - 0^0 - 3^8 + 6^4 + 6^6$
39748 := $-3^1 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 4^7 - 8^0$ **39863** := $-3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 3^1$ **40367** := $-4^6 + 0^0 - 3^7 + 6^6 - 7^1$
39752 := $-3^3 - 9^0 + 7^6 - 5^7 + 2^8$ **39864** := $-3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 4^1$ **40368** := $-4^1 - 0^0 - 3^7 + 6^6 - 8^4$
39753 := $-3^4 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 5^3 - 3^9$ **39865** := $-3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 5^1$ **40436** := $-4^6 - 0^0 + 4^3 - 3^7 + 6^6$
39754 := $-3^1 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 5^1 + 4^7$ **39866** := $-3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 6^6$ **40493** := $-4^7 - 0^0 + 4^2 + 9^5 - 3^7$
39756 := $-3^8 - 9^0 - 7^3 + 5^1 + 6^6$ **39867** := $-3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 7^1$ **40639** := $-4^7 - 0^0 - 6^4 - 3^6 + 9^5$
39760 := $-3^8 + 9^1 - 7^3 + 6^6 - 0^0$ **39868** := $-3^2 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 8^5$ **40693** := $-4^7 - 0^0 + 6^3 + 9^5 - 3^7$
40756 := $-4^3 + 0^1 + 7^6 - 5^7 + 6^4$

$40864 := -4^7 + 0^1 - 8^3 - 6^5 + 4^8$	$42349 := -4^7 + 2^0 - 3^5 + 4^8 - 9^4$	$42529 := -4^5 + 2^0 - 5^6 + 2^7 + 9^5$
$41258 := -4^6 - 1^0 - 2^1 + 5^7 - 8^5$	$42356 := -4^6 - 2^7 - 3^4 + 5^1 + 6^6$	$42534 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 5^2 - 3^8 + 4^8$
$41266 := -4^6 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 6^6 - 6^4$	$42358 := -4^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^5$	$42536 := -4^5 + 2^1 - 5^5 + 3^3 + 6^6$
$41369 := -4^7 - 1^0 + 3^0 - 6^4 + 9^5$	$42359 := -4^1 - 2^7 - 3^9 + 5^5 + 9^5$	$42537 := -4^8 - 2^9 - 5^6 + 3^8 + 7^6$
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$41769 := -4^4 - 1^0 - 7^5 - 6^3 + 9^5$	$42386 := -4^6 - 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^0 + 6^6$	$42539 := -4^7 - 2^1 - 5^3 + 3^0 + 9^5$
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$41968 := -4^6 + 1^0 - 9^2 + 6^6 - 8^3$	$42391 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 3^5 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$42553 := -4^4 - 2^3 - 5^6 + 5^7 - 3^9$
$42046 := -4^6 - 2^9 - 0^0 - 4^0 + 6^6$	$42392 := -4^7 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 9^5 - 2^5$	$42556 := -4^6 - 2^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 6^6$
$42053 := -4^7 - 2^2 - 0^0 + 5^7 - 3^9$	$42393 := -4^7 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 9^5 - 3^5$	$42559 := -4^7 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 5^3 + 9^5$
$42064 := -4^6 - 2^9 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 4^2$	$42394 := -4^2 - 2^8 + 3^0 + 9^5 - 4^7$	$42560 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 0^1$
$42089 := -4^7 - 2^6 + 0^1 - 8^3 + 9^5$	$42395 := -4^3 - 2^5 - 3^9 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$42561 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 1^0$
$42097 := -4^2 - 2^7 - 0^0 + 9^5 - 7^5$	$42396 := -4^6 - 2^1 - 3^4 - 9^2 + 6^6$	$42561 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 1^0$
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$42249 := -4^4 - 2^5 - 2^7 - 4^7 + 9^5$	$42399 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 9^5$	$42562 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 2^1$
$42263 := -4^6 - 2^5 - 2^8 + 6^6 - 3^2$	$42409 := -4^4 - 2^0 - 4^7 + 0^0 + 9^5$	$42563 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 3^0$
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$42265 := -4^6 - 2^6 - 2^8 + 6^6 + 5^2$	$42429 := -4^4 + 2^2 - 4^7 + 2^4 + 9^5$	$42564 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^1$
$42266 := -4^6 - 2^1 - 2^8 - 6^2 + 6^6$	$42436 := -4^6 - 2^7 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 6^6$	$42565 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 5^1$
$42268 := -4^1 - 2^5 - 2^8 + 6^6 - 8^4$	$42456 := -4^6 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 6^6$	$42565 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 5^1$
$42279 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 2^6 + 7^6 - 9^5$	$42462 := -4^3 - 2^1 - 4^6 + 6^6 - 2^5$	$42566 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^1 + 6^6$
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$42316 := -4^6 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$42496 := -4^3 - 2^0 - 4^6 + 9^0 + 6^6$	$42579 := -4^4 - 2^5 + 5^4 - 7^5 + 9^5$
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$42329 := -4^7 - 2^8 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 9^5$	$42506 := -4^5 - 2^0 - 5^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$42593 := -4^7 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 9^5 - 3^4$
$42334 := -4^7 - 2^8 - 3^0 - 3^8 + 4^8$	$42509 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 5^3 + 0^0 + 9^5$	$42594 := -4^3 - 2^1 - 5^1 + 9^5 - 4^7$
$42336 := -4^6 - 2^3 + 3^3 - 3^5 + 6^6$	$42516 := -4^5 + 2^3 - 5^5 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$42595 := -4^7 - 2^6 - 5^0 + 9^5 - 5^1$
$42339 := -4^7 - 2^1 - 3^4 - 3^5 + 9^5$	$42526 := -4^6 - 2^0 - 5^0 - 2^5 + 6^6$	$42596 := -4^5 + 2^3 - 5^5 + 9^2 + 6^6$

$42597 := -4^7 + 2^3 - 5^3 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$42652 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 5^3 - 2^5$	$42739 := -4^2 + 2^9 - 7^5 + 3^0 + 9^5$
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$42634 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$42685 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 5^3$	$42863 := -4^1 + 2^6 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 3^5$
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$42636 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 6^1 + 3^4 + 6^6$	$42688 := -4^3 + 2^7 + 6^6 + 8^2 - 8^4$	$42865 := -4^3 - 2^8 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 5^4$
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$42643 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 3^4$	$42696 := -4^6 + 2^7 - 6^0 + 9^1 + 6^6$	$42903 := -4^7 - 2^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 3^5$
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$42922 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 2^8$	$42979 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 9^5$	$43365 := -4^1 - 3^4 - 3^4 + 6^6 - 5^5$
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$42924 := -4^7 + 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^4$	$42986 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 6^0$	$43382 := -4^2 + 3^9 + 3^9 + 8^4 - 2^6$
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$42933 := -4^7 - 2^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 3^5$	$43168 := -4^5 - 3^8 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 8^4$	$43396 := -4^7 + 3^0 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 6^0$
$42934 := -4^2 - 2^9 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^6$	$43226 := -4^6 + 3^6 - 2^6 + 2^0 + 6^6$	$43398 := -4^7 + 3^1 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 8^0$
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$42945 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	$43256 := -4^2 - 3^1 - 2^8 - 5^5 + 6^6$	$43453 := -4^1 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 5^5 + 3^6$
$42946 := -4^7 + 2^0 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^3$	$43258 := -4^8 - 3^9 - 2^2 + 5^8 - 8^6$	$43456 := -4^3 - 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^5 + 6^6$
$42953 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 3^3$	$43259 := -4^7 + 3^0 - 2^5 + 5^4 + 9^5$	$43459 := -4^1 - 3^9 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 9^5$
$42954 := -4^7 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 4^4$	$43263 := -4^6 - 3^3 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 3^6$	$43460 := -4^5 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 6^6 - 0^0$
$42956 := -4^3 - 2^9 + 9^0 - 5^5 + 6^6$	$43265 := -4^4 - 3^2 - 2^0 + 6^6 - 5^5$	$43462 := -4^5 - 3^7 + 4^0 + 6^6 + 2^4$
$42957 := -4^1 - 2^9 + 9^5 - 5^6 + 7^2$	$43276 := -4^5 - 3^7 - 2^9 + 7^3 + 6^6$	$43465 := -4^3 - 3^0 - 4^0 + 6^6 - 5^5$
$42959 := -4^4 - 2^7 - 9^2 - 5^6 + 9^5$	$43286 := -4^6 + 3^6 - 2^2 + 8^0 + 6^6$	$43475 := -4^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 7^6 - 5^7$
$42963 := -4^7 + 2^0 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 3^4$	$43292 := -4^7 + 3^5 + 2^7 + 9^5 + 2^8$	$43506 := -4^2 - 3^2 - 5^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$
$42965 := -4^4 + 2^0 - 9^4 + 6^6 + 5^5$	$43293 := -4^7 + 3^3 - 2^7 + 9^5 + 3^6$	$43526 := -4^1 - 3^1 - 5^5 + 2^1 + 6^6$
$42970 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 0^1$	$43295 := -4^1 + 3^1 - 2^7 + 9^5 - 5^6$	$43542 := -4^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 4^8 + 2^8$
$42971 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 1^0$	$43296 := -4^6 - 3^0 + 2^3 + 9^3 + 6^6$	$43546 := -4^1 + 3^1 - 5^5 + 4^2 + 6^6$
$42972 := -4^7 + 2^1 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 2^8$	$43298 := -4^7 + 3^6 - 2^5 + 9^5 - 8^2$	$43547 := -4^3 - 3^2 - 5^7 + 4^6 + 7^6$
$42973 := -4^7 - 2^3 + 9^5 + 7^3 - 3^3$	$43324 := -4^7 + 3^6 - 3^8 + 2^2 + 4^8$	$43549 := -4^7 + 3^1 + 5^4 + 4^4 + 9^5$
$42974 := -4^7 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 4^4$	$43326 := -4^5 - 3^7 + 3^2 - 2^7 + 6^6$	$43562 := -4^1 + 3^1 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 2^5$
$42975 := -4^1 + 2^2 - 9^5 + 7^6 - 5^6$	$43329 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 3^6 - 2^6 + 9^5$	$43563 := -4^1 + 3^2 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 3^3$
$42976 := -4^5 - 2^8 + 9^0 - 7^4 + 6^6$	$43345 := -4^1 - 3^0 - 3^8 + 4^8 - 5^6$	$43564 := -4^1 - 3^3 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 4^3$
$42977 := -4^7 - 2^5 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 7^3$	$43362 := -4^5 - 3^4 - 3^7 + 6^6 - 2^1$	$43565 := -4^3 - 3^3 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^5$
$42978 := -4^1 - 2^5 - 9^4 + 7^5 + 8^5$	$43363 := -4^5 - 3^0 - 3^4 + 6^6 - 3^7$	$43566 := -4^1 + 3^1 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 6^6$

$43567 := -4^1 - 3^2 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^2$	$43898 := -4^4 + 3^6 + 8^4 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$44465 := -4^6 + 4^4 + 4^5 + 6^6 + 5^4$
$43568 := -4^5 - 3^6 + 5^7 - 6^2 - 8^5$	$43922 := -4^7 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 2^4 + 2^9$	$44556 := -4^1 + 4^5 - 5^5 + 5^1 + 6^6$
$43569 := -4^2 - 3^3 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 9^2$	$43926 := -4^7 - 3^1 + 9^5 - 2^5 + 6^4$	$44558 := -4^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 5^6 + 8^5$
$43583 := -4^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^4 + 3^9$	$43942 := -4^7 - 3^1 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 2^8$	$44574 := -4^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 7^5 + 4^8$
$43584 := -4^4 - 3^7 - 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^7$	$43943 := -4^6 + 3^7 - 9^0 + 4^8 - 3^9$	$44576 := -4^5 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 7^1 + 6^6$
$43606 := -4^5 - 3^6 - 6^4 - 0^0 + 6^6$	$43944 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 4^5$	$44579 := -4^7 - 4^7 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^3$
$43607 := -4^8 - 3^6 - 6^5 - 0^0 + 7^6$	$43945 := -4^7 + 3^6 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 5^4$	$44588 := -4^4 - 4^0 + 5^7 - 8^3 - 8^5$
$43635 := -4^1 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 3^4 - 5^5$	$43960 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 0^1$	$44597 := -4^4 - 4^7 + 5^7 - 9^2 - 7^5$
$43649 := -4^7 + 3^6 - 6^0 + 4^4 + 9^5$	$43961 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 1^0$	$44598 := -4^5 + 4^4 + 5^7 + 9^1 - 8^5$
$43652 := -4^1 - 3^1 + 6^6 - 5^5 + 2^7$	$43962 := -4^1 - 3^7 + 9^1 + 6^6 - 2^9$	$44604 := -4^1 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 0^1 - 4^5$
$43655 := -4^1 + 3^1 + 6^6 + 5^3 - 5^5$	$43963 := -4^7 + 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 3^0$	$44606 := -4^5 - 4^5 - 6^0 - 0^0 + 6^6$
$43656 := -4^3 - 3^3 + 6^3 - 5^5 + 6^6$	$43964 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 4^1$	$44607 := -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 0^1 - 7^0$
$43657 := -4^6 + 3^6 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 7^3$	$43965 := -4^5 + 3^6 + 9^3 + 6^6 - 5^5$	$44608 := -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 0^0 - 8^0$
$43658 := -4^4 + 3^6 + 6^6 + 5^4 - 8^4$	$43966 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 6^4$	$44609 := -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 9^0$
$43660 := -4^5 - 3^7 + 6^3 + 6^6 - 0^0$	$43967 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 7^1$	$44610 := -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 0^0$
$43662 := -4^5 - 3^7 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 2^0$	$43968 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 8^1$	$44622 := -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 - 2^1 + 2^4$
$43664 := -4^6 + 3^4 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$43969 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^1 + 6^4 + 9^5$	$44623 := -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 2^4 - 3^0$
$43672 := -4^8 - 3^6 - 6^5 + 7^6 + 2^6$	$44176 := -4^2 - 4^3 + 1^0 - 7^4 + 6^6$	$44624 := -4^2 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 2^5 - 4^5$
$43678 := -4^3 - 3^0 + 6^6 - 7^4 - 8^3$	$44236 := -4^6 + 4^0 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$44625 := -4^2 - 4^8 - 6^7 - 2^9 + 5^8$
$43689 := -4^5 - 3^8 - 6^5 + 8^0 + 9^5$	$44267 := -4^1 - 4^2 + 2^5 + 6^6 - 7^4$	$44628 := -4^2 + 4^6 + 6^5 + 2^2 + 8^5$
$43692 := -4^2 - 3^7 + 6^6 - 9^3 - 2^5$	$44269 := -4^8 + 4^6 + 2^2 + 6^6 + 9^5$	$44634 := -4^5 - 4^0 + 6^6 + 3^3 - 4^5$
$43694 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 4^5$	$44285 := -4^1 - 4^6 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 5^6$	$44636 := -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 6^6$
$43695 := -4^5 - 3^0 + 6^4 + 9^5 - 5^6$	$44288 := -4^4 + 4^7 - 2^9 + 8^5 - 8^4$	$44637 := -4^6 + 4^8 + 6^0 + 3^1 - 7^5$
$43726 := -4^2 - 3^0 - 7^4 - 2^9 + 6^6$	$44318 := -4^5 + 4^8 - 3^9 + 1^0 - 8^3$	$44643 := -4^1 - 4^4 + 6^6 - 4^5 - 3^6$
$43762 := -4^2 - 3^9 + 7^5 + 6^6 - 2^1$	$44328 := -4^6 + 4^7 - 3^6 + 2^0 + 8^5$	$44645 := -4^2 - 4^5 + 6^6 - 4^6 + 5^5$
$43763 := -4^2 - 3^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^9$	$44355 := -4^8 + 4^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 5^7$	$44657 := -4^6 + 4^8 - 6^0 + 5^2 - 7^5$
$43765 := -4^2 + 3^5 + 7^1 + 6^6 - 5^5$	$44358 := -4^5 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 8^5$	$44665 := -4^7 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 6^6 + 5^6$
$43767 := -4^2 - 3^7 - 7^3 + 6^6 - 7^3$	$44364 := -4^5 - 4^0 - 3^5 + 6^6 - 4^5$	$44677 := -4^7 - 4^0 + 6^6 - 7^4 + 7^5$
$43768 := -4^1 - 3^9 + 7^5 + 6^6 - 8^1$	$44366 := -4^5 - 4^5 - 3^5 + 6^0 + 6^6$	$44687 := -4^2 - 4^3 + 6^6 + 8^3 - 7^4$
$43769 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 7^4 - 6^4 + 9^5$	$44374 := -4^2 - 4^6 - 3^5 - 7^5 + 4^8$	$44688 := -4^2 + 4^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 + 8^5$
$43784 := -4^3 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 8^4 + 4^7$	$44395 := -4^7 + 4^5 + 3^4 + 9^5 + 5^4$	$44690 := -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 0^0$
$43789 := -4^2 - 3^9 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$44397 := -4^2 - 4^2 + 3^7 + 9^5 - 7^5$	$44706 := -4^4 - 4^6 + 7^4 + 0^0 + 6^6$
$43835 := -4^3 - 3^6 - 8^5 - 3^6 + 5^7$	$44398 := -4^5 + 4^8 - 3^9 + 9^2 - 8^3$	$44714 := -4^6 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 1^0 + 4^8$
$43866 := -4^6 + 3^2 + 8^0 + 6^4 + 6^6$	$44425 := -4^6 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 5^6$	$44736 := -4^1 - 4^6 - 7^1 + 3^7 + 6^6$
$43895 := -4^1 - 3^6 - 8^5 - 9^3 + 5^7$	$44436 := -4^2 - 4^0 - 4^2 - 3^7 + 6^6$	$44739 := -4^3 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 3^7 + 9^5$
$43896 := -4^5 - 3^8 + 8^4 + 9^3 + 6^6$	$44463 := -4^1 - 4^0 - 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^7$	$44752 := -4^6 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 5^6 + 2^5$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| $44754 := -4^1 - 4^6 - 7^5 + 5^3 + 4^8$ | $45256 := -4^5 - 5^3 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6$ | $45420 := -4^7 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 2^6 - 0^0$ |
| $44756 := -4^6 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$ | $45258 := -4^4 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 5^7 - 8^5$ | $45422 := -4^7 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 2^0 + 2^6$ |
| $44757 := -4^6 + 4^8 - 7^0 + 5^3 - 7^5$ | $45259 := -4^7 - 5^6 - 2^7 + 5^7 - 9^3$ | $45433 := -4^5 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 3^6 - 3^9$ |
| $44758 := -4^4 - 4^8 - 7^3 + 5^7 + 8^5$ | $45262 := -4^4 - 5^4 - 2^0 + 6^6 - 2^9$ | $45434 := -4^1 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 3^4 - 4^7$ |
| $44759 := -4^4 - 4^7 - 7^5 + 5^7 + 9^2$ | $45263 := -4^5 - 5^3 - 2^0 + 6^6 - 3^5$ | $45436 := -4^1 - 5^5 + 4^6 - 3^7 + 6^6$ |
| $44762 := -4^1 - 4^0 - 7^4 + 6^6 + 2^9$ | $45264 := -4^4 - 5^4 - 2^9 + 6^6 + 4^0$ | $45437 := -4^7 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 3^4 - 7^0$ |
| $44794 := -4^2 - 4^4 + 7^4 + 9^5 - 4^7$ | $45276 := -4^5 - 5^1 - 2^3 - 7^3 + 6^6$ | $45438 := -4^1 + 5^7 + 4^1 + 3^4 - 8^5$ |
| $44823 := -4^5 + 4^8 - 8^1 + 2^1 - 3^9$ | $45278 := -4^2 + 5^7 - 2^6 + 7^0 - 8^5$ | $45439 := -4^5 - 5^7 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 9^5$ |
| $44825 := -4^1 - 4^2 - 8^5 - 2^9 + 5^7$ | $45279 := -4^7 + 5^5 - 2^9 + 7^0 + 9^5$ | $45453 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 - 3^9$ |
| $44833 := -4^5 + 4^8 + 8^0 + 3^1 - 3^9$ | $45294 := -4^6 - 5^6 - 2^9 - 9^1 + 4^8$ | $45463 := -4^4 - 5^5 + 4^0 + 6^6 + 3^7$ |
| $44845 := -4^4 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 4^8 + 5^7$ | $45296 := -4^1 - 5^4 - 2^1 - 9^3 + 6^6$ | $45471 := -4^6 - 5^6 + 4^8 - 7^3 - 1^0$ |
| $44853 := -4^5 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 5^2 - 3^9$ | $45297 := -4^2 - 5^6 - 2^9 + 9^5 + 7^4$ | $45472 := -4^1 - 5^5 + 4^8 - 7^5 - 2^7$ |
| $44862 := -4^4 - 4^5 - 8^3 + 6^6 - 2^1$ | $45298 := -4^1 + 5^7 - 2^6 + 9^1 - 8^5$ | $45473 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 7^0 - 3^9$ |
| $44863 := -4^4 - 4^5 - 8^3 + 6^6 - 3^0$ | $45299 := -4^6 - 5^5 + 2^5 - 9^4 + 9^5$ | $45474 := -4^6 - 5^1 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 4^7$ |
| $44864 := -4^4 - 4^5 + 8^3 + 6^6 - 4^5$ | $45324 := -4^2 - 5^0 - 3^9 - 2^9 + 4^8$ | $45475 := -4^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 - 7^5 - 5^5$ |
| $44865 := -4^4 - 4^5 - 8^3 + 6^6 + 5^0$ | $45326 := -4^3 - 5^2 - 3^6 - 2^9 + 6^6$ | $45478 := -4^6 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 7^5 - 8^5$ |
| $44887 := -4^6 + 4^7 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 7^3$ | $45328 := -4^1 + 5^7 - 3^3 + 2^1 - 8^5$ | $45493 := -4^7 + 5^4 + 4^2 + 9^5 + 3^7$ |
| $44932 := -4^7 + 4^2 + 9^5 + 3^7 + 2^6$ | $45342 := -4^1 + 5^1 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 2^9$ | $45498 := -4^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 9^2 - 8^5$ |
| $44953 := -4^5 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 5^3 - 3^9$ | $45346 := -4^1 + 5^4 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 6^6$ | $45506 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 5^3 + 0^1 + 6^6$ |
| $44966 := -4^5 + 4^3 - 9^3 + 6^6 - 6^0$ | $45347 := -4^4 - 5^5 - 3^0 + 4^8 - 7^5$ | $45523 := -4^7 - 5^6 + 5^7 - 2^9 - 3^4$ |
| $44967 := -4^2 - 4^0 + 9^3 + 6^6 - 7^4$ | $45348 := -4^1 + 5^7 - 3^2 + 4^1 - 8^5$ | $45529 := -4^5 + 5^5 - 5^6 + 2^2 + 9^5$ |
| $44968 := -4^5 + 4^0 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 8^2$ | $45362 := -4^1 - 5^4 - 3^6 + 6^6 + 2^6$ | $45546 := -4^5 - 5^2 - 5^3 + 4^3 + 6^6$ |
| $44974 := -4^6 - 4^7 - 9^2 - 7^0 + 4^8$ | $45363 := -4^5 + 5^0 - 3^3 + 6^6 - 3^5$ | $45548 := -4^3 - 5^0 + 5^7 + 4^4 - 8^5$ |
| $44976 := -4^1 - 4^1 + 9^3 - 7^4 + 6^6$ | $45364 := -4^1 - 5^3 - 3^7 + 6^6 + 4^5$ | $45560 := -4^6 - 5^3 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 0^1$ |
| $44977 := -4^6 + 4^8 + 9^0 + 7^3 - 7^5$ | $45365 := -4^5 + 5^0 - 3^5 + 6^6 - 5^2$ | $45561 := -4^6 - 5^3 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 1^0$ |
| $44986 := -4^7 + 4^5 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 6^4$ | $45366 := -4^1 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 6^6 - 6^4$ | $45562 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 2^6$ |
| $45006 := -4^5 - 5^4 - 0^0 + 0^1 + 6^6$ | $45368 := -4^1 + 5^4 + 3^7 + 6^6 - 8^4$ | $45563 := -4^5 - 5^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 3^4$ |
| $45169 := -4^7 + 5^6 + 1^0 + 6^6 - 9^3$ | $45382 := -4^8 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 2^4$ | $45564 := -4^3 + 5^0 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 4^5$ |
| $45183 := -4^5 + 5^6 + 1^0 + 8^5 - 3^7$ | $45383 := -4^8 + 5^7 - 3^0 + 8^5 + 3^3$ | $45565 := -4^6 + 5^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 5^5$ |
| $45228 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 2^0 + 2^7 - 8^5$ | $45384 := -4^6 - 5^6 + 3^4 - 8^3 + 4^8$ | $45566 := -4^5 - 5^1 - 5^2 - 6^2 + 6^6$ |
| $45234 := -4^7 - 5^5 - 2^6 - 3^6 + 4^8$ | $45385 := -4^8 + 5^0 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 5^7$ | $45567 := -4^6 - 5^3 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^1$ |
| $45236 := -4^3 - 5^4 - 2^1 - 3^6 + 6^6$ | $45386 := -4^1 - 5^2 - 3^6 - 8^3 + 6^6$ | $45568 := -4^1 - 5^0 + 5^7 + 6^3 - 8^5$ |
| $45238 := -4^3 + 5^7 - 2^6 + 3^2 - 8^5$ | $45388 := -4^1 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 8^1 - 8^5$ | $45569 := -4^4 - 5^3 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 9^2$ |
| $45239 := -4^7 - 5^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 9^5$ | $45389 := -4^7 + 5^2 + 3^7 + 8^3 + 9^5$ | $45583 := -4^2 - 5^0 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^5$ |
| $45246 := -4^5 + 5^3 - 2^9 + 4^0 + 6^6$ | $45407 := -4^7 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 0^0 + 7^2$ | $45584 := -4^1 - 5^2 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 4^4$ |
| $45254 := -4^6 - 5^4 + 2^6 - 5^6 + 4^8$ | $45418 := -4^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 1^0 - 8^5$ | $45586 := -4^4 - 5^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 + 6^6$ |

$45588 := -4^4 - 5^2 + 5^7 + 8^3 - 8^5$	$45644 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 4^2$	$45693 := -4^2 - 5^5 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 3^7$
$45589 := -4^5 + 5^5 - 5^6 + 8^2 + 9^5$	$45646 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 6^0 + 4^2 + 6^6$	$45694 := -4^3 + 5^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 - 4^5$
$45602 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 0^0 - 2^5$	$45648 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^2 - 8^0$	$45695 := -4^4 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 9^3 + 5^2$
$45603 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 0^0 - 3^3$	$45648 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^0$	$45697 := -4^7 + 5^4 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 7^4$
$45604 := -4^1 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 0^0 - 4^5$	$45649 := -4^5 + 5^2 + 6^6 + 4^0 - 9^1$	$45698 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 8^2$
$45605 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 0^0 - 5^2$	$45650 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 0^1$	$45699 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 9^2$
$45606 := -4^5 - 5^2 - 6^0 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$45651 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 1^0$	$45706 := -4^5 + 5^2 + 7^2 + 0^1 + 6^6$
$45607 := -4^5 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 7^0$	$45652 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 2^1$	$45726 := -4^1 + 5^6 - 7^5 + 2^8 + 6^6$
$45608 := -4^5 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 8^0$	$45653 := -4^3 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 5^5 + 3^7$	$45728 := -4^1 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 2^5 - 8^5$
$45609 := -4^5 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 0^0 + 9^0$	$45654 := -4^1 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 5^2 - 4^5$	$45729 := -4^3 - 5^6 + 7^4 - 2^5 + 9^5$
$45612 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 1^0 - 2^4$	$45655 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 5^1 - 5^4$	$45743 := -4^3 - 5^7 + 7^6 + 4^6 + 3^7$
$45614 := -4^2 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 1^0 - 4^5$	$45656 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^1 - 5^4 + 6^6$	$45744 := -4^3 - 5^6 - 7^1 - 4^6 + 4^8$
$45618 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 1^0 - 8^1$	$45657 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$45745 := -4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3 + 4^8 - 5^5$
$45619 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 1^0 - 9^1$	$45658 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 8^1$	$45746 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 7^2 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$45620 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 2^3 + 0^0$	$45659 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 9^1$	$45748 := -4^2 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 4^3 - 8^5$
$45622 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 2^3$	$45662 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 2^5$	$45762 := -4^3 + 5^2 - 7^3 + 6^6 - 2^9$
$45623 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 2^0 - 3^2$	$45663 := -4^5 + 5^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^3$	$45763 := -4^1 - 5^5 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 3^7$
$45624 := -4^1 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 2^0 - 4^5$	$45664 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$45764 := -4^1 - 5^4 - 7^1 + 6^6 - 4^4$
$45625 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 5^1$	$45666 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 6^0 + 6^2 + 6^6$	$45765 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 5^3$
$45626 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 6^0 - 2^2 + 6^6$	$45668 := -4^2 + 5^5 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 8^4$	$45767 := -4^4 - 5^4 - 7^0 + 6^6 - 7^1$
$45627 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 2^0 - 7^1$	$45669 := -4^4 - 5^0 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 9^3$	$45768 := -4^4 - 5^4 + 7^0 + 6^6 - 8^1$
$45628 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 2^1 - 8^0$	$45671 := -4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 1^0$	$45769 := -4^4 - 5^4 - 7^1 + 6^6 + 9^0$
$45629 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 9^0$	$45672 := -4^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 2^9$	$45786 := -4^5 - 5^3 + 7^3 - 8^2 + 6^6$
$45630 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 0^1$	$45673 := -4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^3 + 3^0$	$45788 := -4^7 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^1 - 8^5$
$45631 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 1^0$	$45674 := -4^5 + 5^2 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 4^2$	$45790 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 - 0^0$
$45632 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 2^1$	$45675 := -4^4 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 5^5$	$45790 := -4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 + 9^5 + 0^0$
$45633 := -4^1 - 5^5 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 3^7$	$45676 := -4^5 + 5^0 - 6^1 + 7^2 + 6^6$	$45792 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 2^0$
$45634 := -4^1 + 5^1 + 6^6 + 3^0 - 4^5$	$45677 := -4^1 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^1 - 7^3$	$45796 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^5 - 6^0$
$45635 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 3^0 + 5^0$	$45678 := -4^2 + 5^7 - 6^1 + 7^3 - 8^5$	$45798 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 8^0$
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$45637 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 7^1$	$45682 := -4^6 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 8^0 - 2^2$	$45830 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^6 + 0^1$
$45638 := -4^2 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 3^7 - 8^2$	$45683 := -4^6 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 8^0 - 3^1$	$45831 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^6 + 1^0$
$45639 := -4^4 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 3^3 - 9^3$	$45685 := -4^6 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 5^5$	$45832 := -4^3 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^3 + 2^9$
$45640 := -4^5 + 5^1 + 6^6 + 4^1 - 0^0$	$45687 := -4^5 + 5^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 7^2$	$45833 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^1 + 3^6$
$45642 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 2^3$	$45689 := -4^5 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 9^2$	$45834 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^6 + 4^1$
$45643 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 3^2$	$45692 := -4^4 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 9^2 - 2^1$	$45835 := -4^4 + 5^1 - 8^5 + 3^6 + 5^7$

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$45837 := -4^4 - 5^7 + 8^1 + 3^8 + 7^6$	$45968 := -4^3 - 5^4 + 9^1 + 6^6 - 8^1$	$46234 := -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 3^6 + 4^0$
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$45852 := -4^2 - 5^0 - 8^5 + 5^7 + 2^9$	$45986 := -4^1 - 5^0 - 9^3 + 8^2 + 6^6$	$46246 := -4^4 - 6^3 - 2^1 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$45854 := -4^3 + 5^4 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^3$	$45987 := -4^1 + 5^6 - 9^0 + 8^5 - 7^4$	$46247 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 7^3$
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$45859 := -4^7 + 5^1 + 8^2 + 5^5 + 9^5$	$46025 := -4^7 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 2^7 + 5^6$	$46250 := -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^3 + 5^4 + 0^0$
$45862 := -4^4 - 5^2 - 8^0 + 6^6 - 2^9$	$46035 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 3^2 - 5^4$	$46252 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 5^3 - 2^9$
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$45863 := -4^3 - 5^0 + 8^0 + 6^6 - 3^6$	$46075 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 7^2 - 5^4$	$46254 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 2^0 + 5^4 - 4^5$
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$45876 := -4^3 - 5^5 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 6^6$	$46128 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 1^0 + 2^0 - 8^3$	$46258 := -4^5 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 5^4 - 8^0$
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$45926 := -4^1 + 5^0 - 9^3 + 2^1 + 6^6$	$46178 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 7^2 - 8^3$	$46272 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 7^0 - 2^7$
$45942 := -4^6 - 5^6 - 9^0 + 4^8 + 2^7$	$46186 := -4^4 - 6^3 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^6$	$46274 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 7^0 + 4^0$
$45943 := -4^2 + 5^2 + 9^2 + 4^8 - 3^9$	$46204 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 0^1 + 4^3$	$46275 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 7^0 - 5^3$
$45945 := -4^7 - 5^0 - 9^2 + 4^8 - 5^5$	$46205 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 0^1 + 5^3$	$46276 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 2^5 - 7^3 + 6^6$
$45946 := -4^8 + 5^8 + 9^3 + 4^3 - 6^7$	$46208 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 2^7 + 0^1 - 8^3$	$46278 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 7^1 - 8^0$
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$45964 := -4^1 + 5^2 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 4^2$	$46227 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 2^2 - 7^2$	$46284 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 8^1 + 4^1$
$45965 := -4^3 - 5^0 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 5^4$	$46229 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 9^2$	$46285 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 8^1 - 5^3$

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$46288 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 8^1 + 8^1$	$46355 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 5^1$	$46397 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 9^0 - 7^0$
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$46319 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 1^0 - 9^2$	$46363 := -4^4 - 6^0 - 3^2 + 6^6 - 3^3$	$46406 := -4^4 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 6^6$
$46320 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 0^1$	$46364 := -4^3 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 6^6 - 4^4$	$46407 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 7^1$
$46321 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 1^0$	$46365 := -4^4 - 6^0 - 3^2 + 6^6 - 5^2$	$46408 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 8^1$
$46322 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 2^1$	$46366 := -4^3 - 6^0 - 3^2 - 6^3 + 6^6$	$46409 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 9^1$
$46323 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 2^0 - 3^5$	$46367 := -4^4 + 6^0 - 3^3 + 6^6 - 7^1$	$46416 := -4^4 - 6^0 + 4^2 + 1^0 + 6^6$
$46324 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 4^1$	$46368 := -4^3 - 6^3 - 3^2 + 6^6 + 8^0$	$46418 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 1^0 + 8^0$
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$46327 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 7^1$	$46373 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 7^0 - 3^3$	$46422 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 2^4$
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$46334 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 3^0 - 4^3$	$46380 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 8^1 - 0^0$	$46427 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^4 + 2^5 - 7^0$
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$46349 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 4^0 - 9^0$	$46391 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 9^0 - 1^0$	$46437 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 3^7 - 7^4$
$46350 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^1$	$46392 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 9^1 - 2^9$	$46444 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^2 + 4^3 - 4^4$
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$46448 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 4^4 - 8^3$	$46523 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 2^0 - 3^5$	$46565 := -4^3 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 5^2$
$46449 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 4^4 + 4^3 + 9^0$	$46524 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 2^0 - 4^1$	$46567 := -4^2 + 6^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^2$
$46453 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 5^2 + 3^3$	$46525 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 2^0 + 5^3$	$46569 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 9^2$
$46462 := -4^3 - 6^0 - 4^0 + 6^6 - 2^7$	$46526 := -4^2 - 6^0 - 5^4 + 2^9 + 6^6$	$46572 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 7^2 - 2^7$
$46464 := -4^4 + 6^0 - 4^0 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$46527 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 2^0 - 7^0$	$46573 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 7^0 - 3^4$
$46464 := -4^4 - 6^0 + 4^0 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$46528 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 2^1 - 8^0$	$46575 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 7^2 - 5^3$
$46465 := -4^1 - 6^3 + 4^1 + 6^6 + 5^2$	$46529 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 9^0$	$46577 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 7^0 + 7^2$
$46466 := -4^4 + 6^0 + 4^3 + 6^0 + 6^6$	$46530 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 0^1$	$46578 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 7^0 - 8^2$
$46469 := -4^4 + 6^1 + 4^3 + 6^6 - 9^0$	$46531 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 1^0$	$46579 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 7^1 - 9^2$
$46470 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 7^1 - 0^0$	$46532 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 3^2 - 2^7$	$46580 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 8^2 + 0^0$
$46472 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 7^3 - 2^9$	$46533 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 3^1$	$46582 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 8^0 - 2^6$
$46475 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 7^1 - 5^3$	$46534 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 4^1$	$46583 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 8^0 - 3^2$
$46480 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 0^1$	$46535 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 3^2 - 5^3$	$46584 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^1 + 8^0 - 4^3$
$46481 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 1^0$	$46536 := -4^1 + 6^1 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 6^6$	$46586 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 5^0 - 8^2 + 6^6$
$46482 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 2^1$	$46537 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 7^1$	$46587 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^1 + 8^0 - 7^2$
$46483 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 3^4$	$46538 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 8^1$	$46588 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 8^0 - 8^2$
$46484 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 4^2$	$46539 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 9^1$	$46589 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 5^1 + 8^0 + 9^0$
$46485 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^4 + 8^2 + 5^2$	$46540 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 4^2 - 0^0$	$46591 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 9^0 - 1^0$
$46486 := -4^4 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 6^6$	$46542 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 4^2 - 2^0$	$46592 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^1 + 9^1 - 2^6$
$46487 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 4^3 + 8^1 - 7^2$	$46543 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 4^0 + 3^3$	$46593 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 9^1 - 3^4$
$46488 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 8^2$	$46544 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 4^0 + 4^2$	$46594 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 9^0 - 4^3$
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$46508 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 0^0 - 8^1$	$46554 := -4^2 - 6^3 - 5^5 - 5^6 + 4^8$	$46600 := -4^3 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 0^0 + 0^0$
$46512 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 1^0 - 2^4$	$46555 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 5^2 + 5^3$	$46602 := -4^2 - 6^1 + 6^6 + 0^1 - 2^5$
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$46515 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 1^0 - 5^3$	$46558 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 5^2 - 8^2$	$46605 := -4^2 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 5^0$
$46517 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 1^0 + 7^0$	$46559 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 5^0 - 9^2$	$46606 := -4^2 + 6^0 - 6^2 + 0^0 + 6^6$
$46518 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 1^0 - 8^1$	$46560 := -4^1 - 6^3 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 0^0$	$46608 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 0^1 - 8^1$
$46519 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 1^0 - 9^1$	$46562 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 2^6$	$46613 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 1^0 - 3^3$
$46520 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 2^2 + 0^0$	$46563 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 3^4$	$46614 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 - 1^0 - 4^0$
$46522 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 2^0 - 2^8$	$46564 := -4^1 + 6^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 4^3$	$46615 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 1^0 - 5^2$

$46616 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 6^2 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$46654 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 4^1$	$46698 := -4^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 8^0$
$46618 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 8^0$	$46655 := -4^1 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 5^0$	$46700 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 0^1 - 0^0$
$46620 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 2^5 + 0^0$	$46656 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^1 - 5^0 + 6^6$	$46701 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 0^0 - 1^0$
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$46623 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 3^3$	$46659 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 9^1$	$46704 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 0^0 + 4^3$
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$46625 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 5^2$	$46662 := -4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 2^3$	$46712 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 2^6$
$46626 := -4^1 + 6^1 - 6^2 + 2^2 + 6^6$	$46663 := -4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^2$	$46714 := -4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4 - 1^0 + 4^8$
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$46628 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 2^2 + 8^1$	$46668 := -4^3 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^2$	$46718 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 8^2$
$46629 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 - 2^3 - 9^1$	$46669 := -4^2 - 6^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 - 9^0$	$46720 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 2^5 - 0^0$
$46630 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 0^1$	$46672 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 2^5$	$46722 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^6 - 2^0$
$46631 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 1^0$	$46673 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^2 - 3^3$	$46723 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 3^4$
$46632 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^1 - 2^4$	$46674 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 4^2$	$46724 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^0 + 4^3$
$46633 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^2 - 3^2$	$46675 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 5^2$	$46725 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^0 + 5^3$
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$46635 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^2 - 5^2$	$46678 := -4^2 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 8^0$	$46728 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 8^0$
$46636 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 6^1 - 3^2 + 6^6$	$46679 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^2 - 9^1$	$46729 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^0 + 9^2$
$46637 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 - 7^0$	$46680 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 0^1$	$46731 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 3^4 - 1^0$
$46638 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 8^0$	$46681 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 1^0$	$46732 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 3^4 - 2^1$
$46639 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^1 - 9^1$	$46682 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 8^0 + 2^5$	$46733 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 3^0 + 3^4$
$46640 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 0^1$	$46683 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 - 3^3$	$46735 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 3^4 + 5^0$
$46641 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 - 4^1 - 1^0$	$46684 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 4^1$	$46736 := -4^4 - 6^1 + 7^3 - 3^0 + 6^6$
$46642 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 4^0 - 2^3$	$46685 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 - 5^2$	$46737 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 7^2 + 3^5 - 7^2$
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$46647 := -4^1 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 - 7^1$	$46690 := -4^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^0$	$46744 := -4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4 - 4^0 + 4^8$
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$46649 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 4^0 - 9^0$	$46693 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 9^2 - 3^3$	$46746 := -4^4 - 6^0 + 7^3 + 4^1 + 6^6$
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$46652 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 2^1$	$46696 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 6^6$	$46752 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 5^3 - 2^5$
$46653 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 3^0$	$46697 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2$	$46753 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 5^2 + 3^3$

$46754 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 7^1 + 5^3 - 4^2$	$46841 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 4^4 + 1^0$	$46932 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^3 + 2^8$
$46757 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 5^3 - 7^1$	$46842 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 8^2 + 4^4 - 2^1$	$46933 := -4^6 - 6^5 + 9^5 - 3^0 - 3^5$
$46758 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 7^1 + 5^4 - 8^3$	$46843 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 8^2 + 4^4 - 3^0$	$46934 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 3^3 + 4^4$
$46759 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 5^2 + 9^2$	$46844 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 4^3 + 4^3$	$46935 := -4^6 - 6^5 + 9^5 - 3^5 + 5^0$
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$46782 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 2^7$	$46860 := -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 0^1$	$46962 := -4^6 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 6^5 + 2^0$
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$46798 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 9^2 + 8^2$	$46865 := -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 5^1$	$46973 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 7^3 - 3^2$
$46807 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 0^1 + 7^3$	$46866 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 8^0 + 6^3 + 6^6$	$46975 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 7^3 + 5^0$
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$46824 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 2^7 + 4^3$	$46868 := -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^0 + 6^6 + 8^0$	$46978 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 7^3 - 8^1$
$46825 := -4^2 - 6^4 + 8^5 - 2^8 + 5^6$	$46869 := -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 9^1$	$46987 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 8^0 + 7^3$
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$46830 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 8^2 + 3^5 - 0^0$	$46876 := -4^1 + 6^3 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 6^6$	$46997 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 7^3$
$46832 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 3^5 - 2^6$	$46883 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 8^0 + 8^0 + 3^5$	$47026 := -4^1 + 7^3 - 0^0 + 2^5 + 6^6$
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$46835 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 3^5 - 5^0$	$46912 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 2^9$	$47062 := -4^3 + 7^3 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 2^7$
$46835 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^0 + 3^5 + 5^0$	$46920 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 2^9 - 0^0$	$47063 := -4^2 + 7^3 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 3^4$
$46836 := -4^3 + 6^3 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 6^6$	$46922 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 2^0 + 2^9$	$47064 := -4^2 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 6^6 - 4^7$
$46837 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 3^5 + 7^0$	$46927 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 2^0 + 7^3$	$47069 := -4^7 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 6^6 - 9^1$
$46840 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 4^4 + 0^1$	$46928 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 2^8 - 8^0$	$47086 := -4^7 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 8^1 + 6^6$

$47162 := -4^1 - 7^0 - 1^0 + 6^6 + 2^9$	$47458 := -4^6 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 8^5$	$47664 := -4^2 - 7^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^5$
$47169 := -4^6 - 7^1 - 1^0 - 6^5 + 9^5$	$47463 := -4^5 - 7^5 + 4^8 + 6^0 - 3^5$	$47674 := -4^1 - 7^0 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 4^5$
$47236 := -4^1 + 7^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 6^6$	$47473 := -4^7 - 7^1 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 3^6$	$47684 := -4^1 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 4^5$
$47256 := -4^1 + 7^3 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6$	$47475 := -4^7 - 7^4 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 5^5$	$47692 := -4^1 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^3 - 2^5$
$47264 := -4^7 - 7^4 + 2^9 + 6^0 + 4^8$	$47478 := -4^5 - 7^2 - 4^5 + 7^5 + 8^5$	$47696 := -4^4 - 7^0 + 6^4 + 9^0 + 6^6$
$47265 := -4^2 + 7^0 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 5^4$	$47479 := -4^7 - 7^0 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 9^3$	$47697 := -4^7 - 7^3 + 6^5 + 9^5 - 7^4$
$47265 := -4^2 - 7^0 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 5^4$	$47495 := -4^2 - 7^4 + 4^8 + 9^0 - 5^6$	$47704 := -4^5 - 7^0 - 7^5 + 0^1 + 4^8$
$47276 := -4^3 + 7^3 - 2^1 + 7^3 + 6^6$	$47526 := -4^1 - 7^1 + 5^4 + 2^8 + 6^6$	$47743 := -4^4 - 7^0 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 3^6$
$47296 := -4^3 + 7^1 - 2^5 + 9^3 + 6^6$	$47543 := -4^7 - 7^0 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 3^7$	$47745 := -4^2 - 7^3 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 5^4$
$47324 := -4^7 + 7^3 - 3^7 + 2^4 + 4^8$	$47546 := -4^2 + 7^1 - 5^3 + 4^5 + 6^6$	$47747 := -4^5 - 7^1 + 7^2 + 4^8 - 7^5$
$47326 := -4^3 + 7^0 + 3^6 + 2^2 + 6^6$	$47560 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 0^1$	$47763 := -4^5 - 7^1 - 7^2 + 6^6 + 3^7$
$47328 := -4^3 + 7^5 - 3^7 + 2^2 + 8^5$	$47561 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 1^0$	$47784 := -4^5 - 7^0 - 7^3 + 8^5 + 4^7$
$47346 := -4^2 - 7^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^6$	$47562 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 2^1$	$47823 := -4^5 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 2^0 - 3^6$
$47361 := -4^2 - 7^1 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 1^0$	$47563 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 3^1$	$47835 := -4^1 + 7^4 - 8^5 + 3^4 + 5^7$
$47362 := -4^2 + 7^0 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 2^3$	$47564 := -4^3 + 7^0 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 4^6$	$47855 := -4^4 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 - 5^4$
$47363 := -4^2 - 7^1 + 3^0 + 6^6 + 3^6$	$47565 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 + 5^4$	$47858 := -4^2 - 7^1 - 8^3 + 5^6 + 8^5$
$47364 := -4^1 - 7^0 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 4^2$	$47566 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^1 + 6^6$	$47872 := -4^6 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 7^5 - 2^3$
$47365 := -4^1 + 7^1 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 5^4$	$47567 := -4^3 + 7^1 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 7^3$	$47874 := -4^5 - 7^3 + 8^3 - 7^5 + 4^8$
$47367 := -4^1 - 7^1 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 7^1$	$47568 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^1$	$47875 := -4^6 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 7^5 - 5^1$
$47368 := -4^2 + 7^1 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 8^1$	$47569 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 9^1$	$47879 := -4^6 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 7^5 - 9^0$
$47369 := -4^2 + 7^0 - 3^0 + 6^6 + 9^3$	$47583 := -4^5 + 7^4 + 5^6 + 8^5 - 3^7$	$47947 := -4^1 - 7^2 - 9^3 + 4^8 - 7^5$
$47369 := -4^2 - 7^0 + 3^0 + 6^6 + 9^3$	$47585 := -4^7 - 7^2 + 5^6 + 8^5 + 5^6$	$47965 := -4^3 + 7^6 + 9^3 + 6^5 - 5^7$
$47382 := -4^1 + 7^5 - 3^7 + 8^5 - 2^1$	$47586 := -4^4 + 7^2 + 5^4 + 8^3 + 6^6$	$47968 := -4^5 + 7^4 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 8^2$
$47383 := -4^1 + 7^5 - 3^0 + 8^5 - 3^7$	$47606 := -4^1 - 7^3 + 6^4 + 0^0 + 6^6$	$47985 := -4^3 - 7^3 - 9^0 + 8^5 + 5^6$
$47385 := -4^1 + 7^5 - 3^7 + 8^5 + 5^0$	$47614 := -4^2 - 7^2 + 6^6 - 1^0 + 4^5$	$48017 := -4^8 - 8^4 + 0^0 - 1^0 + 7^6$
$47386 := -4^3 + 7^0 + 3^6 + 8^2 + 6^6$	$47624 := -4^3 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 2^0 + 4^5$	$48017 := -4^8 - 8^4 - 0^0 + 1^0 + 7^6$
$47388 := -4^3 + 7^5 - 3^7 + 8^2 + 8^5$	$47632 := -4^2 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 2^8$	$48096 := -4^5 - 8^4 - 0^0 + 9^4 + 6^6$
$47416 := -4^2 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 1^0 - 6^4$	$47635 := -4^2 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 3^3 + 5^4$	$48097 := -4^8 - 8^4 - 0^0 + 9^2 + 7^6$
$47426 := -4^4 + 7^0 + 4^5 + 2^0 + 6^6$	$47642 := -4^5 - 7^5 + 6^0 + 4^8 - 2^6$	$48152 := -4^4 + 8^5 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 2^4$
$47445 := -4^3 - 7^4 - 4^0 + 4^8 - 5^6$	$47646 := -4^4 - 7^2 + 6^4 - 4^0 + 6^6$	$48154 := -4^4 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 4^2$
$47448 := -4^4 - 7^5 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 8^0$	$47652 := -4^1 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 5^4 + 2^5$	$48224 := -4^5 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 2^6 + 4^7$
$47452 := -4^5 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 5^3 - 2^7$	$47656 := -4^1 + 7^3 + 6^2 + 5^4 + 6^6$	$48243 := -4^5 + 8^5 - 2^7 + 4^7 + 3^5$
$47454 := -4^4 - 7^5 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 4^8$	$47657 := -4^2 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 5^4 + 7^3$	$48245 := -4^5 + 8^5 - 2^3 + 4^7 + 5^3$
$47455 := -4^5 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 5^3 - 5^3$	$47658 := -4^3 + 7^4 - 6^2 + 5^7 - 8^5$	$48248 := -4^5 - 8^1 + 2^7 + 4^7 + 8^5$
$47456 := -4^3 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$47663 := -4^3 + 7^3 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^6$	$48250 := -4^2 + 8^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 0^0$
$47457 := -4^1 - 7^2 + 4^8 - 5^6 - 7^4$	$47664 := -4^2 + 7^0 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$48254 := -4^5 + 8^5 + 2^0 + 5^3 + 4^7$

$48263 := -4^1 - 8^2 - 2^9 + 6^6 + 3^7$	$48383 := -4^6 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$48532 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 3^3 + 2^7$
$48267 := -4^8 - 8^4 + 2^8 - 6^1 + 7^6$	$48385 := -4^1 - 8^0 - 3^1 + 8^5 + 5^6$	$48533 := -4^3 + 8^5 - 5^5 + 3^9 - 3^6$
$48272 := -4^8 - 8^4 - 2^0 + 7^6 + 2^8$	$48389 := -4^1 - 8^4 - 3^8 + 8^0 + 9^5$	$48534 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 4^3$
$48274 := -4^6 + 8^0 + 2^8 + 7^6 - 4^8$	$48390 := -4^6 - 8^0 - 3^8 + 9^5 - 0^0$	$48535 := -4^3 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 3^4 + 5^6$
$48276 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 2^0 + 7^5 - 6^4$	$48392 := -4^1 - 8^4 - 3^8 + 9^5 + 2^2$	$48536 := -4^1 - 8^3 + 5^5 - 3^6 + 6^6$
$48283 := -4^3 - 8^4 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$48393 := -4^6 - 8^1 + 3^2 + 9^5 - 3^8$	$48539 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 9^2$
$48287 := -4^5 - 8^1 - 2^8 + 8^5 + 7^5$	$48394 := -4^6 + 8^0 - 3^8 + 9^5 + 4^0$	$48542 := -4^7 - 8^0 - 5^4 + 4^8 + 2^4$
$48294 := -4^7 - 8^0 - 2^7 - 9^3 + 4^8$	$48395 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 3^1 + 9^1 + 5^6$	$48544 := -4^7 + 8^0 - 5^4 + 4^2 + 4^8$
$48307 := -4^6 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 0^0 - 7^2$	$48396 := -4^2 - 8^3 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 6^6$	$48546 := -4^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 4^0 + 6^3$
$48316 := -4^2 - 8^3 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$48399 := -4^6 + 8^1 - 3^0 + 9^5 - 9^4$	$48547 := -4^5 + 8^5 - 5^1 + 4^0 + 7^5$
$48326 := -4^1 - 8^0 + 3^7 - 2^9 + 6^6$	$48405 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 5^6$	$48549 := -4^7 + 8^0 + 5^3 + 4^8 - 9^3$
$48329 := -4^3 - 8^4 - 3^8 + 2^0 + 9^5$	$48423 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 2^2 - 3^6$	$48554 := -4^5 - 8^5 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 4^6$
$48332 := -4^6 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 3^9 - 2^5$	$48425 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 2^5 + 5^6$	$48557 := -4^5 + 8^5 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 7^5$
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$48335 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 3^4 + 3^3 + 5^6$	$48433 := -4^7 + 8^0 + 4^8 + 3^2 - 3^6$	$48563 := -4^4 + 8^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 3^7$
$48336 := -4^1 - 8^3 + 3^2 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$48445 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 5^6$	$48564 := -4^7 + 8^0 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 4^8$
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$48355 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 5^2$	$48472 := -4^5 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 2^0$	$48596 := -4^3 + 8^3 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 6^5$
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$48362 := -4^6 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 2^0$	$48514 := -4^7 - 8^3 - 5^3 - 1^0 + 4^8$	$48637 := -4^4 + 8^0 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 7^2$
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$48375 := -4^2 + 8^5 - 3^1 + 7^0 + 5^6$	$48524 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 5^4 + 2^0 + 4^7$	$48640 := -4^7 - 8^3 - 6^0 + 4^8 + 0^0$
$48376 := -4^1 - 8^3 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 6^6$	$48527 := -4^5 + 8^5 - 5^2 + 2^0 + 7^5$	$48642 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 4^7 - 2^9$
$48378 := -4^8 - 8^5 + 3^7 - 7^6 + 8^6$	$48528 := -4^7 + 8^5 - 5^4 + 2^0 + 8^5$	$48643 := -4^4 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 3^7$

$48645 := -4^5 - 8^5 + 6^3 + 4^6 + 5^7$	$48824 := -4^3 - 8^1 + 8^5 - 2^8 + 4^7$	$49144 := -4^2 + 9^1 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 4^7$
$48647 := -4^7 - 8^3 + 6^1 + 4^8 + 7^0$	$48825 := -4^2 - 8^2 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 5^6$	$49145 := -4^7 - 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 5^1$
$48649 := -4^7 + 8^2 - 6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3$	$48836 := -4^2 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$49146 := -4^7 + 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 6^1$
$48653 := -4^3 - 8^0 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^7$	$48845 := -4^3 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 5^6$	$49146 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 6^1$
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$48663 := -4^3 + 8^4 - 6^4 + 6^6 - 3^6$	$48864 := -4^3 - 8^1 + 8^5 - 6^3 + 4^7$	$49148 := -4^1 + 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^7 + 8^5$
$48669 := -4^1 - 8^1 + 6^4 + 6^6 + 9^3$	$48865 := -4^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 5^6$	$49148 := -4^1 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 8^5$
$48672 := -4^4 - 8^0 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 2^7$	$48883 := -4^7 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 3^5$	$49149 := -4^7 - 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 9^0$
$48675 := -4^4 - 8^0 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 5^3$	$48894 := -4^4 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 9^0 + 4^7$	$49186 := -4^6 + 9^4 + 1^0 + 8^2 + 6^6$
$48684 := -4^7 - 8^3 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 4^8$	$48932 := -4^7 + 8^4 + 9^5 + 3^7 - 2^4$	$49214 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 2^6 - 1^0 + 4^8$
$48685 := -4^1 + 8^3 - 6^3 + 8^5 + 5^6$	$48939 := -4^7 + 8^4 - 9^1 + 3^7 + 9^5$	$49219 := -4^7 + 9^4 - 2^3 + 1^0 + 9^5$
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$48735 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 3^1 + 5^6$	$48954 := -4^7 - 8^2 - 9^1 - 5^3 + 4^8$	$49231 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 1^0$
$48736 := -4^4 - 8^2 + 7^4 - 3^0 + 6^6$	$48955 := -4^3 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 5^4 + 5^6$	$49232 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 2^2$
$48738 := -4^8 - 8^1 + 7^6 + 3^6 - 8^4$	$48956 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 9^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$49233 := -4^7 + 9^5 - 2^1 + 3^2 + 3^8$
$48742 := -4^1 + 8^0 - 7^5 + 4^8 + 2^4$	$48974 := -4^7 - 8^3 - 9^1 + 7^3 + 4^8$	$49234 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^8$
$48744 := -4^3 - 8^0 - 7^3 - 4^7 + 4^8$	$48976 := -4^2 - 8^2 - 9^0 + 7^4 + 6^6$	$49235 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^1$
$48746 := -4^3 + 8^5 - 7^3 + 4^7 + 6^0$	$48977 := -4^4 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 7^5 - 7^3$	$49236 := -4^6 + 9^4 - 2^7 + 3^5 + 6^6$
$48752 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 2^5$	$48978 := -4^1 - 8^3 - 9^2 + 7^5 + 8^5$	$49237 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^1$
$48753 := -4^3 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 3^4$	$48995 := -4^1 - 8^5 - 9^5 + 9^6 - 5^8$	$49238 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1$
$48754 := -4^3 + 8^2 - 7^5 + 5^2 + 4^8$	$48999 := -4^5 + 8^4 - 9^4 + 9^5 - 9^4$	$49239 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 9^5$
$48755 := -4^4 + 8^5 - 7^1 + 5^4 + 5^6$	$49024 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 0^0 - 2^7 + 4^8$	$49240 := -4^7 + 9^2 + 2^3 + 4^8 - 0^0$
$48756 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$49043 := -4^7 - 9^2 - 0^0 + 4^8 - 3^3$	$49242 := -4^7 + 9^2 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 2^3$
$48763 := -4^5 + 8^0 + 7^4 + 6^6 + 3^6$	$49045 := -4^7 - 9^2 - 0^0 + 4^8 - 5^2$	$49243 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 3^4$
$48765 := -4^5 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 5^5$	$49046 := -4^6 - 9^5 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 6^6$	$49248 := -4^7 + 9^2 + 2^4 + 4^8 - 8^0$
$48766 := -4^4 + 8^0 + 7^4 + 6^6 - 6^2$	$49058 := -4^3 + 9^3 + 0^1 + 5^6 + 8^5$	$49253 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 3^8$
$48768 := -4^5 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 6^3 + 8^5$	$49064 := -4^7 - 9^2 - 0^0 - 6^1 + 4^8$	$49254 := -4^3 - 9^2 - 2^9 - 5^6 + 4^8$
$48776 := -4^8 + 8^4 + 7^3 + 7^6 - 6^5$	$49083 := -4^6 + 9^3 - 0^0 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$49256 := -4^1 - 9^1 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 6^6$
$48783 := -4^3 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 8^5 - 3^6$	$49126 := -4^6 + 9^4 + 1^0 + 2^2 + 6^6$	$49259 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^3 + 5^2 + 9^5$
$48794 := -4^2 + 8^5 - 7^3 + 9^0 + 4^7$	$49141 := -4^7 - 9^1 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 1^0$	$49263 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 6^2 + 3^8$
$48798 := -4^4 - 8^3 + 7^5 - 9^1 + 8^5$	$49142 := -4^7 - 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 2^3$	$49273 := -4^7 + 9^5 - 2^1 + 7^2 + 3^8$
$48799 := -4^6 + 8^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 - 9^4$	$49143 := -4^7 + 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 3^2$	$49274 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 2^6 + 7^2 + 4^8$
$48807 := -4^4 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$49143 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 3^2$	$49278 := -4^4 - 9^1 - 2^5 + 7^5 + 8^5$

$49279 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^2 + 7^2 + 9^5$	$49524 := -4^7 - 9^1 + 5^3 + 2^8 + 4^8$	$49762 := -4^2 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 6^6 - 2^3$
$49289 := -4^7 + 9^4 - 2^0 + 8^2 + 9^5$	$49526 := -4^4 - 9^0 + 5^5 + 2^1 + 6^6$	$49763 := -4^4 + 9^5 - 7^5 + 6^5 + 3^0$
$49290 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 0^1$	$49529 := -4^6 - 9^4 + 5^4 + 2^9 + 9^5$	$49765 := -4^2 + 9^0 - 7^0 + 6^6 + 5^5$
$49291 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$49542 := -4^4 - 9^2 - 5^6 + 4^8 - 2^5$	$49765 := -4^2 - 9^0 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 5^5$
$49292 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^1 + 9^5 + 2^6$	$49543 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 5^4 + 4^8 - 3^5$	$49768 := -4^4 - 9^3 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 8^4$
$49293 := -4^5 - 9^4 + 2^4 + 9^5 - 3^7$	$49548 := -4^7 + 9^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 8^3$	$49769 := -4^2 - 9^0 + 7^4 + 6^6 + 9^3$
$49294 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 4^3$	$49563 := -4^1 + 9^3 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 3^7$	$49786 := -4^1 - 9^0 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 6^3$
$49295 := -4^1 - 9^4 - 2^6 + 9^5 - 5^5$	$49584 := -4^7 - 9^2 + 5^0 + 8^3 + 4^8$	$49788 := -4^1 + 9^3 + 7^5 + 8^5 - 8^3$
$49296 := -4^6 - 9^2 + 2^8 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$49587 := -4^1 - 9^1 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 7^5$	$49834 := -4^5 + 9^5 - 8^4 + 3^0 - 4^6$
$49297 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 7^1$	$49606 := -4^6 - 9^3 + 6^5 - 0^0 + 6^6$	$49835 := -4^2 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 5^6$
$49298 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 8^2$	$49625 := -4^5 + 9^5 - 6^5 + 2^0 - 5^4$	$49836 := -4^5 + 9^2 + 8^4 + 3^3 + 6^6$
$49299 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 2^6 + 9^4 + 9^5$	$49632 := -4^1 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 2^6$	$49837 := -4^8 - 9^2 - 8^1 - 3^7 + 7^6$
$49322 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 3^8 + 2^5 + 2^6$	$49635 := -4^3 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 5^5$	$49845 := -4^3 - 9^0 - 8^0 + 4^8 - 5^6$
$49323 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 2^4 + 3^8$	$49638 := -4^5 - 9^1 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 8^4$	$49846 := -4^7 + 9^3 + 8^0 + 4^8 - 6^2$
$49324 := -4^7 - 9^2 - 3^1 + 2^8 + 4^8$	$49645 := -4^4 - 9^1 - 6^0 + 4^8 - 5^6$	$49854 := -4^1 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 5^4 + 4^7$
$49326 := -4^2 + 9^5 - 3^7 + 2^8 - 6^5$	$49646 := -4^5 - 9^2 - 6^0 + 4^6 + 6^6$	$49856 := -4^9 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 6^7$
$49342 := -4^7 + 9^3 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 2^9$	$49647 := -4^8 - 9^4 - 6^0 + 4^6 + 7^6$	$49858 := -4^5 + 9^5 - 8^4 + 5^2 - 8^4$
$49347 := -4^7 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 4^8 - 7^2$	$49648 := -4^5 - 9^2 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 8^4$	$49859 := -4^2 - 9^4 + 8^3 - 5^5 + 9^5$
$49350 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 0^0$	$49652 := -4^2 - 9^2 + 6^6 + 5^5 - 2^5$	$49874 := -4^7 + 9^3 - 8^1 + 7^0 + 4^8$
$49352 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 2^0$	$49654 := -4^3 + 9^0 + 6^6 + 5^5 - 4^3$	$49880 := -4^7 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 8^5 - 0^0$
$49362 := -4^6 + 9^4 + 3^5 + 6^6 - 2^1$	$49657 := -4^2 - 9^1 + 6^6 + 5^4 + 7^4$	$49882 := -4^7 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 2^0$
$49363 := -4^6 - 9^0 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 3^8$	$49658 := -4^6 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 8^3$	$49885 := -4^7 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 8^4 + 5^5$
$49364 := -4^7 - 9^0 - 3^1 + 6^3 + 4^8$	$49672 := -4^5 - 9^5 - 6^5 + 7^6 - 2^7$	$49895 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 8^4 + 9^5 + 5^5$
$49365 := -4^1 + 9^5 - 3^8 + 6^1 - 5^5$	$49675 := -4^2 + 9^1 + 6^6 + 7^4 + 5^4$	$49925 := -4^3 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 2^2 - 5^6$
$49434 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 4^8$	$49677 := -4^8 + 9^0 - 6^2 + 7^6 - 7^4$	$49944 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 9^3 + 4^3 + 4^8$
$49446 := -4^7 - 9^3 + 4^5 + 4^8 - 6^0$	$49678 := -4^5 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 7^2 + 8^4$	$49963 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 9^1 + 6^6 + 3^9$
$49448 := -4^7 - 9^3 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 8^0$	$49685 := -4^2 - 9^2 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 5^5$	$49968 := -4^3 + 9^1 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 8^4$
$49452 := -4^7 - 9^2 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 2^8$	$49689 := -4^6 - 9^4 + 6^4 + 8^0 + 9^5$	$49985 := -4^3 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 8^2 - 5^6$
$49453 := -4^7 - 9^2 + 4^8 + 5^4 - 3^5$	$49692 := -4^6 - 9^4 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 2^2$	$50247 := -5^6 + 0^0 - 2^3 + 4^8 + 7^3$
$49454 := -4^7 + 9^0 + 4^6 + 5^7 - 4^7$	$49695 := -4^1 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 9^2 + 5^5$	$50249 := -5^6 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^8 + 9^2$
$49458 := -4^1 + 9^1 + 4^6 + 5^7 - 8^5$	$49725 := -4^8 + 9^3 + 7^6 + 2^3 - 5^5$	$50336 := -5^5 + 0^0 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 6^6$
$49472 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 7^3 - 2^5$	$49726 := -4^3 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 2^2 + 6^6$	$50342 := -5^6 + 0^1 - 3^4 + 4^8 + 2^9$
$49478 := -4^2 - 9^0 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^5$	$49727 := -4^8 - 9^0 - 7^4 + 2^4 + 7^6$	$50354 := -5^7 - 0^0 - 3^0 + 5^8 - 4^9$
$49483 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 8^0 + 3^8$	$49742 := -4^7 - 9^1 + 7^3 + 4^8 + 2^8$	$50358 := -5^7 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 5^8 - 8^6$
$49487 := -4^7 - 9^1 + 4^8 + 8^0 + 7^3$	$49745 := -4^7 - 9^2 + 7^2 + 4^8 + 5^4$	$50421 := -5^6 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^9 - 1^0$
$49497 := -4^7 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 9^0 + 7^3$	$49761 := -4^4 + 9^5 - 7^5 + 6^5 - 1^0$	$50422 := -5^6 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^8 + 2^8$

- 50423 := $-5^6 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^9 - 3^0$ 51954 := $-5^5 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 5^3 - 4^6$ 52472 := $-5^2 + 2^7 - 4^8 + 7^6 + 2^8$
50424 := $-5^6 + 0^0 + 4^4 + 2^8 + 4^8$ 51992 := $-5^4 + 1^0 - 9^4 + 9^5 + 2^7$ 52473 := $-5^3 + 2^9 - 4^8 + 7^6 - 3^3$
50425 := $-5^6 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^9 + 5^0$ 51996 := $-5^1 - 1^0 + 9^3 + 9^5 - 6^5$ 52475 := $-5^2 + 2^9 - 4^8 + 7^6 - 5^3$
50428 := $-5^6 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^2 + 8^3$ 52034 := $-5^6 - 2^6 + 0^1 + 3^7 + 4^8$ 52476 := $-5^6 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 7^4 + 6^2$
50432 := $-5^6 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 2^9$ 52083 := $-5^4 + 2^8 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 3^9$ 52485 := $-5^1 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 5^6$
50472 := $-5^6 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 7^2 + 2^9$ 52234 := $-5^6 + 2^3 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 4^8$ 52493 := $-5^5 - 2^6 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 3^6$
50488 := $-5^6 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 8^2 + 8^3$ 52239 := $-5^2 - 2^8 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 9^5$ 52496 := $-5^4 - 2^5 - 4^3 + 9^4 + 6^6$
50534 := $-5^6 - 0^0 + 5^4 - 3^0 + 4^8$ 52247 := $-5^6 - 2^0 - 2^6 + 4^8 + 7^4$ 52497 := $-5^5 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 9^5 - 7^4$
50548 := $-5^6 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 8^3$ 52295 := $-5^5 + 2^3 - 2^9 + 9^5 - 5^5$ 52499 := $-5^1 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 9^5 - 9^4$
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50628 := $-5^3 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 8^4$ 52328 := $-5^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 2^0 + 8^5$ 52536 := $-5^6 - 2^0 + 5^7 - 3^7 - 6^5$
50633 := $-5^6 + 0^1 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 3^9$ 52329 := $-5^3 - 2^1 - 3^8 - 2^5 + 9^5$ 52548 := $-5^1 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 4^6 + 8^5$
50634 := $-5^6 + 0^1 - 6^1 + 3^6 + 4^8$ 52343 := $-5^6 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 3^7$ 52549 := $-5^6 - 2^7 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 9^4$
50639 := $-5^4 + 0^1 - 6^5 - 3^2 + 9^5$ 52344 := $-5^6 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^6 + 4^8$ 52563 := $-5^2 - 2^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 + 3^8$
50642 := $-5^3 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 4^6 + 2^4$ 52346 := $-5^4 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^6$ 52564 := $-5^6 - 2^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 4^8$
50644 := $-5^3 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 4^6$ 52347 := $-5^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^8 + 7^6$ 52569 := $-5^2 + 2^1 - 5^4 + 6^6 + 9^4$
50649 := $-5^4 + 0^1 - 6^5 + 4^0 + 9^5$ 52363 := $-5^4 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 3^8$ 52583 := $-5^2 + 2^5 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 3^9$
50664 := $-5^3 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 4^6$ 52368 := $-5^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 8^5$ 52587 := $-5^4 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 7^5$
50678 := $-5^2 + 0^1 + 6^6 - 7^2 + 8^4$ 52381 := $-5^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 1^0$ 52596 := $-5^4 - 2^0 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 6^6$
50682 := $-5^1 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 8^4 - 2^6$ 52382 := $-5^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 2^5$ 52609 := $-5^4 + 2^4 + 6^6 + 0^0 + 9^4$
50684 := $-5^1 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 8^4 - 4^3$ 52383 := $-5^1 - 2^6 + 3^0 + 8^5 + 3^9$ 52623 := $-5^4 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 2^5 + 3^8$
50697 := $-5^4 + 0^1 - 6^5 + 9^5 + 7^2$ 52384 := $-5^1 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 4^3$ 52632 := $-5^4 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 2^5$
50745 := $-5^6 + 0^1 - 7^6 + 4^9 - 5^7$ 52385 := $-5^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 5^3$ 52633 := $-5^4 + 2^5 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 3^8$
50746 := $-5^1 + 0^1 - 7^0 + 4^6 + 6^6$ 52386 := $-5^2 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 6^2$ 52636 := $-5^4 + 2^3 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 6^6$
50763 := $-5^6 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 3^9$ 52387 := $-5^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 7^1$ 52637 := $-5^4 - 2^2 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 7^2$
50867 := $-5^1 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 7^5$ 52388 := $-5^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 8^5$ 52638 := $-5^2 - 2^2 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 8^5$
50944 := $-5^6 + 0^1 + 9^1 + 4^5 + 4^8$ 52389 := $-5^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 9^0$ 52639 := $-5^4 + 2^7 + 6^6 + 3^8 - 9^2$

51269 := $-5^1 - 1^0 + 2^1 - 6^5 + 9^5$ 52394 := $-5^3 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 9^5 - 4^0$ 52653 := $-5^4 - 2^6 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 3^8$
51448 := $-5^6 + 1^0 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 8^3$ 52396 := $-5^3 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 9^5 + 6^0$ 52659 := $-5^5 + 2^6 + 6^6 + 5^6 - 9^4$
51462 := $-5^6 - 1^0 + 4^8 + 6^4 + 2^8$ 52398 := $-5^2 - 2^0 - 3^8 + 9^5 - 8^2$ 52673 := $-5^2 - 2^9 + 6^6 - 7^1 + 3^8$
51464 := $-5^6 + 1^0 + 4^4 + 6^4 + 4^8$ 52434 := $-5^2 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 3^9 + 4^7$ 52679 := $-5^2 - 2^9 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 9^4$
51738 := $-5^2 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 3^7 + 8^5$ 52437 := $-5^6 - 2^2 + 4^8 + 3^7 + 7^3$ 52683 := $-5^2 + 2^8 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 3^9$
51823 := $-5^4 - 1^0 + 8^5 - 2^1 + 3^9$ 52438 := $-5^1 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 3^9 + 8^5$ 52692 := $-5^1 - 2^3 + 6^6 + 9^4 - 2^9$
51829 := $-5^5 - 1^0 - 8^4 + 2^1 + 9^5$ 52439 := $-5^2 - 2^3 - 4^2 - 3^8 + 9^5$ 52693 := $-5^2 - 2^8 + 6^6 + 9^4 - 3^5$
51843 := $-5^4 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 3^9$ 52457 := $-5^2 - 2^8 - 4^8 + 5^4 + 7^6$ 52695 := $-5^1 - 2^9 + 6^6 + 9^4 - 5^1$
51863 := $-5^4 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^9$ 52463 := $-5^4 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 6^6 + 3^8$ 52698 := $-5^1 - 2^1 + 6^6 + 9^4 - 8^3$

$52699 := -5^1 - 2^9 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 9^4$	$53249 := -5^6 - 3^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$53648 := -5^2 + 3^2 - 6^5 + 4^8 - 8^4$
$52743 := -5^6 + 2^9 + 7^4 + 4^8 - 3^4$	$53264 := -5^2 + 3^8 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$53649 := -5^1 - 3^1 - 6^4 - 4^6 + 9^5$
$52744 := -5^6 - 2^7 + 7^6 + 4^7 - 4^8$	$53268 := -5^1 + 3^8 - 2^3 + 6^6 + 8^2$	$53662 := -5^2 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 6^6 - 2^4$
$52746 := -5^5 + 2^9 - 7^4 + 4^8 - 6^5$	$53269 := -5^2 + 3^4 - 2^2 + 6^6 + 9^4$	$53664 := -5^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 4^4$
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$52769 := -5^4 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^4$	$53283 := -5^2 + 3^6 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$53669 := -5^2 - 3^2 + 6^5 + 6^6 - 9^3$
$52784 := -5^2 - 2^4 - 7^5 + 8^4 + 4^8$	$53289 := -5^5 - 3^7 + 2^6 - 8^3 + 9^5$	$53674 := -5^4 + 3^7 - 6^0 + 7^6 - 4^8$
$52793 := -5^5 - 2^0 - 7^4 + 9^5 - 3^6$	$53336 := -5^3 + 3^0 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 6^6$	$53685 := -5^4 - 3^9 - 6^2 - 8^4 + 5^7$
$52834 := -5^3 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 3^9 - 4^1$	$53355 := -5^6 - 3^4 + 3^8 - 5^6 + 5^7$	$53686 := -5^2 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 6^6$
$52836 := -5^3 + 2^8 - 8^3 + 3^8 + 6^6$	$53396 := -5^6 + 3^2 + 3^7 + 9^5 + 6^5$	$53729 := -5^5 - 3^7 - 7^1 - 2^0 + 9^5$
$52837 := -5^3 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 3^9 - 7^0$	$53397 := -5^5 + 3^1 - 3^7 + 9^5 - 7^3$	$53739 := -5^5 - 3^3 - 7^4 + 3^5 + 9^5$
$52839 := -5^3 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 9^0$	$53398 := -5^2 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$53753 := -5^6 - 3^7 + 7^0 + 5^7 - 3^8$
$52859 := -5^5 - 2^2 + 8^2 - 5^5 + 9^5$	$53426 := -5^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 2^9 + 6^6$	$53758 := -5^6 + 3^9 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 8^5$
$52874 := -5^6 + 2^1 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 4^7$	$53436 := -5^2 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 3^8 + 6^6$	$53759 := -5^6 - 3^7 + 7^1 + 5^7 - 9^4$
$52895 := -5^5 + 2^5 + 8^2 + 9^5 - 5^5$	$53464 := -5^1 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^6 + 4^4$	$53776 := -5^5 - 3^8 - 7^0 + 7^5 + 6^6$
$52925 := -5^5 - 2^1 + 9^5 + 2^7 - 5^5$	$53467 := -5^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^6 - 7^0$	$53779 := -5^5 - 3^7 - 7^1 + 7^2 + 9^5$
$52944 := -5^7 - 2^1 - 9^0 + 4^8 + 4^8$	$53468 := -5^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^6 + 8^3$	$53792 := -5^5 - 3^5 - 7^4 + 9^5 + 2^9$
$52947 := -5^5 - 2^9 + 9^5 - 4^3 - 7^4$	$53469 := -5^1 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^4$	$53793 := -5^5 + 3^3 - 7^4 + 9^5 + 3^5$
$52954 := -5^6 - 2^0 - 9^2 + 5^5 + 4^8$	$53482 := -5^2 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 2^5$	$53794 := -5^5 - 3^7 - 7^1 + 9^5 + 4^3$
$52962 := -5^3 - 2^1 + 9^4 + 6^6 - 2^7$	$53486 := -5^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^4$	$53795 := -5^6 - 3^8 + 7^5 + 9^5 + 5^3$
$52963 := -5^2 - 2^8 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 3^3$	$53489 := -5^5 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 8^1 + 9^5$	$53798 := -5^4 - 3^4 + 7^6 - 9^5 - 8^4$
$52964 := -5^1 + 2^3 + 9^4 + 6^6 - 4^4$	$53493 := -5^5 - 3^5 - 4^0 + 9^5 - 3^7$	$53829 := -5^4 - 3^5 - 8^4 - 2^8 + 9^5$
$52965 := -5^3 - 2^1 + 9^4 + 6^6 - 5^3$	$53497 := -5^5 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 9^5 - 7^4$	$53869 := -5^4 - 3^5 - 8^4 - 6^3 + 9^5$
$52967 := -5^4 + 2^5 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 7^3$	$53529 := -5^5 + 3^6 - 5^5 + 2^0 + 9^5$	$53934 := -5^5 - 3^4 + 9^5 + 3^7 - 4^6$
$52968 := -5^4 - 2^6 + 9^5 - 6^4 - 8^4$	$53536 := -5^6 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 3^8 - 6^3$	$53973 := -5^5 - 3^7 + 9^5 - 7^1 + 3^5$
$52983 := -5^2 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 8^3 - 3^8$	$53537 := -5^6 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 3^8 - 7^4$	$53992 := -5^5 - 3^7 - 9^0 + 9^5 + 2^8$
$52994 := -5^1 + 2^9 - 9^4 + 9^5 - 4^0$	$53574 := -5^5 - 3^8 + 5^3 - 7^4 + 4^8$	$53994 := -5^5 - 3^7 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 4^4$
$52996 := -5^1 + 2^9 - 9^4 + 9^5 + 6^0$	$53592 := -5^5 + 3^6 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^6$	$54008 := -5^6 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 0^1 + 8^4$
$53045 := -5^6 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 5^5$	$53594 := -5^1 - 3^6 - 5^4 + 9^5 - 4^6$	$54024 := -5^6 + 4^6 + 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^8$
$53093 := -5^3 + 3^6 + 0^0 + 9^5 - 3^8$	$53596 := -5^6 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 6^5$	$54034 := -5^6 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 4^8$
$53096 := -5^3 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$53598 := -5^4 - 3^6 - 5^0 + 9^5 - 8^4$	$54089 := -5^6 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 9^2$
$53193 := -5^2 + 3^6 + 1^0 + 9^5 - 3^8$	$53604 := -5^2 - 3^9 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$54099 := -5^3 - 4^6 + 0^1 - 9^3 + 9^5$
$53196 := -5^2 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$53623 := -5^2 - 3^4 + 6^6 + 2^9 + 3^8$	$54234 := -5^6 + 4^6 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^8$
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$53229 := -5^5 - 3^7 + 2^2 - 2^9 + 9^5$	$53627 := -5^6 + 3^9 + 6^6 + 2^9 + 7^4$	$54253 := -5^3 - 4^6 + 2^5 + 5^7 - 3^9$
$53245 := -5^6 + 3^4 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 5^5$	$53643 := -5^2 + 3^6 + 6^6 + 4^6 + 3^7$	$54259 := -5^1 - 4^6 - 2^6 - 5^4 + 9^5$

$54264 := -5^6 + 4^6 + 2^8 + 6^0 + 4^8$	$54565 := -5^2 - 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 5^7$	$54829 := -5^3 - 4^0 - 8^4 + 2^1 + 9^5$
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$54936 := -5^2 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 3^2 - 6^0$	$55298 := -5^4 - 5^5 - 2^1 + 9^5 + 8^0$	$55599 := -5^7 + 5^0 + 5^6 + 9^5 + 9^5$
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$54942 := -5^1 - 4^1 + 9^5 - 4^6 - 2^1$	$55299 := -5^4 - 5^5 - 2^0 + 9^0 + 9^5$	$55667 := -5^2 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 7^5$
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$54965 := -5^2 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 5^0$	$55326 := -5^5 + 5^7 - 3^9 + 2^3 + 6^0$	$55791 := -5^3 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 9^5 - 1^0$
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$54983 := -5^1 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 3^3$	$55374 := -5^4 + 5^5 + 3^9 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$55796 := -5^5 - 5^0 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 6^3$
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$55906 := -5^2 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 6^1$	$55943 := -5^6 + 5^7 - 9^4 + 4^0 + 3^1$	$55988 := -5^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 8^2$
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$55916 := -5^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 6^1$	$55951 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 1^0$	$56097 := -5^6 - 6^6 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 7^6$
$55917 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 7^0$	$55952 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 2^5$	$56219 := -5^5 - 6^3 + 2^9 - 1^0 + 9^5$
$55918 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 1^0 - 8^1$	$55953 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 3^2$	$56235 := -5^6 - 6^3 + 2^9 - 3^8 + 5^7$
$55919 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^0 - 1^0 + 9^5$	$55954 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 4^1$	$56239 := -5^4 - 6^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 9^5$
$55919 := -5^1 - 5^5 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 9^5$	$55955 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 5^2$	$56253 := -5^2 + 6^6 - 2^6 + 5^5 + 3^8$
$55920 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 0^1$	$55956 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 6^2$	$56254 := -5^4 - 6^5 - 2^8 - 5^4 + 4^8$
$55921 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 1^0$	$55957 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 7^1$	$56269 := -5^5 + 6^0 + 2^7 + 6^3 + 9^5$
$55922 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 2^1$	$55958 := -5^1 - 5^2 + 9^5 - 5^5 + 8^2$	$56273 := -5^4 + 6^6 - 2^2 + 7^5 - 3^8$
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$55927 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 7^1$	$55964 := -5^2 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 4^3$	$56342 := -5^4 - 6^5 - 3^6 + 4^8 - 2^6$
$55928 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 8^1$	$55965 := -5^6 + 5^2 - 9^4 + 6^0 + 5^7$	$56344 := -5^5 + 6^3 - 3^7 + 4^8 - 4^6$
$55929 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^1 + 2^0 + 9^5$	$55966 := -5^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 6^2$	$56347 := -5^3 + 6^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1$
$55930 := -5^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 0^1$	$55967 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 6^0 + 7^2$	$56364 := -5^6 - 6^4 - 3^3 + 6^5 + 4^8$
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$55932 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 3^1 + 2^4$	$55971 := -5^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 + 7^2 - 1^0$	$56384 := -5^4 + 6^4 + 3^8 + 8^5 + 4^7$
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$56637 := -5^6 - 6^6 + 6^4 - 3^3 + 7^6$	$56998 := -5^2 - 6^4 - 9^3 + 9^5 - 8^0$	$57684 := -5^1 - 7^1 - 6^5 - 8^2 + 4^8$
$56672 := -5^6 + 6^4 - 6^6 + 7^6 + 2^3$	$57264 := -5^2 - 7^3 - 2^7 - 6^5 + 4^8$	$57688 := -5^6 + 7^0 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 8^5$
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$57839 := -5^4 - 7^3 + 8^0 - 3^5 + 9^5$	$58193 := -5^3 - 8^0 - 1^0 + 9^5 - 3^6$	$58354 := -5^2 + 8^0 - 3^9 + 5^7 - 4^3$
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$57885 := -5^6 - 7^1 - 8^3 - 8^4 + 5^7$	$58246 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^5$	$58365 := -5^4 + 8^3 - 3^9 + 6^2 + 5^7$
$57894 := -5^3 - 7^1 + 8^0 + 9^5 - 4^5$	$58253 := -5^3 + 8^2 - 2^7 + 5^7 - 3^9$	$58369 := -5^4 - 8^2 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 9^5$
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$58493 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^2 + 9^5 - 3^1$	$58656 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 6^3$	$58899 := -5^3 - 8^1 - 8^1 - 9^1 + 9^5$
$58495 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^2 + 9^5 - 5^0$	$58678 := -5^4 - 8^2 + 6^6 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$58908 := -5^3 - 8^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 - 8^1$
$58496 := -5^1 + 8^3 - 4^5 + 9^5 - 6^2$	$58679 := -5^2 - 8^0 - 6^0 - 7^3 + 9^5$	$58913 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 3^2$
$58497 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^2 + 9^5 + 7^0$	$58692 := -5^1 - 8^1 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 2^7$	$58914 := -5^3 - 8^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 4^0$
$58499 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^1 - 9^1 + 9^5$	$58693 := -5^4 + 8^3 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 3^3$	$58916 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 6^1$
$58523 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 5^7 + 2^7 - 3^2$	$58694 := -5^4 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 4^4$	$58917 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 1^0 - 7^1$
$58524 := -5^6 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^7 - 4^6$	$58695 := -5^1 - 8^1 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 5^3$	$58918 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 1^0 - 8^1$
$58525 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 5^3 - 2^2 + 5^7$	$58697 := -5^4 + 8^1 + 6^3 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$58920 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 2^1 - 0^0$
$58526 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 5^7 + 2^7 - 6^1$	$58699 := -5^3 - 8^1 - 6^3 - 9^0 + 9^5$	$58921 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 2^0 - 1^0$
$58527 := -5^5 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 7^5$	$58705 := -5^5 + 8^3 - 7^5 + 0^1 + 5^7$	$58922 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 2^0 - 2^1$
$58529 := -5^1 - 8^1 + 5^1 - 2^9 + 9^5$	$58709 := -5^1 + 8^1 - 7^3 + 0^1 + 9^5$	$58923 := -5^1 - 8^1 + 9^5 - 2^5 - 3^4$
$58534 := -5^5 - 8^0 + 5^7 - 3^4 - 4^7$	$58726 := -5^4 - 8^4 + 7^5 - 2^4 + 6^6$	$58924 := -5^1 - 8^1 + 9^5 - 2^7 + 4^2$
$58539 := -5^4 - 8^0 + 5^3 - 3^2 + 9^5$	$58739 := -5^4 - 8^0 + 7^3 - 3^3 + 9^5$	$58925 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 2^0 - 5^0$
$58543 := -5^5 - 8^2 + 5^7 - 4^7 - 3^2$	$58746 := -5^4 - 8^4 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 6^6$	$58925 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 5^0$
$58544 := -5^3 - 8^4 + 5^7 + 4^5 - 4^7$	$58749 := -5^2 + 8^2 - 7^3 + 4^1 + 9^5$	$58926 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 2^1 - 6^2$
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$58549 := -5^1 - 8^3 + 5^0 + 4^2 + 9^5$	$58793 := -5^1 - 8^0 - 7^1 + 9^5 - 3^5$	$58931 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 3^2 - 1^0$
$58563 := -5^5 - 8^3 + 5^6 + 6^6 - 3^4$	$58794 := -5^1 - 8^0 + 7^1 + 9^5 - 4^4$	$58932 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 3^3 - 2^6$
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$58635 := -5^5 - 8^3 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 5^6$	$58873 := -5^6 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 3^8$	$58942 := -5^2 + 8^1 - 9^4 + 4^8 - 2^4$

$58943 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 4^3 + 3^3$	$58983 := -5^3 - 8^1 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 3^1$	$59040 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 4^2 + 0^0$
$58944 := -5^3 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 4^2 - 4^1$	$58984 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 8^1 - 4^1$	$59041 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 1^0$
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$58960 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 6^0 + 0^0$	$59024 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 2^1 - 4^0$	$59058 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 8^1$
$58962 := -5^2 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 6^0 - 2^6$	$59025 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 2^0 - 5^0$	$59059 := -5^1 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 9^5$
$58963 := -5^1 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 6^0 - 3^4$	$59025 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 5^0$	$59060 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 6^2 + 0^0$
$58964 := -5^2 + 8^1 - 9^4 + 6^1 + 4^8$	$59026 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 2^1 - 6^0$	$59061 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 1^0$
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$58975 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 7^2 + 5^0$	$59035 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 3^2 + 5^0$	$59071 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 7^2 - 1^0$
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$58978 := -5^1 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 7^0 - 8^2$	$59037 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 3^0 - 7^1$	$59073 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 3^3$
$58980 := -5^1 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 8^2 + 0^0$	$59038 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 3^0 - 8^1$	$59074 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 4^0$
$58981 := -5^3 - 8^1 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 1^0$	$59039 := -5^1 - 9^0 - 0^0 - 3^1 + 9^5$	$59075 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 7^1 + 5^2$
$58982 := -5^1 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 8^0 - 2^6$	$59040 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 4^2 - 0^0$	$59084 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 8^2 - 4^1$

$59086 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 8^2 - 6^0$	$59233 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 3^6$	$59287 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 8^1 - 7^0$
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$59151 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 1^0$	$59260 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 6^3 - 0^0$	$59326 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 2^8 - 6^0$
$59152 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 5^3 - 2^4$	$59260 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 2^0 + 6^3 + 0^0$	$59328 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 2^8 + 8^0$
$59153 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 3^1$	$59261 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 6^3 - 1^0$	$59332 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 3^5 + 2^6$
$59154 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3 - 4^2$	$59262 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 6^3 + 2^0$	$59334 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^5 + 4^3$
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$59205 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 0^1 + 5^2$	$59274 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 7^3 - 4^0$	$59359 := -5^4 + 9^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 9^5$
$59223 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 2^8 - 3^4$	$59276 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 7^3 + 6^0$	$59362 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 6^0 + 2^8$
$59224 := -5^1 - 9^4 - 2^1 + 2^8 + 4^8$	$59278 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 2^0 + 7^3 + 8^3$	$59367 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 3^0 + 6^0 + 7^3$
$59225 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 2^3 + 2^6 + 5^3$	$59280 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 8^0 - 0^0$	$59368 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^0$
$59226 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^4 + 2^1 + 6^3$	$59281 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^8 + 8^3 + 1^0$	$59369 := -5^1 + 9^2 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 9^5$
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$59230 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 3^5 - 0^0$	$59285 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 8^1 + 5^3$	$59373 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 7^3 + 3^1$
$59232 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 2^7$	$59286 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^8 + 8^3 + 6^1$	$59374 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 7^3 - 4^2$

$59375 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 7^3 + 5^1$	$59454 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 4^5$	$59557 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 7^1$
$59376 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 7^3 + 6^1$	$59455 := -5^5 + 9^2 - 4^0 + 5^7 - 5^6$	$59558 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 8^3$
$59377 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 3^1 + 7^3 - 7^1$	$59462 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 4^4 + 6^4 - 2^1$	$59559 := -5^3 + 9^1 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 9^5$
$59378 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 3^0 + 7^3 - 8^1$	$59463 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 4^8 - 6^3 + 3^6$	$59562 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 2^9$
$59379 := -5^1 + 9^0 - 3^2 + 7^3 + 9^5$	$59465 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 4^4 + 6^4 + 5^0$	$59569 := -5^2 - 9^2 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 9^5$
$59382 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 8^0 + 2^8$	$59467 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 6^3 - 7^2$	$59572 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 7^1 + 2^4$
$59387 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 3^0 + 8^0 + 7^3$	$59468 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 8^3$	$59573 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^3 + 3^4$
$59392 := -5^4 + 9^3 + 3^5 + 9^5 - 2^2$	$59481 := -5^1 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 8^3 - 1^0$	$59574 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 5^4 - 7^0 + 4^8$
$59393 := -5^4 + 9^3 - 3^1 + 9^5 + 3^5$	$59483 := -5^1 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 8^3 - 3^8$	$59575 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 5^4$
$59394 := -5^3 + 9^3 - 3^1 + 9^5 - 4^4$	$59484 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 8^3 + 4^3$	$59578 := -5^6 - 9^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^3$
$59395 := -5^4 + 9^3 + 3^5 + 9^5 - 5^0$	$59486 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 4^3 + 8^3 - 6^1$	$59580 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 8^3 - 0^0$
$59396 := -5^4 - 9^2 - 3^5 + 9^5 + 6^4$	$59488 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 8^3 - 8^2$	$59582 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 8^0 + 2^9$
$59397 := -5^1 + 9^0 + 3^2 + 9^5 + 7^3$	$59496 := -5^2 + 9^3 - 4^4 + 9^5 - 6^0$	$59583 := -5^6 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 8^0 - 3^7$
$59405 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 0^1 + 5^3$	$59497 := -5^4 + 9^3 + 4^0 + 9^5 + 7^3$	$59586 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 8^0 + 6^2$
$59409 := -5^4 + 9^3 + 4^4 + 0^1 + 9^5$	$59498 := -5^2 + 9^3 - 4^4 + 9^5 + 8^0$	$59589 := -5^1 - 9^2 + 5^4 + 8^0 + 9^5$
$59420 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 2^9 + 0^1$	$59512 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 5^2 + 1^0 + 2^9$	$59592 := -5^1 - 9^2 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 2^2$
$59421 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 2^9 + 1^0$	$59522 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 2^0 - 2^7$	$59593 := -5^6 - 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^1 - 3^7$
$59422 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 2^1 + 2^9$	$59523 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 2^0 - 3^3$	$59594 := -5^1 - 9^0 + 5^4 - 9^4 + 4^8$
$59423 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 4^8 - 2^8 + 3^6$	$59525 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 5^4$	$59596 := -5^2 - 9^3 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 6^4$
$59424 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 2^7 + 4^4$	$59529 := -5^3 + 9^3 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 9^5$	$59597 := -5^3 - 9^0 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2$
$59425 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 4^4 + 2^9 + 5^3$	$59532 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 5^2 + 3^0 + 2^9$	$59604 := -5^5 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 0^1 - 4^6$
$59426 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^9 - 6^2$	$59534 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 3^0 - 4^2$	$59623 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 2^9 + 3^4$
$59427 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 2^7 - 7^0$	$59536 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 5^0 + 3^6 - 6^3$	$59624 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 2^7 + 4^4$
$59428 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 2^8 + 8^2$	$59537 := -5^4 - 9^5 - 5^4 + 3^7 + 7^6$	$59625 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 6^2 + 2^9 + 5^3$
$59429 := -5^1 + 9^0 + 4^4 + 2^7 + 9^5$	$59538 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 8^3$	$59628 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 6^2 + 2^7 + 8^3$
$59436 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^0 + 3^6 - 6^3$	$59539 := -5^3 - 9^0 + 5^4 - 3^2 + 9^5$	$59629 := -5^4 + 9^3 - 6^2 + 2^9 + 9^5$
$59438 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 8^3$	$59542 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 4^0 - 2^7$	$59638 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 3^4 + 8^3$
$59442 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 4^5 - 2^1$	$59545 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 5^3 + 4^0 + 5^4$	$59642 := -5^4 - 9^4 + 6^4 + 4^8 - 2^2$
$59443 := -5^1 + 9^3 - 4^4 + 4^8 - 3^8$	$59549 := -5^3 - 9^0 + 5^4 + 4^0 + 9^5$	$59643 := -5^2 + 9^3 - 6^2 + 4^8 - 3^8$
$59444 := -5^7 + 9^4 - 4^3 + 4^8 + 4^8$	$59550 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 0^1$	$59645 := -5^4 - 9^4 + 6^4 + 4^8 - 5^0$
$59445 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 4^5 + 5^0$	$59551 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 1^0$	$59647 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 4^3 + 7^3$
$59446 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 4^0 + 4^5 - 6^0$	$59552 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 5^1 + 5^0 + 2^9$	$59648 := -5^2 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 4^7 - 8^4$
$59447 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 4^3 + 7^3$	$59553 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 5^3 + 5^4 + 3^2$	$59650 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 0^1$
$59448 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 4^2 + 8^3$	$59554 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 4^1$	$59651 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 1^0$
$59450 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 0^0$	$59555 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 5^4$	$59652 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 6^0 + 5^4 - 2^4$
$59452 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 2^0$	$59556 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 6^1$	$59653 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 3^1$

$$\begin{aligned} 59654 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 - 4^2 & 59793 &:= -5^1 + 9^3 - 7^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 & 60452 &:= -6^4 - 0^0 - 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^3 \\ 59655 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 5^4 & 59796 &:= -5^2 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 6^2 & 60453 &:= -6^4 - 0^0 - 4^7 + 5^7 + 3^2 \\ 59656 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 6^1 & 59798 &:= -5^2 - 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 8^3 & 60487 &:= -6^4 + 0^1 + 4^8 - 8^4 + 7^3 \\ 59657 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 7^1 & 59824 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 2^5 + 4^4 & 60494 &:= -6^3 - 0^0 - 4^6 - 9^3 + 4^8 \\ 59658 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 8^1 & 59827 &:= -5^5 - 9^5 + 8^4 + 2^8 + 7^6 & 60845 &:= -6^7 + 0^1 + 8^3 + 4^9 + 5^7 \\ 59659 &:= -5^1 - 9^1 - 6^0 + 5^4 + 9^5 & 59829 &:= -5^1 + 9^3 - 8^1 + 2^6 + 9^5 & 60885 &:= -6^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 5^5 \\ 59662 &:= -5^4 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 6^4 - 2^6 & 59833 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 3^4 + 3^6 & 60939 &:= -6^3 + 0^1 - 9^2 + 3^7 + 9^5 \\ 59675 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 - 6^0 + 7^1 + 5^4 & 59834 &:= -5^6 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 & 60943 &:= -6^2 - 0^0 + 9^5 - 4^4 + 3^7 \\ 59683 &:= -5^4 + 9^2 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 3^9 & 59836 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 3^6 - 6^0 & 60959 &:= -6^4 + 0^1 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 9^5 \\ 59688 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 8^3 - 8^2 & 59838 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 3^6 + 8^2 & 60965 &:= -6^1 + 0^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 5^4 \\ 59690 &:= -5^3 + 9^3 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 & 59843 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 4^3 + 3^5 & 61239 &:= -6^1 + 1^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 9^5 \\ 59693 &:= -5^1 - 9^2 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 3^6 & 59878 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 7^3 + 8^3 & 61293 &:= -6^1 - 1^0 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 3^7 \\ 59703 &:= -5^3 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 0^0 + 3^6 & 59884 &:= -5^3 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 8^3 - 4^3 & 61297 &:= -6^3 - 1^0 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 7^4 \\ 59732 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^2 + 3^6 + 2^3 & 59887 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 8^3 + 7^3 & 61329 &:= -6^2 + 1^0 + 3^7 + 2^7 + 9^5 \\ 59733 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^2 + 3^2 + 3^6 & 59902 &:= -5^1 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 2^7 & 61404 &:= -6^2 - 1^0 - 4^6 + 0^0 + 4^8 \\ 59734 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 & 59932 &:= -5^2 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^5 - 2^6 & 61434 &:= -6^1 - 1^0 - 4^6 + 3^0 + 4^8 \\ 59735 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 & 59936 &:= -5^1 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 3^7 - 6^4 & 61438 &:= -6^1 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 3^1 - 8^4 \\ 59736 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 3^6 - 6^2 & 59937 &:= -5^7 + 9^0 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 7^6 & 61457 &:= -6^4 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 5^5 + 7^3 \\ 59737 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 7^3 & 59938 &:= -5^5 - 9^0 + 9^5 - 3^4 + 8^4 & 61458 &:= -6^1 - 1^0 + 4^8 + 5^2 - 8^4 \\ 59738 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 - 7^1 + 3^6 - 8^1 & 59940 &:= -5^3 - 9^1 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 0^0 & 61475 &:= -6^3 - 1^0 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 5^7 \\ 59739 &:= -5^4 + 9^3 + 7^3 + 3^5 + 9^5 & 59946 &:= -5^3 - 9^0 + 9^5 + 4^5 - 6^0 & 61479 &:= -6^2 + 1^0 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 9^5 \\ 59752 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^4 + 5^5 - 2^4 & 59948 &:= -5^3 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 4^5 - 8^0 & 61746 &:= -6^4 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 4^7 + 6^6 \\ 59753 &:= -5^2 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 5^0 + 3^6 & 59948 &:= -5^3 - 9^0 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 8^0 & 61748 &:= -6^2 + 1^0 + 7^3 + 4^8 - 8^4 \\ 59756 &:= -5^3 + 9^0 - 7^4 + 5^6 + 6^6 & 59953 &:= -5^2 - 9^1 + 9^5 + 5^5 - 3^7 & 61839 &:= -6^4 - 1^0 + 8^4 - 3^2 + 9^5 \\ 59757 &:= -5^2 - 9^5 + 7^5 - 5^6 + 7^6 & 59954 &:= -5^3 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 4^5 & 61849 &:= -6^4 + 1^0 - 8^0 + 4^6 + 9^5 \\ 59759 &:= -5^1 - 9^1 - 7^4 + 5^5 + 9^5 & 59959 &:= -5^2 + 9^2 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 9^5 & 61849 &:= -6^4 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 4^6 + 9^5 \\ 59768 &:= -5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 6^4 - 8^0 & 59968 &:= -5^2 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 6^3 - 8^0 & 61854 &:= -6^5 - 1^0 + 8^4 - 5^0 + 4^8 \\ 59772 &:= -5^3 + 9^5 - 7^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 & 59974 &:= -5^2 - 9^2 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 4^5 & 61895 &:= -6^3 + 1^0 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 5^5 \\ 59773 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 7^0 + 3^6 & 59976 &:= -5^2 - 9^0 + 9^5 - 7^3 + 6^4 & 61897 &:= -6^4 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 \\ 59774 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^3 + 7^2 + 4^5 & 59997 &:= -5^3 + 9^0 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 7^3 & 61925 &:= -6^3 - 1^0 + 9^5 - 2^5 + 5^5 \\ 59775 &:= -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^4 + 7^1 + 5^5 & & & 61927 &:= -6^2 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 7^4 \\ 59776 &:= -5^4 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 6^4 & 60144 &:= -6^4 - 0^0 + 1^0 - 4^6 + 4^8 & 61956 &:= -6^3 - 1^0 + 9^5 + 5^5 - 6^0 \\ 59778 &:= -5^3 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 7^3 + 8^3 & 60294 &:= -6^2 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 4^5 & 61958 &:= -6^3 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 5^5 - 8^0 \\ 59779 &:= -5^1 + 9^3 - 7^0 + 7^1 + 9^5 & 60395 &:= -6^3 + 0^1 + 3^7 + 9^5 - 5^4 & 61958 &:= -6^3 - 1^0 + 9^5 + 5^5 + 8^0 \\ 59780 &:= -5^3 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 8^3 + 0^0 & 60397 &:= -6^4 + 0^1 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 7^4 & 61965 &:= -6^3 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 5^5 \\ 59792 &:= -5^2 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 2^5 & 60435 &:= -6^4 - 0^0 - 4^7 - 3^2 + 5^7 & 62056 &:= -6^3 - 2^3 - 0^0 + 5^6 + 6^6 \\ 60445 &:= -6^4 - 0^0 + 4^0 - 4^7 + 5^7 & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$62065 := -6^3 + 2^0 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 5^6$	$62504 := -6^2 + 2^7 - 5^5 + 0^0 + 4^8$	$62689 := -6^2 - 2^2 + 6^5 - 8^4 + 9^5$
$62065 := -6^3 - 2^0 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 5^6$	$62525 := -6^1 - 2^0 - 5^6 + 2^5 + 5^7$	$62694 := -6^2 + 2^0 + 6^5 + 9^5 - 4^6$
$62155 := -6^3 - 2^7 - 1^0 - 5^6 + 5^7$	$62534 := -6^1 + 2^7 - 5^5 + 3^0 + 4^8$	$62697 := -6^2 - 2^0 + 6^6 - 9^3 + 7^5$
$62159 := -6^1 - 2^3 - 1^0 + 5^5 + 9^5$	$62535 := -6^1 + 2^5 - 5^6 + 3^2 + 5^7$	$62706 := -6^5 - 2^9 + 7^6 + 0^0 - 6^6$
$62167 := -6^4 + 2^0 - 1^0 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$62536 := -6^5 - 2^6 + 5^7 + 3^3 - 6^5$	$62736 := -6^3 - 2^9 + 7^5 + 3^0 + 6^6$
$62167 := -6^4 - 2^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$62539 := -6^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 3^5 + 9^5$	$62755 := -6^3 + 2^7 + 7^3 + 5^7 - 5^6$
$62176 := -6^4 + 2^3 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$62553 := -6^1 + 2^5 - 5^6 + 5^7 + 3^3$	$62756 := -6^2 + 2^9 - 7^0 + 5^6 + 6^6$
$62245 := -6^1 - 2^1 + 2^9 - 4^7 + 5^7$	$62554 := -6^1 - 2^2 - 5^6 + 5^7 + 4^3$	$62776 := -6^3 - 2^7 - 7^3 + 7^5 + 6^6$
$62248 := -6^3 + 2^9 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 8^4$	$62555 := -6^1 - 2^6 + 5^3 - 5^6 + 5^7$	$62794 := -6^1 - 2^1 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 4^6$
$62264 := -6^4 + 2^3 + 2^9 + 6^6 + 4^7$	$62556 := -6^1 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 6^6$	$62798 := -6^1 + 2^1 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 8^4$
$62265 := -6^1 - 2^1 - 2^3 + 6^6 + 5^6$	$62557 := -6^1 + 2^6 - 5^6 + 5^7 - 7^0$	$62843 := -6^4 + 2^9 - 8^4 + 4^8 + 3^7$
$62289 := -6^3 - 2^7 - 2^9 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$62558 := -6^1 + 2^7 - 5^6 + 5^7 - 8^2$	$62845 := -6^2 - 2^6 - 8^6 - 4^8 + 5^8$
$62295 := -6^1 - 2^0 + 2^7 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$62559 := -6^1 - 2^4 - 5^6 + 5^7 + 9^2$	$62847 := -6^3 - 2^3 - 8^2 + 4^8 - 7^4$
$62347 := -6^5 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 7^4$	$62563 := -6^5 - 2^0 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 3^2$	$62849 := -6^2 - 2^2 + 8^4 - 4^4 + 9^5$
$62354 := -6^3 + 2^5 - 3^9 + 5^7 + 4^6$	$62564 := -6^5 - 2^3 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 4^0$	$62864 := -6^3 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 4^7$
$62356 := -6^5 + 2^9 - 3^6 + 5^7 - 6^5$	$62566 := -6^1 - 2^0 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 6^5$	$62867 := -6^1 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 6^6 - 7^5$
$62373 := -6^6 + 2^7 - 3^7 + 7^6 - 3^8$	$62568 := -6^5 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 8^0$	$62874 := -6^1 - 2^8 + 8^0 - 7^4 + 4^8$
$62374 := -6^1 - 2^9 - 3^5 - 7^4 + 4^8$	$62575 := -6^1 + 2^5 - 5^6 + 7^2 + 5^7$	$62879 := -6^3 - 2^0 + 8^4 - 7^2 + 9^5$
$62376 := -6^4 + 2^7 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$62576 := -6^1 - 2^5 + 5^7 - 7^5 + 6^4$	$62887 := -6^3 - 2^5 + 8^5 + 8^5 - 7^4$
$62394 := -6^1 - 2^4 - 3^6 + 9^5 + 4^6$	$62595 := -6^3 + 2^9 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$62889 := -6^3 - 2^5 - 8^1 + 8^4 + 9^5$
$62395 := -6^1 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$62598 := -6^2 - 2^9 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 8^4$	$62896 := -6^3 - 2^5 + 8^4 + 9^5 - 6^0$
$62405 := -6^1 - 2^0 + 4^8 + 0^0 - 5^5$	$62599 := -6^1 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^5 - 9^2$	$62898 := -6^3 - 2^5 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 8^4$
$62407 := -6^3 - 2^9 + 4^8 + 0^1 - 7^4$	$62605 := -6^5 + 2^5 - 6^5 + 0^1 + 5^7$	$62914 := -6^3 - 2^4 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 4^6$
$62425 := -6^1 + 2^2 + 4^8 + 2^4 - 5^5$	$62624 := -6^4 - 2^6 - 6^4 - 2^8 + 4^8$	$62924 := -6^3 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 2^2 + 4^6$
$62428 := -6^2 + 2^9 + 4^8 + 2^9 - 8^4$	$62643 := -6^5 - 2^4 + 6^6 + 4^6 + 3^9$	$62928 := -6^3 - 2^1 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 8^4$
$62435 := -6^2 + 2^0 - 4^7 + 3^6 + 5^7$	$62645 := -6^5 + 2^3 - 6^5 + 4^3 + 5^7$	$62934 := -6^2 - 2^8 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 4^6$
$62444 := -6^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 4^8 - 4^6$	$62647 := -6^3 - 2^7 + 6^6 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$62938 := -6^3 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 8^4$
$62448 := -6^4 - 2^8 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 8^3$	$62648 := -6^3 + 2^7 + 6^4 + 4^8 - 8^4$	$62944 := -6^3 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 4^6$
$62449 := -6^5 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 4^8 + 9^2$	$62649 := -6^3 - 2^6 - 6^3 + 4^6 + 9^5$	$62946 := -6^3 + 2^4 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 6^0$
$62455 := -6^2 - 2^3 - 4^0 - 5^6 + 5^7$	$62653 := -6^5 - 2^0 - 6^5 + 5^7 + 3^4$	$62958 := -6^3 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 8^4$
$62463 := -6^2 + 2^8 - 4^6 + 6^6 + 3^9$	$62664 := -6^3 - 2^6 - 6^4 - 6^4 + 4^8$	$62964 := -6^3 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 4^6$
$62467 := -6^2 + 2^6 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$62678 := -6^4 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^3$	$62974 := -6^2 - 2^7 + 9^5 - 7^1 + 4^6$
$62469 := -6^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^6 + 9^3$	$62684 := -6^2 - 2^4 + 6^4 - 8^4 + 4^8$	$62980 := -6^2 - 2^7 + 9^5 + 8^4 - 0^0$
$62479 := -6^3 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 7^6 - 9^5$	$62685 := -6^4 - 2^8 - 6^6 + 8^5 + 5^7$	$62982 := -6^2 + 2^0 + 9^5 + 8^4 - 2^7$
$62485 := -6^1 + 2^4 + 4^8 + 8^2 - 5^5$	$62687 := -6^4 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 8^3 + 7^5$	$62985 := -6^2 + 2^0 + 9^5 + 8^4 - 5^3$
$62489 := -6^4 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 8^3 + 9^5$	$62688 := -6^4 - 2^8 - 6^4 + 8^5 + 8^5$	$62994 := -6^1 - 2^6 - 9^2 + 9^5 + 4^6$

$62995 := -6^2 + 2^7 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$63364 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 3^3 - 6^1 + 4^8$	$63479 := -6^1 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 9^5$
$62997 := -6^3 + 2^2 + 9^4 + 9^5 - 7^4$	$63367 := -6^1 - 3^2 - 3^4 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$63483 := -6^4 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 8^0 - 3^6$
$63047 := -6^1 - 3^4 - 0^0 + 4^8 - 7^4$	$63368 := -6^4 - 3^7 + 3^9 + 6^6 + 8^3$	$63484 := -6^4 - 3^5 - 4^0 - 8^3 + 4^8$
$63059 := -6^5 - 3^6 + 0^1 + 5^7 - 9^4$	$63369 := -6^3 - 3^6 + 3^8 - 6^4 + 9^5$	$63485 := -6^4 - 3^6 + 4^8 - 8^0 - 5^2$
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$63142 := -6^3 - 3^7 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 2^3$	$63407 := -6^6 - 3^8 - 4^5 - 0^0 + 7^6$	$63492 := -6^4 - 3^1 + 4^8 - 9^3 - 2^4$
$63143 := -6^3 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 3^7$	$63408 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 8^2$	$63493 := -6^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 9^1 - 3^6$
$63149 := -6^1 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 9^5$	$63423 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 3^4$	$63494 := -6^4 - 3^0 - 4^2 - 9^3 + 4^8$
$63167 := -6^3 - 3^4 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$63429 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 - 9^3$	$63495 := -6^4 - 3^6 + 4^8 + 9^1 - 5^2$
$63189 := -6^2 + 3^4 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$63430 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 3^6 + 0^1$	$63496 := -6^1 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 9^3 - 6^4$
$63214 := -6^1 - 3^7 - 2^7 - 1^0 + 4^8$	$63431 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 3^6 + 1^0$	$63497 := -6^5 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 9^5 + 7^4$
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$63239 := -6^3 + 3^7 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 9^5$	$63433 := -6^1 + 3^2 + 4^8 + 3^4 - 3^7$	$63508 := -6^6 - 3^6 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 8^5$
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$63677 := -6^2 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 7^5$	$63894 := -6^1 + 3^5 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 4^6$	$64213 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 1^0 - 3^3$
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$63746 := -6^3 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 6^6$	$63988 := -6^4 - 3^5 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 8^5$	$64237 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^0 + 3^1 - 7^1$
$63748 := -6^4 + 3^3 - 7^1 + 4^8 - 8^3$	$64023 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 0^1 + 2^9 - 3^6$	$64238 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^1 + 3^0 - 8^0$
$63762 := -6^3 + 3^1 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 2^9$	$64026 := -6^3 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 2^0 - 6^4$	$64239 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 3^0 - 9^0$
$63764 := -6^1 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$64043 := -6^5 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$64240 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 0^1$
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$63834 := -6^2 + 3^5 - 8^4 + 3^7 + 4^8$	$64159 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 1^0 + 5^0 - 9^2$	$64246 := -6^1 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 4^8 - 6^4$

$64247 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 7^1$	$64290 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^5 + 9^2 + 0^0$	$64353 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 3^5 + 5^1 - 3^6$
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$64250 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 0^0$	$64295 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 9^2 - 5^2$	$64356 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^4$
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$64273 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 7^1 + 3^3$	$64329 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 3^8 + 2^4 + 9^5$	$64386 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 6^0$
$64274 := -6^4 + 4^0 - 2^4 + 7^2 + 4^8$	$64330 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 0^1$	$64393 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 3^2 + 9^2 + 3^4$
$64276 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 7^0 + 6^2$	$64331 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 1^0$	$64394 := -6^2 - 4^5 - 3^0 - 9^2 + 4^8$
$64278 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^5 + 7^1 - 8^0$	$64332 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 2^6$	$64395 := -6^3 - 4^5 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 5^2$
$64279 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 7^2 - 9^1$	$64333 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 3^4$	$64396 := -6^1 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 9^2 - 6^4$
$64280 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 0^1$	$64334 := -6^3 - 4^4 - 3^0 - 3^6 + 4^8$	$64397 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 7^2$
$64281 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 1^0$	$64335 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 5^1$	$64399 := -6^4 + 4^1 + 3^4 + 9^4 + 9^5$
$64282 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 2^5$	$64336 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 6^1$	$64422 := -6^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 2^1 + 2^7$
$64283 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^3 + 8^1 + 3^3$	$64337 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 7^1$	$64423 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 2^1 - 3^4$
$64284 := -6^2 - 4^5 - 2^7 - 8^2 + 4^8$	$64338 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 8^1$	$64424 := -6^3 + 4^3 - 4^5 + 2^6 + 4^8$
$64285 := -6^4 - 4^7 - 2^8 + 8^4 + 5^7$	$64339 := -6^4 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 9^5$	$64425 := -6^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 2^2 + 5^3$
$64286 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 6^2$	$64342 := -6^4 + 4^0 - 3^3 + 4^8 + 2^7$	$64426 := -6^1 + 4^3 + 4^8 + 2^7 - 6^4$
$64287 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^4 + 8^2 - 7^0$	$64345 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 3^4 + 4^8 + 5^2$	$64427 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 2^7 + 7^2$
$64288 := -6^3 - 4^5 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 8^5$	$64349 := -6^3 + 4^0 - 3^5 + 4^8 - 9^3$	$64428 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 2^4 - 8^2$
$64289 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^4 + 8^2 + 9^0$	$64352 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 3^0 + 5^4 - 2^9$	$64429 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 2^2 - 9^2$

- 64441 := $-6^1 - 4^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 1^0$ 64498 := $-6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 9^1 + 8^0$ 64650 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 6^4 + 5^4 + 0^0$
64442 := $-6^1 + 4^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 2^7$ 64502 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 0^0 + 2^8$ 64663 := $-6^2 + 4^8 - 6^4 + 6^3 + 3^5$
64443 := $-6^1 - 4^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 3^0$ 64504 := $-6^1 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 0^0 + 4^8$ 64665 := $-6^2 + 4^8 - 6^3 + 6^1 - 5^4$
64444 := $-6^2 - 4^2 - 4^2 - 4^5 + 4^8$ 64520 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 2^8 - 0^0$ 64666 := $-6^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 6^3 - 6^4$
64445 := $-6^1 + 4^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 5^3$ 64522 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 2^8$ 64667 := $-6^2 + 4^5 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 7^5$
64448 := $-6^4 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 4^8 - 8^2$ 64533 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 3^4 - 3^5$ 64668 := $-6^2 + 4^4 + 6^6 + 6^7 - 8^6$
64449 := $-6^4 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 4^8 + 9^2$ 64534 := $-6^1 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 3^3 + 4^8$ 64675 := $-6^1 - 4^0 + 6^6 + 7^4 + 5^6$
64450 := $-6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 5^2 - 0^0$ 64535 := $-6^3 + 4^3 - 5^6 + 3^7 + 5^7$ 64682 := $-6^1 + 4^8 - 6^4 + 8^3 - 2^6$
64452 := $-6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 2^0$ 64536 := $-6^4 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 3^4 + 6^3$ 64684 := $-6^2 - 4^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 4^8$
64456 := $-6^4 - 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^0 + 6^3$ 64537 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 3^5 + 7^2$ 64695 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 6^0 + 9^0 - 5^4$
64457 := $-6^4 - 4^0 + 4^8 - 5^3 + 7^3$ 64538 := $-6^2 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 3^2 - 8^4$ 64712 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 2^7$
64460 := $-6^4 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 0^1$ 64539 := $-6^4 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 3^5 + 9^2$ 64722 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 7^3 + 2^0 - 2^8$
64461 := $-6^4 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 1^0$ 64540 := $-6^4 - 4^7 + 5^7 + 4^6 - 0^0$ 64723 := $-6^2 + 4^8 - 7^2 + 2^0 - 3^6$
64462 := $-6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 6^2 - 2^3$ 64542 := $-6^4 - 4^7 + 5^7 + 4^6 + 2^0$ 64732 := $-6^4 + 4^8 - 7^1 + 3^5 + 2^8$
64463 := $-6^4 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 3^1$ 64553 := $-6^4 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 5^5 - 3^7$ 64733 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 3^5 + 3^5$
64464 := $-6^4 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 4^8$ 64554 := $-6^1 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 5^5 + 4^8$ 64735 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 5^3$
64465 := $-6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 6^2 - 5^1$ 64556 := $-6^4 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 5^3 + 6^3$ 64739 := $-6^6 + 4^3 + 7^6 + 3^5 - 9^4$
64466 := $-6^1 + 4^2 + 4^8 + 6^3 - 6^4$ 64557 := $-6^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 5^2 - 7^3$ 64745 := $-6^3 + 4^0 + 7^2 + 4^8 - 5^4$
64467 := $-6^2 + 4^2 + 4^5 + 6^6 + 7^5$ 64558 := $-6^1 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 5^5 - 8^4$ 64752 := $-6^4 + 4^8 - 7^0 + 5^0 + 2^9$
64468 := $-6^4 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 8^1$ 64563 := $-6^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 + 6^0 + 3^7$ 64753 := $-6^1 + 4^8 - 7^2 + 5^0 - 3^6$
64469 := $-6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 6^2 - 9^0$ 64572 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 7^3 - 2^4$ 64757 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 7^2 + 5^3 + 7^3$
64470 := $-6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 7^1 + 0^0$ 64573 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 7^1 - 3^6$ 64758 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 8^3$
64474 := $-6^2 - 4^0 - 4^5 - 7^0 + 4^8$ 64574 := $-6^4 - 4^1 - 5^1 + 7^3 + 4^8$ 64773 := $-6^2 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 7^0 - 3^6$
64476 := $-6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 7^0 - 6^0$ 64576 := $-6^1 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 7^3 - 6^4$ 64775 := $-6^2 + 4^8 - 7^0 + 7^4 - 5^5$
64476 := $-6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 7^0 + 6^0$ 64577 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 5^0 + 7^3 - 7^1$ 64779 := $-6^2 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 7^1 - 9^3$
64478 := $-6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 8^0$ 64578 := $-6^2 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^4$ 64792 := $-6^4 + 4^8 - 7^2 + 9^3 - 2^7$
64482 := $-6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 8^1 - 2^4$ 64579 := $-6^4 + 4^8 - 5^1 + 7^3 + 9^0$ 64795 := $-6^2 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 5^5$
64483 := $-6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 8^1 - 3^0$ 64593 := $-6^1 + 4^8 - 5^5 + 9^0 + 3^7$ 64803 := $-6^1 + 4^8 + 8^0 + 0^0 - 3^6$
64484 := $-6^2 - 4^5 + 4^2 - 8^1 + 4^8$ 64597 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 5^5 + 9^0 + 7^4$ 64804 := $-6^3 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 0^1 + 4^8$
64485 := $-6^2 - 4^4 + 4^7 + 8^5 + 5^6$ 64599 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 9^1 - 9^3$ 64807 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 0^1 - 7^0$
64487 := $-6^7 - 4^3 + 4^8 + 8^6 + 7^5$ 64627 := $-6^4 + 4^8 + 6^2 + 2^3 + 7^3$ 64808 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 0^0 - 8^3$
64488 := $-6^3 - 4^4 + 4^8 - 8^2 - 8^3$ 64629 := $-6^3 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 2^5 - 9^3$ 64809 := $-6^1 + 4^8 + 8^1 + 0^1 - 9^3$
64489 := $-6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 8^1 - 9^1$ 64643 := $-6^1 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 4^8 - 3^7$ 64810 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 1^0 + 0^0$
64493 := $-6^4 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 9^1 + 3^5$ 64645 := $-6^3 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 4^8 + 5^4$ 64822 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 2^4 - 2^1$
64494 := $-6^4 - 4^0 + 4^4 - 9^0 + 4^8$ 64648 := $-6^4 + 4^4 + 6^3 + 4^8 - 8^2$ 64823 := $-6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 2^4 - 3^0$
64496 := $-6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 9^1 - 6^0$ 64649 := $-6^1 + 4^3 - 6^3 + 4^8 - 9^3$ 64824 := $-6^3 - 4^2 - 8^3 + 2^5 + 4^8$

$64825 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 2^4 + 5^0$	$64962 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 6^0 - 2^3$	$65248 := -6^1 - 5^2 - 2^8 + 4^8 - 8^0$
$64832 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 3^4 + 2^9$	$64963 := -6^4 + 4^0 - 9^2 + 6^6 + 3^9$	$65254 := -6^1 - 5^2 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 4^8$
$64833 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 3^5 - 3^6$	$64964 := -6^4 - 4^1 + 9^3 - 6^0 + 4^8$	$65259 := -6^2 + 5^5 - 2^2 + 5^5 + 9^5$
$64834 := -6^2 - 4^0 + 8^2 - 3^6 + 4^8$	$64965 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 6^0 - 5^1$	$65264 := -6^3 - 5^2 - 2^5 + 6^0 + 4^8$
$64835 := -6^7 - 4^8 - 8^0 + 3^9 + 5^8$	$64969 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 6^0 + 9^3$	$65274 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 2^8 + 7^0 + 4^8$
$64836 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 3^3 + 6^0$	$64970 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 0^1$	$65276 := -6^4 + 5^5 - 2^4 + 7^5 + 6^6$
$64843 := -6^1 - 4^4 - 8^3 + 4^8 + 3^4$	$64971 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 1^0$	$65284 := -6^3 - 5^1 - 2^5 + 8^0 + 4^8$
$64845 := -6^1 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 4^8 - 5^4$	$64972 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 2^1$	$65293 := -6^2 - 5^2 - 2^8 + 9^5 + 3^8$
$64847 := -6^4 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 7^3$	$64973 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 3^1$	$65294 := -6^3 - 5^0 - 2^4 - 9^1 + 4^8$
$64849 := -6^1 - 4^2 + 8^2 + 4^8 - 9^3$	$64974 := -6^3 - 4^1 + 9^0 - 7^3 + 4^8$	$65295 := -6^1 + 5^5 + 2^1 + 9^5 + 5^5$
$64856 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 8^1 + 5^4 - 6^0$	$64975 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 7^2 + 5^3$	$65304 := -6^3 - 5^2 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 4^8$
$64857 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 5^4 - 7^1$	$64976 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 6^1$	$65324 := -6^1 + 5^1 - 3^5 + 2^5 + 4^8$
$64858 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 8^0 + 5^4 - 8^1$	$64977 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 7^0 - 7^3$	$65329 := -6^3 - 5^0 + 3^8 - 2^6 + 9^5$
$64865 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 6^0 + 5^4$	$64978 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 8^1$	$65341 := -6^3 - 5^1 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 1^0$
$64869 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 9^2$	$64979 := -6^4 + 4^6 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 9^5$	$65342 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 3^0 + 4^8 - 2^6$
$64875 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 7^0 - 5^4$	$64984 := -6^3 - 4^4 - 9^2 + 8^0 + 4^8$	$65343 := -6^1 - 5^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 3^4$
$64885 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 8^1 + 8^3 + 5^3$	$64987 := -6^3 + 4^8 + 9^1 + 8^0 - 7^3$	$65344 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 4^8$
$64890 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 + 0^0$	$64988 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 8^0 - 8^3$	$65345 := -6^3 + 5^0 - 3^0 + 4^8 + 5^2$
$64904 := -6^4 - 4^3 + 9^3 - 0^0 + 4^8$	$64992 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 9^2 + 9^1 - 2^8$	$65345 := -6^3 - 5^0 + 3^0 + 4^8 + 5^2$
$64905 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 0^0 - 5^4$	$64994 := -6^4 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 9^3 + 4^8$	$65346 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^3$
$64908 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 9^2 + 0^0 - 8^3$	$64995 := -6^1 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 9^5 - 5^4$	$65347 := -6^1 - 5^3 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 7^2$
$64915 := -6^1 + 4^8 + 9^1 + 1^0 - 5^4$	$64996 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 9^1 + 6^3$	$65348 := -6^1 + 5^3 - 3^5 + 4^8 - 8^2$
$64928 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 2^7 - 8^0$	$64998 := -6^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 + 9^5 - 8^3$	$65349 := -6^2 - 5^3 - 3^3 + 4^8 + 9^0$
$64932 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 3^1 + 2^7$	$65042 := -6^1 + 5^2 - 0^0 + 4^8 - 2^9$	$65364 := -6^1 - 5^4 + 3^5 + 6^3 + 4^8$
$64933 := -6^2 + 4^8 + 9^2 + 3^4 - 3^6$	$65074 := -6^4 - 5^7 + 0^1 - 7^6 + 4^9$	$65369 := -6^3 - 5^2 + 3^9 + 6^6 - 9^3$
$64935 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 3^2 + 5^3$	$65094 := -6^4 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 4^8$	$65384 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 3^4 - 8^2 + 4^8$
$64936 := -6^2 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 3^1 - 6^4$	$65142 := -6^1 + 5^3 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 2^9$	$65385 := -6^5 - 5^4 - 3^5 - 8^4 + 5^7$
$64937 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 3^1 + 7^3$	$65147 := -6^3 - 5^3 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 7^2$	$65387 := -6^2 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 8^4 - 7^5$
$64938 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^2 + 3^0 - 8^3$	$65204 := -6^3 - 5^3 + 2^3 + 0^0 + 4^8$	$65390 := -6^3 - 5^1 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 0^0$
$64939 := -6^1 + 4^3 - 9^3 + 3^8 + 9^5$	$65234 := -6^2 - 5^0 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^8$	$65392 := -6^3 - 5^0 + 3^8 + 9^5 - 2^0$
$64943 := -6^4 + 4^0 + 9^3 + 4^8 - 3^3$	$65240 := -6^2 - 5^1 - 2^8 + 4^8 + 0^0$	$65394 := -6^3 + 5^0 + 3^8 + 9^5 - 4^0$
$64945 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 9^2 + 4^8 + 5^4$	$65242 := -6^2 - 5^0 - 2^0 + 4^8 - 2^8$	$65394 := -6^3 - 5^0 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 4^0$
$64953 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 5^3 + 3^3$	$65243 := -6^3 + 5^1 - 2^0 + 4^8 - 3^4$	$65396 := -6^3 + 5^0 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 6^0$
$64954 := -6^4 - 4^2 + 9^3 + 5^0 + 4^8$	$65244 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 4^8$	$65398 := -6^3 + 5^1 + 3^8 + 9^5 - 8^0$
$64956 := -6^4 - 4^6 - 9^0 + 5^7 - 6^5$	$65246 := -6^2 + 5^0 - 2^8 + 4^8 + 6^0$	$65402 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 0^0 - 2^7$
$64958 := -6^4 - 4^2 + 9^5 + 5^5 + 8^4$	$65247 := -6^1 - 5^4 - 2^0 + 4^8 + 7^3$	$65403 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 - 0^0 - 3^0$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| $65404 := -6^1 - 5^3 - 4^0 + 0^1 + 4^8$ | $65455 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 5^2 - 5^2$ | $65504 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 5^2 + 0^1 + 4^8$ |
| $65405 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 0^0 - 5^3$ | $65456 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 6^1$ | $65524 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 - 2^2 + 4^8$ |
| $65406 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 0^1 + 6^0$ | $65457 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 5^0 - 7^2$ | $65525 := -6^2 - 5^6 + 5^5 - 2^6 + 5^7$ |
| $65407 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 7^0$ | $65458 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 8^1$ | $65540 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 0^1$ |
| $65412 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 - 1^0 + 2^3$ | $65459 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 5^1 - 9^2$ | $65541 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 1^0$ |
| $65413 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 - 1^0 + 3^2$ | $65460 := -6^2 - 5^1 + 4^8 - 6^2 + 0^0$ | $65542 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 2^3$ |
| $65418 := -6^1 - 5^4 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 8^3$ | $65462 := -6^1 - 5^1 + 4^8 + 6^0 - 2^6$ | $65543 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 3^2$ |
| $65419 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 1^0 - 9^2$ | $65464 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 4^3 - 6^0 + 4^8$ | $65544 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 4^2 + 4^8$ |
| $65420 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 2^4 - 0^0$ | $65466 := -6^2 + 5^0 + 4^8 + 6^0 - 6^2$ | $65545 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 5^1$ |
| $65422 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 2^0 + 2^4$ | $65467 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 6^0 - 7^1$ | $65546 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 6^1$ |
| $65423 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 2^0 - 3^4$ | $65468 := -6^1 + 5^0 + 4^8 + 6^0 - 8^2$ | $65547 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 5^2 + 4^8 - 7^1$ |
| $65424 := -6^3 - 5^2 + 4^0 + 2^7 + 4^8$ | $65472 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 7^1 - 2^6$ | $65548 := -6^1 + 5^0 + 5^2 + 4^8 - 8^1$ |
| $65427 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 2^0 - 7^2$ | $65473 := -6^1 - 5^1 + 4^8 - 7^2 - 3^1$ | $65549 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 9^1$ |
| $65431 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 3^3 - 1^0$ | $65474 := -6^1 + 5^0 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 4^8$ | $65564 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 4^8$ |
| $65432 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 3^4 - 2^4$ | $65475 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 7^2 - 5^1$ | $65569 := -6^1 - 5^4 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^5$ |
| $65433 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 3^2 - 3^4$ | $65476 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 7^1 - 6^2$ | $65584 := -6^1 - 5^1 - 5^1 + 8^2 + 4^8$ |
| $65434 := -6^1 - 5^1 - 4^3 - 3^3 + 4^8$ | $65477 := -6^1 - 5^1 + 4^8 + 7^0 - 7^2$ | $65624 := -6^2 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 2^7 + 4^8$ |
| $65435 := -6^3 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 3^2 + 5^3$ | $65478 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 7^1 - 8^2$ | $65634 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 6^3 - 3^4 + 4^8$ |
| $65436 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 3^3 - 6^2$ | $65479 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 7^2 - 9^0$ | $65639 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 9^5$ |
| $65437 := -6^1 - 5^1 + 4^8 - 3^4 - 7^1$ | $65482 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 8^0 - 2^4$ | $65642 := -6^1 + 5^4 - 6^0 + 4^8 - 2^9$ |
| $65438 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$ | $65483 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 3^2$ | $65647 := -6^1 + 5^3 - 6^0 + 4^8 - 7^1$ |
| $65439 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 3^2 - 9^2$ | $65484 := -6^2 - 5^0 - 4^2 + 8^0 + 4^8$ | $65648 := -6^1 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 4^8 - 8^1$ |
| $65440 := -6^1 - 5^2 - 4^3 + 4^8 - 0^0$ | $65486 := -6^2 - 5^1 + 4^8 - 8^1 - 6^0$ | $65653 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 3^9$ |
| $65442 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^0 + 4^8 - 2^6$ | $65487 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 8^0 - 7^2$ | $65654 := -6^1 + 5^1 - 6^1 + 5^3 + 4^8$ |
| $65443 := -6^1 - 5^1 - 4^0 + 4^8 - 3^4$ | $65488 := -6^2 - 5^1 + 4^8 + 8^0 - 8^1$ | $65655 := -6^1 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 5^7 - 5^6$ |
| $65445 := -6^3 + 5^0 - 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^3$ | $65489 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 8^0 - 9^1$ | $65658 := -6^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 5^7 + 8^5$ |
| $65445 := -6^3 - 5^0 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^3$ | $65490 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 9^1 + 0^1$ | $65659 := -6^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 5^3 + 9^5$ |
| $65447 := -6^2 - 5^1 + 4^0 + 4^8 - 7^2$ | $65491 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 9^1 + 1^0$ | $65674 := -6^3 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 4^8$ |
| $65448 := -6^3 + 5^3 + 4^1 + 4^8 - 8^0$ | $65492 := -6^1 - 5^1 + 4^8 - 9^0 - 2^5$ | $65685 := -6^3 - 5^7 - 6^0 + 8^7 - 5^9$ |
| $65449 := -6^1 + 5^0 - 4^0 + 4^8 - 9^2$ | $65493 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 9^1 - 3^3$ | $65693 := -6^1 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 9^5 + 3^8$ |
| $65449 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^0 + 4^8 - 9^2$ | $65494 := -6^2 - 5^0 - 4^1 - 9^0 + 4^8$ | $65695 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 9^5 + 5^7$ |
| $65450 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 0^1$ | $65495 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 9^1 - 5^2$ | $65704 := -6^1 + 5^3 + 7^2 + 0^1 + 4^8$ |
| $65451 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 1^0$ | $65496 := -6^1 + 5^0 + 4^8 + 9^0 - 6^2$ | $65724 := -6^1 + 5^2 - 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^8$ |
| $65452 := -6^1 + 5^2 + 4^8 + 5^2 - 2^7$ | $65497 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 9^2 + 7^2$ | $65742 := -6^1 + 5^1 - 7^2 + 4^8 + 2^8$ |
| $65453 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 5^1 - 3^4$ | $65498 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 9^0 - 8^1$ | $65743 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 7^4 + 4^8 - 3^7$ |
| $65454 := -6^2 - 5^1 - 4^2 - 5^2 + 4^8$ | $65499 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 9^0 - 9^0$ | $65744 := -6^1 - 5^3 + 7^3 - 4^1 + 4^8$ |

$65746 := -6^1 + 5^0 - 7^0 + 4^8 + 6^3$	$66133 := -6^3 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 3^9$	$66338 := -6^1 + 6^6 - 3^1 + 3^9 + 8^1$
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$65747 := -6^1 - 5^3 - 7^0 + 4^8 + 7^3$	$66194 := -6^2 - 6^2 + 1^0 + 9^3 + 4^8$	$66342 := -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 2^3$
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$65764 := -6^1 + 5^2 - 7^1 + 6^3 + 4^8$	$66234 := -6^2 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^8$	$66344 := -6^3 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 4^5 + 4^8$
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$65788 := -6^3 + 5^3 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 8^5$	$66243 := -6^2 + 6^1 + 2^3 + 4^8 + 3^6$	$66357 := -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 7^0$
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$65858 := -6^2 - 5^7 - 8^1 - 5^9 + 8^7$	$66254 := -6^2 + 6^0 + 2^7 + 5^4 + 4^8$	$66374 := -6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 4^3$
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$65876 := -6^6 + 5^7 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 6^4$	$66264 := -6^1 + 6^1 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 4^8$	$66377 := -6^3 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 7^4 + 7^5$
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$65942 := -6^3 + 5^4 - 9^0 + 4^8 - 2^1$	$66303 := -6^2 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 0^0 + 3^9$	$66393 := -6^2 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 3^9$
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$66132 := -6^3 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 2^3$	$66337 := -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^1 + 3^9 + 7^0$	$66464 := -6^3 - 6^3 + 4^3 + 6^4 + 4^8$

$66469 := -6^1 - 6^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 9^3$	$66748 := -6^2 + 6^4 - 7^2 + 4^8 + 8^0$	$66936 := -6^1 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 6^5$
$66474 := -6^2 - 6^0 + 4^5 - 7^2 + 4^8$	$66759 := -6^4 - 6^5 + 7^5 - 5^2 + 9^5$	$66945 := -6^1 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 5^3$
$66483 := -6^1 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^1 + 3^6$	$66769 := -6^1 - 6^0 - 7^2 + 6^5 + 9^5$	$66952 := -6^1 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 2^7$
$66484 := -6^1 - 6^1 + 4^5 - 8^2 + 4^8$	$66789 := -6^2 + 6^5 - 7^0 + 8^0 + 9^5$	$66953 := -6^1 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 3^2$
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$66489 := -6^3 - 6^4 + 4^8 - 8^4 + 9^4$	$66791 := -6^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$66994 := -6^1 + 6^1 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 4^8$
$66534 := -6^2 + 6^6 - 5^2 + 3^9 + 4^4$	$66792 := -6^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 2^1$	$66995 := -6^2 + 6^4 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 5^3$
$66539 := -6^1 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 9^2$	$66793 := -6^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 - 3^3$	$66996 := -6^2 + 6^3 - 9^1 + 9^5 + 6^5$
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$66576 := -6^1 - 6^1 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$66804 := -6^2 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$67298 := -6^5 - 7^5 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 8^5$
$66592 := -6^3 + 6^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 - 2^4$	$66819 := -6^1 + 6^5 - 8^0 + 1^0 + 9^5$	$67328 := -6^6 + 7^6 - 3^4 + 2^9 - 8^4$
$66593 := -6^3 + 6^5 - 5^2 + 9^5 + 3^2$	$66823 := -6^2 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^9 + 3^9$	$67342 := -6^1 - 7^3 + 3^7 + 4^8 - 2^5$
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$66609 := -6^3 - 6^0 + 6^5 + 0^0 + 9^5$	$66834 := -6^1 + 6^4 - 8^0 + 3^2 + 4^8$	$67363 := -6^4 + 7^4 - 3^4 + 6^6 + 3^9$
$66614 := -6^3 - 6^0 + 6^4 - 1^0 + 4^8$	$66842 := -6^1 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 2^3$	$67364 := -6^1 + 7^1 + 3^9 + 6^6 + 4^5$
$66624 := -6^3 + 6^1 + 6^4 + 2^1 + 4^8$	$66843 := -6^1 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 3^2$	$67385 := -6^3 - 7^5 + 3^7 + 8^4 + 5^7$
$66642 := -6^1 - 6^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 2^5$	$66844 := -6^2 + 6^4 + 8^2 + 4^8 - 4^2$	$67415 := -6^4 + 7^2 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 5^5$
$66643 := -6^3 + 6^2 + 6^4 + 4^8 - 3^2$	$66854 := -6^4 + 6^0 - 8^3 + 5^5 + 4^8$	$67432 := -6^2 + 7^0 + 4^8 + 3^7 - 2^8$
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$66692 := -6^1 + 6^0 + 6^5 + 9^5 - 2^7$	$66905 := -6^5 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^6$	$67453 := -6^3 - 7^2 + 4^8 - 5^1 + 3^7$
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$66746 := -6^2 - 6^0 - 7^2 + 4^8 + 6^4$	$66935 := -6^5 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 5^6$	$67524 := -6^3 + 7^6 + 5^6 + 2^1 - 4^8$

$67527 := -6^6 - 7^3 - 5^5 + 2^1 + 7^6$	$67923 := -6^3 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 3^8$	$68425 := -6^4 + 8^4 + 4^8 + 2^6 + 5^2$
$67542 := -6^4 + 7^2 + 5^5 + 4^8 + 2^7$	$67924 := -6^1 + 7^4 - 9^1 + 2^1 + 4^8$	$68427 := -6^1 - 8^5 - 4^7 - 2^6 + 7^6$
$67543 := -6^1 - 7^2 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$67925 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 - 2^5 + 5^7$	$68435 := -6^3 - 8^0 + 4^8 - 3^2 + 5^5$
$67547 := -6^3 - 7^2 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 7^4$	$67927 := -6^6 - 7^4 - 9^3 + 2^6 + 7^6$	$68445 := -6^3 + 8^0 - 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^5$
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$67568 := -6^6 + 7^6 - 5^4 + 6^4 - 8^4$	$67941 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 1^0$	$68447 := -6^1 + 8^3 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 7^4$
$67634 := -6^1 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 3^4 + 4^6$	$67942 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 2^1$	$68452 := -6^3 - 8^0 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 2^3$
$67636 := -6^1 + 7^1 + 6^4 + 3^9 + 6^6$	$67943 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 3^1$	$68453 := -6^3 - 8^0 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 3^2$
$67644 := -6^2 + 7^4 - 6^0 + 4^8 - 4^4$	$67944 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 4^8$	$68454 := -6^3 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 4^8$
$67649 := -6^5 - 7^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$67945 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 5^1$	$68467 := -6^2 - 8^5 - 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^6$
$67652 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 6^3 + 5^7 - 2^9$	$67946 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 6^1$	$68534 := -6^2 - 8^2 + 5^5 - 3^3 + 4^8$
$67694 := -6^2 + 7^4 - 6^3 + 9^1 + 4^8$	$67947 := -6^1 + 7^1 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 7^4$	$68543 := -6^2 - 8^0 + 5^5 + 4^8 - 3^4$
$67724 := -6^2 - 7^2 + 7^4 - 2^7 + 4^8$	$67948 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 8^1$	$68557 := -6^6 + 8^2 - 5^5 + 5^4 + 7^6$
$67729 := -6^5 - 7^3 + 7^5 - 2^3 + 9^5$	$67949 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 9^1$	$68573 := -6^4 - 8^4 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 3^8$
$67743 := -6^2 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$67950 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 9^0 + 5^7 + 0^0$	$68576 := -6^1 - 8^3 + 5^7 - 7^5 + 6^5$
$67744 := -6^3 + 7^1 + 7^4 + 4^2 + 4^8$	$67956 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 + 5^7 - 6^0$	$68597 := -6^5 + 8^3 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^5$
$67745 := -6^3 - 7^0 + 7^4 + 4^8 + 5^2$	$67958 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 + 5^7 + 8^0$	$68649 := -6^4 - 8^4 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 9^3$
$67746 := -6^4 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 4^8 - 6^4$	$67962 := -6^4 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 2^5$	$68674 := -6^4 + 8^0 - 6^6 + 7^6 - 4^5$
$67764 := -6^3 + 7^1 + 7^4 + 6^2 + 4^8$	$67966 := -6^4 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 6^5$	$68733 := -6^6 - 8^2 + 7^6 - 3^2 - 3^7$
$67782 := -6^2 - 7^5 + 7^6 - 8^5 - 2^8$	$67983 := -6^2 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 3^8$	$68734 := -6^1 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 3^5 - 4^7$
$67784 := -6^3 - 7^0 + 7^4 + 8^2 + 4^8$	$67984 := -6^4 - 7^3 - 9^1 + 8^4 + 4^8$	$68735 := -6^5 - 8^4 + 7^4 + 3^4 + 5^7$
$67805 := -6^6 + 7^6 - 8^2 + 0^0 - 5^5$	$67987 := -6^1 - 7^5 - 9^2 - 8^5 + 7^6$	$68736 := -6^1 - 8^2 + 7^6 - 3^7 - 6^6$
$67834 := -6^3 + 7^2 - 8^4 + 3^8 + 4^8$	$67998 := -6^4 + 7^5 - 9^4 + 9^5 - 8^0$	$68737 := -6^6 + 8^2 - 7^4 + 3^4 + 7^6$
$67835 := -6^2 - 7^5 - 8^1 + 3^8 + 5^7$	$68079 := -6^5 - 8^0 + 0^1 + 7^5 + 9^5$	$68743 := -6^6 - 8^2 + 7^6 + 4^0 - 3^7$
$67837 := -6^6 - 7^4 - 8^3 - 3^5 + 7^6$	$68153 := -6^5 - 8^1 - 1^0 + 5^7 - 3^7$	$68744 := -6^3 - 8^0 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 4^8$
$67845 := -6^3 + 7^4 - 8^0 + 4^8 + 5^3$	$68224 := -6^4 + 8^4 - 2^7 + 2^4 + 4^8$	$68777 := -6^1 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 7^5 + 7^5$
$67849 := -6^1 + 7^4 - 8^0 + 4^8 - 9^2$	$68334 := -6^4 + 8^4 - 3^1 + 3^0 + 4^8$	$68797 := -6^1 - 8^5 - 7^5 + 9^3 + 7^6$
$67852 := -6^5 - 7^4 - 8^2 + 5^7 - 2^5$	$68340 := -6^4 + 8^4 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 0^0$	$68844 := -6^4 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 4^8 - 4^1$
$67853 := -6^3 - 7^1 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$68344 := -6^4 - 8^0 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 4^8$	$68845 := -6^6 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 5^7$
$67854 := -6^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 5^3 + 4^8$	$68346 := -6^4 + 8^4 + 3^2 + 4^8 + 6^0$	$68847 := -6^4 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 4^8 - 7^0$
$67857 := -6^3 - 7^5 - 8^5 - 5^0 + 7^6$	$68354 := -6^1 + 8^3 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 4^8$	$68848 := -6^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 8^5$
$67859 := -6^4 - 7^4 - 8^1 + 5^7 - 9^4$	$68359 := -6^4 - 8^4 + 3^7 + 5^7 - 9^4$	$68849 := -6^4 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 4^8 + 9^0$
$67874 := -6^1 + 7^1 - 8^2 + 7^4 + 4^8$	$68364 := -6^4 + 8^4 + 3^3 + 6^0 + 4^8$	$68934 := -6^3 - 8^4 + 9^5 - 3^7 + 4^7$
$67875 := -6^6 - 7^0 + 8^1 + 7^6 - 5^5$	$68374 := -6^6 + 8^5 - 3^4 + 7^5 + 4^8$	$68967 := -6^4 - 8^0 - 9^3 - 6^6 + 7^6$
$67885 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 8^0 - 8^2 + 5^7$	$68394 := -6^4 + 8^4 + 3^8 + 9^5 - 4^2$	$68976 := -6^4 + 8^1 - 9^3 + 7^6 - 6^6$
$67894 := -6^2 + 7^4 - 8^1 + 9^0 + 4^8$	$68424 := -6^3 + 8^4 - 4^5 + 2^5 + 4^8$	$69055 := -6^1 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 - 5^6$

$$\begin{aligned} 69064 &:= -6^5 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 6^7 - 4^9 & 69493 &:= -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 3^1 & 69697 &:= -6^4 - 9^0 - 6^6 + 9^0 + 7^6 \\ 69079 &:= -6^3 - 9^4 + 0^1 + 7^5 + 9^5 & 69494 &:= -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 9^5 + 4^6 & 69706 &:= -6^4 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 0^1 - 6^6 \\ 69234 &:= -6^3 + 9^5 - 2^8 + 3^8 + 4^6 & 69495 &:= -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 5^1 & 69724 &:= -6^2 + 9^4 - 7^4 + 2^6 + 4^8 \\ 69237 &:= -6^6 - 9^2 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 7^6 & 69496 &:= -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 6^1 & 69743 &:= -6^3 + 9^4 + 7^2 + 4^8 - 3^7 \\ 69245 &:= -6^4 - 9^4 + 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^7 & 69497 &:= -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 7^1 & 69746 &:= -6^3 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 4^8 + 6^4 \\ 69273 &:= -6^1 + 9^5 - 2^4 + 7^5 - 3^8 & 69498 &:= -6^3 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 9^2 + 8^4 & 69748 &:= -6^6 - 9^3 + 7^6 - 4^1 - 8^3 \\ 69275 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 - 2^1 - 7^3 + 5^7 & 69499 &:= -6^3 + 9^1 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 9^5 & 69749 &:= -6^1 + 9^4 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 9^5 \\ 69279 &:= -6^6 - 9^3 - 2^8 + 7^6 - 9^3 & 69523 &:= -6^4 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 2^4 - 3^8 & 69762 &:= -6^1 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 - 2^8 \\ 69297 &:= -6^1 - 9^4 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 7^5 & 69524 &:= -6^2 - 9^5 + 5^8 + 2^7 - 4^9 & 69769 &:= -6^4 - 9^1 + 7^6 - 6^6 + 9^2 \\ 69325 &:= -6^2 - 9^4 - 3^7 - 2^4 + 5^7 & 69538 &:= -6^4 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 3^8 - 8^0 & 69785 &:= -6^2 - 9^5 - 7^6 + 8^6 - 5^6 \\ 69327 &:= -6^6 + 9^1 - 3^7 + 2^9 + 7^6 & 69543 &:= -6^3 + 9^5 + 5^5 + 4^5 + 3^8 & 69786 &:= -6^4 + 9^2 + 7^6 + 8^1 - 6^6 \\ 69343 &:= -6^4 - 9^3 - 3^6 + 4^8 + 3^8 & 69544 &:= -6^1 - 9^2 - 5^0 + 4^6 + 4^8 & 69835 &:= -6^5 - 9^0 - 8^3 - 3^0 + 5^7 \\ 69344 &:= -6^2 - 9^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 4^8 & 69548 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 4^3 - 8^1 & 69843 &:= -6^5 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 4^7 + 3^7 \\ 69345 &:= -6^1 - 9^5 - 3^4 - 4^9 + 5^8 & 69562 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 5^7 + 6^1 - 2^6 & 69852 &:= -6^5 - 9^0 - 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^4 \\ 69347 &:= -6^5 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 4^5 + 7^5 & 69564 &:= -6^2 + 9^4 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^7 & 69853 &:= -6^2 - 9^4 + 8^3 + 5^7 - 3^7 \\ 69348 &:= -6^2 + 9^5 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 8^3 & 69570 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 0^0 & 69854 &:= -6^5 + 9^0 - 8^3 + 5^7 + 4^2 \\ 69365 &:= -6^1 - 9^4 - 3^7 - 6^1 + 5^7 & 69572 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 7^2 + 2^0 & 69895 &:= -6^5 - 9^5 - 8^4 + 9^6 - 5^8 \\ 69367 &:= -6^5 + 9^5 - 3^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 & 69583 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 8^2 + 3^3 & 69927 &:= -6^6 - 9^2 - 9^3 - 2^8 + 7^6 \\ 69384 &:= -6^1 + 9^0 - 3^5 + 8^4 + 4^8 & 69615 &:= -6^1 - 9^3 - 6^5 + 1^0 + 5^7 & 69943 &:= -6^1 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 3^5 \\ 69385 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 - 3^5 + 8^1 + 5^7 & 69617 &:= -6^4 - 9^2 - 6^6 + 1^0 + 7^6 & 69945 &:= -6^3 - 9^5 + 9^3 - 4^9 + 5^8 \\ 69408 &:= -6^3 - 9^1 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 8^4 & 69625 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 5^7 & 69967 &:= -6^3 - 9^2 - 9^3 - 6^6 + 7^6 \\ 69414 &:= -6^3 - 9^0 + 4^6 - 1^0 + 4^8 & 69633 &:= -6^4 + 9^5 - 6^5 + 3^9 - 3^3 & & & 70386 &:= -7^2 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 6^6 \\ 69418 &:= -6^3 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 8^4 & 69634 &:= -6^2 + 9^5 - 6^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 & & & 70595 &:= -7^3 - 0^0 - 5^4 - 9^4 + 5^7 \\ 69425 &:= -6^1 - 9^5 - 4^9 - 2^0 + 5^8 & 69635 &:= -6^4 + 9^5 - 6^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 & & & 70675 &:= -7^3 + 0^1 - 6^6 + 7^6 + 5^2 \\ 69434 &:= -6^2 - 9^2 + 4^6 - 3^4 + 4^8 & 69652 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^2 + 5^7 - 2^2 & & & 70846 &:= -7^4 - 0^0 - 8^2 + 4^8 + 6^5 \\ 69435 &:= -6^1 - 9^4 + 4^3 - 3^7 + 5^7 & 69653 &:= -6^3 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 5^5 - 3^4 & & & 70855 &:= -7^2 + 0^1 - 8^4 - 5^5 + 5^7 \\ 69452 &:= -6^5 - 9^0 - 4^5 + 5^7 + 2^7 & 69655 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^2 - 5^0 + 5^7 & & & 70976 &:= -7^1 - 0^0 - 9^1 + 7^6 - 6^6 \\ 69453 &:= -6^1 - 9^5 - 4^9 + 5^8 + 3^3 & 69657 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 7^0 & & & 71243 &:= -7^3 + 1^0 - 2^9 + 4^8 + 3^8 \\ 69474 &:= -6^3 + 9^1 + 4^6 + 7^2 + 4^8 & 69672 &:= -6^4 - 9^1 - 6^6 + 7^6 - 2^4 & & & 71513 &:= -7^2 - 1^0 + 5^7 - 1^0 - 3^8 \\ 69475 &:= -6^1 - 9^5 - 4^9 + 7^2 + 5^8 & 69674 &:= -6^4 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 7^2 + 4^6 & & & 71553 &:= -7^1 + 1^0 - 5^1 + 5^7 - 3^8 \\ 69476 &:= -6^1 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 6^5 & 69675 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 5^7 & & & 71559 &:= -7^1 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 5^7 - 9^4 \\ 69479 &:= -6^3 - 9^0 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 9^4 & 69679 &:= -6^4 - 9^1 - 6^6 + 7^6 - 9^1 & & & 71578 &:= -7^2 - 1^0 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^4 \\ 69489 &:= -6^3 + 9^4 - 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^5 & 69685 &:= -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 5^7 & & & 72043 &:= -7^2 - 2^2 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 3^8 \\ 69490 &:= -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 0^1 & 69687 &:= -6^4 - 9^1 - 6^6 - 8^0 + 7^6 & & & 72049 &:= -7^2 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 9^4 \\ 69491 &:= -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 1^0 & 69694 &:= -6^1 + 9^4 - 6^1 + 9^5 + 4^6 & & & 72094 &:= -7^1 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 9^4 + 4^8 \\ 69492 &:= -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 2^1 & 69695 &:= -6^1 - 9^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 + 5^7 & & & 72234 &:= -7^1 + 2^4 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^8 \end{aligned}$$

$72259 := -7^4 + 2^1 - 2^4 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$72944 := -7^2 - 2^7 + 9^4 + 4^5 + 4^8$	$73578 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 8^1$
$72304 := -7^2 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$72946 := -7^3 - 2^5 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 6^5$	$73579 := -7^4 - 3^0 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^5$
$72325 := -7^1 + 2^8 - 3^8 + 2^9 + 5^7$	$72947 := -7^4 - 2^9 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 7^5$	$73587 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 8^0 + 7^2$
$72334 := -7^1 + 2^0 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 4^8$	$72949 := -7^4 - 2^1 - 9^2 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$73592 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 9^1 + 2^6$
$72342 := -7^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^8 + 2^8$	$72958 := -7^3 + 2^0 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 8^4$	$73593 := -7^3 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 9^5 - 3^6$
$72343 := -7^1 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^8 + 3^8$	$72964 := -7^3 - 2^2 - 9^0 + 6^5 + 4^8$	$73596 := -7^3 - 3^6 + 5^6 + 9^5 - 6^1$
$72344 := -7^1 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 4^8$	$73025 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 0^1 - 2^9 + 5^7$	$73599 := -7^3 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 9^3 + 9^5$
$72345 := -7^1 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 4^8 - 5^0$	$73246 := -7^1 - 3^3 - 2^5 + 4^8 + 6^5$	$73625 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 6^3 - 2^7 + 5^7$
$72347 := -7^1 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 4^8 + 7^0$	$73249 := -7^4 + 3^6 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$73626 := -7^1 - 3^9 + 6^6 + 2^2 + 6^6$
$72349 := -7^1 + 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 9^4$	$73258 := -7^4 - 3^8 - 2^0 + 5^7 + 8^4$	$73642 := -7^1 + 3^4 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 2^8$
$72355 := -7^4 - 2^0 - 3^5 - 5^5 + 5^7$	$73264 := -7^1 - 3^2 - 2^5 + 6^5 + 4^8$	$73645 := -7^2 - 3^5 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 5^4$
$72358 := -7^4 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^7 - 8^4$	$73285 := -7^1 - 3^6 - 2^3 - 8^4 + 5^7$	$73647 := -7^1 - 3^0 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 7^3$
$72383 := -7^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$73355 := -7^4 + 3^3 + 3^6 + 5^7 - 5^5$	$73648 := -7^2 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 4^7 + 8^4$
$72432 := -7^2 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 3^8 + 2^8$	$73358 := -7^4 - 3^5 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 8^2$	$73658 := -7^3 - 3^3 - 6^0 + 5^7 - 8^4$
$72435 := -7^2 + 2^9 + 4^8 + 3^8 - 5^3$	$73359 := -7^3 - 3^5 - 3^6 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$73686 := -7^1 - 3^9 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 6^6$
$72437 := -7^1 + 2^2 + 4^8 + 3^8 + 7^3$	$73425 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 4^2 - 2^7 + 5^7$	$73697 := -7^4 + 3^5 - 6^0 + 9^5 + 7^5$
$72439 := -7^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 3^4 + 9^5$	$73520 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 2^4 - 0^0$	$73752 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 7^3 + 5^7 - 2^7$
$72453 := -7^1 - 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^7 - 3^8$	$73522 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^0 - 2^4$	$73755 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 7^3 - 5^3 + 5^7$
$72455 := -7^4 - 2^7 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 5^7$	$73528 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 2^0 - 8^1$	$73756 := -7^2 + 3^7 + 7^6 + 5^4 - 6^6$
$72456 := -7^3 - 2^9 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 6^5$	$73529 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^0 - 9^1$	$73792 := -7^4 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 9^5 + 2^8$
$72459 := -7^1 - 2^8 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 9^4$	$73532 := -7^4 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 3^7 - 2^2$	$73797 := -7^4 - 3^0 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 7^5$
$72493 := -7^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 9^5 - 3^3$	$73533 := -7^4 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 3^1 - 3^7$	$73824 := -7^4 + 3^8 + 8^4 + 2^5 + 4^8$
$72495 := -7^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 9^5 - 5^2$	$73534 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 3^0 - 4^1$	$73825 := -7^2 - 3^3 - 8^4 - 2^7 + 5^7$
$72497 := -7^1 + 2^6 + 4^8 + 9^4 + 7^3$	$73535 := -7^1 - 3^6 - 5^5 - 3^6 + 5^7$	$73849 := -7^3 - 3^6 - 8^3 + 4^7 + 9^5$
$72499 := -7^3 + 2^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 9^4$	$73537 := -7^4 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 3^7 + 7^0$	$73895 := -7^2 - 3^6 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 5^6$
$72529 := -7^4 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 2^7 + 9^5$	$73538 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 3^2 - 8^1$	$73935 := -7^1 - 3^1 + 9^5 - 3^6 + 5^6$
$72543 := -7^2 + 2^2 + 5^7 + 4^5 - 3^8$	$73539 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 3^0 + 9^0$	$73940 := -7^3 + 3^7 + 9^4 + 4^8 - 0^0$
$72549 := -7^1 - 2^5 + 5^7 + 4^5 - 9^4$	$73540 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 4^1 - 0^0$	$73942 := -7^3 + 3^7 + 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^0$
$72687 := -7^4 - 2^0 - 6^6 + 8^4 + 7^6$	$73542 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 4^0 + 2^2$	$73954 := -7^1 - 3^6 + 9^5 + 5^6 + 4^2$
$72855 := -7^4 - 2^8 + 8^3 - 5^5 + 5^7$	$73552 := -7^4 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 5^7 + 2^4$	$73955 := -7^3 + 3^3 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 5^5$
$72875 := -7^4 - 2^9 + 8^2 - 7^4 + 5^7$	$73553 := -7^4 - 3^2 + 5^2 + 5^7 - 3^7$	$73957 := -7^1 - 3^0 - 9^4 + 5^7 + 7^4$
$72879 := -7^4 - 2^6 - 8^3 + 7^5 + 9^5$	$73554 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 5^7 + 4^2$	$73975 := -7^1 - 3^5 - 9^5 + 7^6 + 5^6$
$72896 := -7^2 + 2^3 - 8^5 + 9^5 + 6^6$	$73556 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 5^7 - 6^1$	$74025 := -7^1 - 4^6 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 5^7$
$72904 := -7^4 - 2^7 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 4^7$	$73558 := -7^3 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 8^4$	$74045 := -7^2 - 4^6 + 0^0 + 4^3 + 5^7$
$72927 := -7^4 - 2^4 + 9^5 - 2^9 + 7^5$	$73563 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 6^0 + 3^3$	$74085 := -7^1 - 4^6 - 0^0 + 8^2 + 5^7$
$72943 := -7^4 - 2^3 + 9^5 + 4^7 - 3^4$	$73567 := -7^4 + 3^5 + 5^7 + 6^0 - 7^4$	$74233 := -7^2 + 4^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 3^8$

$74235 := -7^2 - 4^6 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 5^7$	$74750 := -7^4 - 4^5 + 7^2 + 5^7 + 0^0$	$75229 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 9^1$
$74239 := -7^2 + 4^8 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 9^4$	$74755 := -7^3 - 4^0 - 7^4 - 5^4 + 5^7$	$75235 := -7^1 - 5^5 - 2^0 + 3^5 + 5^7$
$74252 := -7^2 - 4^6 + 2^4 + 5^7 + 2^8$	$74858 := -7^6 - 4^8 - 8^4 - 5^1 + 8^6$	$75238 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^0 + 3^3 - 8^3$
$74253 := -7^3 + 4^8 - 2^2 + 5^6 - 3^8$	$74859 := -7^1 + 4^4 - 8^2 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$75239 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 2^0 + 3^5 - 9^3$
$74259 := -7^3 - 4^3 - 2^3 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$74864 := -7^6 - 4^6 + 8^6 + 6^0 - 4^8$	$75243 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^3 + 4^4 - 3^6$
$74266 := -7^3 + 4^8 + 2^0 + 6^4 + 6^5$	$74879 := -7^2 + 4^7 - 8^3 + 7^1 + 9^5$	$75244 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 4^2$
$74293 := -7^1 + 4^8 + 2^4 + 9^4 + 3^7$	$74897 := -7^2 - 4^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 - 7^5$	$75245 := -7^1 - 5^5 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^7$
$74295 := -7^3 - 4^1 - 2^5 + 9^5 + 5^6$	$74922 := -7^1 + 4^7 + 9^5 + 2^3 - 2^9$	$75248 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 4^1 - 8^3$
$74296 := -7^4 + 4^7 - 2^5 + 9^5 + 6^4$	$74925 := -7^1 + 4^4 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 5^6$	$75249 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 9^3$
$74359 := -7^3 + 4^0 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$74944 := -7^6 - 4^6 + 9^2 - 4^8 + 4^9$	$75250 := -7^1 - 5^5 + 2^8 + 5^7 + 0^0$
$74365 := -7^4 - 4^3 + 3^0 - 6^4 + 5^7$	$74945 := -7^2 + 4^3 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 5^6$	$75257 := -7^3 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 5^7 - 7^4$
$74435 := -7^4 - 4^4 - 4^5 - 3^2 + 5^7$	$74955 := -7^3 - 4^0 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 5^6$	$75264 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 6^2 + 4^2$
$74445 := -7^4 - 4^4 + 4^0 - 4^5 + 5^7$	$74968 := -7^2 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 8^4$	$75267 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 6^1 + 7^2$
$74452 := -7^4 - 4^4 - 4^5 + 5^7 + 2^3$	$74976 := -7^1 + 4^7 - 9^5 + 7^6 - 6^0$	$75268 := -7^2 + 5^7 - 2^3 + 6^4 - 8^4$
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$74454 := -7^3 - 4^4 + 4^5 + 5^7 - 4^6$	$74982 := -7^5 + 4^1 + 9^5 + 8^5 - 2^5$	$75292 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^0 + 9^2 - 2^9$
$74459 := -7^3 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$74986 := -7^3 - 4^6 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 6^6$	$75294 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 9^2 + 4^0$
$74495 := -7^1 - 4^4 - 4^6 + 9^3 + 5^7$	$74987 := -7^1 - 4^2 + 9^5 + 8^5 - 7^5$	$75305 := -7^1 - 5^4 - 3^7 - 0^0 + 5^7$
$74498 := -7^5 - 4^4 - 4^4 + 9^5 + 8^5$	$74995 := -7^4 - 4^0 + 9^0 - 9^3 + 5^7$	$75318 := -7^3 + 5^7 - 3^8 + 1^0 + 8^4$
$74525 := -7^3 - 4^1 - 5^5 - 2^7 + 5^7$	$75025 := -7^1 - 5^5 + 0^1 + 2^5 + 5^7$	$75332 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 3^6 + 3^4 + 2^8$
$74527 := -7^1 - 4^6 + 5^7 + 2^9 - 7^1$	$75058 := -7^1 - 5^5 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 8^2$	$75352 := -7^2 - 5^2 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 2^9$
$74529 := -7^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 2^5 + 9^5$	$75094 := -7^3 + 5^1 - 0^0 + 9^5 + 4^7$	$75353 := -7^3 + 5^0 - 3^5 + 5^7 - 3^7$
$74585 := -7^3 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 8^1 + 5^7$	$75203 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 0^1 - 3^2$	$75354 := -7^4 - 5^4 - 3^0 + 5^7 + 4^4$
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$74655 := -7^3 - 4^0 - 6^0 - 5^5 + 5^7$	$75214 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 1^0 + 4^0$	$75359 := -7^2 + 5^1 + 3^6 + 5^6 + 9^5$
$74657 := -7^1 - 4^5 - 6^2 + 5^7 - 7^4$	$75220 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 0^1$	$75375 := -7^2 - 5^5 + 3^4 + 7^3 + 5^7$
$74658 := -7^4 + 4^8 - 6^1 + 5^6 - 8^4$	$75221 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 1^0$	$75378 := -7^2 + 5^7 - 3^7 + 7^0 - 8^3$
$74659 := -7^1 + 4^8 + 6^5 + 5^4 + 9^3$	$75222 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 2^3 - 2^9$	$75379 := -7^3 - 5^3 - 3^2 + 7^5 + 9^5$
$74665 := -7^4 - 4^5 + 6^0 - 6^2 + 5^7$	$75223 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^1 + 3^2$	$75385 := -7^3 - 5^5 + 3^6 - 8^0 + 5^7$
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$74698 := -7^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 8^3$	$75226 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 6^1$	$75394 := -7^1 - 5^1 - 3^3 + 9^5 + 4^7$
$74725 := -7^1 - 4^5 - 7^4 + 2^5 + 5^7$	$75227 := -7^2 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^6 - 7^4$	$75395 := -7^1 - 5^0 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 5^6$
$74745 := -7^4 - 4^1 + 7^2 - 4^5 + 5^7$	$75228 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 2^3 + 2^3 - 8^3$	$75396 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 6^6$

$75397 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 7^0$	$75582 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 8^0 - 2^4$	$75705 := -7^4 - 5^2 + 7^1 - 0^0 + 5^7$
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$75429 := -7^1 + 5^0 + 4^7 + 2^1 + 9^5$	$75594 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 9^0 - 4^1$	$75720 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 2^1 + 0^0$
$75430 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 4^5 + 3^6 + 0^0$	$75595 := -7^4 - 5^1 - 5^3 + 9^0 + 5^7$	$75722 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 2^0 + 2^2$
$75445 := -7^1 - 5^4 - 4^5 - 4^5 + 5^7$	$75596 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 9^1 + 6^1$	$75723 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 2^0 - 3^0$
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$75467 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 7^4$	$75602 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 6^1 + 0^1 - 2^7$	$75726 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 2^3 + 6^0$
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$75537 := -7^2 - 5^5 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 7^3$	$75688 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 6^2 + 8^0 - 8^0$	$75751 := -7^4 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 1^0$
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$75554 := -7^1 + 5^4 - 5^5 + 5^7 - 4^3$	$75690 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 6^2 + 9^0 + 0^0$	$75753 := -7^4 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 3^3$
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$75760 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 6^2 + 0^0$	$75843 := -7^3 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 4^4 - 3^7$	$75978 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 9^2 + 7^3 - 8^1$
$75762 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 6^2 + 2^0$	$75844 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 4^3 + 4^3$	$75982 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^8$
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$75793 := -7^1 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^5 - 3^4$	$75868 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 6^3 - 8^2$	$76297 := -7^3 + 6^4 - 2^9 + 9^5 + 7^5$
$75794 := -7^1 + 5^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 4^7$	$75869 := -7^1 + 5^7 + 8^4 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$76298 := -7^5 + 6^4 - 2^3 + 9^5 + 8^5$
$75796 := -7^2 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^5 - 6^1$	$75886 := -7^4 - 5^4 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 6^6$	$76325 := -7^3 - 6^3 - 3^6 - 2^9 + 5^7$
$75797 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 9^2 - 7^4$	$75923 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 9^1 + 2^0 - 3^7$	$76326 := -7^5 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 2^6 + 6^6$
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$75823 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^1 + 2^6 + 3^3$	$75954 := -7^4 - 5^2 - 9^0 + 5^7 + 4^4$	$76389 := -7^4 - 6^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 9^5$
$75824 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 4^1$	$75955 := -7^4 + 5^2 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 5^7$	$76394 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 4^3$
$75825 := -7^4 + 5^1 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 5^7$	$75956 := -7^4 + 5^2 - 9^1 + 5^7 + 6^3$	$76405 := -7^5 - 6^4 + 4^7 - 0^0 + 5^7$
$75826 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$75957 := -7^2 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$76449 := -7^1 - 6^0 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 9^5$
$75827 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 7^1$	$75962 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 9^5 + 6^4 - 2^0$	$76452 := -7^2 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 2^6$
$75828 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 8^2$	$75964 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 4^0$	$76453 := -7^4 + 6^0 - 4^0 + 5^7 + 3^6$
$75829 := -7^3 + 5^7 + 8^4 + 2^9 - 9^4$	$75972 := -7^1 - 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^5 + 2^7$	$76453 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 4^0 + 5^7 + 3^6$

$76454 := -7^3 - 6^4 - 4^2 + 5^7 - 4^2$	$76582 := -7^3 - 6^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^5$	$77285 := -7^2 - 7^3 + 2^6 - 8^3 + 5^7$
$76455 := -7^1 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 5^5$	$76583 := -7^2 - 6^5 + 5^7 + 8^4 + 3^7$	$77286 := -7^4 + 7^1 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 6^6$
$76475 := -7^1 - 6^4 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 5^7$	$76586 := -7^3 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 8^2 - 6^4$	$77345 := -7^2 - 7^0 - 3^6 - 4^0 + 5^7$
$76494 := -7^3 + 6^7 - 4^1 + 9^5 - 4^9$	$76605 := -7^1 - 6^3 - 6^4 - 0^0 + 5^7$	$77352 := -7^2 + 7^0 - 3^6 + 5^7 + 2^2$
$76497 := -7^3 + 6^7 - 4^9 + 9^5 - 7^0$	$76655 := -7^5 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 5^3$	$77353 := -7^2 + 7^1 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 3^6$
$76499 := -7^3 + 6^7 - 4^9 + 9^0 + 9^5$	$76745 := -7^1 - 6^1 - 7^3 - 4^5 + 5^7$	$77354 := -7^3 - 7^3 - 3^4 + 5^7 - 4^1$
$76502 := -7^3 - 6^4 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 2^4$	$76754 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 7^1 + 5^7 + 4^5$	$77355 := -7^2 + 7^1 - 3^6 + 5^0 + 5^7$
$76506 := -7^5 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$76762 := -7^5 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 2^8$	$77357 := -7^3 - 7^0 - 3^4 + 5^7 - 7^3$
$76508 := -7^4 + 6^4 + 5^7 + 0^1 - 8^3$	$76768 := -7^3 - 6^5 + 7^6 + 6^1 - 8^5$	$77358 := -7^3 + 7^1 + 3^4 + 5^7 - 8^3$
$76522 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 5^7 - 2^1 - 2^8$	$76784 := -7^4 - 6^6 + 7^6 + 8^4 + 4^6$	$77359 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 3^0 + 5^7 - 9^2$
$76523 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 5^7 - 2^8 - 3^0$	$76795 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 5^7$	$77375 := -7^1 - 7^1 - 3^6 - 7^1 + 5^7$
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$76528 := -7^4 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 2^8 + 8^3$	$76845 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 8^0 + 4^3 + 5^7$	$77456 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 6^0$
$76533 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 5^7 + 3^4 + 3^6$	$76852 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^6$	$77462 := -7^4 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 6^6 + 2^4$
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$76543 := -7^3 - 6^3 + 5^7 - 4^5 + 3^0$	$76885 := -7^1 - 6^4 - 8^0 + 8^2 + 5^7$	$77502 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 0^0 + 2^6$
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$76546 := -7^5 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 4^2 + 6^6$	$76898 := -7^1 + 6^7 + 8^2 + 9^5 - 8^6$	$77516 := -7^2 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 1^0 - 6^3$
$76547 := -7^6 + 6^5 - 5^7 + 4^9 + 7^4$	$76925 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 9^2 + 2^6 + 5^7$	$77519 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 1^0 + 9^2$
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$76549 := -7^3 - 6^4 + 5^7 + 4^3 - 9^0$	$76982 := -7^4 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 8^5 - 2^5$	$77524 := -7^3 - 7^0 + 5^7 - 2^0 - 4^4$
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$76578 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 8^3$	$77225 := -7^2 - 7^3 + 2^2 - 2^9 + 5^7$	$77556 := -7^1 - 7^3 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 6^6$
$76579 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 9^5$	$77243 := -7^4 + 7^5 - 2^9 + 4^8 - 3^7$	$77557 := -7^1 - 7^3 + 5^3 + 5^7 - 7^3$

$77558 := -7^1 + 7^0 - 5^4 + 5^7 + 8^2$	$77939 := -7^3 + 7^6 - 9^0 + 3^9 - 9^5$	$78273 := -7^2 - 8^5 + 2^1 + 7^6 - 3^8$
$77560 := -7^1 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 6^3 + 0^0$	$77945 := -7^2 - 7^2 - 9^2 - 4^0 + 5^7$	$78275 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 2^8 - 7^2 + 5^7$
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$77753 := -7^1 - 7^2 - 7^3 + 5^7 + 3^3$	$78125 := -7^1 - 8^1 - 1^0 + 2^4 + 5^7$	$78389 := -7^3 - 8^0 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 9^5$
$77755 := -7^3 - 7^0 - 7^0 - 5^2 + 5^7$	$78145 := -7^2 + 8^2 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 5^7$	$78390 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 0^1$
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$77775 := -7^1 - 7^0 + 7^0 - 7^3 + 5^7$	$78156 := -7^1 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 6^2$	$78392 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 2^1$
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$77849 := -7^2 + 7^4 + 8^2 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$78245 := -7^1 - 8^0 + 2^6 + 4^3 + 5^7$	$78397 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 7^1$
$77852 := -7^3 + 7^1 - 8^0 + 5^7 + 2^6$	$78252 := -7^1 + 8^1 - 2^1 + 5^7 + 2^7$	$78398 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 8^1$
$77854 := -7^1 - 7^1 - 8^0 + 5^7 - 4^4$	$78253 := -7^1 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 5^7 - 3^0$	$78399 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 9^5$
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$78453 := -7^4 - 8^2 + 4^8 + 5^6 - 3^5$	$78582 := -7^1 - 8^2 + 5^7 + 8^3 + 2^4$	$78864 := -7^2 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 6^6 + 4^0$
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$78522 := -7^2 - 8^2 + 5^7 - 2^1 + 2^9$	$78625 := -7^1 + 8^0 - 6^1 + 2^9 + 5^7$	$78966 := -7^6 + 8^6 - 9^5 + 6^4 - 6^5$
$78523 := -7^2 - 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^9 - 3^0$	$78635 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 6^4 - 3^6 + 5^7$	$78975 := -7^1 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 7^5 + 5^5$
$78524 := -7^2 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^7 + 4^4$	$78638 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 6^6 - 3^6 + 8^5$	$78986 := -7^1 - 8^3 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 6^6$
$78525 := -7^2 - 8^2 + 5^0 + 2^9 + 5^7$	$78639 := -7^2 - 8^1 - 6^2 + 3^9 + 9^5$	$79236 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 3^9 - 6^0$
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$78528 := -7^2 - 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^2 + 8^3$	$78652 := -7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 2^4$	$79285 := -7^2 + 9^3 - 2^5 + 8^3 + 5^7$
$78535 := -7^3 - 8^0 + 5^2 + 3^6 + 5^7$	$78653 := -7^2 + 8^2 - 6^3 + 5^7 + 3^6$	$79286 := -7^2 - 9^2 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 6^6$
$78536 := -7^2 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 6^3$	$78654 := -7^1 + 8^2 + 6^3 + 5^7 + 4^4$	$79335 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 3^9 + 5^4$
$78538 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 8^3$	$78658 := -7^1 - 8^1 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 8^3$	$79350 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 0^1$
$78539 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 9^3$	$78665 := -7^1 + 8^3 - 6^0 + 6^2 + 5^7$	$79351 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 1^0$
$78542 := -7^3 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^4 + 2^9$	$78689 := -7^1 + 8^0 + 6^6 + 8^5 - 9^3$	$79352 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 2^1$
$78543 := -7^4 + 8^3 + 5^6 + 4^8 - 3^6$	$78695 := -7^1 + 8^2 - 6^3 + 9^3 + 5^7$	$79353 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 5^4 + 3^9$
$78545 := -7^3 + 8^3 - 5^1 + 4^4 + 5^7$	$78725 := -7^1 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 2^8 + 5^7$	$79354 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 4^1$
$78547 := -7^2 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 7^3$	$78745 := -7^1 - 8^1 - 7^4 + 4^8 + 5^6$	$79355 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 5^4$
$78549 := -7^1 - 8^3 + 5^7 + 4^5 - 9^2$	$78754 := -7^1 + 8^0 - 7^4 + 5^6 + 4^8$	$79356 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 6^1$
$78562 := -7^2 + 8^3 + 5^7 + 6^1 - 2^5$	$78783 := -7^2 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 8^3 - 3^8$	$79357 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 7^1$
$78563 := -7^1 + 8^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 3^6$	$78836 := -7^2 - 8^3 + 8^5 - 3^3 + 6^6$	$79358 := -7^1 - 9^0 + 3^6 + 5^7 + 8^3$
$78565 := -7^3 - 8^3 - 5^0 + 6^4 + 5^7$	$78845 := -7^2 + 8^0 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 5^7$	$79359 := -7^1 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 9^5$
$78567 := -7^3 - 8^3 + 5^7 + 6^4 + 7^0$	$78852 := -7^2 + 8^1 + 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^8$	$79442 := -7^3 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 2^8$
$78568 := -7^3 - 8^3 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 8^5$	$78855 := -7^3 - 8^2 + 8^3 + 5^4 + 5^7$	$79448 := -7^1 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 8^4$
$78580 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 8^3 + 0^1$	$78857 := -7^2 - 8^5 - 8^6 + 5^8 - 7^5$	$79480 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 0^1$
$78581 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 8^3 + 1^0$	$78862 := -7^2 - 8^0 + 8^5 + 6^6 - 2^9$	$79481 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 1^0$

$79482 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 2^1$	$80394 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 3^9 - 9^3 + 4^8$	$82158 := -8^2 + 2^1 - 1^0 + 5^7 + 8^4$
$79483 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 3^1$	$80457 := -8^2 - 0^0 - 4^1 + 5^7 + 7^4$	$82245 := -8^1 + 2^4 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^7$
$79484 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 4^7$	$80517 := -8^1 + 0^1 + 5^7 - 1^0 + 7^4$	$82247 := -8^2 - 2^4 - 2^4 + 4^8 + 7^5$
$79485 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 5^1$	$80527 := -8^1 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 2^3 + 7^4$	$82274 := -8^2 - 2^0 - 2^2 + 7^5 + 4^8$
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$79488 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^1 + 8^4$	$80590 := -8^4 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 9^4 - 0^0$	$82358 := -8^1 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 5^7 + 8^4$
$79489 := -7^2 + 9^1 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$80591 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 1^0$	$82374 := -8^5 - 2^6 - 3^7 + 7^6 - 4^4$
$79532 := -7^2 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 3^6 - 2^1$	$80592 := -8^4 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 2^0$	$82396 := -8^4 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 6^5$
$79533 := -7^2 - 9^0 + 5^7 + 3^6 + 3^6$	$80593 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 3^1$	$82407 := -8^2 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 0^1 + 7^5$
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$79592 := -7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 2^4$	$80754 := -8^2 + 0^1 - 7^3 + 5^6 + 4^8$	$82477 := -8^5 + 2^0 - 4^1 + 7^6 - 7^4$
$79594 := -7^4 + 9^4 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 4^7$	$80778 := -8^4 + 0^1 - 7^1 + 7^6 - 8^5$	$82485 := -8^1 + 2^4 + 4^4 + 8^4 + 5^7$
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$79756 := -7^1 - 9^0 + 7^3 + 5^7 + 6^4$	$81452 := -8^3 - 1^0 + 4^6 + 5^7 - 2^8$	$82703 := -8^5 + 2^3 + 7^6 + 0^0 - 3^7$
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$80305 := -8^1 + 0^0 + 3^7 + 0^1 + 5^7$	$82154 := -8^2 - 2^1 - 1^0 + 5^7 + 4^6$	$83342 := -8^4 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 2^5$

$83346 := -8^4 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 6^2$	$83925 := -8^2 - 3^6 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 5^7$	$84535 := -8^2 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 3^9 - 5^4$
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$83550 := -8^3 + 3^8 - 5^4 + 5^7 + 0^0$	$84334 := -8^4 + 4^5 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 4^8$	$84574 := -8^2 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 4^6$
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$83586 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 8^2 + 6^5$	$84337 := -8^3 + 4^8 - 3^3 + 3^9 - 7^3$	$84576 := -8^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^6 - 6^3$
$83650 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 0^1$	$84345 := -8^2 + 4^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^7$	$84577 := -8^5 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^6 - 7^3$
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$84750 := -8^5 - 4^4 + 7^6 + 5^3 + 0^1$	$84879 := -8^5 - 4^0 + 8^1 + 7^6 - 9^1$	$85342 := -8^1 - 5^3 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 2^8$
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$84753 := -8^5 - 4^1 + 7^6 - 5^3 + 3^0$	$84907 := -8^5 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 7^6$	$85348 := -8^5 + 5^9 - 3^0 + 4^9 - 8^7$
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$84755 := -8^5 - 4^4 + 7^6 + 5^1 + 5^3$	$84935 := -8^1 + 4^4 + 9^0 + 3^8 + 5^7$	$85363 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 3^0 + 6^5 - 3^3$
$84756 := -8^5 - 4^0 + 7^6 - 5^3 + 6^0$	$84937 := -8^3 + 4^9 - 9^5 + 3^1 - 7^6$	$85364 := -8^2 + 5^7 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 4^4$
$84757 := -8^5 - 4^4 + 7^1 + 5^3 + 7^6$	$84938 := -8^2 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 3^9 + 8^3$	$85365 := -8^3 - 5^2 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 5^7$
$84758 := -8^2 - 4^3 + 7^6 + 5^1 - 8^5$	$84947 := -8^5 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 7^6$	$85367 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$
$84759 := -8^5 - 4^2 + 7^6 - 5^2 - 9^2$	$84957 := -8^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 7^3$	$85387 := -8^5 - 5^1 - 3^0 + 8^3 + 7^6$
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$84792 := -8^4 + 4^8 + 7^5 + 9^4 - 2^4$	$84977 := -8^5 + 4^2 + 9^2 + 7^6 - 7^0$	$85473 := -8^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 3^9$
$84793 := -8^5 - 4^1 + 7^6 - 9^2 - 3^1$	$84979 := -8^5 + 4^2 + 9^0 + 7^6 + 9^2$	$85474 := -8^5 + 5^4 - 4^2 + 7^6 - 4^2$
$84795 := -8^5 - 4^1 + 7^6 - 9^2 - 5^0$	$84993 := -8^5 - 4^4 + 9^5 + 9^5 - 3^4$	$85476 := -8^3 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 7^3 + 6^5$
$84797 := -8^5 - 4^1 + 7^0 - 9^2 + 7^6$	$85007 := -8^5 + 5^3 + 0^0 + 0^1 + 7^6$	$85479 := -8^5 + 5^3 - 4^4 + 7^6 + 9^3$
$84798 := -8^5 - 4^0 + 7^6 - 9^2 - 8^0$	$85163 := -8^1 + 5^7 - 1^0 + 6^5 - 3^6$	$85507 := -8^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 0^1 + 7^6$
$84799 := -8^4 + 4^8 + 7^5 + 9^4 - 9^1$	$85189 := -8^1 + 5^7 - 1^0 + 8^3 + 9^4$	$85526 := -8^3 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 2^6 - 6^5$
$84817 := -8^2 - 4^0 - 8^5 + 1^0 + 7^6$	$85234 := -8^1 + 5^2 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^8$	$85527 := -8^5 + 5^1 + 5^4 + 2^4 + 7^6$
$84827 := -8^5 - 4^3 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 7^6$	$85237 := -8^5 + 5^4 - 2^9 + 3^5 + 7^6$	$85547 := -8^5 + 5^2 + 5^4 + 4^2 + 7^6$
$84837 := -8^5 - 4^2 - 8^0 - 3^3 + 7^6$	$85248 := -8^1 + 5^6 - 2^0 + 4^8 + 8^4$	$85564 := -8^4 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 6^1 - 4^6$
$84864 := -8^6 + 4^5 + 8^3 + 6^7 + 4^8$	$85256 := -8^1 - 5^3 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 6^5$	$85567 := -8^5 + 5^2 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^6$
$84867 := -8^1 - 4^8 + 8^5 - 6^1 + 7^6$	$85257 := -8^5 - 5^1 + 2^8 + 5^3 + 7^6$	$85606 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 6^3 + 0^0 + 6^5$
$84870 := -8^1 - 4^1 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 0^0$	$85259 := -8^2 + 5^3 + 2^9 + 5^7 + 9^4$	$85631 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 6^5 + 3^5 - 1^0$
$84871 := -8^1 - 4^0 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 1^0$	$85260 := -8^3 + 5^7 - 2^7 + 6^5 - 0^0$	$85633 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 6^5 + 3^0 + 3^5$
$84872 := -8^1 + 4^0 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 2^1$	$85262 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 2^0 + 6^5 - 2^7$	$85644 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 6^5 + 4^4 - 4^0$
$84873 := -8^1 + 4^0 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 3^0$	$85265 := -8^3 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 6^5 + 5^7$	$85646 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 4^4 + 6^5$
$84873 := -8^1 - 4^0 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 3^0$	$85267 := -8^5 - 5^3 + 2^9 - 6^0 + 7^6$	$85654 := -8^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 5^7 - 4^4$
$84874 := -8^1 + 4^0 + 8^5 + 7^6 - 4^8$	$85272 := -8^5 - 5^3 + 2^2 + 7^6 + 2^9$	$85659 := -8^4 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 9^3$
$84875 := -8^1 + 4^0 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 5^0$	$85275 := -8^5 + 5^2 - 2^8 + 7^6 + 5^4$	$85667 := -8^3 - 5^7 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^6$
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$84877 := -8^5 - 4^1 - 8^0 + 7^0 + 7^6$	$85299 := -8^5 + 5^0 - 2^5 + 9^5 + 9^5$	$85724 := -8^5 - 5^5 + 7^6 - 2^7 + 4^6$
$84878 := -8^1 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 7^6 - 8^5$	$85327 := -8^5 + 5^4 - 3^5 + 2^6 + 7^6$	$85726 := -8^5 + 5^4 + 7^6 + 2^2 + 6^3$

$85734 := -8^5 + 5^3 + 7^6 + 3^6 - 4^0$	$86454 := -8^6 + 6^7 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 4^8$	$87474 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 4^3 + 7^6 + 4^4$
$85736 := -8^5 + 5^3 + 7^6 + 3^6 + 6^0$	$86465 := -8^2 - 6^5 - 4^7 - 6^7 + 5^8$	$87589 := -8^4 - 7^1 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^5$
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$85788 := -8^2 - 5^5 + 7^6 + 8^4 - 8^5$	$86573 := -8^2 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 3^6$	$87680 := -8^5 + 7^6 - 6^4 + 8^4 - 0^0$
$85846 := -8^2 + 5^7 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 6^5$	$86593 := -8^2 - 6^3 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 3^7$	$87682 := -8^5 + 7^6 - 6^4 + 8^4 + 2^0$
$85857 := -8^5 - 5^5 + 8^4 + 5^1 + 7^6$	$86645 := -8^2 - 6^3 + 6^5 + 4^5 + 5^7$	$87763 := -8^3 - 7^4 + 7^6 - 6^6 + 3^9$
$85862 := -8^1 + 5^7 + 8^0 + 6^5 - 2^5$	$86648 := -8^4 + 6^3 - 6^5 + 4^8 + 8^5$	$87787 := -8^5 - 7^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 7^6$
$85863 := -8^2 + 5^7 - 8^0 + 6^5 + 3^3$	$86684 := -8^3 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 8^5 - 4^1$	$87895 := -8^4 + 7^2 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 5^3$
$85886 := -8^1 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 8^0 + 6^5$	$86687 := -8^3 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 8^5 - 7^0$	$87928 := -8^4 - 7^2 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 8^5$
$85896 := -8^2 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$86689 := -8^3 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 9^0$	$87944 := -8^5 + 7^6 - 9^1 + 4^6 - 4^5$
$85926 := -8^1 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 2^5 + 6^5$	$86907 := -8^5 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 7^6$	$87983 := -8^4 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 8^5 - 3^4$
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$85967 := -8^1 + 5^7 + 9^2 + 6^5 - 7^1$	$86998 := -8^4 + 6^1 - 9^3 + 9^5 + 8^5$	$87986 := -8^4 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 8^5 + 6^3$
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$86135 := -8^1 + 6^5 - 1^0 + 3^5 + 5^7$	$87255 := -8^4 - 7^4 + 2^1 + 5^6 + 5^7$	$88249 := -8^4 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^5$
$86172 := -8^5 + 6^4 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 2^2$	$87267 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^4 + 6^0 + 7^6$	$88269 := -8^4 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^5$
$86173 := -8^5 + 6^4 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 3^1$	$87272 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^1 + 7^6 - 2^3$	$88365 := -8^4 - 8^0 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 5^7$
$86174 := -8^5 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 7^6 - 4^1$	$87273 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^3 + 7^6 - 3^0$	$88489 := -8^4 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 9^5$
$86175 := -8^5 + 6^4 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 5^0$	$87274 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^2 + 7^6 - 4^1$	$88536 := -8^2 + 8^3 + 5^7 + 3^7 + 6^5$
$86177 := -8^5 + 6^4 - 1^0 + 7^0 + 7^6$	$87275 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^1 + 7^6 - 5^1$	$88559 := -8^5 + 8^6 - 5^0 + 5^8 - 9^6$
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$86352 := -8^2 + 6^5 + 3^1 + 5^7 + 2^9$	$87287 := -8^5 + 7^4 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 7^6$	$88972 := -8^5 + 8^4 - 9^0 + 7^6 - 2^2$
$86358 := -8^2 + 6^5 + 3^2 + 5^7 + 8^3$	$87309 := -8^4 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 0^1 - 9^4$	$88973 := -8^5 + 8^4 - 9^0 + 7^6 - 3^1$
$86374 := -8^5 + 6^5 - 3^7 + 7^6 - 4^6$	$87322 := -8^5 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 2^8 - 2^1$	$88974 := -8^5 + 8^4 + 9^0 + 7^6 - 4^1$
$86395 := -8^4 - 6^6 - 3^3 + 9^5 + 5^7$	$87323 := -8^5 + 7^6 - 3^0 + 2^8 + 3^7$	$88975 := -8^5 + 8^4 - 9^0 + 7^6 - 5^0$
$86398 := -8^4 - 6^4 - 3^3 + 9^5 + 8^5$	$87324 := -8^5 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 2^9 - 4^4$	$88977 := -8^2 - 8^5 + 9^4 - 7^4 + 7^6$
$86428 := -8^4 - 6^5 + 4^8 - 2^2 + 8^5$	$87325 := -8^5 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 2^8 + 5^0$	$88978 := -8^1 + 8^4 + 9^1 + 7^6 - 8^5$
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$86448 := -8^4 - 6^5 + 4^2 + 4^8 + 8^5$	$87435 := -8^3 - 7^0 + 4^7 - 3^8 + 5^7$	$89298 := -8^5 + 9^5 - 2^7 + 9^5 + 8^4$
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$89417 := -8^5 + 9^5 + 4^8 + 1^0 - 7^4$	$92984 := -9^4 + 2^9 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 4^8$	$94275 := -9^2 - 4^3 - 2^9 + 7^5 + 5^7$
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$89567 := -8^2 - 9^5 - 5^6 + 6^6 + 7^6$	$93376 := -9^4 + 3^7 - 3^9 + 7^6 - 6^3$	$94445 := -9^2 + 4^0 + 4^2 + 4^7 + 5^7$
$89569 := -8^3 + 9^0 - 5^6 + 6^6 + 9^5$	$93426 := -9^2 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 2^9 + 6^5$	$94447 := -9^4 - 4^0 - 4^4 - 4^7 + 7^6$
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$89834 := -8^4 - 9^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 4^8$	$93475 := -9^3 - 3^6 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 5^7$	$94453 := -9^2 + 4^2 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 3^2$
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$91372 := -9^4 - 1^0 - 3^9 + 7^6 - 2^5$	$93575 := -9^3 - 3^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 5^7$	$94495 := -9^1 - 4^1 + 4^7 - 9^0 + 5^7$
$91378 := -9^5 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 7^6 + 8^5$	$93577 := -9^3 - 3^8 + 5^2 - 7^5 + 7^6$	$94500 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^0 - 0^0$
$91538 := -9^5 - 1^0 - 5^9 + 3^8 + 8^7$	$93643 := -9^2 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 3^9$	$94501 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 1^0$
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$92965 := -9^1 + 2^9 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 5^7$	$94253 := -9^1 + 4^7 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 3^5$	$94567 := -9^2 - 4^7 + 5^8 - 6^7 + 7^3$
$92966 := -9^1 - 2^8 - 9^2 + 6^6 + 6^6$	$94256 := -9^2 - 4^7 + 2^5 + 5^8 - 6^7$	$94578 := -9^4 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^6 - 8^0$
$92968 := -9^2 - 2^6 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$94273 := -9^4 - 4^7 - 2^9 + 7^6 + 3^4$	$94587 := -9^2 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 7^5$

94589 := $-9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 8^1 + 9^2$	94875 := $-9^1 + 4^2 - 8^2 + 7^5 + 5^7$	95627 := $-9^3 + 5^7 + 6^4 + 2^7 + 7^5$
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94645 := $-9^2 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 5^7$	94985 := $-9^3 - 4^9 + 9^0 - 8^5 + 5^8$	95678 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^6 - 8^0$
94652 := $-9^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 5^7 - 2^6$	95054 := $-9^2 + 5^4 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 4^7$	95687 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1 + 7^6$
94653 := $-9^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 5^7 + 3^2$	95056 := $-9^1 - 5^6 + 0^0 + 5^8 - 6^7$	95720 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 7^6 + 2^8 + 0^0$
94657 := $-9^3 + 4^8 + 6^6 + 5^0 - 7^5$	95067 := $-9^2 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$	95732 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 7^6 - 3^5 + 2^9$
94667 := $-9^4 - 4^7 - 6^0 - 6^2 + 7^6$	95207 := $-9^4 - 5^6 - 2^8 + 0^1 + 7^6$	95733 := $-9^1 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 3^6$
94672 := $-9^4 - 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^6 + 2^2$	95227 := $-9^3 + 5^7 + 2^9 + 2^9 + 7^5$	95778 := $-9^1 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 7^5 + 8^3$
94673 := $-9^5 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^6 + 3^9$	95258 := $-9^1 - 5^6 - 2^0 + 5^7 + 8^5$	95779 := $-9^1 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 9^5$
94675 := $-9^3 + 4^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 5^7$	95267 := $-9^1 + 5^7 + 2^7 + 6^3 + 7^5$	95796 := $-9^2 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 6^3$
94696 := $-9^6 + 4^8 + 6^7 + 9^3 + 6^7$	95327 := $-9^2 + 5^7 + 3^9 + 2^0 - 7^4$	95797 := $-9^1 - 5^6 + 7^3 - 9^4 + 7^6$
94697 := $-9^4 - 4^7 - 6^1 - 9^0 + 7^6$	95334 := $-9^1 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 3^8 + 4^6$	95844 := $-9^4 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 4^8$
94702 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 - 0^0 - 2^0$	95337 := $-9^2 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 3^5 + 7^5$	95846 := $-9^3 - 5^6 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 6^6$
94703 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 0^1 - 3^0$	95342 := $-9^4 + 5^7 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 2^0$	95847 := $-9^2 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 - 7^4$
94704 := $-9^4 - 4^0 + 7^6 + 0^0 - 4^7$	95344 := $-9^4 + 5^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 4^6$	95863 := $-9^2 + 5^7 - 8^6 + 6^7 + 3^3$
94705 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 0^1 + 5^0$	95354 := $-9^1 + 5^3 + 3^6 + 5^7 + 4^7$	95874 := $-9^2 + 5^7 - 8^0 + 7^5 + 4^5$
94706 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 0^0 + 6^0$	95357 := $-9^2 - 5^2 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 7^6$	95939 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 9^5$
94720 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^4 + 0^1$	95372 := $-9^2 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 2^9$	95976 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 9^3 + 7^6 - 6^3$
94721 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^4 + 1^0$	95373 := $-9^1 - 5^6 - 3^4 + 7^6 - 3^8$	95993 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 9^5 + 9^5 + 3^4$
94722 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^1 + 2^4$	95376 := $-9^2 - 5^6 - 3^8 + 7^6 - 6^1$	96275 := $-9^2 + 6^4 + 2^7 + 7^5 + 5^7$
94723 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 - 2^3 + 3^3$	95379 := $-9^2 - 5^6 - 3^1 + 7^6 - 9^4$	96278 := $-9^2 + 6^6 + 2^7 + 7^5 + 8^5$
94724 := $-9^4 + 4^1 + 7^6 + 2^4 - 4^7$	95427 := $-9^2 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 2^9 + 7^5$	96365 := $-9^2 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 6^6 + 5^5$
94725 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 - 2^2 + 5^2$	95437 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 4^0 - 3^3 + 7^6$	96435 := $-9^2 - 6^4 + 4^1 + 3^9 + 5^7$
94726 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^4 + 6^1$	95443 := $-9^1 + 5^7 + 4^5 + 4^7 - 3^4$	96453 := $-9^2 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 3^6$
94727 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 2^4 + 7^6$	95446 := $-9^2 + 5^7 + 4^5 + 4^7 - 6^1$	96475 := $-9^1 + 6^4 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 5^7$
94728 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^4 + 8^1$	95457 := $-9^4 - 5^1 - 4^0 - 5^6 + 7^6$	96478 := $-9^1 + 6^6 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 8^5$
94729 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^4 + 9^1$	95472 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 4^0 + 7^6 + 2^3$	96495 := $-9^2 + 6^6 + 4^8 + 9^1 - 5^6$
94730 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 3^3 - 0^0$	95473 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 4^0 + 7^6 + 3^2$	96503 := $-9^1 - 6^4 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 3^9$
94732 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 3^3 + 2^0$	95475 := $-9^2 + 5^4 - 4^0 + 7^5 + 5^7$	96542 := $-9^1 + 6^6 - 5^6 + 4^8 - 2^4$
94745 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 4^2 + 5^2$	95478 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 4^2 + 7^6 - 8^0$	96543 := $-9^4 - 6^7 + 5^8 - 4^5 - 3^8$
94762 := $-9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 - 6^1 + 2^6$	95483 := $-9^1 - 5^4 + 4^8 + 8^5 - 3^7$	96549 := $-9^1 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 4^6 + 9^4$
94765 := $-9^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 6^3 + 5^7$	95487 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 7^6$	96564 := $-9^1 + 6^1 - 5^6 + 6^6 + 4^8$
94784 := $-9^4 + 4^2 + 7^6 + 8^2 - 4^7$	95572 := $-9^4 + 5^3 - 5^6 + 7^6 - 2^4$	96583 := $-9^4 - 6^5 + 5^7 + 8^5 + 3^3$
94852 := $-9^4 + 4^8 + 8^5 + 5^5 - 2^4$	95579 := $-9^1 + 5^3 - 5^6 + 7^6 - 9^4$	96680 := $-9^3 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 8^4 + 0^0$
94859 := $-9^1 + 4^8 + 8^5 + 5^5 - 9^4$	95587 := $-9^4 - 5^6 + 5^3 - 8^0 + 7^6$	96735 := $-9^3 - 6^0 - 7^3 + 3^9 + 5^7$
94873 := $-9^4 + 4^8 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 3^6$	95597 := $-9^4 + 5^3 - 5^6 + 9^1 + 7^6$	96745 := $-9^6 - 6^5 - 7^5 + 4^9 + 5^8$

$96765 := -9^4 + 6^1 + 7^6 + 6^4 - 5^6$	$97795 := -9^3 + 7^0 - 7^7 + 9^6 + 5^8$	$98386 := -9^3 + 8^1 + 3^9 + 8^5 + 6^6$
$96875 := -9^5 - 6^8 + 8^2 - 7^6 + 5^9$	$97823 := -9^2 + 7^6 - 8^2 + 2^1 - 3^9$	$98422 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 2^7 - 2^0$
$96879 := -9^2 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 9^3$	$97824 := -9^1 - 7^3 + 8^5 - 2^7 + 4^8$	$98424 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 2^7 + 4^8$
$96893 := -9^4 + 6^6 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 3^7$	$97826 := -9^1 - 7^6 + 8^6 - 2^2 - 6^6$	$98432 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 2^7$
$96963 := -9^4 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 6^6 - 3^7$	$97837 := -9^2 - 7^2 + 8^0 - 3^9 + 7^6$	$98452 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 2^5$
$96967 := -9^4 - 6^5 - 9^4 + 6^3 + 7^6$	$97846 := -9^1 - 7^6 + 8^6 + 4^2 - 6^6$	$98456 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 6^2$
$97223 := -9^3 + 7^6 - 2^4 + 2^1 - 3^9$	$97862 := -9^1 - 7^6 + 8^6 - 6^6 + 2^5$	$98472 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 7^2 + 2^7$
$97237 := -9^3 - 7^0 + 2^0 - 3^9 + 7^6$	$97866 := -9^1 - 7^6 + 8^6 + 6^2 - 6^6$	$98473 := -9^1 + 8^3 + 4^1 + 7^6 - 3^9$
$97243 := -9^3 + 7^6 + 2^1 + 4^1 - 3^9$	$97893 := -9^2 + 7^6 - 8^0 + 9^1 - 3^9$	$98536 := -9^4 - 8^0 + 5^7 - 3^9 + 6^6$
$97246 := -9^2 - 7^6 - 2^9 + 4^9 - 6^6$	$97935 := -9^3 + 7^5 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^5$	$98543 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 3^5$
$97248 := -9^3 - 7^3 + 2^4 + 4^8 + 8^5$	$97938 := -9^5 + 7^6 + 9^1 + 3^8 + 8^5$	$98545 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 5^3$
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$97334 := -9^3 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$97978 := -9^5 + 7^2 + 9^4 + 7^6 + 8^5$	$98634 := -9^3 + 8^5 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 4^4$
$97335 := -9^1 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 3^1 - 5^4$	$98143 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 3^4$	$98674 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 7^3 + 4^8$
$97352 := -9^2 - 7^3 + 3^9 + 5^7 - 2^5$	$98224 := -9^2 + 8^5 - 2^0 + 2^1 + 4^8$	$98693 := -9^3 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 9^5 - 3^7$
$97353 := -9^1 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 5^7 + 3^7$	$98234 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^8$	$98742 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 2^9$
$97355 := -9^3 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 5^7$	$98235 := -9^2 + 8^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^7$	$98784 := -9^2 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 8^5 + 4^8$
$97356 := -9^3 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^1$	$98240 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 2^4 + 4^8 + 0^0$	$98834 := -9^1 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8$
$97358 := -9^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 5^7 - 8^2$	$98247 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 2^0 + 4^8 - 7^2$	$98943 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 9^2 + 4^8 + 3^6$
$97359 := -9^5 + 7^6 + 3^9 + 5^7 - 9^5$	$98264 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 2^5 + 6^0 + 4^8$	$98946 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 4^8 - 6^1$
$97372 := -9^2 - 7^0 - 3^9 + 7^6 - 2^9$	$98274 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 7^2 + 4^8$	$99063 := -9^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^6 - 3^8$
$97385 := -9^2 - 7^3 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 5^7$	$98293 := -9^2 + 8^5 - 2^2 + 9^5 + 3^8$	$99146 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 6^6$
$97399 := -9^3 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 9^2 + 9^2$	$98294 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 4^8$	$99263 := -9^1 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 6^6 - 3^8$
$97443 := -9^4 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 3^9$	$98299 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 9^5$	$99265 := -9^4 + 9^5 - 2^2 + 6^6 + 5^3$
$97533 := -9^2 + 7^2 + 5^7 + 3^9 - 3^5$	$98304 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$99266 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 6^6 - 6^1$
$97537 := -9^2 - 7^3 - 5^1 - 3^9 + 7^6$	$98324 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 3^1 + 2^5 + 4^8$	$99396 := -9^4 + 9^1 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 6^6$
$97545 := -9^5 + 7^3 + 5^7 + 4^0 + 5^7$	$98329 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 3^8 + 2^5 + 9^5$	$99447 := -9^1 + 9^3 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 7^5$
$97552 := -9^5 + 7^3 + 5^7 + 5^7 + 2^3$	$98342 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 3^4 + 4^8 + 2^7$	$99464 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 4^4$
$97553 := -9^2 - 7^2 - 5^3 + 5^7 + 3^9$	$98345 := -9^2 + 8^5 - 3^1 + 4^8 + 5^3$	$99643 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 6^6 + 4^4 + 3^5$
$97554 := -9^2 + 7^0 + 5^5 + 5^7 + 4^7$	$98347 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 7^2$	$99648 := -9^1 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 4^3 + 8^5$
$97572 := -9^2 - 7^5 - 5^5 + 7^6 - 2^6$	$98349 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 3^3 + 4^8 + 9^2$	$99662 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 2^9$
$97735 := -9^1 - 7^5 + 7^6 + 3^3 - 5^5$	$98362 := -9^3 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 6^6 - 2^4$	$99683 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 6^6 + 8^3 + 3^3$
$97753 := -9^2 - 7^1 + 7^6 - 5^3 - 3^9$	$98369 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 6^6 - 9^3$	$99843 := -9^3 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 3^7$
$97757 := -9^1 - 7^5 + 7^2 - 5^5 + 7^6$	$98384 := -9^1 + 8^1 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 4^8$	

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